

Université Lumière Lyon 2
Laboratoire Dynamique du Langage (UMR 5596)
Ecole Doctorale Neurosciences et Cognition (ED 476)

IMPACT OF INTER-INDIVIDUAL & INTER-GROUP VARIATION ON LANGUAGE EVOLUTION

Doctoral thesis by
Mathilde JOSSERAND

IMPACT OF INTER-INDIVIDUAL AND INTER-GROUP VARIATION ON LANGUAGE EVOLUTION

Doctoral thesis by **Mathilde Josserand**

to be defended in public on Friday, December the 1st, 2023

Supervisors:

Dan Dediu, Superviseur, University of Barcelona
François Pellegrino, Co-Superviseur, University of Lyon 2
Serge Caparos, Co-Encadrant, University of Paris VIII

Doctoral Examination Committee:

Jennifer Culbertson, Présidente, University of Edinburgh
Marieke Schouwstra, Rapportrice, University of Amsterdam
Francesca Tria, Rapportrice, University of Rome
Nicolas Claidière, Examineur, University of Aix-Marseille

Laboratoire Dynamique du Langage
Université Lumière Lyon 2 / CNRS UMR 5596
Ecole Doctorale Neurosciences et Cognition (ED 476)

Acknowledgments

I did not intend for this section to be so lengthy, but the more I write, the more I realize how many people were a part of my Ph.D. By the time you read these words, I would still be writing if I could convey the extent of my gratitude for the people who have accompanied me on my Ph.D. journey. Now, let me thank the three amazing researchers on my supervisory board.

Dan, you are the cornerstone of this Ph.D. I may have faced something akin to the Total Perspective Vortex during this journey, but you were always here to support me. Your investment extended beyond the scientific aspects of each chapter; you also guided me to become a better scientist and opened doors to a promising future in academia (fingers crossed). For all of this, I am profoundly grateful.

François, you have been there since the very beginning. I always felt that your door was open whenever I needed assistance. I highly value your expertise and knowledge, and you always made great comments and suggestions on my work. It has truly been a pleasure working with you over these three years.

Serge, I was thrilled to officially welcome you as a supervisor on my board, as your contributions, both intellectually and emotionally, have been significant. While it can be hard to gauge our direct impact in academia, I believe that you are giving a lot back to the world - investing substantial time and effort in mentoring me is just one example. I not only hold your research expertise in high regard but also genuinely appreciate you as a person.

I also would like to thank the members of my thesis committee. I truly appreciate that you are taking the time to read my manuscript, and I am looking forward to discussing it with you.

I am also grateful to **François Osiurak** for advising me on the comité de suivi de thèse.

Now, I would like to express my gratitude to all the researchers I have had the chance to collaborate with throughout my Ph.D. I will acknowledge you in the chronological order in which we met.

Giorgio Vallortigara: I cannot thank you enough for making the fieldwork trip to Namibia a reality. I was pleased to maintain a connection with the field of animal cognition and truly valued our insightful conversations.

Marc Allasonnière-Tang: Collaborating with you was not only professionally rewarding but also immensely enjoyable. I deeply admire your social skills, and I genuinely hope that I can become less socially awkward and more effortlessly cool like you in the future.

Asifa Majid: Thank you for your support and guidance during my initial research study for this PhD, which paved the way for future research.

Bart de Boer: Despite being busy with your adorable kid, you generously took the time to welcome me into your lab in Brussels and made me feel like part of the team. Collaborating with you was a pleasure, and I hope our paths will cross again in the future.

Limor Raviv: Last but not least, I want to extend my deepest thanks to you. I genuinely admire both you and your work. You are like the Beta version of humanity and a genuinely wonderful person, and I sincerely hope we have the opportunity to collaborate again in the future.

I would also like to express my gratitude to the members of the Laboratoire Dynamique du Langage, where I spent three and a half years of my life. I would like to thank **Antoine Guillaume**, the former lab director, and **Françoise Rose**, the new lab director, for their support. I would also like to extend my thanks to the heads of the DiLiS axis, **Anetta Kopecka**, **Brigitte Pakendorf**, and later **Maïa Ponsonnet**. Of course, I also thank all the other researchers from the lab who are not mentioned here. I was touched by the care you took in looking after the well-being of the Ph.D. students and helped create a positive atmosphere in the lab.

En parlant de bonne atmosphère au laboratoire, comment ne pourrais-je pas mentionner ma chère **Rabia Makine** et mon cher **Christian Fressard** ? Vous êtes tous les deux des piliers du DDL, et passer trois ans en votre compagnie (même si je n'étais pas si souvent là que ça, je sais) a été un plaisir. En plus de l'aide administrative et technique inestimable que vous m'avez apportée, vous êtes également des personnes chaleureuses et pétillantes, et ce fut toujours un plaisir de discuter avec vous. Merci également à toi **Laurence Husni** pour m'avoir aidé dans de nombreuses tâches administratives et ne pas avoir jugé mon niveau de souplesse lamentable pendant tes cours de yoga.

Still at the DDL lab, I would like to extend my gratitude to the PhDs and postdocs. You have been the travel buddies who visited me wherever I went – from

Brussels to Nijmegen, and we have even shared some memorable holidays together. I will thank you in the chronological order of how we met.

Rémi Anselme, you were the first Ph.D. student I met at the lab, and it did not take long for me to realize that I could rely on you for help with data-related issues, saucisson cravings problems, basic gossip, or even intense life issues, making you a very multi-functional person. So, if you allow me to 'vomit' some nice words at you, I would have to thank you for being such an excellent colleague. **Tessa Vermeir**, you are the Blue Fire of my stay in DDL, and your J-ness is what I need in my life. I would turn into your soulmate just to meet you and enjoy your delicious brownies every day of my life. I also thank **Lea Mouton** and **Jinke Song**, who had an important role since they respectively fed me with barbecue and ice cream. **Matt Stave**, it was an absolute pleasure to have you around. You shattered all the norms of small talk, and our conversations were truly meaningful. And speaking of post-docs, I want to express my gratitude to **Jayden Cordes** for his visit to our lab in Lyon and for entertaining us with his very cool name and Australian-ness. **Karl Seifen**, my Ph.D. 'buddy' (since we both started our Ph.Ds at the same time), in these acknowledgments, I will forgive the treachery you committed by not finishing your Ph.D. at the same time as me. I cannot help but wonder how life will be after I leave the DDL, knowing I won't hear anymore your whispered words of love in my ear. **Tzuyi Tseng**, you are undeniably the most adorable and cute human being I have ever encountered in my life. Simply witnessing you cutely walking through the lab had the power to brighten my day. I am not sure I could have survived through this Ph.D. without your regular cuddles. **Nargil**, my best companion for going to the CROUS, thanks for your support and for regularly bringing me delicious tea. I also thank **Lucie Métral**, your radiant and genuinely kind-hearted nature has been a shining presence in the DDL. **Nelly Bonhomme**, you are the embodiment of the perfect office mate, and the office was always a better place with you inside. **Laurène Barbier**, what a delight it was to have such a belle personne solaire, droite et admirable, join our office! I would even say more - that it was absolutely fantastchique. No words could convey the "depth of my feelings" (Barbier, 2023) for your support. Of course, there are plenty of other PhD students who were at the DDL during my PhD and whom I would like to thank: **Aitana Garcia Arasco**, **Natalja Ulrich**, **Virgile Daunay**, **Yana Aquilina**, **Minella Duzerol**, **Daniela Valente**, **Krishna Parajuli**, **Marion Naffrechoux**, **Denis Bertet**, **Magdalena Lemus Serrano**, **Nichuta Bunkham**.

Even though my betweenness centrality is not that high (you will understand that after reading Chapter 5!), I am pleased to have had the opportunity to meet so

many remarkable young researchers during my Ph.D. journey. First and foremost, I want to express my gratitude to **Esther Boissin**, who never ceased to amaze me with her ability to be a fantastic and fun travel companion (#namibia2021), an exceptionally intelligent researcher, and a devoted mother all at once. **Anna Blumenthal** (#namibia2022), thanks to you, my kiki-ness found its perfect matching bouba-ness (but definitely not booba-ness). Traveling with you was amazing! I would also like to extend my thanks to **Koen de Reus** and **Yannick Jadoul**, who were part of both my experiences in Brussels and Nijmegen. You both played a significant role in making me love your respective countries. I never imagined I would be so fascinated by seals, and it is all thanks to you. Of course, my gratitude also goes out to all my colleagues from Brussels (**Katie Mudd, Marnix Van Soom, Rodrigo Manriquez, Peter Dekker, Heikki Rasilo**), and my colleagues from the MPI (**Lukas Galke, Oxana Grosseck, Lewis Cheung, and Kotryna Motiekaityte**). Additionally, I want to give a special thanks to the fantastic M2 quartet who turned my time in Nijmegen into an unforgettable period of my life (**Kayleigh, Mikkel, Aroa, and Jemima**).

My stay at the MPI in the Netherlands would not have been possible without the **Van Gogh program**, which provided the funding for this exchange. I would also like to express my gratitude to **ASLAN** for awarding me two Au Fil de L'eau scholarships, which enabled me to participate in a summer school and compensate the participants in my color experiments.

Speaking of color experiments, I extend my heartfelt thanks to all the Himba participants who generously took part in these experiments, as well as our incredible guides and translators in Namibia: **Chinho Lopez, Fanny Kavari, Hilde Simon, and Cancy Luise**. My trips to Namibia were a highlight of my Ph.D. journey, and this is largely due to the warm welcome and support of the Namibian people. I am also immensely grateful to all the participants from France who volunteered for my experiments. In particular, I want to express a special thank you to my friends who dedicated their time to my pretests several times without any financial compensation.

Of course, many other friends have added their own special touch to this journey. Thus, I would like to express my gratitude to my dear **Basak, Auriane, Océane, Solène, Anaëlle**. While you may not have directly contributed to my Ph.D., you all played a significant role in making life enjoyable during these three years. **Jean**, I have not forgotten your support during the first two years of my Ph.D., and I want to thank you for that.

Last but not least, je tiens à exprimer ma gratitude envers ma famille, en particulier mes parents et mes frères, pour avoir patiemment participé à tous mes pré-tests de psychologie cognitive depuis ma première année de licence. Je vous remercie pour avoir toujours encouragé mes choix de vie et pour vous être intéressé à mes recherches.

Abstract

Languages diversity is influenced by many factors, including cultural and environmental ones, as well as variation in anatomy and physiology. While recent research has focused on variation in the vocal tract and its impact on language sound systems, it remains unclear whether this applies to other aspects of language, such as language lexicons.

Therefore, the first part of this PhD research focuses on the influence of perceptual variation on language lexicons, particularly in the color domain. Specifically, we explore the hypothesis that UV incidence, through its impact on eye physiology, affects the perception of blue colors, potentially explaining why populations with high UV exposure often lack a specific term for the color blue. Two methods are employed: a cross-cultural statistical analysis and a natural (quasi-)experiment comparing color perception between participants from France and the Himba ethnic group. The findings suggest that color lexicons are shaped by a combination of environmental and cultural factors, and variation in color perception may play a role in accounting for the observed diversity.

While these patterns of variation manifest at the group level, our analyses also revealed substantial variation among individuals within the same group, prompting us to ponder the extent to which language adapts to the idiosyncrasies of its speakers. Thus, the second part of this PhD aims to understand the precise mechanisms by which inter-individual variation affects language evolution. First, we conducted a laboratory experiment to study language evolution in groups of four individuals, with one participant deliberately biased. Second, we used Bayesian agent-based models to explore how a shared language emerges in heterogenous groups and how network structure contributes to language variability. The results suggest that the emergent shared language of the whole community is influenced by the language idiosyncrasies carried by a minority of biased agents, and put forward the crucial role of network structure in shaping inter-individual variation in language.

Overall, this PhD research highlights that variation in languages can only be understood in the context of their cultural, biological, and physical environments and sheds light on the processes through which inter-individual and inter-group variation affect language evolution.

Résumé

La diversité linguistique émerge due à des différences dans nos cultures et environnements. Des recherches récentes proposent également que des variations dans la physiologie et l'anatomie de notre appareil vocal influencerait les sons présents dans les langues, mais nous ne savons pas ces effets peuvent également s'étendre à d'autres aspects du langage, comme le lexique.

Ainsi, la première partie de cette recherche se concentre sur l'influence de notre perception sur le lexique, en particulier dans le domaine des couleurs. Plus précisément, nous explorons une hypothèse suggérant que l'exposition au soleil (rayonnement UV) impacterait notre perception des couleurs bleues, ce qui expliquerait en partie pourquoi les populations exposées à des niveaux élevés de rayons UV n'ont souvent pas de terme pour décrire la couleur bleue. Nous avons employé deux méthodes : une analyse statistique incluant des données de nombreuses populations dans le monde, et une expérience naturelle visant à comparer la perception des couleurs entre des participants français et himbas. Les résultats suggèrent que les vocabulaires des couleurs sont façonnés par une combinaison de facteurs environnementaux et culturels. De plus, des différences dans notre perception des couleurs pourraient également jouer un rôle pour expliquer la diversité des vocabulaires des couleurs dans le monde.

Bien que cette variation se manifeste au niveau du groupe, nos analyses ont également révélé une variation importante entre individus d'un même groupe, ce qui nous a amenés à nous interroger sur la mesure dans laquelle la langue s'adapte aux particularités de ses locuteurs. La deuxième partie vise donc à comprendre les mécanismes par lesquels la variation interindividuelle affecte l'évolution du langage. Dans un premier temps, nous avons réalisé une expérience en laboratoire visant à étudier l'évolution du langage au sein de groupes composés de quatre individus, et dans lesquels un individu a des capacités langagières différentes des autres. Ensuite, nous avons utilisé des modèles multi-agents bayésiens pour explorer comment une langue émerge au sein de groupes hétérogènes, et comment la structure du réseau contribue à la variabilité linguistique. Les résultats suggèrent que la langue d'un groupe est influencée par la variation apportée par les individus biaisés, même lorsqu'ils sont en minorité.

Dans l'ensemble, cette thèse propose que pour comprendre l'évolution des langues, il est crucial de les replacer dans le contexte environnemental, culturel et biologique dans lesquelles elles sont parlées. De plus, ce travail doctoral met en lumière la manière dont la variation entre individus et entre groupes peut influencer l'évolution du langage.

Contents

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	5
ABSTRACT	11
RÉSUMÉ	13
INTRODUCTION	19
Linguistic diversity	19
The effects of anatomy and physiology	24
First part: the link between color perception and lexicon	28
Second part: inter-individual variation and language change	35
Methods	37
Plan	40
1. ENVIRONMENT AND CULTURE SHAPE BOTH THE COLOUR LEXICON AND THE GENETICS OF COLOUR PERCEPTION	47
Context	47
Abstract	47
Introduction	48
Methods and materials	52
Results	55
UV-B incidence predicts the existence of a specific word for blue	55
Population frequency of abnormal red-green vision	59
Discussion	61
Follow-up: comment on the paper	63
Criticisms	63
Response	64
2. DIFFERENCES IN COLOR LEXICON IN THE FRENCH AND HIMBA POPULATIONS: THERE IS MORE TO PERCEPTION THAN MEETS THE EYE	69
Context	69
Abstract	70
Introduction	71
Methods	75
Himba sample	76

French sample	77
Tasks.....	78
Additional data	81
Analysis	86
Results	90
Understanding the predictors effect.....	90
Investigating the lens-brunescence hypothesis.....	94
Discussion.....	97
TRANSITION	101
3. DIVERSITY RULES: THE INFLUENCE OF A MINORITY ON LANGUAGE CHANGE.....	105
Context.....	105
Abstract.....	105
Introduction	106
Method	112
Participants	112
Production Bias	113
Stimuli.....	113
Procedure.....	114
Additional tasks	116
Specific research questions	118
Measures.....	118
Analysis	119
Results	120
How did language evolve in the heterogeneous groups?	121
Has the language of the group adapted to the specificity of the biased participant?.....	122
Who adapts and when?	124
Discussion.....	125
4. INTERINDIVIDUAL VARIATION REFUSES TO GO AWAY: A BAYESIAN COMPUTER MODEL OF LANGUAGE CHANGE IN COMMUNICATIVE NETWORKS.....	130
Context.....	130
Abstract.....	130
Introduction	131

Methods	138
Language value.....	146
Heterogeneity between groups.....	147
Stabilization time	148
Results	149
Can a Minority of Biased Agents Affect the Language of the Whole Population?	150
How Do the Biased Agents Affect the Language of the Whole Population?	155
When Does the Language Stabilize?	161
Discussion.....	163
5. HOW NETWORK STRUCTURE SHAPES LANGUAGES: SIZE AND DENSITY AS PROXIES AND NOT CAUSES.....	168
Context.....	168
Abstract.....	168
Introduction	169
Data and methods.....	173
The language	174
How do agents represent language?.....	174
The initial language exposure	176
The communication process.....	176
The network	178
Measurements	181
The procedure.....	184
Results	184
Dataset 1	184
Dataset 2	187
Dataset 3.....	188
Discussion.....	190
DISCUSSION.....	194
Differences in color perception may shape color lexicons	195
A biased minority can influence the language of a group	202
General conclusion	208
REFERENCES.....	213

INTRODUCTION

LINGUISTIC DIVERSITY

Imagine a world where every person, regardless of their background or birthplace, effortlessly communicates in a single universal language. The appeal of such an idea is not unfounded, considering the common genetic and cognitive traits shared among humans. Yet, as we explore the rich diversity of human languages, we find ourselves confronted with a perplexing question: why are there over 8000 languages on our planet today (see Illustration 1)?

Illustration 1: Map showing the 8735 languages and dialects with a known longitude and latitude (according to Glottolog version 4.7; Hammarström et al., 2023). The color gradient

INTRODUCTION

shows the density of language in an area, with blue showing areas with high linguistic density and red showing areas with low linguistic density.

To fully understand the diversification of languages, it is necessary to explore the dynamics of language change. A language does not transform into another language in the blink of an eye; instead, it is a slow and cumulative process that spans generations. As linguistic innovations are initiated and adopted by a community, they slowly accumulate within that population, gradually causing it to diverge from the original language¹. When studying language change, researchers typically distinguish between two main processes: the emergence of a new linguistic feature, known as *innovation*, and the spread of that feature throughout a speech community, known as *actuation* (Croft, 2008; Dediu & Moisik, 2019; Solé & Vives, 2012; Stevens & Harrington, 2014; Yu, 2013). While innovation is often seen as an individual-level process, actuation is mostly a group-level process that involves competing language variants.

At the individual level, differences in a person's characteristics may help explain why certain people are more likely to innovate. These phenomena have been extensively studied in the field of socio-linguistics. For example, Eckert (2000) and Labov (2001) suggested that teenagers are particularly likely to create and adopt linguistic innovations. They also point out that linguistic innovations often emerge from individuals who are part of socially marginalized groups (Labov, 1966, 1972). More generally, an intricate interplay would exist among age, gender, social class, and personality (Labov, 1972; see Illustration 2). The recent advent of social media has given a new tool to researchers, as it can help identify the specific individuals innovating and driving language change in online social networks (Del Tredici & Fernández, 2018; Dietz et al., 2007; Eisenstein, 2019; Eisenstein et al., 2014; Gerow et al., 2018; Gerrish & Blei, 2010; Goel et al., 2016; Kooti et al., 2012).

¹ Determining when a linguistic variety is considered a separate language versus a dialect can be challenging as it depends on the criteria used to differentiate them (Rooy, 2020). It is a complex issue that we will not explore further here.

INTRODUCTION

Illustration 2: Aya Nakamura is a French musical artist known for her linguistic innovations. For instance, in her lyrics “J’suis pas ta catin djadja, genre en catchana baby tu dead ça”, “djadja” and “catchana” are borrowed from Bambara (a language spoken in Mali), while “baby” and “dead” are loanwords from English. The entire sentence, however, is structured in French, blending traditional vocabulary like “catin” with contemporary slang such as “genre”. The French language she uses strongly showcases the evolving nature of language, and supports previous theories of sociolinguistics. (Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license, from Wikipedia)

After a linguistic innovation appears in a population, it can (or not) spread through a speech community (“actuation”). Here too, sociolinguists suggest that an individual’s personal characteristics may help explain why certain individuals are more inclined to adopt and propagate innovative forms compared to others. For example, Labov (2001) suggested that women more often drive linguistic change, as they would be more sensitive to social norms and thus more likely to adopt and propagate ‘prestige’ forms of language. Also at the individual-level, the position of a person within their social circle can impact their ability to effectively spread new innovative forms. While intuitively we might think that individuals central to their community would be the most likely to propagate linguistic innovations, it has been suggested that it is actually the individuals who bridge different groups and communities who are the real propagators of innovations (J. Milroy & Milroy, 1978, 1985; L. Milroy, 1987; L. Milroy & Milroy, 1992).

While these factors primarily operate at the individual level, the spread and adoption of linguistic innovations within a population depend on various group-related factors. A common perspective in language sciences compares the evolution of language to biological evolution, where genetic mutations are likened to linguistic innovations, selected or not depending on their relevance. Just as a mutation that allows greater resistance to the sun (such as a higher melanin production) is more likely to be selected in countries near the equator than in Scandinavia, certain language traits (whether words, sounds, or grammar) are likely to be more relevant in certain cultures or environments (Honkola et al., 2018). This relates to the idea of the *communicative need* proposal, which suggests that language evolves under the pressure of efficient communication (Gao & Regier, 2022; Gibson et al., 2019; Kemp et al., 2018). In this perspective, languages adopt particular forms partly due to the necessity of being both informative (to support effective communication) and at a minimal

cost (to minimize cognitive load, among others). To do so, they must adapt to the culture, environment, and network structure in which they are evolving.

Culture. The lexicon of a given human society is likely to reflect its beliefs, activities, and adapt to the emergence of new concepts or objects within it. For example, the Tzotzil people, known for their hand-weaving of colorful textiles, have developed hundreds of compound forms to describe different dimensions of color (MacKeigan & Muth, 2006). A population's lexicon may also adapt to its subsistence mode. For instance, the Piraha people have a limited number of words for counting (M. C. Frank et al., 2008), whereas the Himba people have a wider range of number-related words. This difference is likely because the Piraha people rely predominantly on hunting and gathering for sustenance, while the Himba people primarily engage in herding. Furthermore, recent studies suggest that due to their subsistence mode, hunter-gatherers would be particularly proficient in naming odor (Majid & Kruspe, 2018).

Throughout this thesis, we take a non-judgmental stance on the world's different languages, without placing any above others. Unlike 19th-century anthropologists who believed in a single path of cultural evolution (also called unilineal evolution; Morgan, 1877; Spencer, 1898; among others), stating that Western society represented the highest form of development, we strongly disagree with such a view. Instead, we embrace the concept of *multilineal* evolution (Boas, 1940; Steward, 1955) which recognizes the adaptation of each human culture to diverse environments, resulting in distinct evolutionary pathways where multiple independent paths of development coexist. Thus, even if differences in complexity between languages may exist, we study these differences in a value-neutral manner, avoiding comparisons that imply notions of superiority or inferiority.

Environment. Languages also adapt to their environment. As populations reside in diverse environments such as jungles, deserts, temperate or equatorial climates, there arises a need to refer to distinct features. Consequently, it is reasonable to assume that a population's lexicon is tailored to describe its specific environment (Wierzbicka, 1990). Even though the idea that Inuit people would have over 50 words to describe the snow has been exaggerated (Krupnik & Müller-Wille, 2010), Regier et al. (2016) showed that languages that tend to merge "snow" and "ice" under a single term tend to be spoken in warmer climates. Similarly, Urban (2012) found that populations living at high altitudes often use the same word to describe cloud and fog (but see Urban, 2023, for a more nuanced approach). Furthermore, there are even more surprising

examples of language adapting to the environment. For instance, languages spoken in dry climates tend to have fewer tonal distinctions, presumably due to the difficulty of precisely controlling vocal cords in such environments (Everett et al., 2015). Ejective consonants would be more prevalent in high-altitude regions due to the lower air pressure making it easier to produce them (Everett, 2013). Rugged terrain and denser vegetation can reduce the acoustic propagation of consonants; thus, languages spoken in such regions would tend to have fewer consonants (Maddieson & Coupé, 2015). These correlational studies illustrate how languages adapt to their environments, and some of their conclusions are also supported by experimental studies (Nölle et al., 2020).

Network structure. Finally, there are fundamental differences in the communicative networks in which we are embedded. Throughout this thesis, we will conceptualize populations in terms of *networks*, where individuals are "*nodes*" or "*agents*" and their interactions (whether they communicate with each other) are defined as "*links*". These networks are shaped by our daily interactions and can take different forms. For instance, they may vary in size - some being big and others small. Additionally, in some networks, individuals may be really well-connected to each other, whereas in others, the density of connections tends to be more sparse. This type of variation in network type can be induced by differences in culture. For example, it has been suggested that social networks in modern societies are very large and highly structured, while hunter-gatherer networks are typically smaller, distinguished by more densely interconnected individuals (Lupyan & Dale, 2010; Migliano et al., 2017). They can also be shaped by environmental factors. In a study employing portable wireless sensing technology, Migliano et al. (2020) meticulously tracked the movements of the Agta community members in the Philippines. Their findings revealed that the Agta residing in coastal camps had denser and more interconnected networks compared to their counterparts living in forest camps (see Illustration 3).

Illustration 3: This figure displays individuals (dots) in camps (encoded by dot colors). Width of lines connecting individuals is proportional to dyadic weights (non-kin links: gray lines; close kin links: red lines). (A) Forest camps. (B) Coastal camps. Scale bars, 1 km. Figure extracted from the study of Migliano et al (2020).

Thus, the diversity in network structures is vast, and each of us is part of these intricate interaction webs. Nevertheless, how does this relate to the evolution of language? The idea that network structure could influence language evolution was suggested, among others, by Trudgill (2011a) and Wray & Grace (2007), then expanded with correlational observational data (Lupyan & Dale, 2010; Nettle, 2012) and laboratory studies (Raviv et al., 2020). The latter shows that languages spoken by larger, more open populations tend to be morphologically simpler and easier to learn by adults compared to those spoken by smaller, more isolated populations.

THE EFFECTS OF ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY

We saw that cultural and environmental factors, as well as factors related to network structure, can affect languages. However, another important factor that has remained largely unexplored is human *anatomy* and *physiology*.

Our anatomy and physiology are primarily influenced by genetics, although they are also shaped to some degree by the environment and culture through processes of ontogenetic/individual adaptation. Contrary to common intuition, variation is predominantly distributed between individuals rather than between populations (Bamshad et al., 2003; Lewontin, 1972). Nevertheless, patterns of

variations between populations still exist. The relationship between genes and phenotypic traits involves very complex interactions, often not well understood. Additionally, the field of epigenetics has shown that gene expression can be modified during an individual's lifetime. These genetic differences, combined with environmental and cultural differences, are at the root of the phenotypic diversity observable within the world.

The variability in human anatomico-physiology is related to language in many ways. First, variability can concern the organs of our articulatory systems. Thus, each of us possesses a distinct speech production system, characterized by presumably unique attributes such as tone pitch, vocal qualities, and articulation settings. Beyond this natural variation, some individuals may also experience speech impairments or other idiosyncrasies. Stuttering is one example, among others. While most of the variation occurs between individuals, there is also a certain degree of variation across groups. As a result, some populations may differ in their average speech production or perception systems, which can potentially influence their language. This raises an intriguing question: to what extent can these physiological differences impact and shape the language of an entire group? This question has recently been addressed using various methods, including MRI scans, agent-based modeling, and statistical analyses, specifically in the context of cross-cultural variation in vocal tract anatomy. Below is a list of examples, indicating the anatomico-physiological system involved (in bold).

Hard palate. Dediu et al. (2019) examined how variations in the hard palate affect the acoustics of five vowels. The findings revealed that small biases² in the hard palate shapes resulted in subtle variations in the acoustics of the produced vowels. Notably, the study identified distinct patterns of variation among participants belonging to four broad ethnolinguistic groups. These subtle differences in speech production were likely amplified over generations as languages were passed down, potentially contributing to cross-linguistic differences in the use of these vowels between the four groups.

Anterior vocal tract. Producing the /r/ sound in North American English was known to involve distinct articulatory strategies, classified into two main categories relative to the shape of the tongue used (“bunched” vs “tip-up”). Using various techniques, Dediu & Moisik (2019) found that there is, in fact, a

² In this context, we define a bias as a systematic tendency or preference where one behavior is consistently favored or given a higher probability over another.

continuum of tongue shapes and that variation in the anatomy of the anterior vocal tract among individuals seems to influence the choice of articulatory strategies. Although these different articulatory strategies lead to acoustically similar sounds (Delattre & Freeman, 1968; Tiede et al., 2004; Zhou et al., 2008), the authors suggest that these differences may contribute to sound changes either because listeners may reinterpret subtle differences in the acoustic cues produced, or through indirect co-articulatory effects.

Palate. Illustrating another example, palates with no alveolar ridge prominence (see Illustration 4) have been found to potentially facilitate the production of click sounds (Dediu & Moisik, 2016; Kirchner, 1998; Napoli et al., 2014). Languages of populations where this particular palate type is on average more common are more likely to feature click sounds.

Illustration 4: Mid-sagittal palate profiles: (a) an example of a !Xóõ speaker's palate (retracing of Fig. 24 from Traill, 1985: 107) and (b) the palate of author SRM. While the !Xóõ language traditionally features clicks, the author's native language does not. Dediu & Moisik (2016) propose that the absence of alveolar ridge prominence would make the production of clicks slightly easier, thus promoting the presence of clicks in the language. Indeed, the absence of alveolar ridge seems more frequent in populations speaking click languages than in other populations. Extracted from Dediu & Moisik (2016).

Dentition. Additionally, evidence suggests that culture, through its impact on anatomy, may also indirectly influence language. Blasi et al. (2019) provide strong support for the theory that the increased usage of labiodentals (such as sounds like "f" and "v") coincided with the transition to agriculture (Hockett, 1985). The shift in diet resulted in the bite configuration commonly observed today (see Illustration 5, left). Conversely, the bite configuration of hunter-gatherers (see Illustration 5, right) due to the consumption of harder foods, also made the production of labiodental sounds more challenging, making these sounds less likely to occur in hunter-gatherer languages.

Illustration 5: Biomechanical modeling shows that labiodental sounds like “f” are easier to produce (and to accidentally arise) under overbite and overjet (A) than under the edge-to-edge bite (B) that prevailed before the Neolithic. Figure extracted from Blasi et al (2019)’s paper.

Middle ear. A large proportion of the Australian Aboriginal population used to develop chronic otitis media, a chronic ear infection that often causes partial hearing loss. This means that many speakers have lifelong changes in their ability to hear sounds, especially in the high or low frequencies. Butcher (2006; 2018) suggested that this altered hearing sensitivity might provide an explanation for why most Aboriginal languages tend to possess a centralized vowel system and often lack fricative sounds, among other typologically rare characteristics.

A *cultural evolution* perspective provides a lens through which we can understand the mechanisms underlying these examples. Indeed, one noteworthy aspect of cultural evolution is its ability to amplify very weak biases (S. Kirby et al., 2007). Many characteristics of a given language emerge from its repeated usage, learning, and processing in various social contexts. Thus, even a very weak bias (such as a small deviation in the production of a vowel acoustic) can be greatly amplified as language is repeatedly used and transmitted within a population. Because patterns of variation are not randomly distributed across populations (due to genetic, environmental, or cultural disparities), it is plausible to suggest that these subtle inter-individual differences may play a role in explaining cross-linguistic differences (Dediu et al., 2017; Dediu & Moisik, 2019).

Inner ear. While the previous examples highlight how small biases shared by many people could influence language at the group level, it is also likely that strong differences shared by few people can also impact language. An example of how a minority with significant physiological differences can influence a group’s language lies in the emergence of newly born sign languages. In the AI-

Sayyid Bedouin community, a small community of approximately 3,000 people in Israel, around 4% of the population is born deaf (Fox, 2008). Despite their small size and relative isolation, the Al-Sayyid Bedouin community has developed a unique sign language. The language is used by both deaf and hearing members of the community, and is taught in schools alongside spoken Arabic. It is a complex and sophisticated language, with its own grammar, syntax, and vocabulary. The language is not based on any existing sign language, and appears to have developed spontaneously within the community over generations through interactions between deaf and hearing members (Sandler et al., 2005). This is relatively similar to the Kata Kolok community, in which 2.2% of the population is born congenitally deaf, corresponding to approximately 50 individuals in a village of 2000 individuals. The sign language that emerged in this community is used by both deaf and hearing individuals, and is believed to be relatively recent (De Vos, 2011).

Taken together, these examples demonstrate how differences in anatomy and physiology can influence the evolution of language, potentially explaining several dimensions of variation between languages. This research is fascinating but relatively new, leaving ample room for further investigation and exploration of various dimensions. All of the previous examples primarily focus on inter-individual differences in anatomy and physiology and their impact on the *sound systems* of language. But does inter-individual variation in anatomy and physiology solely influence sound systems? What about other aspects of language, such as a language's *lexicon*? While the previous examples discuss the existing studies, I will now turn to the background and research questions of my Ph.D. dissertation.

FIRST PART: THE LINK BETWEEN COLOR PERCEPTION AND LEXICON

One exciting avenue for further investigation involves studying how inter-individual variation impacts other aspects of language than phonetics and phonology, such as semantics. Specifically, is it likely that small biases in our perception, when collectively shared, can result in cross-linguistic differences in our lexicons. Our focus is on the color domain, and we seek to comprehend how variations in color perception can influence our color vocabulary.

INTRODUCTION

While we could have investigated numerous other areas of perception and semantics, we chose to concentrate on the color domain for several reasons. First, color lexicons have long fascinated researchers in cognitive science, leading to a lot of available data. One notable example is the World Color Survey (Kay, 2009), initiated in the 1970s, which has continued to gather valuable information ever since. Additionally, linguists commonly describe the color systems of the languages they study, available in many online databases, like CLICS (Rzymiski et al., 2020) and Lexibank (List et al., 2022). Second, our understanding of the eye physiology and the genetics of color perception is well-established and extensively documented, which allows us to explore the genetic aspects of color perception. Third, the relation between eye physiology, color perception, and color lexicon has already been documented, which makes it possible to deepen hypotheses related to the impact of physiology on language (a more detailed explanation of this hypothesis will be provided later on).

Here too, we aim to understand patterns of diversity across languages, particularly in relation to colors. Indeed, color lexicons across the world show great diversity, both in the number of color terms³ used (ranging from just two to up to twelve - but see Witzel, 2019 for a more nuanced approach) or in the way they divide the color spectrum. Notably, numerous languages lack a specific term to talk about blue colors (285 out of a subset of 834 languages, as reported by Dediu, 2023; see Illustration 6), instead combining them under a more generic term encompassing other colors. As an example, many languages use a single word to talk about blue and green colors, called “grue” by linguists.

³ All along this Ph.D. dissertation, I will use the “color term” or “color word” to talk about *Basic Color Term*, as defined by Berlin & Kay (1991) criteria. To be considered a Basic Color Term, a color term should be monolexic, monomorphemic, its signification should not be included in any other color term, it must not be restricted to a single class of object, and it must be psychologically salient for all informants. More details about this definition are provided in Berlin & Kay’s (1991) book. This definition is the one most commonly used in color naming research.

Illustration 6: Map of the languages in the dataset, showing, for each, if there is a specific term for “blue” in the languages (dark blue dots) or not (yellow dots). Figure extracted from Dediu (2023).

When looking at color lexicons around the world, researchers are traditionally divided into two big categories. The first category consists of *universalists* who focus on the similarities among languages rather than the differences, suggesting that what may appear as diversity actually follows a structured universalist pattern. They argue that there exists a universal repertoire of thoughts and perceptions that influences all languages. Berlin and Kay (1969) provided compelling evidence in support of the universalist position by identifying two key regularities. First, languages tend to follow a predetermined pattern where colors are learned in successive stages. For example, languages with only two color terms have words for dark and light, while those with three terms have dark, light, and reddish colors; and so on. Secondly, the foci (most representative color of each color term) of different languages are located in similar specific regions. Several studies support this universalist claim using computer simulations (Lindsey & Brown, 2006), data analysis (Lindsey & Brown, 2009), or experiments (Heider & Olivier, 1972).

Relativists, on the other hand, argue that the division of the color spectrum is influenced by our environment and culture, and put forward the absence of physical or natural distinctions in the spectrum. Furthermore, they believe that our language can influence the way we perceive and think about the world, in line with the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis (Sapir, 1921; Whorf, 1940). Providing evidence for the latter, many cross-cultural studies are dedicated to observing whether different ways of naming color affect their perceived similarities, memorization, or development with time (Davidoff et al., 1999; Kay & Kempton,

1984; Roberson et al., 2004). Also, studies on hemispheric lateralization have shown that language influences color perception in the right visual field, highlighting the presence of interference related to language (Gilbert et al., 2006).

Of course, the truth probably lies between universalism and relativism (Regier & Kay, 2009). While language does affect color perception to a certain extent, there are also universal constraints that shape color vocabulary (Lindsey & Brown, 2021). Recent view on color lexicon suggests that color categorization may be independent of language (Siuda-Krzywicka et al., 2019), and that color lexicons are shaped by perceptual structure (as has traditionally been suggested), but also by patterns of communicative need (Gibson et al., 2017; Zaslavsky et al., 2018, 2019). Thus, color lexicons across the world would exhibit a quasi-optimal trade-off between complexity and accuracy (Zaslavsky et al., 2018). In this Ph.D. thesis, we recognize the importance of universalist constraints and the potential influence of language on perception. However, we will not explore the Sapir-Whorf direction of causation (language → perception) but rather the opposite one (perception → language). Specifically, we aim to investigate another important factor: variations in the eye physiology and their impact on color perception.

Traditionally, it has been assumed that given the shared architecture of their perceptual system, humans all perceive the world in a uniform manner. However, it is now recognized that variations in our color perceptual abilities do exist (Bosten, 2022). To better grasp the relationship between color perceptual abilities and color lexicons, let us first look at the processes underlying typical and atypical color perception. Color perception is a complex process involving the interaction between light, the eye, and the brain. When light strikes an object, certain wavelengths are reflected, enter the eye, pass through the lens, and focus on the retina. The retina contains specialized cells called cones, responsible for converting incoming light into electrical signals that the brain processes. Within these cones are pigments known as opsins, which are molecules that respond to specific wavelengths of light. Three types of cones (see Illustration 7) exhibit sensitivity to different wavelengths: opsins absorbing short wavelength (blue light) are coded on chromosome 7, while those absorbing middle (green light) and long wavelength (red light) are located on chromosome X. This means that males, who have one X chromosome, only possess one allele of the gene coding for red and green cones, and thus, are much more likely to develop genetic abnormal color perception.

Illustration 7: Normalized responsivity spectra of human cone cells: S (short wavelength; blue), M (middle wavelength; green), and L (long wavelength; red) types. From Wikipedia, attribution: BenRG / Public domain

Atypical color perception can be inherited or acquired. When *inherited*, it results from variations in the DNA sequences coding for the pigments in the cones (Deeb, 2005). The most common type of color blindness, deuteranopia, designates the condition where green cones are missing. A continuum of abnormal color perception between deuteranopia and normal color vision exists, and is called deuteranomaly. In this case, green cones exist but absorb almost the same wavelength as red cones (Deeb, 2005). Protanopia and protanomaly are slightly less frequent conditions caused by variations in the red-pigment gene. Overall, deuteranomaly, deuteranopia, protanomaly, and protanopia are pretty frequent (around 8% of Caucasian males; Birch, 2012) and lead to similar atypical color perception, affecting the distinction between red and green colors: throughout this Ph.D. dissertation, we will refer to them as *red-green abnormal color perception*.

Atypical color perception can also be *acquired* through various factors; here, we will focus only on the potential effect of UV incidence. It is well-established in the literature that UV-B causes damage to the lens (Hammond, 2012; Javitt & Taylor, 1995; Pokorny et al., 1987; Remington, 2012, 2012; Werner et al., 1990; Young, 1991), which occurs through two mechanisms: an increase in the lens opacity (Duncan et al., 1997; Hightower, 1995; West et al., 1998) and an increase in the concentration of yellow pigments (Young, 1994) that leads to a continuous darkening process known as *lens brunescence*. Although we know that UV incidence is strongly associated with lens brunescence, its impact on color

INTRODUCTION

perception is still yet not fully understood, and more data is needed to confirm the hypothesis of a causal pathway. Werner et al. (2010) found that an infant's lens allows 25 times more blue light transmission compared to the lens of an average 70-year-old. Delahunt et al. (2004) further suggest that the presence of yellow pigments in the lens can influence blue color perception, although compensation mechanisms might mask the effects. Their study shows that cataract⁴ removal leads to a noticeable improvement in color perception, particularly in the blue range. Furthermore, other studies suggest that color vision deficiencies in the blue range become more common as people age (Beirne et al., 2008; Cooper et al., 1991; D. W. Kline & Scialfa, 1996; Kinnear & Sahraie, 2002; Knoblauch et al., 1987; V. C. Smith et al., 1985; Verriest, 1963; Wijk et al., 1999), and in populations living in high UV incidence regions (Kaimbo Wa Kaimbo et al., 1994; Nacer et al., 2001). For example, Davies et al. (1998) studied color perception in 597 participants from Africa (Botswana, Malawi, and South Africa) and Europe (Greece, Spain, Ireland, and the UK), and found that African participants, and Greeks to a lesser extent, made more errors in the blue range than the other participants they tested. In addition, they found that the pattern of errors made by African participants resembled those exhibited by older British participants, suggesting that this is due to lens brunescence.

The question of the impact of eye physiology on color lexicons was discussed over a century ago. Early observations by Gladstone (1858) and later Geiger (1923) noted the confusion between green and blue in ancient texts, and are among the first to link this fact with a possible eye deficit linked to color perception. Rivers (1901) conducted color blindness tests on diverse native populations - mostly in Papua New Guinea and Australia - and found imperfect color discrimination in the green-blue-purple range in many of them. Supporting evidence emerged much later when Bornstein (1973) found that the proximity with the equator is correlated with the frequency of a composite color category "grue" and with the thickness of blue-absorbing intraocular pigment. He linked those two facts with the intensity and annual amount of UV that tends to be higher near the equator, and concluded that the use of a composite category including both blue and green colors is the result of increasing density of intraocular pigment (Ratliff, 1976). More recently, Lindsey and Brown (2002) proposed the *lens brunescence hypothesis* (see Illustration 8). To support this

⁴ Lens brunescence and cataract are both conditions that affect the lens of the eye, with the accumulation of yellow pigments. However, lens brunescence refers to the natural aging process of the lens, and typically does not cause significant vision impairment on its own. On the other hand, cataract is an abnormal condition where the lens becomes cloudy or opaque, leading to a significant impairment of vision.

INTRODUCTION

hypothesis, they asked young participants to classify color stimuli while wearing filtering glasses simulating different “lens-aging” conditions. They found that when participants were wearing the simulated aging condition, they used the term “blue” less often and tended to use a categorization pattern that could match a “grue” categorization schema.

Illustration 8: Schematic representation of the lens brunescence hypothesis. Populations living in areas with high UV incidence are more likely to experience a lens brunescence condition. This condition causes the lens to have a slight yellowish tint, filtering out blue wavelengths before they reach the retina. As a result, the ability to discriminate blue colors is diminished. This would be one of the reasons why populations in high UV incidence regions, like those near the Equator, frequently refer to “grue” colors.

However, there are some criticisms of this hypothesis. First, Ratliff (1976) argued that the differences in eye physiology between populations are minor and not responsible for variations in color perception. Second, compensatory strategies exist to counter visual deterioration over time (Kraft & Werner, 1999), suggesting that lens brunescence may not significantly impact color perception in the long term, especially since there are no inherent differences in eye physiology at birth. Furthermore, Hardy et al. (2005) conducted a study with both young and older participants, contradicting the findings of Lindsey & Brown (2002). They found that older individuals, despite experiencing lens aging, could still accurately identify different colors. Third, technological development and latitude are often correlated (Ember, 1978; Regier & Kay, 2004); thus, technological development could be seen as a confound for exposure to UV incidence. Finally, Regier & Kay (2004) showed that the actual focus for “grue” tends to align with either the English “blue” or “green” focus rather than being positioned in the middle of the green-blue range, as initially suggested.

Given the existence of arguments both in favor and against this theory, the first objective of this Ph.D. thesis was to reevaluate it using two additional approaches: a cross-cultural statistical analysis, and a natural experiment with the Himba population (these methods will be introduced in the **Methods** part). This will be the focus of the first part of the dissertation; more details will be provided in the **Plan** part of this Introduction.

SECOND PART: INTER-INDIVIDUAL VARIATION AND LANGUAGE CHANGE

In the example of “blue” developed above, differences in color perception are subtle, and shared by most people who have been exposed to the sun. Along with other examples related to variations in the vocal tract, it demonstrates how weak biases in the anatomy and physiology of a large proportion of the group can influence language. However, evidence also shows that strong biases shared by a minority can also affect the language of the entire group (e.g., the emergence of new sign languages in Israel or Indonesia). These real-world examples suggest that both small biases shared by many people and strong biases held by a few can affect language. Nevertheless, the precise processes underlying these mechanisms remain to be understood.

How many? We have yet to determine the specific ratio of biased individuals required to drive language change. If only half of the Himba population (in Northern Namibia) had lower discrimination abilities in the blue range, would that be sufficient to promote the retention of the usage of a single term for “blue” and “green” colors?

How strong? Additionally, one may wonder how this interacts with the strength of the bias. How strong should a bias be in order to spread within a population? For example, if people have a bias that is so strong it cannot be overcome (like in the case of deaf people in the Al-sayyid community), would a very small percentage of the population be enough to drive language changes within the group? Similarly, when it comes to color perception, what would the color lexicon look like if some Himba people were completely unable to see the difference between blue and green colors?

Who? Sociolinguistic work has helped us understand how individual differences affect the likelihood of innovating. Then, one could hypothesize that if the individuals carrying a bias are not popular or influential enough, their biases may not spread through the population. This aspect can be linked to various individual characteristics like gender, age, or social class, as mentioned earlier. For instance, let us consider the scenario where the chief of a Himba village (who is assumed to be popular and someone whom others would want to imitate or resemble) has a slight difficulty distinguishing between closely related shades of blue and green, leading to a consistent usage of the term “grue”: it is likely to imagine that he would potentially influence the population to avoid adopting two separate terms for “blue” and “green”.

Where in the network? This question is closely related to the previous one, but here we are not examining popularity as defined in previous sociolinguistic theory. Instead, we focus on an individual's position within a network. Regardless of the number of friends or social prestige, some individuals may be positioned within a network in a way that enhances their propensity to effectively spread linguistic innovations. Previous research has suggested that individuals with weak ties, who serve as bridges between different communities, are more likely to facilitate the spread of innovation (J. Milroy & Milroy, 1978, 1985; L. Milroy, 1987; L. Milroy & Milroy, 1992). Returning to color perception, we can imagine that a Himba person with a significant lens brunescence condition, whose family is spread across multiple villages (and who regularly travels between these villages), would be more likely to slow down the spread of a "blue/green" linguistic innovation.

For how long? Finally, we saw that, because these biases can be subtle and occur over extended periods, it is also necessary for individuals to interact for a sufficiently long time. This raises an interesting question: how long is it needed for a language to change and adapt to the idiosyncrasies of its speakers?

It is important to raise these questions, especially since many examples exist where a language has not (yet) adapted to the peculiarities of its speakers. A striking example is the "trill" sound. The trill sound (which corresponds to the rolled "r" in Spanish, among other languages), is relatively common in Romance languages like Spanish or Romanian (Anselme et al., 2023). However, it seems that a few percent of the native population cannot produce this sound due to physiological factors that remain to be determined (D. Dediu, p.c). These individuals have to employ alternative strategies and often face negative judgment from others. Interestingly, despite the existence of these biased individuals, these languages still feature trills in their sound systems. Therefore, a language does not always adapt to the specificity of its speakers, as coping with variability is the essence of human communication.

Certainly, addressing these questions individually is intriguing, but it is also crucial to consider them together, as they may interact with one another. These questions have rarely been addressed in the previous literature, because there is traditionally a strong focus on studying homogenous groups and universal biases. While widespread variations across various dimensions (such as speech perception and production) exist, these patterns of variation often go unnoticed or are overlooked due to their inherent nature. Here, we argue that variation may hold valuable insight into the mechanisms of language adaptation and change.

Thus, we aim to investigate these questions, namely to what extent and how individual-level variations impact language evolution. This will be the focus of the second part of this Ph.D. dissertation, which we will discuss in more detail in the *Plan* part of this Introduction.

METHODS

In general, studying language evolution poses significant challenges due to a number of factors. First, there is a lack of direct evidence from the past as we (very sadly) do not have a time machine to go back in time and observe how language emerged and changed over time. This scarcity of historical data makes it difficult to precisely understand the mechanisms and specific changes that occurred over time. Additionally, language is a complex system influenced by multiple interacting factors, such as culture, cognition, anatomy, physiology, and social dynamics, and disentangling the intricate interplay between these variables can be challenging. Furthermore, language change operates on a timescale spanning thousands of years, making it arduous to accurately track and measure its gradual transformations. Needless to say, the historical data we have about languages is limited to a very small number of languages, and also to a very short period of time. While evidence suggests that written systems date back to around 3200 BCE (as discussed in Robinson, 2007, among other sources), it is widely acknowledged that humans had developed forms of communication long before this period. Researchers in language sciences have ingeniously devised strategies to overcome this challenge and employ various innovative methods, which I have used throughout my Ph.D. research.

(1) Statistical analysis. One approach involves examining current language data and conducting cross-cultural statistical analyses to draw inferences. This approach provides generalizable results about language evolution that can be applied to a wide range of populations, thanks to the large sample sizes and controls over various factors. However, this approach has potential flaws (Roberts & Winters, 2012). First, it heavily depends on data quality, which can be challenging as it involves large-scale datasets encompassing a wide range of languages, making it impossible for any researcher to be an expert on all of them. Another concern is temporal resolution, as the data used for studying language evolution over time are often drawn from only one period in time. Also, some caution should be taken to avoid overgeneralizing findings and overlooking contextual variation. Finally, a significant risk is the presence of spurious

correlations, where large datasets with multiple variables may exhibit correlations misinterpreted as direct causal links.

(2) Natural experiment. In natural experiments, researchers observe and analyze naturally occurring events in a real-world context, without deliberate manipulation (Dinardo, 2010; Dunning, 2012). Unlike traditional controlled experiments, natural experiments take advantage of naturally existing variations or circumstances acting as quasi-experimental conditions. Unlike controlled laboratory experiments, natural experiments have high real-world relevance, as they occur in natural settings and might generalize well to real-world contexts. However, they lack the ability to control or manipulate variables, making it difficult to establish causal relationships. Furthermore, there are a lot of various confounding factors that may influence the observed outcomes and lead to inaccurate conclusions.

(3) Laboratory experiments. In the field of language evolution, laboratory experiments are often based on a key paradigm: *iterated learning*. Iterated learning designates the process by which individuals learn from and then transmit information to others, who, in turn, learn and transmit it to subsequent generations (see Illustration 9). While this paradigm can be applied to a wide range of methods (S. Kirby et al., 2014), it was extensively used to design laboratory experiments using generational transmission (S. Kirby et al., 2008; see Scott-Phillips & Kirby, 2010 for a review). These experiments could simulate the emergence of core properties of language in-vivo, such as the emergence of compositionality. When applied to sign languages, iterated learning experiments also observe the development of key language-like properties similar to those documented in newly emerging sign systems (Motamedi et al., 2019). They have several advantages: first, they make it possible to test specific hypotheses about language evolution. Second, by manipulating specific variables and isolating their effects, they help understand the causal relationships between different factors. Third, they provide the opportunity to investigate multiple groups, making it a valuable tool for studying variation. However, they are constrained in terms of group size and timespan. They also might not fully capture the complexity of real-world language evolution, thus not providing a comprehensive understanding of language as a whole. This makes it hard to determine their ecological validity, namely whether their conclusions will generalize to “real” language evolution. Finally, they can only be conducted with modern humans, and due to practical considerations, they are often limited to WEIRD humans (Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich, and Democratic; Henrich et al., 2010).

Illustration 9: Graphical representation of Iterated Learning

(4) Computer modeling. Computer modeling aims to offer a simplified version of reality, and allows the manipulation of different parameters, in order to understand how each part works. Indeed, social networks are typically influenced by several different interacting forces. While these forces may seem understandable when considered individually, their interactions can lead to complex patterns. Modeling is widely used in various scientific fields, but its application in the social sciences is relatively new and met with skepticism (Acerbi et al., 2020, p. 11, lines 2-12):

“Social scientists tend to be sceptical that very simple models can tell us anything useful about something as immensely complex as human culture. But the clear lesson from biology is that models are extremely useful in precisely this situation. Biologists face similarly immense complexity in the natural world. Despite this, models are useful. Population genetics models of the early 20th century helped to reconcile new findings in genetics with Darwin’s theory of evolution. Ecological models helped understand interactions between species, such as predator-prey cycles. These models are hugely simplified: population genetics models typically make ridiculous assumptions like infinitely large populations and random mating. But they are useful because they precisely specify each part of a complex system, improving understanding of reality.”

Modeling can take a wide range of forms, but here, we focus on *agent-based models*, which take the general form of a population of artificial agents communicating with each other. These models make it possible to formulate hypotheses on aspects that other methods cannot investigate, as they allow researchers to study language evolution over very long periods, in large populations and various network structures (Ke et al., 2008). Also, modeling can take into account the complexity of language evolution dynamics and study the causal roles of specific factors and interactions. However, finding a good compromise between simplicity and specificity is not always an easy task (Gong

INTRODUCTION

& Shuai, 2013): these models are often criticized for oversimplifying reality, but excessive simplicity can be problematic as certain features only emerge at higher levels of complexity. Also, some scientists propose that they only function as exploration tools (Fagiolo et al., 2007). Indeed, the results of agent-based simulations rely on the settings chosen by users, and specific values assigned to these settings most often influence the model's results.

The above methods offer researchers means to overcome the challenges encountered in the study of language evolution, and they might help us answer our research questions. During this Ph.D. thesis, we explored the effect of inter-individual variation in color perception and its impact on color naming (Part 1) using Method 1 and Method 2. The results raised intriguing questions about the exact mechanisms underlying the impact of inter-individual variation on language evolution, such as the proportion of biased individuals, the strength of their biases, their position in the network, and how these individuals influence language. To address these questions, we used two other methods in Part 2: a laboratory experiment (Method 3) and an agent-based model (Method 4). The use of several different methods, also called “triangulation” practice, can help us strengthen the reliability of the findings by corroborating results obtained through different methods (Motamedi et al., 2022), and allows to gain a more nuanced understanding of our research question.

PLAN

	Part 1		Part 2		
Hypothesis	Variations in color perception affect color lexicons		Individual-level biases can influence languages at a group-level		
Chapter	1	2	3	4	5
Method	(1) Cross-cultural analysis 				
Focus	What factors shape color lexicons? What role of UV incidence?	Are there differences in color perception between Himba and French people?	How do participants adapt to the idiosyncracies of a minority?	How does language evolve in heterogeneous groups?	How do variations emerge in different type of network structure?

Illustration 10: Summary of the plan of the Ph.D. dissertation.

This doctoral dissertation is divided into two parts (see Illustration 10). The first part adopts a transversal view of the evolution of languages, particularly delving into the relationship between perception and language in the domain of colors.

Specifically, [Chapter 1](#) addresses this issue through a cross-cultural statistical study (**Method 1**) involving 142 populations for which we gathered data on color vocabulary, environmental (including UV incidence rates), and cultural factors. We aimed to determine if the influence of UV incidence remains significant when considering other cultural and environmental factors. By applying several statistical tests, the study highlights the multifactorial nature of color vocabularies, shaped by a combination of cultural and environmental influences. Moreover, the significance of the impact of UV incidence on vocabularies was still present after controlling for multiple confounding factors, supporting the lens brunescence hypothesis. This study was published in *Scientific Reports*. Additionally, we present a debate that emerged following the publication of this article, in which other researchers raise concerns about the relevance of the lens brunescence hypothesis, and to which we had the opportunity to answer. This interaction was made public and available in “*Matters Arising*”, a section of the *Scientific Reports* journal.

[Chapter 2](#) aims to investigate the same hypothesis using a natural experiment (**Method 2**). We conducted two fieldworks in 2021 and 2022 in a remote region of northern Namibia with the Himba population (see Illustrations 3 and 11). The Himba people are a cultural group which has been relatively isolated from the industrialized world until recent years, but which is increasingly gaining access to education, technology, and urban exposure. The Himba population is particularly relevant to study our hypothesis because it is exposed to high levels of UV radiation, which, added to the mostly outdoor lifestyle of the Himba, might strongly impact their eye physiology. Furthermore, the Himba people initially lacked a distinct term to differentiate between blue and green colors, and they only acquired such term relatively recently due to exposure to schooling (Mylonas et al., 2022). We conducted numerous color perception and color naming tests, comparing their results with those of a French group. We found significant differences in color perception, with the Himba people performing less accurately on average. However, these differences apply to both red and blue colors, challenging the processes underlying the lens brunescence hypothesis. Nevertheless, since differences in perception exist, they may still be responsible for variations in color vocabulary. These findings will be supplemented by future modeling work before being submitted for publication. Therefore, the findings presented in this Chapter 2 should be considered preliminary.

Illustration 11: Experimental setup during the second fieldwork (October 2022). Credit: Serge Caparos.

The second part of the thesis adopts an interactive view of language evolution and explores the mechanisms that explain how inter-individual variation can impact language evolution.

[Chapter 3](#) presents a controlled laboratory experiment (**Method 3**) conducted during a research exchange at the *Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics* in Nijmegen (the Netherlands). The laboratory experiment we used builds upon the work of Raviv et al. (2019a, 2019b), who examined language evolution using closed micro-societies. In our experiment, we deliberately introduce a bias by restricting one participant's keyboard to prevent the production of certain letters (the *biased letters*). This aims to simulate a speech idiosyncrasy that individuals may experience in real life, similar to examples observed in vocal tract variation. While we could have explored a perceptual impairment related to color perception, we chose to keep the design as simple as possible to start with, leaving this idea for future research. During the experiment, all participants are briefly exposed to a fake miniature language represented by unique images of aliens. One participant acts as the *producer* and is tasked with describing the image they are shown, while their partner, the *guesser*, tries to identify the correct image out of a set of eight options. Both participants are instructed to communicate as effectively as possible and receive feedback on the success of their interaction. They interact successively in pairs and switch their partner every round. We compare two types of groups: the *control* groups, in which no participant is biased, and the *heterogeneous* groups, in which one person is

deliberately biased. Specifically, we aim to understand whether participants converge on a shared language featuring the biased letters. The preliminary findings suggest that introducing some variation within a group slightly changes the group's language, especially for groups that struggle to learn the initial language. They also highlight the presence of a significant adaptation observed during interactions between pairs.

The Chapter 3 experiment gives us valuable insight into how groups with variation behave. However, the groups contain only four people, with only one biased individual at a time, with a fixed biased and a fixed network structure. Aiming to complement this approach, the last studies used a multi-agent model (**Method 4**) based on Bayesian communication (Griffiths & Kalish, 2007). In this model, language is represented by abstract features (binary, multinomial, or continuous) that are expressed in each individual's utterances. The latter features can represent various linguistic aspects, such as the use of different sounds, word order preferences, etc. Each agent possesses an internal representation of their language, with agents being born with *unbiased* priors (no prior expectations towards the language) or *biased* priors (inclined towards a particular language value). These agents "speak" by sampling an utterance from their internal representation of the language. They also "listen" to the utterances of their neighbors and adjust their internal language representation based on what they hear. We create populations of agents in specific network structures and allow them to interact over an extended period, which helped us understand how language evolves and adapts within heterogeneous social groups.

In [Chapter 4](#), we used this multi-agent model to understand how different parameters affect language, such as varying percentages of biased individuals and different bias strengths, in diverse network types. The results, published in *Frontiers in Psychology*, show that even unbiased agents, even when belonging to the majority, do adapt their language to the biased agents. Thus, the emergent shared language of the whole community is influenced by the bias of a minority. Furthermore, we observed that biased individuals retain traces of their biases even after interacting with the unbiased majority (in scale-free networks), and inter-individual variation promotes the emergence of linguistic communities in certain types of networks. Ultimately, we found substantial differences in our results among various network types (small-world, scale-free, random). These findings pushed us to explore in greater detail how these networks can facilitate or generate variation from the beginning.

Thus, [Chapter 5](#) is based on the same type of agent-based models as Chapter 4 but investigates how different network structures influence the emergence of inter- and intra-individual variation. The research was conducted during a research exchange at the *Artificial Intelligence Lab* in Brussels (Belgium), and is currently being reviewed for publication in the *Cognitive Science* journal. The chapter highlights the significant role of global network structure in shaping inter-individual language variation (but not intra-individual variation), suggesting that inter-individual language variation is more likely to emerge in networks with high average path length and a network structure characterized by the presence of many sub-groups.

Finally, I will summarize the main findings from all the Chapters in the general [Discussion](#) and contextualize them within the context of my personal scientific journey during the Ph.D. I will present a general conclusion, acknowledge specific limitations, and propose potential directions for future research.

In summary, through this Ph.D. research, our aim is to enhance our comprehension of how human physiology influences semantics and to explore the effects of inter-individual variation on language evolution, using a variety of methodologies. We believe it may provide valuable insights into the mechanisms underlying language evolution within heterogeneous populations, and it may help us develop a comprehensive understanding of how to effectively incorporate patterns of variation into the study of language evolution.

INTRODUCTION

PART 1

Image generated by MidJourney AI using the following prompt: "environment and culture shape color perception"

INTRODUCTION

1

ENVIRONMENT AND CULTURE SHAPE BOTH THE COLOUR LEXICON AND THE GENETICS OF COLOUR PERCEPTION

CONTEXT

This work was published in *Scientific Reports* in 2021 (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-98550-3>), in collaboration with Emma Meeussen, Asifa Majid, and Dan Dediu. Supplementary Materials (containing all the data, script, and analyses) are available on GitHub: <https://github.com/ddediu/colors-UV>.

Acknowledgements

We thank Delwin Lindsey and Angela Brown for making available their database.

ABSTRACT

Many languages express ‘blue’ and ‘green’ under an umbrella term ‘grue’. To explain this variation, it has been suggested that changes in eye physiology, due to UV-light incidence, can lead to abnormalities in blue-green color perception which causes the color lexicon to adapt. Here, we apply advanced statistics on a set of 142 populations to model how different factors shape the presence of a specific term for blue. In addition, we examined if the ontogenetic effect of UV-light on color perception generates a negative selection pressure against

inherited abnormal red-green perception. We found the presence of a specific term for blue was influenced by UV incidence as well as several additional factors, including cultural complexity. Moreover, there was evidence that UV incidence was negatively related to abnormal red-green color perception. These results demonstrate that variation in languages can only be understood in the context of their cultural, biological, and physical environments.

INTRODUCTION

One of the major puzzles facing the language sciences is how to best account for the factors and processes shaping the observed patterns of linguistic diversity today. The color lexicon is particularly interesting from this perspective. The long-standing emphasis has been on establishing universals (Berlin & Kay, 1969). Recent work shows that universal tendencies in color naming systems arise from perceptual structure (Regier et al., 2007) and communicative needs (Conway et al., 2020; Gibson et al., 2017; Zaslavsky et al., 2019). At the same time, it is just as important to be able to characterize and explain variation found in color terminologies (Malt & Majid, 2013). Languages differ in the number of basic color terms and which distinctions exactly are recognized for naming. Some languages only lexicalize 'black', 'white', and 'red'; while others make many more distinctions, including 'green' and 'blue'.

Blue is a particularly interesting color term to study since there are competing explanations for why it would emerge as a word. According to one class of theories, color terms emerge from salient features of the environment: for blue this would include water bodies, such as the sea, lakes, or rivers, as well as visibility of a blue sky which is affected by climate and humidity. That is, the ecological environment (such as the presence of lakes) may be a factor relevant in shaping the color lexicon (Brown & Lindsey, 2004; Rivers, 1901; Webster et al., 2007; Wierzbicka, 1990), suggesting that languages spoken in different environments may categorize the color continuum in different ways. An alternative account appeals to cultural practices, such as the presence of dyeing technologies (Berlin & Kay, 1969; Conklin, 1973; Levinson, 2000) and industrialization (Gibson et al., 2017). On this account, the emergence of blue comes about in those societies where blue dyes are used to color artifacts. More generally, it has been predicted that complex color terminologies (including the presence of blue) emerge in more complex societies (Ember, 1978; Levinson, 2000; Naroll, 1970).

A third explanation for the emergence of blue is grounded in physiology (Bornstein, 1973; Lindsey & Brown, 2002). It has been suggested that increased exposure to ultraviolet light, specifically to UV-B, affects the physiology of the lens of the eye (Hammond, 2012; Javitt & Taylor, 1995; Pokorny et al., 1987; Remington, 2012; Werner et al., 1990; Young, 1991), increasing, in the long term, lens opacity (Hightower, 1995; West et al., 1998) and yellow pigmentation density inside the lens (Young, 1994), which affects in turn how light reaches the retina (see Figure 1 Panel D). This process of lens brunescence, where yellow pigments absorb short-wavelength (blue) before reaching the retina, may reduce the ability to perceive the blue part of the color spectrum (Delahunt et al., 2004; Tregillus et al., 2016; Weale, 1988; Werner et al., 2010; see Figure 1 Panel E), increasing the probability that a single 'grue' term combining 'blue' and 'green' is used instead. That is, there is no distinct lexicalization of 'blue' (Lindsey & Brown, 2002; S. Walter, 2011). Lens brunescence is driven by environmental exposure to UV-B radiation which is related to latitude (locations closer to the equator receive more sunlight than those closer to the poles), altitude (higher elevations have less ozone filtering), climate and humidity (cloud coverage), vegetation (close versus open environments), and culture (amount and type of outdoor activity). This predicts that in populations with high exposure to UV-B radiation, the persistent loss of sensitivity to blue in adults across generations should generate negative pressure against the development of a 'blue' category or a tendency to lose it, while in populations with low exposure to UV-B incidence, other processes may proceed unhindered enabling the emergence and retention of 'blue'. If true, we should observe a statistical tendency for fewer languages with a dedicated word for blue at high UV-B incidence (particularly close to the equator).

Figure 1: (Panel **A**): Map of languages and populations in our data. Each circle represents one language and corresponding population, with the presence (blue) or absence (yellow) for a specific term for 'blue'. The circle radius is proportional to the population frequency of red/green abnormal color perception. The intensity of the background magenta is proportional to the incidence of UV-B radiation as given by the NASA *Total Ozone Mapping Spectrometer* (TOMS) for the year 1998. This map was generated with the package *maps* in R version 4.0.559, which uses public domain data from the *Natural Earth project*. (Panel **B**): Posterior density plots of the presence of a word for blue across Bayesian regression models. (Panel **C**): Posterior density plots of the best predictors of the frequency of red-green abnormal color perception across Bayesian regression models. The plots in panels (**B**) and (**C**) are based on the analyses detailed in the “Results” section and were generated using R59. (Panel **D**): The lens brunescence hypothesis, as detailed in this paper. UV rays cause the lens to opacity and become yellower (top), filtering blue light, so that the perceived spectrum (on the right) contains less blue and more green, compared to the non-affected eye (bottom). (Panel **E**): A simulation of different types of color perception abnormalities. From left to right: normal vision; one type of red-green abnormal color perception (deuteranopia); strong lens brunescence (yellow filter and darkening of the image); both lens brunescence and deuteranopia, hypothesized to result in decreased biological fitness relative to other color vision types. Background image cropped from a photo by Joydeep Pal on [Unsplash](#) under a free-to-use [license](#). For deuteranopia we used Coblis—The Color Blindness [Simulator](#) and checked the results with the Colorblind [Web Page Filter](#). The lens brunescence filter is inspired by Walter, 2011: we used Adobe Lightroom classic version 10.0 with a yellow filter and darkening to simulate a Kodak yellow filter. For more details, see the “Results”, “Materials and Methods” and Supplementary Materials.

Previous cross-cultural analyses linking UV-B incidence and the presence of 'blue' (Lindsey & Brown, 2002) may have been biased by the lack of control for various confounds (especially language contact and inheritance from a shared proto-language; Ladd et al., 2015), exclusion of possible alternative explanatory factors (such as cultural complexity, environmental influences), lack of modeling of causal pathways, and the statistical methods used. Therefore, we combine multiple explanatory factors and potential confounds, including language contact generally (since specific data about the borrowing of words for blue is not available for most languages under consideration) and language family, subsistence strategy and population size (as proxies for cultural complexity; Henrich, 2004; Powell et al., 2009 as systematic, quantitative data about cultural artefacts and dyeing techniques across cultures does not exist), latitude (which partly determines UV-B incidence), climate, ecology and distance to large bodies of water (as proxies for various environmental influences) using a comprehensive database and advanced statistical methods. In doing so, we not only test the role of UV-B light on the development of the color lexicon, but also explicate the extent to which additional hypothesized factors shape the presence of a specific term for blue, and where relevant through which causal pathways specifically.

Environmentally-induced (or acquired) abnormal color perception is not the only type of color deficiency. Notably, inherited red-green color-blindness has a relatively simple genetic basis where certain alleles at the opsin genes on the X chromosome encode for abnormal pigments, resulting in a higher incidence of abnormal color perception in males specifically affecting the low (red) and mid (green) frequencies of the visual spectrum (Figure 1 Panel E). It has previously been suggested that a subsistence strategy based on hunting and gathering might generate selective pressures against red-green abnormal color perception due to the high survival relevance of these colors in the wild, while the transition to agriculture and, in particular the industrial revolution, may have greatly relaxed these pressures (Adam, 1969; Stark, 2020).

Moreover, these two broad types of abnormal color perception could interact with each other. At the individual level, for somebody already affected by a relatively profound red-green deficiency, also acquiring lens brunescence would have devastating effects on the ability to use color (Figure 1 Panel E), and may affect survival and possibly the ability to produce and raise offspring. This predicts that, despite their different and a priori independent causal mechanisms (environmental exposure vs genetic), a negative correlation between the two could emerge across evolutionary time, in that there may be stronger selective

pressure against the alleles responsible for red-green abnormal color perception in populations with high UV-B exposure, leading across generations to an overall lower frequency of such inherited abnormalities in these populations (Brown & Lindsey, 2004). Here, we not only test the hypothesis that there is a negative relationship between UV-B incidence and the population frequency of red-green color deficiency using advanced methods and controls, we also include the potential influence of subsistence strategy.

In summary, we test two main hypotheses, one linking the existence of a dedicated word for blue to UV-B incidence while simultaneously controlling for other factors, and a second concerning the selective pressures against abnormal red-green vision in different environments. We do so on a large dataset of 142 populations (Figure 1 Panel A) speaking languages from 32 families across the world, for which we collected information about the existence of a dedicated word for blue, the incidence of ultraviolet light, and the frequency of red-green color deficiency, as well as data on elevation, population size, subsistence strategy, climate, ecology, distance to large bodies of water, and several additional variables concerning the populations and physical environments they inhabit (see Methods and materials and Supplementary Materials). We used Bayesian hierarchical regression, mediation and path analysis, and various machine learning techniques, informed by previous research and causal modeling, to specifically test these hypotheses in a comprehensive manner. We found that both hypotheses were by and large supported, but importantly they only captured part of the overall picture (Figure 1 Panels B and C). While variation in UV-B incidence (ultimately due to variation in latitude) was the most important predictor of 'blue', population size and distance to large bodies of standing water also played a role, with their effects mediated by climate and subsistence strategy. Likewise, there was a lower frequency of people with red-green color deficiency in populations closer to the equator (i.e., with more lens brunescence), and whose languages lacked a dedicated word for blue.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

We collected data from 142 populations, extending and re-checking earlier databases (Brown & Lindsey, 2004) considerably, especially concerning information about the color lexicon and the incidence of abnormal red-green color perception. Each population was uniquely identified by its *Glottolog* code (Hammarström et al., 2018) of the primary language spoken and its geographic

location. According to *Glottolog*, these languages belong to 32 *language families* (the most represented being *Indo-European* (41), *Atlantic-Congo* (19) and *Afro-Asiatic* (13)) distributed across 6 *macroareas* (Africa (31), Australia (2), Eurasia (79), Papunesia (9), North America (9) and South America (12)). We also obtained the geographic location of the putative origins of each family (Hammarström et al., 2018; Wichmann et al., 2010). The geographic locations were cos-transformed: $\cos(\text{longitude})$ ranges between -1.0 (-180) and 1.0 (180), and $1.0 - \cos(\text{latitude})$ ranges between -1.0 (the South Pole), 0.0 (the equator) and 1.0 (the North Pole).

Based on their location, for each population we obtained the following data: the list of its *geographic neighbors* (derived from the Delaunay triangulation of our geographic locations taking into account large bodies of water; Cysouw et al., 2012); its $\log(\text{elevation}+1)$ using the [Mapzen](#) data (through R's `elevatr` package); the $\log(\text{distances})$ to the nearest lake, ocean, river, or large body of water in general (using the OpenStreetMap data as per Bentz et al., 2018); and data about *specific humidity* (using data from the [NOAA](#), as the mean of the yearly medians and interquartile ranges), and *climate* and *ecology* (as in Bentz et al., 2018, we conducted Principal Component Analysis on the 19 variables from [WorldClim](#) for the period 1960–1990, and we retained *PC1*, explaining 49.7% of the variance and reflecting low seasonality, wet and hot climates, *PC2*, 24.7%, high seasonality, hot and dry climates, and *PC3*, 8.6%, unclear interpretation). We calculated the *incidence of ultraviolet light (UV)* using the data from [NASA Total Ozone Mapping Spectrometer \(TOMS\)](#) for the year 1998 (in order to replicate the procedure in Brown & Lindsey, 2004): these contain daily measures of UV radiation received by the human body at four wavelengths (305 nm, 310 nm, 320 nm, and 380 nm) in J/m², taking into account the thickness of the ozone layer in the stratosphere, the amount of cloud cover, the elevation, and how high the sun is in the sky. Here, we use the whole-year means and standard deviations for UV-A (315 nm to 400 nm), UV-B (280 nm to 315 nm) and the full spectrum.

Moreover, we obtained each population's $\log(\text{size})$ (from Bentz et al., 2018) and subsistence strategy, dichotomized into populations whose subsistence mode is primarily based on hunting, fishing, gathering and/or foraging ('HG') and populations with subsistence modes centered around food production ('AGR'), using data from Blasi et al. (2019), Bickel et al. (2017), Kirby et al., (2016), Turchin et al. (2015). The information about color vocabulary specifically concerns the existence of a *specific term for blue* (a dichotomous variable, 'no'/'yes'), and we also collected data about the *frequency of abnormal red/green*

color perception in males excluding, if specified, tritanopia, and those samples that do not distinguish between males and females, or with fewer than 50 individuals (see Figure 1 Panel A and Supplementary Materials for details).

Finally, to control for past demography and selection (about which we do not have direct information here), we estimated the overall pairwise *genetic distances* between populations, estimated by the *fixation index* F_{ST} . We used a set of genetic markers aimed at forensic applications ([FROG-kb](#)) from the [ALFRED](#) database (Rajeevan, 2003) with ultrametric missing value imputation (De Soete, 1984; Lapointe & Kirsch, 1995), followed by classic multi-dimensional scaling (MDS), retaining the first 10 dimensions (goodness-of-fit 10.5%).

We used the following short variable names: *glottocode* (Glottolog language code), *family* (language family), *macroarea* (the macroarea), *latitude* and *longitude* (the transformed geographical coordinates), *elevation* (transformed elevation), *distance to ocean*, *distance to lakes*, *distance to rivers* and *distance to water* (transformed distances to bodies of water), *humidity median* and *humidity IQR* (humidity), *climate PC1*, *climate PC2*, *climate PC3* (the first 3 climate Principal Components, z-scored), *mean UV-A*, *sd UV-A*, *mean UV-B*, *sd UV-B*, *mean UV*, *sd UV* (UV incidence, z-scored), *population size* (transformed population size), *subsistence* (subsistence strategy), *blue* (is there a specific term for blue?), *daltonism* (frequency of abnormal red/green color perception), and *genetic D1 ... genetic D10* (first 10 MDS dimensions of the genetic distances matrix); the suffix *_family* refers to the values at the putative family origins.

All analyses were done using R (R Core Team, 2021). We used five main classes of methods in our analyses (see the Supplementary Materials). First, in order to understand the geographical patterning of our data, we tested it against *complete spatial randomness* (Baddeley et al., 2016; Spielman, 2017) using the χ^2 test based on quadrat counts, and the *G*, *F* and *K* functions, and we also estimated its spatial autocorrelation using Moran's *I* (with either the inverse of the shortest geographical distance "as the crow flies", or the nearest neighbor distance on the Delaunay triangulation). Second, we fitted *Bayesian mixed-effect regression models* (as implemented by R's package *brms* (Bürkner, 2018) using *Stan* (Guo et al., 2020) with *family* and *macroarea* as random effects, and explanatory variables and potential confounds as predictors. For *blue* we performed logistic regression, and for *daltonism* we performed beta regression (after replacing the 0.0% values by 0.01%); we used model selection based on Bayes Factors (BF), leave-one-out cross-validation (LOO), the Widely Applicable Information Criterion (WAIC), and K-Fold Cross-Validation (KFOLD,

with $K = 10$). Third, we conducted *mediation analysis* using a Bayesian mixed effects model (brms with Stan) approach which allowed us to include random effects. Fourth, we used path analysis (as implemented by lavaan; Rosseel, 2012) to test more complex models involving multiple potential predictors (but without controlling for the non-independence due to *family* and *macroarea*). Finally, we quantified the predictive capacity of a set of variables using Bayesian mixed-effects regression (brms with Stan), conditional inference trees (ctree; Hothorn et al., 2006 in package partykit; Hothorn & Zeileis, 2015), random forests (package randomForest; Liaw & Wiener, 2001) and conditional random forests (cforest in package partykit) and Support Vector Machines (rminer package Cortez, 2010).

RESULTS

UV-B incidence predicts the existence of a specific word for blue

Here we tested the hypothesis that the incidence of UV (in particular, UV-B) predicts the existence of a specific word for blue, taking into consideration various potential confounds and causal pathways.

Both UV-A and UV-B affected *blue* negatively (here, *blue* is the dichotomous variable ‘is there a specific term for blue in the language?’, italics indicate variable names; for more information about the variables, see Methods): UV-A: $\beta = -1.03$, 95% HDI = $[-1.65, -0.38]$, $p(\beta=0) = 0.0154$, $p(\beta < 0) = 1$; UV-B: $\beta = -1.12$ $[-1.75, -0.55]$, $p(\beta=0) = 0.0128$, $p(\beta < 0) = 1$. Please note that for such Bayesian regression results we report the slope, β , of the fixed effect(s) of interest in terms of their mean and 95% HDI (Highest Density Interval), as well as specific tests that capture the posterior probability that the hypothesis is true (i.e., they should be interpreted directly, and not as frequentist p-values in terms of the probability of seeing such a result were the null hypothesis true); also, while directional hypotheses should be a priori motivated, point hypothesis do not have the same requirement. However, as UV-A and UV-B were highly multicollinear ($VIF_{meanUVA} = 36.3$, $VIF_{meanUVB} = 36.3$) and UV-A fitted the data worse than UV-B ($BF = 0.31$, $LOO = -1.29 \pm 0.77$, $WAIC = -1.13 \pm 0.77$, $KFOLD = -1.20 \pm 1.63$; for such comparisons between two models, m1 and m2, we report the Bayes Factor, BF, ideally < 0.033 or > 10 , as well as the LOO, WAIC and KFOLD as the difference in the Expected Log pointwise Predictive

Density, ELPD, between the two models and its standard error, for which the absolute difference should be larger than the standard error; ideally, all these criteria should agree, but they capture *a priori* different aspects of model comparison; McElreath, 2020), we retained only UV-B in the following analyses. The variable *blue* was positively affected by *latitude* ($\beta=4.39[0.82,8.01]$, $p(\beta=0)=0.068$, $p(\beta<0)=0.99$), *population size* ($\beta=0.31[0.16,0.48]$, $p(\beta=0)=3.8\times 10^{-7}$) and *climate PC1* ($\beta=0.99[0.40,1.57]$, $p(\beta=0)=0.035$), and negatively by *distance to lakes* ($\beta=-0.56[-0.87,-0.27]$, $p(\beta=0)=0.0074$). Furthermore, 4 of the 10 dimensions, resulting from the multidimensional scaling (MDS) of the matrix of genetic distances (F_{ST} ; Holsinger & Weir, 2009) between all pairs of populations, also affected *blue* (positively for *genetic D7*, and negatively for *genetic D1*, *genetic D4* and *genetic D6*; see Supplementary Materials).

The mediation analysis (Figure 2 Panel B) shows that *latitude* has a positive *total effect* (TE = 5.7, 95% HDI [2.3, 9.6]) on the presence of a distinct word for *blue*. There was a negative *direct effect* (DE = -7.4[-17.9,2.4]), as well as a positive *indirect effect* mediated by UV-B (IE = 13.0[3.6, 23.1]; $\beta_{latitude\rightarrow UVB}=-5.8[-6.2,-5.3]$, $\beta_{UVB\rightarrow blue|latitude}=-2.3[-4.0,-0.6]$). We explored other mediation models (see Supplementary Materials) which, taken together, suggest that *distance to lakes* also mediates between *latitude* and *blue*, and that *subsistence* is linked to *blue* through *population size*. We also constructed a complex (but largely theoretically motivated and conservative) path model (Figure 2 Panel A) linking *latitude* and *blue* through UV-B and controlling for potential confounds. This model fitted the data very well ($\chi^2(1)=0.4$, $p=0.53$; CFI=1.0, TLI=1.05, NNFI=1.05, RMSEA=0.0) and, importantly, showed that the effect of *latitude* on *blue* is fully mediated not only by UV-B ($\beta_{latitude\rightarrow UVB}=-0.96$, $p<0.001$, and $\beta_{UVB\rightarrow blue}=-0.65$, $p=0.032$), but also by *subsistence*, *population size* and *distance to lakes*.

Figure 2: Mediation and path analyses for the presence of a distinct word for blue. (Panel **A** top): Path model with standardized coefficients (line thickness) and p -values (stars). Single-headed arrows represent regressions, while double-headed arrows represent covariances. Edges: solid blue = significant negative effects (at alpha-level 0.05), solid red = significant positive effects, and dotted gray = not significant. The thickness of the line indicates effect size, with a thick line indicating an effect size ≥ 0.5 and thin effect size < 0.5 ; significance stars near each arrow (***) for $p < 0.001$; ** for $p < 0.01$ and * for $p < 0.05$). (Panel **B** bottom): Mediation analysis showing the total, direct, and indirect effects (as point estimate with 95% HDI and p -values), as well as regression coefficients (as point estimates with p -values in parentheses). Note, because the outcome is binary, the direct and indirect effects may be on different scales. Icons made by [Freepik](#) from [Flaticon](#).

The presence of a distinct term for *blue* was predicted by information in the full dataset using Bayesian mixed-effects logistic regression with family and macroarea as random effects, the conditional random trees, the random and conditional random forests, and the Support Vector Machines, with very little difference between them (accuracy from 76% for random forests to 91% for the

Bayesian mixed-effects model). Moreover, all techniques generalized well and had comparable performance (as expected, lower on the testing sets than on the full database), the best being the conditional random forests and conditional trees. Across these, the most important predictors tended to be (not in any particular order): *UV-B*, *population size*, *climate/humidity*, *latitude*, and *distance to lakes* (see Figure 3 Panel A).

Figure 3: Predicting the existence of a dedicated word for blue (Panel A, left) and frequency of abnormal red-green color perception (Panel B, right); only the 7 best predictors are presented here (see Methods). 1st row: Using Bayesian mixed-effect models (BRMS), the best predictors' (according to Bayes Factor, WAIC, LOO and K-Fold methods) slope estimates. 2nd row: specificity-based predictor importance from SVMs. 3rd row: accuracy-based predictor importance from random forests (RF), measuring the amount by which the accuracy decreases when one variable is removed from the model; higher values represent more important predictors. 4th row: Gini-index-based predictor importance from random forests (RF); this measures by how much the Gini impurity decreases when a variable is chosen to split a node (note, only relative values matter, and there is a bias towards using

numeric variables to split nodes). 5th row: unconditional predictor importance from conditional random forests (CF); this is similar to the accuracy-based importance from random forests. 6th row: the performance of the four methods (BRMS, SVM, RF and CF) in terms of accuracy (left; as this is a binary classification problem) and R^2 (right; as this is a regression problem). Variable names have been abbreviated for legibility: *popSize* is population size, *humid_m* is median humidity, *dist2lak* is the distance to the closest lake, *lat* is latitude, *genD4* is the 4th dimension of the multidimensional scaling of the between-populations genetic distances, *climPC1* is the 1st principal component resulting from the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of the climate variables, *macroar* is the macroarea, *long* is the longitude, and *dist2wat* is the distance to the closest body of water (ocean/sea, lake or river). Plots generated using R (R Core Team, 2021).

Population frequency of abnormal red-green vision

In a second set of analyses, we tested whether the population frequency of abnormal red-green color perception (here, we designate this variable as *daltonism*) was linked to the incidence of UV light and the presence of a dedicated word for blue (as a proxy for its physiological effects on blue-green color perception; see Figure 4 Panels A and B). Bayesian mixed-effects regressions showed that *daltonism* was positively influenced by *blue* ($\beta=0.61$ [0.33, 0.88], $p(\beta=0)=0.0004$, $p(\beta>0)=1$) and *latitude* ($\beta=1.69$ [0.78, 2.64], $p(\beta=0)=0.0076$, $p(\beta<0)=0$), and negatively influenced by *UV-B* ($\beta=-0.3$ [- 0.45, - 0.15], $p(\beta=0)=0.083$, $p(\beta<0)=1$); it was also affected by 4 genetic distance dimensions (see Supplementary Materials).

Taken together, the mediation analyses suggested that the effect of *latitude* on *daltonism* was mediated mostly by *UV-B* and *blue*, and especially the mediation *UV-B* \rightarrow *blue* \rightarrow *daltonism* was important ($TE = - 0.74$ [- 1.21, - 0.35], $DE = - 0.21$ [- 0.35, - 0.06], $IE = - 0.53$ [- 1.04, - 0.16]; $\beta_{UVB \rightarrow blue} = -1.14$ [- 1.78, - 0.55], $\beta_{blue \rightarrow daltonism|UVB} = 0.49$ [0.20, 0.77]). A path model (Figure 4 Panel C) fits the data well ($\chi^2(1)=4.0$, $p = 0.137$; $CFI = 0.951$, $TLI = 0.927$, $NNFI = 0.927$, $RMSEA = 0.08$) and showed that *UV-B* has both a direct effect on *daltonism* ($\beta=-0.31$, $p < 0.001$) and one mediated by *blue* ($\beta_{UVB \rightarrow blue} = -0.55$, $p < 0.001$; $\beta_{blue \rightarrow daltonism} = 0.4$, $p < 0.001$). Adding *subsistence* to the model improved the fit further ($\chi^2(1)=1.6$, $p = 0.45$; $CFI = 1.000$, $TLI = 1.011$, $NNFI = 1.011$, $RMSEA = 0.0$). It added a significant influence of *subsistence* ($\beta_{subsistence \rightarrow daltonism} = 0.38$, $p < 0.001$), but removed the influence of *blue* to *daltonism* ($\beta_{blue \rightarrow daltonism} = 0.11$, $p = 0.32$).

Figure 4: Derivation of path models for red-green abnormal color perception. (Panel A): A direct graphical representation of the hypothesis that UV-B affects the unmeasured physiology of color perception during the lifetime of an individual which, in turn, affects the existence of a dedicated word for blue in the person's language (*hypothesis 1*). In addition, the physiology of color perception also drives an evolutionary interaction with alleles resulting in abnormal red/green color perception. (Panel B): a Structural Equation Modelling diagram representation of Panel A with operationalized variables. (Panel C): The latent variable 'abn. blue perc.', representing the unobserved abnormal color perception of blue, is indirectly measured by two indicators ('daltonism' and 'blue'), while the latent 'abn. red-green perc.' (abnormal red/green color perception) is not of interest here. Therefore, we used 'blue' as a proxy for 'abn. blue perc.' and ignored 'abn. red-green perc.', leading to the path model shown here. Icons made by [Freepik](#) from [Flaticon](#).

Converging evidence across analysis methods predicted daltonism on the full dataset, but this performance did not generalize well. Moreover, the importance of the predictors varied across methods. Nevertheless, *UV-B* tended to be among the most important predictors, along with blue and some genetic distance measures (see Figure 3 Panel B).

DISCUSSION

Taken together, these analyses demonstrate that no single explanatory factor explains the color lexicon. This finding resonates with the centuries of debate on this topic with myriad variables being proposed and opposed. Our results show that multiple environmental and cultural factors interact. Specifically, we found that a language is more likely to have a dedicated word for blue when it is spoken by a larger population, which resides at higher latitudes (where the incidence of UV-B radiation is lower), and near large bodies of standing water (in particular, lakes). While number of speakers is an imperfect proxy for the unmeasured and hard-to-define variable, cultural complexity, which in turn is an indirect reflection of the use of complex dyeing techniques and colored artefacts, the environmental influences were more straightforward. For example, large lakes might not always be poster-card blue, but they certainly tend to be a salient feature and reflect the sky more often than not. Importantly, the tendency of languages spoken closer to the equator to have a distinct term for blue, is likely due to the high incidence of UV-B light, and strongly supports the proposal that acquired lens brunescence has a negative effect on the development or maintenance of a lexical distinction between 'blue' and 'green'.

Overall, these results suggest that variability in color perception leads to differences in the perceptual representation of color space, which then causes differences in color lexicons. It also raises interesting questions about the mechanisms and time required for language change, given that we are considering acquired color deficiency related to aging. If language does adapt to the color vision of its speakers, then our data suggest that language adapts to the reduced capacities of older adults, despite also being spoken by younger adults and children, who are still able to perceive the distinction between green and blue. Intriguingly, other evidence suggests extreme variation in exposure to direct sunlight during very early development also affects color vision (Laeng et al., 2007). Nevertheless, our findings show a distinct developmental trajectory. Perhaps older adults change the fitness landscape to which language adapts through cultural evolution at the scale of several generations of language use and transmission (Richerson & Christiansen, 2013), a process that can be studied using agent-based computer models (K. A. Jameson & Komarova, 2009a, 2009b). The fact that we found no influence of environmental conditions at the putative origins of language families suggests that these effects act on timescales shorter than the few thousand years usually needed for language families to differentiate. The present-day languages of the same language family descend from a single ancient proto-language and, due to migrations and

language shifts on the scale of a few thousand years (Bower & Evans, 2014), may end up spoken in very different locations and environments to those of their proto-language. If the color lexicon needs several thousand years to adapt to changes in UV-B incidence, then the location of these ancient proto-languages should still have a detectable effect, but the lack of such a signal in our data suggests that this change is much faster.

It is striking to note that a similar phenomenon, where language adapts to an altered fitness landscape due to acquired changes in some of the speaker population, has been proposed for several typologically striking properties of Australian Aboriginal languages and the distribution of labiodental sounds. For example, the high frequency of chronic ear infections (chronic otitis media) among Australian Aborigine children can produce partial hearing loss affecting the lower and higher parts of the auditory spectrum, resulting in a loss of fricatives, a centralized vowel system, and a long, thin consonant system in the languages of the Australian continent (A. Butcher, 2006). Similarly, consuming processed and softer foods characteristic of agriculture leads to ontogenetic changes in bite (involving the teeth and lower jaw) such that the overbite/overedge is retained into adulthood, favoring the use of labiodental sounds (such as 'f' and 'v') by languages of populations practicing agriculture (Blasi et al., 2019). Our study adds to this literature by showing that external pressures can shape semantic, as well as phonological aspects of language.

Finally, our data also supported an interaction between acquired blue-green and inherited red-green color deficits: populations closer to the equator, more affected by lens brunescence, speaking languages without a dedicated word for blue have a lower frequency of people with red-green color deficiency. The data also suggested that populations of hunter-gatherers tend to have a lower incidence of abnormal red-green color perception. While this hypothesis requires further testing, it would support the idea that certain cultural practices and subsistence strategies might have higher demands on color perception, thereby generating selective pressures against inherited color perception deficits.

Some caution is required in interpretation, however, given limitations in the current study. First, our dataset contained only 14 groups classified as hunter-gatherers, which, even if representative of the current distribution of communities, is too small to allow strong conclusions. Second, more refined genetic data—especially including information about the opsin alleles involved in red-green color deficiencies—would be necessary to better test for selection. Third, there is a need for better and, ideally, more direct measures of the

exposure to complex dyeing technology and colored artefacts. Finally, populations and languages are reduced to geographic dots in our analyses, but a better approach might instead be to use aggregated measures of UV-B incidence, climate, ecology and proximity to large bodies of water across the whole area they occupy.

Nevertheless, our results strongly support the view that the color vocabulary is shaped, at least in part, by environmental factors acting on individual speakers, generating biases that are amplified by the repeated use and transmission of language in communities of similarly affected individuals. This is akin to other cases of individual biases being amplified to shape cross-linguistic diversity (Dediu et al., 2017), biases that can be either rooted in genetics (Dediu et al., 2019; Dediu & Ladd, 2007; Moisik & Dediu, 2017) or emerging due to environmental or cultural factors acting during the lifetime of individuals (Blasi et al., 2019).

FOLLOW-UP: COMMENT ON THE PAPER

After our initial publication, a response to our paper was presented by a team of researchers, including Joseph L. Hardy, John S. Werner, Terry Regier, Paul Kay and Christina M. Frederick. Their response consisted of several criticisms aimed at our research, providing us with an opportunity to address certain aspects that were not covered in our original paper. The exchange took place in the *Matter Arising* section of the *Scientific Reports* journal. Their answer, published in 2023, is called 'Sunlight exposure cannot explain "grue" languages'. Subsequently, we provided a comprehensive reply to their comments, titled 'Reply to: Sunlight exposure cannot explain "grue" languages' (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-28281-0>). In the following discussion, I will first summarize their arguments before presenting our response.

Criticisms

Hardy et al. (2023) put forth three main criticisms of our study. First, they suggest that chromatic adaptation compensates for the effect of lens brunescence (Hering, 1964; Olkkonen et al., 2010; von Helmholtz, 1924). Supporting this claim, they refer to their previous research (Hardy et al., 2005), where they compared color naming patterns between young and older adults. Contrary to Lindsey & Brown (2002), they found that younger and older adults consistently

used a term for "blue", leading them to suggest that lens brunescence has a negligible influence on color naming.

Next, they highlight regularities in color naming systems across different cultures (Berlin & Kay, 1969). For instance, no language is known to lack distinct terms for red while having words for blue and green. These differences in color naming have been attributed to differences in communicative need (Gibson et al., 2017; Twomey et al., 2021; Zaslavsky et al., 2018, 2020). Therefore, their second argument posits that the presence or absence of specific color terms in languages is grounded in need, with technologically more advanced societies having a greater need to incorporate additional color terms. Since less technologically complex societies (who often tend to lack a word for blue), also tend to be spoken in UV-B areas (Ember, 1978; Hays et al., 1972; Naroll, 1970), it is plausible that UV-B exposure could have an effect due to its correlation with technological complexity.

Their third argument addresses historical language changes concerning color terms. Examples from languages like Old Japanese and Nafaanra show shifts in color terminology over time. Both languages had a 'grue' term which eventually evolved into separate terms for 'green' and 'blue'. As UV-B exposure in these countries had remained constant, a parsimonious explanation is that these languages reflect natural patterns of language evolution, with cultures developing more basic color terms as their need for a finer-grained color vocabulary increases.

Response

Hardy et al. (2023) raise two critical points regarding our original research paper (Josserand, Meeussen, et al., 2021). First, they highlight their important earlier work (Hardy et al., 2005)—which we did not discuss in our original article—that suggests lens brunescence cannot explain color naming due to color constancy. Second, they stress a more "parsimonious" account of color naming that relies on the communicative needs of different cultures. We take this opportunity to discuss their findings in light of other recent studies, and to discuss the potential role of lens brunescence as one factor among many that shapes color naming.

Hardy et al. (2023) propose perceptual mechanisms compensate for the deterioration of color perception due to lens brunescence because old and young people tested in the United States name colors similarly (Hardy et al., 2005). In their earlier study, they determined the ocular media of 20 participants (10 young

and 10 old) and also simulated aging and youth by manipulating a computer screen so that it re-created the retinal stimulation of an observer of the other age group. They found simulating aging changed color naming behavior (as also found earlier in Lindsey & Brown, 2002), but actual aging did not (Hardy et al., 2023). They therefore conclude lens brunescence due to UV-B exposure is not a plausible causal mechanism to affect color naming and the presence or absence of blue in a language.

Since then Walter (2011) used yellow-orange ocular filters to simulate aging equivalent to 20–33 years in a high UV-B incidence environment or 105–165 years European UV-B incidence. Ocular filters, unlike changes to a computer monitor, have the advantage of causing chromatic change for the entire visible environment, akin to what may occur with lens brunescence. Walter found the strongest filters affected naming of blue color patches (S. Walter, 2011) which leaves open the possibility that even if there is a compensation mechanism it does not fully offset age-related changes for people exposed to higher levels of UV. Data from NASA’s Total Ozone Mapping Spectrometer for 1998 shows at low latitudes the mean UV incidence is five times higher than central Europe (see also Lindsey & Brown, 2002), so the color vision of a 30-year-old adult living in a high UV region corresponds to a putative 150-year-old European. Differences in lifestyle—such as amount of time spent indoors, use of sunglasses and corrective lenses with UV filters by people in higher latitudes—would further exacerbate differences between groups.

It remains plausible, then, that lens brunescence in some populations through its effect on blue color perception could affect color naming. Other studies support this proposal. Color vision deficiencies in the blue range become more common as people age (Cooper et al., 1991; Kinnear & Sahraie, 2002; V. C. Smith et al., 1985), particularly for people living in high UV incidence regions (Davies et al., 1998; Nacer et al., 2001). For example, Davies et al. (1998) studied color perception in 597 participants from Africa (Botswana, Malawi, and South Africa) and Europe (Greece, Spain, Ireland, and UK), and found African participants, as well as Greeks to some extent, made more errors in the blue range. The pattern of errors made by African participants resembled those of older British participants, again suggesting lens brunescence could be a causal mechanism.

Moreover, recent agent-based computational models using dynamic systems approaches show in realistically heterogeneous populations of perceivers (i.e., where not everyone shares the identical perceptual apparatus), the presence of

dichromats affects color boundaries for the whole population. With as few as 1% dichromats in a population there are changes to color categories for the entire population (K. A. Jameson & Komarova, 2009a, 2009b). So, contrary to Hardy et al. (2023), we do not believe the current data on chromatic adaptation rules out the lens brunescence hypothesis. In addition, there is a plausible account for how perceptual heterogeneity can affect color categories within a population. We conclude additional data from participants of different ages at different latitudes is necessary to adjudicate the matter. Like Hardy et al. (2023) we believe “Further empirical research into the rate of brunescence in geographic areas in question would aid our understanding” because the matter is not yet settled.

As an alternative, Hardy et al. (2023) suggest different communicative needs across cultures are sufficient to account for color naming strategies globally. They appeal to the seminal work of Berlin and Kay (1969) which suggests languages develop color categories in a predictable sequence. They go on to suggest technological complexity alone (developed within a culture or acquired through contact) could account for color categories. While this parsimonious account is attractive, we believe it to be insufficient. The data and analyses in our paper suggest two environmental factors—UV-B incidence and distance to lakes—play a role in shaping color lexicons separately from the role of culture. Similarly, Twomey et al. (2021) showed geographic location and ecological region influence color naming. In addition, a recent study of the hunter-gatherer Maniq (Thailand) showed that color lexicons can emerge in response to environmental not technological demands (Wnuk et al., 2022). We agree communicative needs shape color lexicons, but current accounts underspecify the cultural and environmental demands that themselves drive differential communicative needs. This matter deserves further empirical attention.

Hardy et al. claim that since level of technology, distance from the equator (a proxy for low UV-B exposure), and number of basic color terms are correlated, we can discard the correlation between the latter two. However, our statistical analyses using mediation and path analyses show you cannot rule out the additional role UV-B exposure plays in color language. Instead, the analyses support the alternative hypothesis that the effect of UV-B incidence on color language is not mediated by, or the result of, a spurious relationship with any other variables we considered in our original paper (see Supplementary Materials of Jossierand, Meeussen, et al., 2021 for more information). In our view color naming is affected by a range of variables. Parsimony while attractive does not align well with the complexity of the problem. A parsimony account applied to our model would mean keeping the lowest number of factors that explain the

most variance in the outcome—dropping UV-B incidence makes the explanation worse. Our analyses suggest color language is affected by a range of factors that in turn shape both color perception and communicative need.

In conclusion, while compensatory mechanisms—such as color constancy—exist in color perception, it is possible they only partially offset the effects of aging. There is evidence that people exposed to very high levels of UV radiation develop color vision deficiencies in the blue range. So in our view lens brunescence is still a candidate mechanism for shaping color lexicons. Nevertheless, we agree with Hardy et al. that lens brunescence alone is unlikely to explain these cross-linguistic patterns, and that other factors, such as cultural dyeing technologies and historical processes, are also important to take into consideration. This is in line with the main conclusion of our original paper: the color lexicon is the result of many factors—cultural and environmental—that interact with each other in complex ways.

CHAPTER 1

2

DIFFERENCES IN COLOR LEXICON IN THE FRENCH AND HIMBA POPULATIONS: THERE IS MORE TO PERCEPTION THAN MEETS THE EYE

CONTEXT

This research was conducted in Lyon (France) and near Opuwo (Namibia). This Chapter was written in collaboration with François Pellegrino, Dan Dediu, and Serge Caparos. Serge Caparos, an expert on the Himba population, provided supervision during the fieldwork in Namibia. This Chapter is a draft for an upcoming paper. Please note that this is the only chapter for which we are not openly sharing the data. We will make the data available as soon as we publish the results. However, the code used to conduct the analysis (RMarkdown) and the corresponding HTML file from the Supplementary Materials are accessible on my GitHub repository at: <https://github.com/mathjoss/Chapter2>.

Acknowledgements

We thank Giorgio Vallortigara, without whom the trip to Namibia would not have been possible. I would also like to express my appreciation to Labex Aslan for providing me with a scholarship that enabled me to compensate the French participants. We would also like to express our gratitude to Professor Arash Sahraie for generously sharing the data from their paper (Kinnear & Sahraie, 2002) with us. Additionally, we appreciate the invaluable emotional support and

intellectual contributions of Esther Boissin and Anna Blumenthal during the fieldworks. Our acknowledgements also go to our guides and translators, Chinho Lopez, Fanny Kavari, Hilde Simon, and Cancy Luise, who played a pivotal role in this research. We express our sincere appreciation to the French participants who willingly took part in our study, often without any financial compensation. Last but not least, we strongly thank the Himba participants and the Namibian people in general for their warm welcome in Namibia, embracing our project with openness, benevolence, and generosity.

ABSTRACT

While variations in color lexicons are primarily attributed to differences in communicative needs, conversely, universal features in color lexicons were often attributed to shared perceptual systems among humans. In this research, we challenge the notion of a uniform perceptual structure by conducting a comparative analysis of color perception in two distinct populations: the French and the Himba people. These two groups exhibit markedly different color lexicons, paralleled by exposure to distinct environmental conditions. Notably, Himba participants are exposed to significantly more UV radiation, a factor known to impact color perception through its effects on the eye physiology. This study employs a comprehensive battery of tasks designed to measure color perception while controlling for multiple confounding variables that might bias inter-group comparisons, including factors related to task reliability for cross-cultural comparison, patterns of color naming, and potential other confounds related to color perception. Our findings reveal a direct effect of age, which interacts with population: color perception deteriorates more significantly with age in the Himba sample of participants compared to the French sample. While the precise causal mechanisms behind this difference require further investigation, increased UV exposure emerges as a likely contributing factor. In light of these differences in color perception between the two populations, we suggest that variations in color perception could contribute to shaping color naming. Thus, while communicative need is an important factor in shaping color lexicon, perceptual structure may serve a dual role, contributing to both commonalities and differences in color lexicons. This research advances our understanding of the intricate relationship between perception and language, shedding new light on the factors that may shape our perception of colors.

INTRODUCTION

Despite the continuous nature of the color spectrum, all languages classify it into a finite number of color categories. These color vocabularies reflect remarkable diversity, especially in terms of the number of color terms used. For example, while the Dani language uses only two words to describe colors (Heider, 1972), the Russian language encompasses as many as twelve distinct terms to describe colors (Paramei, 2005). This cross-cultural diversity in the number of color terms is believed to stem from differences in *communicative needs* (Gibson et al., 2017; Kemp et al., 2018; Kemp & Regier, 2012). Defining precisely what these communication needs encompass remains a subject of ongoing discussion (Zaslavsky et al., 2020). While some have proposed cultural factors like dyeing techniques and exposure to colored manufactured items as key contributors (Berlin & Kay, 1969), color technology would not be the only driver of communicative need (Wnuk et al., 2022), and the distribution of colors present in the natural environment could also contribute to differences in the communicative need people have to refer to some colors (Twomey et al., 2021; Yendrikhovskij, 2001).

Beyond the cross-cultural differences in color lexicons, common patterns in color vocabularies across languages also exist (Berlin & Kay, 1969; Heider & Olivier, 1972; Lindsey & Brown, 2006). For example, languages with only two color terms usually distinguish between 'light' and 'dark,' while those with three color terms often also include a separate term for 'red'; those with four color terms typically incorporate a distinct term for 'green' or 'yellow,' and so forth. Since all humans tend to share a similar perceptive system, these similarities in color lexicons in the world's populations were attributed to shared perceptual structure (K. Jameson & D'Andrade, 1997; Kay & McDaniel, 1978; Loreto et al., 2012; Regier et al., 2007). Thus, the current consensus in the field of color research tends to support the idea that, even though differences in color vocabularies may be influenced by differences in communication needs, the commonalities seem to be rooted in a universal perceptual structure (Regier et al., 2015; Zaslavsky et al., 2018, 2019).

However, do we indeed all share a similar perceptual structure? Existing literature hints at differences in our color vision systems, including variations in photoreceptors, ocular filters, and even the neural processing of light (see Bosten, 2022 for a review), which can result in individual differences in color discrimination. A straightforward illustration relates to the prevalence of males with genetically abnormal color perception in Europe (Deeb, 2005), and who

struggle to differentiate between red and green colors. Age is also known to affect color discrimination: the ability to discriminate colors tends to decrease gradually with age (Barbur & Rodriguez-Carmona, 2015; Kinnear & Sahraie, 2002; Knoblauch et al., 2001; Paramei & Oakley, 2014; Shinomori et al., 2016). The decrease in color perception with age is *partially* due to lens brunescence (Scheffrin et al., 1992; Shinomori et al., 2016), a darkening process of the lens due mostly to the impact of UV incidence (Duncan et al., 1997; Hightower, 1995; West et al., 1998; Young, 1994). Thus, people who live in places with high levels of UV incidence might exhibit lower color discrimination abilities (Davies et al., 1998; Kaimbo Wa Kaimbo et al., 1994; Nacer et al., 2001). For example, Davies et al. (1998) used a simple color vision task in 597 participants from Africa (Botswana, Malawi, and South Africa) and many participants in Europe (Greece, Spain, Ireland, and the UK). They found that African participants (and, to a lesser extent, Greek participants) had a higher frequency of errors, especially in the blue range, which resembled the pattern exhibited by the elderly in the British sample.

Could these variations in color perception across different populations potentially impact their color lexicons? Lindsey & Brown (2002), following Bornstein (1973), proposed the *lens brunescence hypothesis*. This hypothesis suggests that the uneven distribution of UV incidence across populations in the world - which leads to group-level differences in color perception, especially in the blue range - may explain why many populations living in high UV incidence places often lack a specific term to talk about the blue color. This hypothesis gains further support through subsequent studies that have replicated its findings (S. Walter, 2011) and comprehensive data analyses (Dediu, 2023; Josserand, Meeussen, et al., 2021). However, an ongoing debate still questions whether the effect of lens brunescence is strong enough to be one of the factors shaping color lexicons, especially given the presence of color compensation mechanisms (Hardy et al., 2005, 2023; Josserand et al., 2023; Regier & Kay, 2004; S. Walter, 2011).

Thus, to address this issue, it is crucial to understand whether differences in color perception exist between populations exposed to varying levels of UV incidence and, if so, to assess the magnitude of these differences. Hence, this study aims to thoroughly examine color perception in two very distinct groups: the French and the Himba people⁵. On the one hand, the French group

⁵ The terms "French people" and "Himba people" can refer to different entities, and we acknowledge that this terminology can be a subject of debate. While these groups are very different in terms of size, homogeneity and structure, our primary focus here is on comparing

experiences relatively low UV exposure due to an average UV incidence of 171 mW/m² in this region (using erythemal UV incidence data from NASA data averaged from the periods 1978-1993 and 1996-2003), coupled with predominantly indoor lifestyles. Conversely, the Himba people, a semi-nomadic group residing in the arid northern region of Namibia, inhabit a desert area closer to the equator. In addition to a high average UV incidence of 226 mW/m², they also live predominantly outdoors. To give an order of magnitude, the lowest UV incidence found for the latitude and longitude of languages present in the Glottolog database (Hammarström et al., 2018) is of 71 mW/m² (Nganasan, spoken in northern Siberia), while the highest spoken UV incidence is of 241 mW/m² (Cusco Quechua, spoken in Peru). Thus, we assume that if lens brunescence indeed results in a notable decline in color perception, this should be reflected when comparing these two populations.

Comparing French and Himba populations is also particularly relevant since the language spoken by the Himba people historically had fewer color terms than the one spoken by French people. Analogous to the English language, French people consistently employ eleven terms to describe colors, with words for black, white, red, yellow, green, blue, brown, pink, purple, orange, and grey. Conversely, Himba people historically had five color terms (Roberson et al., 2004), including words that could refer to the English dark, light, reddish colors, yellowish colors, and a term encompassing blue and green hues, which aligns with the lens brunescence theory. Additionally, the Himba population is particularly interesting to study because this population has had in recent years increased exposure to urban areas and English schooling, which has pushed the population to add new color terms to their lexicon, similarly to what happened in the Nafaanra language in Ghana (Zaslavsky et al., 2022). Thus, 16 years after the original study from Roberson et al. (2004), Mylonas et al. (2022) reported the use of seven color terms in OtjiHimba, the language spoken by Himba people, and a part of their population now employs distinct terms to name blue and green colors (Mylonas et al., 2022). The substantial variability present *within* their population when it comes to naming colors offers a valuable opportunity to investigate the relationship between color perception and the patterns of color naming.

their color perception and vocabularies relative to differences in exposure to UV incidence. Further information about the participants in both groups is provided in the Method and Supplementary Materials sections.

While this Chapter mainly focuses on the lens brunescence hypothesis, and thus, on the environmental effect of UV incidence, we acknowledge the presence of many other confounding factors between the French and Himba populations that may lead to group-level differences in color perception, such as genetics or differences in the statistical distribution of the color environment.

Using data on the allele frequency of common DNA variants in several human populations (ALFRED Database; Rajeevan et al., 2012), we found that the fixation index (i.e., a measure used to quantify the genetic differences between two populations) between French and Bantu speakers is 0.24, which indicates the presence of quite strong group-level differences. For comparison, the fixation index between French and German people is of 0.005, and the highest fixation index in this database is of 0.74 (between Mongolian and Afro-Caribbeans people). Such group-level genetic differences may be relevant because genetics partly predict nonpathological lens brunescence (Shiels & Hejtmancik, 2015) and macular pigment density (Borel et al., 2011; Meyers et al., 2013), which may explain why people from different ethnicities but inhabiting the same country have different macular pigment densities on average (Davey et al., 2020). In turn, macular pigment significantly affects color vision, especially in the blue range (Moreland & Dain, 1995; Woo & Lee, 2002).

Additionally, French and Himba participants are not exposed to the same colors during their lives (Juricevic & Webster, 2009). Exposure to different color environments could lead to long-term differences in color perception. Laeng et al. (2007) found an interaction between season of birth and latitude on color discrimination: People born in the autumn within the Arctic Circle had lower performance in color discrimination tests than those born outside of it, with the opposite pattern for people born in the summer. Additionally, Webster et al. (2002) conducted a comparison between American participants and multiple groups from India exposed to diverse environmental contexts, and observed differences in the way these groups situated focal colors. While they mainly focus on the influence of the environment's color statistics on color naming, they also consider the possibility that long-term contextual influences may lead by group-level differences in color perception (Webster et al., 2000).

Given the presence of numerous confounding factors between the French and Himba populations, our objective is not to study the biological processes underpinning group-level differences in color perception. Instead, we seek to address the following question: Do populations with distinct historical color lexicons also exhibit different color perception abilities? An affirmative answer to

this question would imply that perceptual structure may not be as universally consistent as previously thought. Since perceptual structure has been identified as one of the primary factors shaping color lexicons (K. Jameson & D'Andrade, 1997; Kay & McDaniel, 1978; Regier et al., 2007; Zaslavsky et al., 2018), perceptual structure could not only account for the similarities in our color lexicons, but also the differences.

To address this question, we conducted a set of five tasks to measure color perception among different groups of French and Himba participants. To control for potential confounding factors that could bias the interpretation of group differences, we collected several variables, including color naming patterns, exposure to colored artifacts, general cognitive ability, and other miscellaneous factors such as gender and eye color. Our approach begins by assessing the relative importance of these variables in relation to the results of the color perception tasks and examining how they interact with each other. This preliminary analysis helped us evaluate the reliability of each color perception task and guided the design of our primary hypothesis investigation, the lens brunescence hypothesis. Subsequently, using the results from this preliminary analysis, we performed a comparative analysis of color perception between the French and Himba samples, with a particular emphasis on age, as it constitutes a crucial component of the lens brunescence hypothesis.

METHODS

We conducted a comparative study involving participants from France and the Himba community in Namibia. Ethical approval was granted by the Ethics Evaluation Committee of INSERM (Opinion number 21-855), and we obtained an Ethical Clearance Certificate from the University of Namibia (Reference Number: SAHS37/23). Our research involved two fieldwork trips in Namibia, one in 2021 and another in 2022, during which we conducted various tasks and tested different sets of participants. Data from the French sample were collected in Lyon, France, a few months before or after each of the Namibian fieldwork. In total, we conducted five tasks (two in 2021 and three in 2022), which will be presented in greater detail in the subsection titled Tasks within this section. The five tasks that we used are named FM100 task (standing for Farnsworth Munsell 100 Hue Test), DiffOrSim task (Different or Similar), CityUniv task (for City University Color Vision test), Arrows task, and Squares task (see Illustration 12).

<i>name</i>	FM100	DiffOrSim	CityUniv	Arrows	Squares
<i>year</i>	2021	2021	2022	2022	2022
<i>computer</i>	no	yes	no	yes	yes
<i>task</i>	Order the color caps	Press left if same colors, right if different colors	A. Show odd one B. Show peripheral color most similar to central one	Press left if arrow points left, press right if arrows points right	Press left if odd one is on the left side, press right if on the right
<i>colors</i>	all	blue and red	all	blue and red	blue and red
<i>measures</i>	Errors	Just Noticeable Difference (JND)	Errors	Just Noticeable Difference (JND)	Reaction time and accuracy

Illustration 12: Presentation of the experiments performed (more details below, in the “Tasks” subsection of the method). The first row shows the name by which they will be referred throughout the paper. The second row indicates the year in which they were performed for the Himba participants. The third row indicates whether these experiments took place on the laptop (inside the tent) or outside. The row line is a visual illustration of what the experiment looked like. The fifth row summarizes the instructions for the task in a few words (see below for more information). The sixth row indicates which colors were tested, and the seventh row shows the measures extracted from these tests. Please note that the visual representation of the Farnsworth Munsell in this Illustration shows half of the colors in the real test.

Himba sample

Participants. The Himba people are a semi-nomadic group primarily located in Namibia’s northwestern region, with their primary language being Otjihimba, a dialect very closely related to Otjiherero (glottocode: [here1253](#), the Atlantic-Congo family) but still identified as different by its speakers. Throughout both fieldwork missions, we maintained consistent experimental conditions, materials, and setups. With the assistance of local guides/interpreters, we established camps in various villages near Opuwo and obtained consent from village chiefs to conduct our experiments. Himba participants volunteered to take part and received a set of four gifts (flour, sugar, vaseline, and soap, approximate value ~ 5 euros) for their participation. While our primary focus was on the Himba group, we also included a very small number of participants from other related ethnic groups (Herero, Hakawona, and Zemba), all of whom are part of the Bantu ethnic group. These participants were fully integrated within the Himba village. For simplicity, we collectively refer to these participants as the ‘Himba group’.

Settings. The FM100 and CityUniv tasks were conducted outdoors. We measured the luminosity level and coordinates of the white point for each

participant using an X-Rite i1 Studio spectrophotometer to account for potential variations in luminosity. We applied a model to know whether variations in luminosity affected the results. Similar to Webster et al. (2002), we found no effect on these small variations in luminosity and the coordinate of white points on the color perception results. The three other tasks (DiffSim, Arrow, Squares) were conducted inside a tent, where the lighting conditions remained relatively constant (we ensured stable luminosity throughout the day using the spectrophotometer). Participants performed the experiments on a DELL Latitude 7400 laptop, the display of which had been calibrated using the same spectrophotometer. We adjusted the gamma of the laptop to achieve a linear gamma response. During the experiments, participants were seated in chairs facing a computer screen, maintaining an approximate distance of 50 cm from the stimuli. The viewing geometry was consistently set at approximately 0.45.

French sample

Participants. The French sample was tested in Lyon, France. We excluded individuals who spent more than five years in countries south of France, those who were not fluent in French, individuals who used blue-light filtering glasses, and those with a genetic anomaly affecting red-green color perception. In 2021, participants volunteered their time for the experiment, whereas in 2022, due to the extended duration of the experiment, participants received a compensation of 15 euros. Additional details regarding the recruitment process can be found in the Supplementary Materials.

Settings. We took care to ensure consistent testing conditions and lighting for both the French and Himba groups. The FM100 task was also conducted outdoors, under the shade of a tree, in May 2022. Here too, we measured the luminosity level and coordinates of the white point for each participant using the same spectrophotometer and found similar luminosity settings compared to the Himba sample. The remaining four tasks (DiffSim, Arrow, Squares, CityUniv) were conducted in the basement of a building, where lighting conditions were fixed. To replicate the same luminosity conditions as those in the tent (for the experiments with the Himba participants), we introduced several light sources and measured the luminosity and coordinate of the white point with a spectrophotometer. This group of participants used the same computer, which was calibrated using the same spectrophotometer and maintained consistent settings. Please note that while Himba participants completed the CityUniv task outdoors, French participants completed it in the basement with ample lighting.

Tasks

FM100 (2021). The Farnsworth Munsell 100 Hue Test (Farnsworth, 1957) is composed of four trays containing a total of 85 removable color caps with incremental variations in hue. On the one hand, we used it to identify participants with inherited color perception abnormalities, aiming to exclude them from the analysis of the “DiffOrSim” task. On the other hand, we also used it to measure differences in color perception among our participants. The evaluation involved quantifying errors (Total Error Score, *TES*) in the arrangement of color caps in sequential order, across all colors, but also along the red-green axis (using caps 13–33 and 55–75) and along the blue-yellow axis (using caps 1–12, 34–54, and 76–85; V. C. Smith et al., 1985). A total of 87 Himba participants took part in this experiment. We compared their results with the data from Kinnear & Sahraie (2002) who generously shared their data with us. This dataset includes FM100 results from many participants in the United Kingdom across all age decades (from 10 to 70 years old). To ensure that any potential differences in results were not attributed to differences between experimental conditions, we also assessed a separate group of 28 French participants under conditions similar to those experienced by the Himba participants. Since we found no significant differences between the large British sample and our smaller French sample (see Supplementary Materials), we decided to use the comprehensive data from Kinnear & Sahraie (2002) for further analysis.

DiffOrSim (2021; standing for “Different or Similar”). We used a forced choice stimulus task inspired by Stone et al. (2014) and Szafir et al. (2014). A central cross appears on the screen (500 ms) followed by the presentation of two colored rectangles on a white background. Following CIE recommendations, rectangles were placed side by side (with a visual angle of 4 degrees for the height and width of both rectangles) and separated by a thin line. We chose two target colors: red and blue (see Illustration 2), using the color centers from Mirjalili et al. (2019). We chose blue since the lens brunescence hypothesis posits a stronger effect for blue colors, and we used the red color as a control. One of the rectangles had the target color (either blue or red), while the other rectangle closely resembled the target color with a difference in color magnitude ranging from 1 to 10 CIELAB units and differing only on one dimension, i.e., only on one of the *L*, *a* or *b* axes. Participants were asked to determine whether the colors of the two rectangles were the same or different. French participants used a two-key auxiliary keyboard to answer. However, this approach proved challenging for the Himba participants. Therefore, Himba participants verbally communicated their responses in their native language, and the experimenter

(who was blind to the good answer) pressed the corresponding response button. Here, we used a computerized adaptive testing (CAT) design: the more frequently the participants perceived a difference between the target and deviant colors, the smaller the color difference magnitude between the two becomes, until the participants could not see any differences between the two rectangles. We recorded the JND (“Just Noticeable Difference”), i.e. the minimum number of CIELAB units for which participants can accurately discriminate between the two colors. A control condition with two rectangles of identical colors was implemented. Participants whose accuracy in this condition was below 75% – indicating that they were perceiving identical colors as being different – were excluded from the analysis. After exclusion, we had 67 Himba participants and 30 French participants.

CityUniv (2022). The City University color vision test (Fletcher, 1980) is used to detect color vision deficiencies, in both the red-green and the blue range. In this experiment printed on a book, participants are first presented with three vertically arranged color caps. Their task is to determine whether the colors are the same or if one differs from the others. The subsequent part requires participants to identify the peripheral color cap that most closely resembles the central color cap. We used this test to exclude participants with inherited red-green color blindness from the 2022 experiment set. Additionally, we quantified tritan errors (namely, errors in the blue range), following a methodology similar to Davies et al. (1998), but given the quasi-absence of variation in the results of these, we do not use this test for comparison between French and Himba in the tritan range. A total of 109 Himba participants and 83 French participants passed this test.

Arrows (2022). This experiment is inspired by Cranwell et al. (2015), which they called the “Chromatic Contrast Discrimination Threshold Test”. We kept a similar design but instead of a grey background, we opted for a blue and red background (see Illustration 2) for the same reasons as in the DiffOrSim experiment. The experiment took place in two phases: one with a blue background, and one with a red background, presented in a counterbalanced order across participants. On each trial, a central cross was briefly displayed (500 ms) followed by the presentation of a colored arrow (size 2.5 degrees, duration 300 ms) positioned randomly either at the top or the bottom (± 5.51 degrees) of the screen. Notably, the color of the arrow always differed from the background by a given number of CIELAB color units. This color difference magnitude varied depending on the axis (L, a, and b) and the color (red, blue). Participants were provided with a two-key response box and instructed to press the 'left' key when the arrow pointed

to the left or press 'right' when the arrow pointed to the right⁶. Similarly to the DiffSim task, this experiment uses computerized adaptive testing (CAT): the distance between the color of the background and the arrows decreases until the participant fails to distinguish the arrow above chance level (50% accuracy; Just Noticeable Difference; *JND*). To ensure reliability, we introduced a control condition both before and after each phase, in which participants had to discriminate the direction of a black arrow against either the blue or the red background. Participants who answered correctly less than 8 times out of the 10 black arrow presentations were excluded from the analysis (see Supplementary Materials for more details). After exclusion, we had 60 Himba participants and 77 French participants.

Squares (2022): This experiment was adapted from Gilbert et al. (2006). A fixation cross was presented during 500 ms, then a circular arrangement of twelve squares (of size 1 cm each) was shown on the screen for a short duration (200 ms). Eleven of these squares shared an identical color, while one square, which we will refer to as the *deviant square*, featured a distinct color. Participants were given a two-key response box and asked to press the 'right' button if the deviant square appeared on the right side of the screen and the 'left' button if it appeared on the left side (note that it never appeared in the middle). Similarly with the Arrows experiment, the experiment had two phases, one with blue colors and one with red colors, with the same order of presentation as in the Arrows experiment. The background color was consistently grey, and the eleven identical squares (either red or blue, see Illustration 2) had the same color throughout the experiment. The color of the deviant squares varied from the other squares' color by a small number of Cielab units (*difficult* condition), a high number of Cielab units (*easy* condition), or an intermediate number of Cielab units (*medium* condition), across each one of the Cielab axes (L, a, b). Each combination (for example, "easy" in the L axis of the blue color) was presented ten times, during which reaction time and accuracy were measured. We calculated an inverse efficiency measure by dividing the reaction time by accuracy. We removed participants who failed more than 50% of the time in the "easy" condition of the blue color. We kept 100 Himba participants and 92 French participants in the analysis.

⁶ In this particular context, it is important to highlight that using a two-key response box posed no issues for the Himba participants, as it had a straightforward function (press → 'left' for left and 'right' for 'right'). This stands in contrast to the DiffOrSim experiment, where participants needed to recall an abstract rule (press 'left' for similarity and 'right' for difference).

It is important to mention that, for all computerized experiments, a training phase including feedback was conducted before the test phase, both prior to the red phase and to the blue phase.

Illustration 13: Color centers used in the DiffOrSim, Arrows, and Squares tasks. Please be aware that these colors may not appear the same to you as they do to the participants, depending on your screen's color calibration. The CIELAB of the red color center are L=41, a=33, b=25 and L=37, a=-1, b=-28 for the blue color center.

Additional data

Multiple hypotheses can be considered to account for potential differences in performance between the French and Himba participants. (1) First, the purpose of this project was to investigate the *lens brunescence hypothesis*, which suggests that differences in exposure to UV light may lead to differences in color perception between Himba and French samples. Since this hypothesis also implies that color perception should decline with age, if this hypothesis holds true, we would expect to observe an age-related effect on the color discrimination tasks (*Age* → *color perception* → *task performance*). However, several other confounding factors may explain differences in task performance between the two groups. (2) Since the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis suggests that color naming affects color perception, one could propose that differences in color naming between the French and Himba would lead to group-level differences in color perception, which in turn, would affect the performance at the color tasks (*confounding: color naming* → *color perception* → *task performance*). (3) Additionally, various other factors (such as sex or iris color) may influence color perception and, as a result, affect task performance. If these factors are not equally distributed between the two populations, they could impact the comparison between the two groups (*confounding: miscellaneous factors* → *color perception* → *task performance*). (4) Finally, general cognitive ability may be a confounding factor which does not affect color perception itself, but may affect task performance through other cognitive mechanisms, such as risk taking when making a decision (Deakin et al., 2004; Skagerlund et al., 2022). Since general cognitive ability is related to exposure to formal education (Peng & Kievit, 2020), and considering that French participants have greater access to formal education, it is possible that differences in general cognitive ability may introduce

some bias in the interpretation of the results (*confounding: general cognitive ability* → *task performance*). In order to understand which of these hypotheses would best explain potential performance differences between our two groups, we measured a set of different variables in the French and Himba samples, assuming that these variables would allow us to discriminate between the above accounts for group effects on performance (see Table 1).

Table 1: Table summarizing the variables used in the analyses (first column) along with their range of possible values (second column). The third column indicates on which sample the variable was collected. The fourth column shows the hypothesis under consideration, namely, the reason for which we chose to include these variables. More information will be provided about these variables below.

Predictor	Values	Sample	Hypothesis
<i>Age</i>	between 16 and 60	both	(1) Lens brunescence hypothesis predictor → color perception → task performance
<i>Literacy</i>	None; Some	Himba	(2) Confounding: Sapir-Whorf hypothesis predictor → color naming → color perception → task performance
<i>ModernityExposure</i>	between 0 and 1	Himba	
<i>PatternNaming</i>	English-like; Other	both	
<i>LexiconRichness</i>	between 1 and 5	French	
<i>Sex</i>	male; female	both	(3) Confounding: miscellaneous factors affecting color perception predictor → color perception → task performance
<i>EyeColor</i>	light-irises; dark-irises	French	
<i>CorrectionEye</i>	No problem; Problem corrected; Problem not corrected	French	
<i>ExpertiseColor</i>	Beginner; Intermediate; Advanced	French	
<i>NumAbilities</i>	between 0 and 100	Himba	(4) Confounding: cognitive ability predictor → task performance
<i>Matrice</i>	between 0 and 100	Himba	
<i>NbYearsOfStudy</i>	between 0 and 8	French	

(1) Lens brunescence hypothesis. For both the French and Himba samples, we collected data on participants' *age*. Indeed, *age* is a central variable in the

lens brunescence hypothesis as lens brunescence increases incrementally with exposure to UV incidence. In the French sample, we also recorded whether French participants had already worked outside for a long period of time, which could have exposed them to high levels of UV radiation over their lifetime. It is noteworthy, however, that despite not explicitly excluding participants based on this criterion, all of our French participants held indoor occupations with minimal sun exposure. Since there was not enough variation in the sample (and this minimal variation was pondered by the use of sunglasses), we decided to remove this variable from the analysis.

(2) Confounding: Sapir-Whorf hypothesis. The Sapir-Whorf hypothesis suggests that color naming influences color perception (Kay & Kempton, 1984; Sapir, 1921; Whorf, 1940). Although Sapir-Whorf effects are typically weak and generally occur only when perceiving stimuli across different lexical categories, it is essential to ensure that the differences in the task performance between the Himba and French samples cannot be attributed to differences in color naming patterns. Since we could not collect color naming data for all colors (and this was previously conducted by Mylonas et al., 2022), we asked participants to name a subset of five color chips. Additionally, for Himba participants only, we collected several variables that may affect color naming.

Then, both the French and Himba participants were asked to label five color chips. These colors were chosen from the color prototypes available on the website <https://www.crispedge.com/> (see Illustration 14).

dark blue RGB: 19, 30, 77 bleu - otjiburou	light blue RGB: 92, 146, 190 bleu - otjiburou	blue-green RGB: 19, 126, 109 bleu / vert otjiburou / otjigirine	light green RGB: 118, 255, 123 vert- otjigirine	dark green RGB: 3, 53, 0 vert - otjigirine
---	--	---	--	---

Illustration 14: Color chips chosen for the color naming task. The first term on the third row shows how the color chip is supposed to be named in French (using Basic Color Term definition of Berlin & Kay, 1969) and OtjiHimba (Mylonas et al., 2021). Please be aware that these colors may not appear the same to you as they do to the participants, depending on your screen's color calibration.

From these responses, we created a “*PatternNaming*” variable, which can take two values: “English-like” when the participant names the two blue colors (dark blue and light blue) with the word for blue (‘otjiburou’ in OtjiHimba, ‘bleu’ in French) and the three green colors (dark green, light green and blue-green) with the word for green (‘otjigirine’ in OtjiHimba, ‘vert’ in French); or “Other” if they used a different almost-idiosyncratic pattern (see Illustration 15). We also computed the *color lexicon richness*, which measures the number of different

color terms used by the participants to name the five color chips. Please note that contrary to the PatternNaming measure, we used here the ‘raw’ responses of the participants, without classifying them under the definition of Basic Color Terms by Berlin & Kay (1969). This variable is particularly valuable for the French participants, as it may reflect the desire to communicate precisely about colors.

Illustration 15: Pattern of color naming used by the Himba participants. Each column represents a participant. The first row shows the color terms used to describe the dark blue color chip, the second row the light blue color chip, the third the blue-green one, the fourth the light green one, and the fifth row the dark green one. The color is the visual representation of the color term used by the participant, but it does not mean that the participant had this color in mind when using this color term. For example, in the first row of the first column, the participant has used the term “otjiburou” to describe the first two color chips and “otjigirine” to describe the last three color chips.

In the Himba sample, we recorded the *literacy* level, which we use here as a proxy for their exposure to schooling⁷. Since school is conducted in English, and students may learn the English color names, schooling may bias the patterns of color naming. Additionally, we used a proxy for the exposure to colored manufactured artifacts, which we call *ModernityExposure*. This variable is the average of three indicators: whether the participants dress in a traditional (0) versus modern (1) clothing style, whether they own a cellphone (1) or not (0) and how often they went to the city this year (varying between 0 to 10 times, normalized between 0 and 1). Indeed, while they were tested in their local villages, some of them often go to the city nearby (Opuwo, in the Kaokoland, ~30 000 inhabitants; Mwinga et al., 2022), where there are a few supermarkets, bars, and gaz stations, and thus contain many bright colors and manufactured

⁷ We also collected direct data on exposure to school; however, due to a misunderstanding, we believe our measure of literacy is more representative of their actual exposure to schooling than the initially intended variable (see Supplementary Materials for more details).

artifacts. We hypothesize that people who are more exposed to the modern world may have a greater need to distinguish objects by their color, and thus would communicate more consistently about colors.

Confounding: miscellaneous factors affecting color perception. For both the French and Himba samples, we collected data on the participants' sex. Indeed, women may perceive more shades than men (Jaint et al., 2010), even if a few studies suggest that it may not be the case (Hood et al., 2006; Pickford, 1947) or that this difference may exist only in the red-green axis (Bimler et al., 2004; Rodríguez-Carmona et al., 2008). For the French sample only, we recorded the *eye color*⁸ using two categories: light-coloured irises and dark-coloured irises. Indeed, individuals with light-coloured irises have lower macular pigment than individuals with dark-coloured irises, which may in turn lead to differences in color perception (Hammond & Caruso-Avery, 2000). Furthermore, we documented whether the French participants had a vision deficiency and, if yes, how they corrected it. This variable *CorrectionEye* can take three values: no vision deficiency, vision deficiency corrected (by lens or glasses), and vision deficiency not corrected (usually when participants had a very small vision impairment). Although we did not have specific hypotheses regarding this variable, we aimed to ensure that it would not introduce biases into our results. Additionally, we assessed French participants' level of expertise with colors (*ExpertiseColor*), distinguishing between those who had minimal interaction with colors in their daily lives, those with hobbies involving some knowledge of colors (such as occasional painting), and those whose professions revolved around color (e.g., photographer). Our hypothesis was that individuals with greater experience with colors might exhibit higher color perception abilities, building on previous observations of perceptual training (Gold & Watanabe, 2010). We collected these variables to ensure that these factors, as they are not equally distributed between the French and Himba samples, do not influence the results of our color tasks.

Confounding: general cognitive ability. In addition, we performed a few tasks to index general cognitive ability (only in the Himba sample), which we solely intended to use for examining inter-individual differences within the Himba sample. Our objective was to select the color perception tasks the least biased by general cognitive ability. Considering that the majority of the Himba people

⁸ All Himba participants have dark-colored iris, which is why we recorded this variable only for French participants.

we tested are non-literate, we assessed inter-individual variations in general cognitive ability using tasks that do not require reading. Specifically, we employed a modified version of the *WAIS matrices task* (Wechsler, 2008) and a *numerical ability task* (Grégoire et al., 2001) involving short problems such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division (e.g., “how much is 3+5?”, or “how much is 2x6?”), and comparisons between quantities (for example, “which number is bigger between 56 and 651?”). Himba participants displayed high variability in their performance on these tasks. Additionally, the outcomes of these tasks were correlated, indicating that they collectively measured a shared underlying factor. In the French sample, we recorded the *number of years of study* of the participants (0 if the participant stopped after secondary school, 2, 3, 5, or 8).

Analysis

Understanding the effects of the predictors

First, we investigated the effect of the confounding factors on the performance at the color tasks. This step is essential to determine which task is least influenced by general cognitive ability and to understand whether we should also control for some confounding factors when comparing the performance of the French and Himba samples.

For each population, we incorporated the predictors of Table 1 in linear regression models using, for each task, color discrimination performance as the dependent variable. In the French sample, we investigated the effect of *Age*, *Sex*, *EyeColor*, *ExpertiseColor*, *CorrectionEye*, *NbYearsStudy*, and *LexiconRichness*, while in the Himba sample, we looked at the effect of *Age*, *Sex*, *ModernityExposure*, *Literacy*, *PatternNaming*, *NumAbilities*, and *Matrice*. We employed several approaches to measure the contribution of each predictor. First, we built models with individual predictors, evaluating the adjusted R^2 to assess the proportion of variance explained by each predictor (*IndividualAdjR²* method). Secondly, we built models containing all the predictors and successively removed each variable from the model to measure the decrease in the adjusted R^2 (*PartialAdjR²* method). Finally, we z-scored all our predictors and incorporated them into a single model, allowing us to compare their standardized

estimates (*StandEstimate* method⁹). These multiple measures of predictor contribution importance were employed due to the absence of a clear consensus on the optimal method for assessing variable importance in regression models.

To examine how these variables interact, we subsequently incorporated them into a Structural Equation Modeling (path model) using the *lavaan* package (Rosseel, 2012). Path models require the a-priori specification of the causal relationships that exist among variables. In the Himba villages we visited, young participants have greater access to schooling and are generally more familiar with the modernized world (Age → Literacy & ModernityExposure). Additionally, boys tend to be given priority to access schooling, almost all men now dress in modern outfits, and men are usually given more opportunities to go to the city (Sex → Literacy & ModernityExposure). We hypothesize that literacy may influence patterns of color naming since schooling is conducted in English (Literacy → PatternNaming). Furthermore, school is supposed to positively impact performance in numerical abilities and matrice tasks (Literacy → NumAbilities & Matrice; Peng & Kievit, 2020). Performance in the numerical abilities and matrices should be correlated, since they should both measure a common underlying factor (NumAbilities ↔ Matrice). Given that many studies have reported a decline in general cognitive ability with age (Murman, 2015), we also consider that age might affect scores at the matrix and numerical ability tasks (Age → NumAbilities & Matrice). Finally, we suggest that exposure to the manufactured colored objects might influence color naming, as individuals who are exposed to colored objects may have a greater communicative need to consistently and efficiently talk about colors (ModernityExposure → PatternNaming).

Using these causal pathways, we built a path model to understand whether the effects of our variables on the performance at the color discrimination tasks are direct or if certain variables, such as age or sex, influence the outcomes through other mediating factors. Path models using the *lavaan* package do not allow the addition of the participant ID as a random factor. Thus, for each conclusion drawn from the path model, we also conducted more specific mediation analyses that include only the results of one task to ensure that these findings hold. For

⁹ Please note that we recoded the binary variables (PatternNaming, Sex, Literacy) into dummy variables (0/1); thus, their standardized estimate is not directly comparable to the others.

the sake of simplicity, we do not include the results from the mediation analysis here, but they are available in the Supplementary Materials.

Investigating the lens-brunescence hypothesis

The preliminary analysis aiming at understanding the predictors' role helped us determine which dataset to use and how to design the analysis for the primary hypothesis under consideration, the lens brunescence hypothesis. This preliminary analysis suggests that we should specifically focus on the results from the Arrows task, and to a lesser extent, from the Squares task, as the impact of general cognitive ability is the weakest for these two tasks. Additionally, it indicates that we should account for the influence of color naming when investigating the lens brunescence hypothesis. As a reminder, the lens brunescence hypothesis posits that Himba participants will demonstrate a greater decline in color discrimination with age compared to French participants, particularly in the case of blue colors, due to their increased exposure to UV radiation.

To test this hypothesis, we first normalized the results for each axis and color. This step was necessary as we did not calibrate our experiment for differences in cone contrasts, and CIELAB differences translate to different cone contrasts and thresholds depending on the cone excitation (blue versus red), which explains the differences in thresholds between our different colors and axis. We had some issues with the b-axis of the red color in the Arrow task, as many participants reached the predetermined 'ceiling' JND value. This 'ceiling' value was set to ensure that the experiment would not continue indefinitely in cases where participants may not have fully grasped the experiment's objectives or had extremely low color vision. Given the absence of data for the 'true' value for many French and Himba participants, we decided to exclude this particular combination of axis and color from further analysis in the Arrows task (note that its exclusion does not alter any of the conclusions presented in this paper). We then aggregated the normalized results by color. Using these datasets, we build mixed-effect models (using `lmerTest` package; Kuznetsova et al., 2017) to predict the tasks' performance function of the three main factors related to the lens brunescence hypothesis: color (red or blue, within-subject), population (French or Himba, inter-subject), and age (treated as a continuous linear or quadratic variable, inter-subject). These factors were evaluated in interaction with each other, and we introduced participant ID as a random effect to account for individual variability in all the models.

Using the data from the Arrows task, we used the color, population, and age as linear (**model 1**) or quadratic (**model 2**) to predict the performance. When comparing model 1 and model 2 (using likelihood ratio Chi-Square test with `anova` function), we found that the quadratic age model (model 2) fitted the data better. We provide the results for both models to ensure a comprehensive understanding of our findings. We build the same model using the data of the Squares task (**model 3**) using only age as linear, since adding age as quadratic did not improve the fit. Then, we also combined the data of the Arrows and the Squares tasks in one dataset, adding the experiment type (two levels: Arrows/Squares) as a fixed effect in interaction with the other effects (**model 4**).

Given the potential influence of PatternNaming on the performance in color tasks observed in our previous analysis, one might argue that the differences in performance we identified between the French and Himba populations stem from differences in color naming, aligning with the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis. To address this possibility, we build **model 5** which is similar to model 4 with the exception that it exclusively incorporates participants who name colors using an 'English-like pattern' in both the Himba and French populations. This model encompasses data from 37 French participants and 27 Himba participants in the Arrows task, and 41 French participants and 49 Himba participants in the Squares task.

Please note that all analyses were run on the set without outliers, but also on the set including all participants. Using the entire set of data (i.e., with outlier participants) did not alter any of the conclusions presented in this Chapter, but added considerable noise to the data. Additionally, for control purposes, we built 'raw' models using unnormalized data and included 'axis' as a fixed factor interacting with other fixed effects. All models are provided in the Supplementary Materials.

RESULTS

Understanding the predictors effect

Figure 5: Importance of the variables on the average performance across tasks: FM100 (top row), DiffOrSim (second row from the top), Squares (third row), and Arrows (fourth row). The two predictors highlighted in green reflect general cognitive ability. The left panel shows the adjusted R^2 of models that exclusively incorporate the specific predictor under consideration. The second panel showcases the partial adjusted R^2 when we remove the predictor from a model that encompasses all variables (i.e., the difference in R^2 between the model containing all predictors and the model with all predictors except the predictor of interest). Finally, in the rightmost panel, we present the standardized estimates when examining a model that includes all z-scored variables. The adjusted R^2 of a model including all variables is 0.27 in the Arrow task and 0.21 in the Squares task. When considering the raw files including color, axis, and level (only for Squares) as fixed factors and participant ID as a random effect, the adjusted R^2 value of the Arrows task becomes 0.85 and the one of Squares task becomes 0.52.

Confounding: general cognitive ability

Surprisingly, our analysis revealed a strong connection between the results of the numerical abilities task and the color discrimination performance for both the DiffOrSim and FM100 tasks (see Figure 5). Notably, irrespective of the various

methods used for assessing the importance of the predictors, numerical ability consistently ranked as the factor contributing most to color discrimination performance, in both tasks. For example, when considered as the sole predictor of the results (method *IndividualAdjR²*), numerical ability accounted for approximately 21% of the variance in these two tasks. Moreover, the standardized estimate for numerical ability was notably high in models that included all fixed factors, hovering at 0.39 for FM100 task and 0.28 for the DiffOrSim task (*StandEstimate*). The removal of numerical ability from these models led to a decrease of around 0.11 in the adjusted R² for these two tasks (*PartialAdjR²*).

While the Squares and Arrows tasks are also connected to numerical ability scores, the predictive strength of numerical ability was lower for both these tasks, accounting for approximately 11% of the variance in the data (*IndividualAdjR²*), with a partial R² of approximately 0.04 and a standardized estimate of 0.16 for the Squares task and 0.19 for the Arrows task. In the Squares task, numerical ability remained the top predictor of the results when using the *IndividualAdjR²* method, the second most significant predictor in the *PartialR²* method and the third most significant in the *StandEstimate* method. As a comparison, the relative importance of numerical ability in the Arrows task was somewhat lower, ranking as the third most important variable in the *IndividualAdjR²* method, the fourth in the *PartialR²* method, and the fifth in the *StandEstimate* method. For this reason, we chose to emphasize the Arrows test in the subsequent analyses, though we will also examine the results of the Squares tasks.

Although we chose to focus our more in-depth analyses on the Arrows and Squares task, we examined the results from all tasks (please refer to the Supplementary Materials for more information). These results consistently revealed differences in performance between French and Himba individuals. Notably, French participants had better performance than their Himba counterparts in all tasks. An intriguing anecdotal observation emerged: the color discrimination tasks with stronger correlations to numerical abilities also displayed more pronounced performance differences across the two groups. Specifically, the results from the DiffOrSim and FM100 tasks show strong differences in the average performance between French and Himba (Cohen's *d*: 1.8, variance: 0.13 for the DiffOrSim experiment; Cohen's *d*: 1.7 and variance: 0.06 for the FM100 experiment), whereas the effect size of the difference was a bit lower for the Squares task (Cohen's *d*: 1.4, variance: 0.06) and even lower for the Arrows task (Cohen's *d*: 0.5, variance: 0.06). This observation underscores the critical importance of accounting for the relation with general

cognitive ability, as it has the potential to influence the interpretation of the findings of cross-cultural studies.

Figure 6: Results from Structural Equation Modeling. The number displays the standardized estimates, and the stars shows the significance (** for $p \leq 0.01$ and * for $p \leq 0.05$). Following lavaan recommendations, sex was coded as a dummy variable, while PatternNaming (English-like/Other) and Literacy (some/none) were coded as ordered variables. This path model only incorporates the results from the Arrows and the Squares tasks for the Himba population.

Confounding: color naming pattern

ModernityExposure had an impact on the performance only in the Squares task ($\beta_{ModernityExposure} = -0.78 \pm 0.25$ where 0.25 is the standard error, $p < 0.01$), with participants who reported being more exposed to urban life performing better. However, its effect disappears when this variable is integrated inside a path model including data from both Squares and Arrows tasks. Similarly, in the Arrows task, we observed that the *color naming pattern* plays a significant role in the performance in the color tasks: Himba participants naming colors using an

“English-like” pattern demonstrated better performance (linear regression model with *PatternNaming* as sole predictor of JND: $\beta_{PatternNamingOther} = 0.63 \pm 0.20$, $p < 0.01$). Here too, the impact of *PatternNaming* disappears when integrated into the path model. *Literacy* also appears to have an impact on the performance in the color tasks: Himba participants who are literate tend to perform better in color discrimination in the Squares task ($\beta_{LiteracySome} = -0.43 \pm 0.15$, $p < 0.01$), and to a smaller extent, in the Arrows task ($\beta_{LiteracySome} = -0.39 \pm 0.21$, $p = 0.065$). However, the path model suggests that literacy affects performance at the color discrimination task primarily because it influences the performance in numerical abilities tasks. This suggests that literacy does not directly affect color perception per se, but affects performance through other cognitive mechanisms (e.g., decision making). To summarize, while the results from the linear regression models suggest that our predictors for color naming (*PatternNaming*, *Literacy*, *ModernityExposure*) indeed affect performance in the color discrimination tasks, the path model suggests that these variables have a negligible direct effect on predicting performance in the color tasks.

Confounding: other factors influencing color perception

In the Himba sample, sex affected the performance only in the Squares task ($\beta_{ModExposure} = -0.35 \pm 0.15$, $p < 0.05$). The observed sex effect observed in the Himba sample is opposite to our expectations: men appeared to discriminate colors better than women. However, the path model revealed that the limited sex effect vanished when education and general cognitive abilities were included in the model, indicating that this effect likely arose because men generally had greater exposure to education, thereby enhancing their overall cognitive ability, which in turn marginally affected their performance on these tasks. With the French sample, sex just reached significance in the Arrows tasks ($\beta_{sex} = -0.5 \pm 0.24$, $p < 0.05$), with men performing slightly better than women; however, it is interesting to note that the effect went in the opposite direction in the Squares task (with women performing slightly better than men). Since very little of the variance was accounted for by sex in the French sample (5% of the variance in the Arrows task and 2% in the Squares task), we should be careful and not over-interpret the “sex” findings.

Additionally, we found a very small effect of *CorrectionEye*: people having no vision deficiency tended to perform slightly better than participants with a reported vision deficiency in the Arrows task only (corrected or not; $\beta_{corrected} = 0.20 \pm 0.10$, $p < 0.05$; $\beta_{notcorrected} = 0.22 \pm 0.10$, $p < 0.05$), but here too, it explains only 6% of the variance present in the data.

Age

Results from both the Arrows and the Squares experiments suggest that age is the most influential variable in predicting performance in the Himba sample, with performance in the color tasks decreasing with age. Additionally, our analyses indicated that, unlike sex, age had a direct impact on performance at the Arrows and Squares color discrimination task (refer to Figure 2). This finding is further corroborated by additional mediation analyses conducted individually on both the Arrows and the Squares tasks, which consistently demonstrate that the influence of age is not mediated by any other variables within this model (see Supplementary Materials). In contrast, in the French sample, we only found a weak effect of age in the Squares task.

Summary

Task performance is partly influenced by our measures of general cognitive ability. When considering the Arrows and Squares tasks, we find that the impact of general cognitive ability is very weak, but nevertheless present. This suggests that any absolute performance differences between the Himba and French populations should be approached cautiously, and that we should primarily focus on interaction effects. Encouragingly, in both the Arrows and Squares tasks, age has the most significant influence on performance, aligning with the lens brunescence hypothesis. Since the influence of age on performance in the tasks is direct (i.e. not mediated through general cognitive ability measures), we hypothesize that the effect of age may reflect genuine differences in color perception. Additionally, since color naming patterns might influence performance in color discrimination tasks, we should consider controlling for this effect when investigating the lens brunescence hypothesis.

Investigating the lens-brunescence hypothesis

We focused on the results of the Arrows and the Squares tasks, given that they were the least influenced by numerical ability in the Himba sample. The reader can refer to Table 2 for a summary of the models used in this analysis.

Table 2: Table summarizing the model used to investigate the differences in performance between French and Himba participants.

Model	Data	Fixed effects
1	Arrows	age*color*population
2	Arrows	age*color*population + I(age^2)*color*population
3	Squares	age*color*population
4	Arrows & Squares	experiment*age*color*population
5	Arrows & Squares (English-like)	experiment*age*color*population

We found that, as participants aged, the decline in performance was significantly more pronounced among Himba than among French participants (see Figure 7). This interaction between population and age was statistically significant in almost all the models: **model 1** predicting the results of the Arrows task with age as a linear variable ($\beta_{Himba*age} = 0.03 \pm 0.01$, $p < 0.05$; please note that results are normalized; for an order of magnitude of the difference, refer to Figure 8), **model 3** predicting the results of the Squares task with age as a linear variable ($\beta_{Himba*age} = 0.025 \pm 0.010$, $p < 0.05$), **model 4** including the results of both the Arrows and the Squares tasks and experiment type as a fixed factors (model 6: $\beta_{Himba*age} = 0.04 \pm 0.01$, $p < 0.01$). This latest model also suggested a difference at the population level ($\beta_{Himba} = -0.90 \pm 0.36$, $p < 0.05$).

Model 2, which predicts the results of the Arrows tasks with age modeled as quadratic, also showed an effect of age and population, but only when considered in interaction with the color type ($\beta_{Himba*red*agelinear} = -0.21 \pm 0.08$, $p < 0.01$; $\beta_{Himba*red*agequadr} = 0.0035 \pm 0.0012$, $p < 0.01$).

When building a model including only the participants that named colors with an English-like pattern (thus keeping approximately 50% of the participants), the interaction between age and population remained significant (**model 5**: $\beta_{Himba*age} = 0.05 \pm 0.02$, $p < 0.05$), as well as the absolute difference between French and Himba samples: (**model 5**: $\beta_{Himba} = -1.3 \pm 0.5$, $p < 0.05$). This suggests that the differences related to age we observe between the Himba and the French sample are not due to differences in color naming observable between the older and younger Himba participants.

Figure 7: Performance for French (plain line) and Himba (dotted line) participants as a function of age for the two types of color, blue (represented in blue) and red (represented in red). Panel A shows the linear regression (using linear method) of the performance of the Arrows task (normalized Just Noticeable Difference), while Panel B shows the results (normalized inverse efficiency) for the Squares task.

Figure 8: Box A shows the approximate average JND for French participants (of any age) and 25 year old Himba, while box B shows the average JND for a 50 year old Himba participant, for the “a” axis of the blue color. The CIELAB difference values are presented in increments of 5. This Figure only aims at giving an order of magnitude of the differences between French and Himba participants. However, please keep in mind that your perception of these colors will highly depend on the printer or on your screen calibration. If your screen is not calibrated, you will not perceive the same colors as the participants did but to get a better visualisation, consider adjusting the brightness of your screen so that you could distinguish the second arrow (located three boxes to the left of 'A'). While it might seem quite easy to distinguish the arrow in A, one has to remember that the arrows were shown only for 200 ms, with a small size, at a random location on the screen (up or down).

DISCUSSION

Our findings indicate differences in performance on various color-discrimination tasks between French and Himba participants. Given the direct effect of age on performance, we can infer that age affects the perception of colors. Notably, color perception deteriorates more strongly with age in the Himba than in the French sample of participants, for both blue and red colors. Given that blue and red occupy opposite ends of the color spectrum (blue with shorter wavelengths and red with longer wavelengths), it is conceivable that these differences in color perception may extend to other colors along the spectrum, such as green or yellow, although this study did not specifically investigate those colors. Furthermore, it is important to note that the interaction between age and population cannot be attributed only to differences in color naming between the two groups. This is not surprising, as both French and Himba participants were presented with stimuli within the same lexical category (e.g., a blue color on a blue background), while the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis proposes that the language influences perception when comparing stimuli across categories (Gilbert et al., 2006; Roberson et al., 2004). Previous research indicates that the decline in color perception with age is, in part, due to the impact of UV exposure on the lens (Scheffrin et al., 1992; Shinomori et al., 2016). Considering that Himba participants experience higher levels of UV exposure compared to their French counterparts, it is likely that lens brunescence plays a significant role in the more pronounced age-related decline observed in Himba participants.

However, while the lens brunescence hypothesis suggests that the decrease in color perception should be more pronounced for blue colors compared to red ones, our study revealed an age-related decline in both red and blue color perception. Only a few of our analyses suggested that there may be a more pronounced age-related decline in the perception of blue colors. Several non-mutually exclusive hypotheses can explain this finding. First, it is possible that a more pronounced decline in blue perception was too subtle to be detected in our data. To further explore this possibility, we delved into the results of Kinnear & Sahraie (2002), who collected color perception norms for participants in the United Kingdom across different age groups, and we found that the interaction between age and color becomes significant only when including participants above 55 years of age. This suggests that the decline in blue color perception is relatively weak and occurs late in life. Even though Himba participants are more exposed to UV incidence than participants from the United Kingdom, we do not have sufficient data for older participants in our dataset, and a larger sample size might have revealed an interaction between population, age, and color. This is

consistent with the observation that some analyses hinted at the presence of this interaction effect, and the results from the Farnsworth Munsell test also indicated that participants performed worse at discriminating colors in the blue-yellow channel. However, it is important to interpret these findings with caution.

Second, while there may indeed be a more pronounced decline in blue color perception compared to red, it is possible that this effect is overshadowed by other factors. Indeed, our study showed that color perception may be also affected by factors non-related to the eye physiology. In line with Webster et al. (2002), we do not rule out the possibility that the differences in the color environment statistics between the Himba and French settings may also contribute to shaping color perception. While in Europe background colors are usually cool-colored (with colors such as brown, green, or blue; Gibson et al., 2017), blue is a rare color in the Himba environment. In contrast, the red color we used for our stimuli¹⁰ is prevalent in the Himba environment, both resembling the color of the earth and the special ochre taint women traditionally apply to their skin. Therefore, in the Himba settings, the blue stimuli color is likely to be more salient than the red stimuli color. Since saliency might enhance detection (Kerzel & Schönhammer, 2013), the high saliency of blue colors for Himba participants could compensate for the more significant decline in blue color perception caused by UV exposure.

Finally, it is possible that lens brunescence is not the primary causal factor to consider when seeking to understand the differences in color perception between Himba and French participants due to aging. For instance, the more significant impact of aging in the Himba sample could also be attributed to variations in genetic factors between the two populations. Furthermore, another distinguishing factor between the Himba and French participants lies in the Himba culture itself. Fire holds a sacred role in Himba culture and is employed for heating their huts during winter nights. Given that these huts are poorly aerated, smoke tends to accumulate indoors, often leading to eye-related issues among Himba participants, which might accelerate the aging of their eyes. In this scenario, the conclusions drawn from this study may not necessarily generalize to other populations with similar color lexicons. Thus, it would be valuable to

¹⁰ This red color was not the typical vibrant "red" that might come to mind but rather a more brownish-red shade, chosen as it was less tiring to see for the participants' eyes.

gather data from other populations worldwide to gain a more comprehensive understanding of this phenomenon.

In summary, while we remain uncertain about the precise cause of the differences in color perception, we still do observe differences across the two groups. However, are these differences strong enough to shape color lexicons, particularly considering that only older individuals exhibit lower color vision abilities? Given that language is actively used, learned, and passed down across generations, it has been proposed that even weak biases can be amplified into group-level linguistic traits (Dediu et al., 2017; S. Kirby et al., 2007). For example, differences in the shape of the hard palate among different ethno-linguistic groups lead to subtle differences in the acoustics of certain vowels, which may contribute to differences in vowel use across these different groups (Dediu et al., 2019). Similarly, Blasi et al. (2019) showed that differences in bite configuration induced by different subsistence mode (e.g., hunter-gatherers vs. agriculturalists) impact the ease of production of labiodentals, consequently affecting the likelihood of each population incorporating labiodentals into their sound repertoire. Since only older individuals in hunter-gatherer groups tend to possess a distinct bite configuration structure discouraging the use of labiodentals, this study also suggests that language may adapt primarily to older adults.

To comprehend how variations in color perception could affect the pattern of color naming, it is possible to employ agent-based models wherein agents possess a representation of Just Noticeable Difference in their color space (Loreto et al., 2012). For example, Chaabouni et al.'s (2021) recent study, which employed an artificial neural network for a discrimination game, offers additional support for the claim that differences in perceptual structure may affect language evolution. In this game, a "producer" agent is tasked to describe a color target using a color term to a "guesser" agent, who must identify the correct color chip from two options: the color target and a distractor. The researchers manipulated what they referred to as "discriminative need" - which they used as a proxy for communicative need - defined as the minimum distance between targets and distractors in the CIELAB space. As such, their measure of discriminative need closely aligns with differences in the agent's perceptual space we evoke here. Their study showed that the higher the discriminative need, the more color terms a language is likely to have in its vocabulary, which suggest that differences in perceptual structure may influence the evolution of color terms. Applying this model to our data, using the CIELAB differences between the French and Himba population, could offer valuable insights for further investigation.

Certainly, we recognize that the effects we are discussing are relatively subtle and may only exert a limited influence on the evolution of color lexicons. Thus, we do *not* claim here that differences in color perception represent the sole factor influencing color lexicons. Instead, we recognize communicative need as a primordial factor influencing color lexicons, which are shaped by both cultural and environmental factors (Josserand, Meeussen, et al., 2021). The Himba population offers a robust illustration of the multifaceted nature of these explanations. While we hypothesize that, over the course of the evolution of their language, lower color perception might have generated a negative pressure for adopting new color terms, the Himba's recent exposure to the English language and the industrialized world has driven the population to adopt new color terms, with two new color terms emerging in only 15 years. Thus, we acknowledge and underscore the considerable strength and significance of cultural factors in shaping color lexicons.

In summary, our assertion is as follows: while color lexicons are undeniably shaped by differences in communicative needs, the perceptual structure may play a dual role, serving as a driver for both similarities and differences in color lexicons. Similarities arise because all humans tend to share a similar perceptual system, yet the perceptual system also introduces differences due to the existence of slight variations in the perceptual space across different groups, which may influence the evolution of language. These subtle variations in color perception may be attributed to differences in UV exposure, which can impact eye physiology (Dediu, 2023; Josserand, Meeussen, et al., 2021; Lindsey & Brown, 2002; S. Walter, 2011). However, further research and data are essential to precisely understand the mechanisms underlying these group-level variations.

TRANSITION

While previous studies have highlighted that weak biases in human anatomico-physiology may influence the phonological repertoire of languages, there was limited evidence to suggest that they can also affect the lexical repertoire of languages. In this section, we conducted a thorough investigation into the lens brunescence hypothesis, which posits that differences in exposure to UV radiation at the group level affect color perception, subsequently influencing color vocabularies. Our statistical analysis suggests that populations living under higher UV exposure tend to have fewer specific terms to describe the color blue. Our natural experiment further supports these findings by revealing differences in color perception among populations exposed to varying levels of UV radiation. Together, these chapters emphasize that color lexicons are shaped by both the environment and culture while also highlighting the potential role of perceptual space in driving diversity within color lexicons.

These findings focus on group-level differences in color perception between populations. However, the situation is not as clear-cut as stating that 'All Himba individuals exhibit lower discrimination abilities in the blue spectrum compared to the French'. Instead, our analyses suggest substantial variation *within* groups, consistent with previous findings from Dediu et al. (2019). Indeed, and similarly to the effect of the bite-configuration shape (Blasi et al., 2019), the lens brunescence effect primarily manifests itself in older adults, and evolves gradually with age. This significant inter-individual variation within a population gives rise to numerous questions: how many participants should be biased toward using a specific language feature within a group in order to influence language evolution, and how strong should their bias be? For example, is it

possible that if slightly fewer individuals were showing differences in color perception abilities, this would also prevent the adoption of new color terms? To be able to answer these questions, it is necessary to take into account the role of network structure. Indeed, the influence of a biased individual will be different depending of whether this individual has a central position in the network, and thus, is more influential to spread their bias.

Studying the influence of individual differences on language evolution within a group has remained relatively understudied, as most studies have focused on group-level differences and universal biases. Therefore, in the following section, we aim to address these questions and explore how language evolves within various types of groups: heterogeneous groups (comprising individuals with high inter-individual variation, i.e., individuals with different language abilities) and homogeneous groups (characterized by low inter-individual variation). To achieve this, we will employ a combination of laboratory experiments (Chapter 3) and agent-based models (Chapters 4 and 5).

Part 2

Image generated by MidJourney AI using the following prompt: "individual differences in network affect language"

3

DIVERSITY RULES: THE INFLUENCE OF A MINORITY ON LANGUAGE CHANGE

CONTEXT

This research was conducted during an exchange at the Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics, in Nijmegen (the Netherlands), under the supervision of Limor Raviv. This Chapter was written in collaboration with François Pellegrino, Dan Dediu, and Limor Raviv. This Chapter will be soon submitted for publication. The data, the code for the analysis and the Supplementary Materials are available on my github: <https://github.com/mathjoss/ExpCommunityVariation>.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our gratitude to all the participants who contributed to this experiment, whether during the pre-tests or the main experiment. Additionally, I would like to express my thanks to the Van Gogh program for their funding support for this exchange to the Netherlands.

ABSTRACT

Variations in language abilities, use, and production style are ubiquitous within any given population. While research on language evolution has traditionally overlooked the potential impact of such individual differences, these can have an important impact on the trajectory of language evolution and ongoing change.

To address this gap, we use a group communication game for studying language evolution in the lab, in which micro-societies of interacting participants develop and use artificial languages to successfully communicate with each other. Importantly, one participant in the group is assigned a keyboard with a limited inventory of letters (simulating a speech impairment that individuals may encounter in real life), forcing them to communicate differently than the rest. We test how languages evolve in such heterogeneous groups and whether they adapt to accommodate the unique characteristics of individuals with language idiosyncrasies. Our results suggest that language evolves differently in groups where some individuals have distinct language abilities, eliciting more innovative elements at the cost of reduced communicative success and convergence. Furthermore, we observed strong partner-specific accommodation to the minority individual, but only a partial carry-over to the group level. Importantly, this degree of group-wide adaptation was not systematic and depended on the participants' attachment to established language forms. Our findings provide compelling evidence that individual differences can permeate and accumulate within a linguistic community, ultimately driving changes in languages over time. They also underscore the importance of integrating individual differences into future research on language evolution.

INTRODUCTION

Languages demonstrate a remarkable capacity to adapt to their environment (Everett et al., 2015; Nölle et al., 2020; Regier et al., 2016), their culture (MacKeigan & Muth, 2006; Majid & Kruspe, 2018), and even the type of network (Lupyan & Dale, 2010; Nettle, 2012) in which they are embedded. Recent studies have also revealed intriguing evidence of languages adapting to the anatomical and physiological biases of their speakers (Dediu et al., 2019; Moisik & Dediu, 2017). For example, the distinctive bite configuration observed in hunter-gatherer populations – which is induced by an intense tooth wear diet – renders the production of labiodental sounds slightly more challenging compared to the typical bite configuration of agriculturalists, which may contribute to the lower occurrence of labiodental sounds from their sound repertoire (Blasi et al., 2019). These studies suggest the existence of different patterns of variation in human anatomy and physiology across people coming from various ethnolinguistic groups. These differences lead to subtle variations in the produced language, which may give rise to cross-linguistic differences in the long-term (Dediu et al., 2017). Indeed, as language is repeatedly used and transmitted within a

population over generations, even weak biases could be amplified, thus playing a role in shaping the landscape of linguistic diversity (S. Kirby et al., 2007).

This literature emphasizes the rich pool of diversity present among different populations, but also sheds light on the substantial variation in anatomico-physiological features that exists within speakers of the same language. This variation in anatomy and physiology is just one of many sources of language variation; other differences in linguistic capacity (Labov, 1979) or cognitive ability (Kapnola, 2016; Kong & Edwards, 2016; Lev-Ari & Peperkamp, 2013, 2014) may also affect language production and perception. Theories of sociolinguistics emphasize additional contributing factors such as gender, age, socioeconomic background, and regional exposure, all of which contribute to the intricate patterns of linguistic diversity within languages (Byrd, 1992; Foulkes & Docherty, 2006; Labov, 1994, 2001). This variation leads to significant individual differences in crucial language aspects, with sound production being one notable example (Allen et al., 2003; Johnson et al., 1993; Mielke et al., 2016; R. Newman, 1997; R. S. Newman et al., 2001; Peterson & Barney, 1952; Zellou, 2017). For example, in Dutch, /r/ can be realized among others as a tap [r], approximant [ɹ], trill [r] or [ʀ] or even as a fricative [ʁ] (Sebregts, 2014). As such, variation in language is ubiquitous, spanning across all levels within a population, encompassing differences not only between social groups but also within social groups (Fillmore et al., 2014; Yu & Zellou, 2019). In this study, we aim to investigate whether individual variation in language present *within* a group, such as the inability to produce a sound, might influence the language employed by the entire group. To do so, we use an experimental approach involving groups of four participants communicating using a miniature artificial language, with one participant assigned a biased keyboard with a limited inventory of letters.

Remarkably, individuals may naturally embrace the language variations of others. Research shows that individuals have an unconscious inclination to adjust their language during communication, mirroring that of their conversation partner (also known as *linguistic alignment*¹¹). This alignment can encompass a range of linguistic characteristics, such as phonetics (Pardo, 2006), speaking rate (Giles et al., 1991), word choices (e.g. Brennan & Clark, 1996), grammatical structure (Branigan et al., 2010), and even nonverbal behaviors like gestures and facial expressions (Chartrand & Bargh, 1999). Numerous explanations for these adjustments have been proposed: it could be a result of priming (Branigan

¹¹ This is also known under *linguistic style adaptation* or *linguistic style matching* concepts, even if these refer to slightly different concepts (Postmus, 2023).

et al., 2010), a way to increase the chances of successful communication (e.g. Bortfeld & Brennan, 1997; Clark, 1996), or a strategy to increase social bonding (van Baaren et al., 2003). Some individuals demonstrate a greater inclination toward linguistic alignment than others. These individual differences in linguistic alignment are associated with the personal characteristics of both the individuals themselves and their communication partners. These personal characteristics encompass hierarchical position in the workplace, leadership roles, gender, ethnic origin, likability, social desirability, and position within a social network (Bilous & Krauss, 1988; Gnisci, 2005; E. Jones et al., 1999; S. Jones et al., 2014; Natale, 1975; Noble & Fernandez, 2015; Willemyns et al., 1997).

Thus, we all have our unique way of expressing language and we adapt differently to the speakers with whom we are communicating. While this alignment mostly concerns pair interaction, the substantial individual differences in language raise an important question at the group level: How may these individual differences shape the trajectory of language evolution?

Studies on language evolution typically overlook these individual differences, focusing instead on universal cognitive and communicative biases. This emphasis on universal biases is motivated by the intention to offer insights into the core aspects of language that are shared by all human languages, to better understand the origins, development, and constraints of language. This approach has also led to an increased emphasis on group-level patterns and phenomena typical of populations (Yu & Zellou, 2019), aimed at understanding how languages are shaped by environmental and cultural factors (De Busser, 2015; Raviv et al., 2019b). The use of statistical analyses that focus on averaging data and excluding outliers may also contribute to this oversight. Yet, treating groups as homogeneous units can lead to a substantial loss of valuable information for understanding language change (Yu & Zellou, 2019).

Notably, while languages adapt to universal cognitive and communicative biases (such as biases in learning; Culbertson, 2012), they could also accommodate the biases of only a subset of their speakers. For example, The Al-Sayyid Bedouin community in Israel and the Kata-Kolok community in Indonesia experience 2 to 5% of their population being born with congenital deafness (compared to approximately 0.1% in the United States; De Vos, 2011; Fox, 2008). In response to this unique situation where there is a relatively high degree of deafness in the population, both communities have developed local sign languages that are used by both deaf and hearing members. These sign languages showcase a sophisticated structure and appear to have evolved

spontaneously over generations through interactions between deaf and hearing members (Sandler et al., 2005). Without considering this minority's influence, our grasp of how these languages have emerged and evolved would remain incomplete. Linguistic alignment can also contribute to reducing unpredictable language variations and promotes language regularization (Fehér et al., 2016). Asymmetry in linguistic alignment also facilitates the diffusion of categorical structures (Fehér et al., 2019) or the simplification of language due to linguistic alignment between adults native and non-native speakers (S. Frank & Smith, 2018). These examples highlight the idea that small-scale interactions may influence population-level linguistic phenomena, and that it is therefore crucial to consider individual differences when studying the evolution of language.

However, little is known about the exact dynamics underlying the processes of language adaptation to a minority, let alone in the context of the evolution of language. Recently, Josserand et al. (2021; in-review; see also this thesis) tackled this issue by using agent-based models in complex communicative networks. In this model, Bayesian agents interact using an abstract language feature. While some agents lack prior expectations about language, others are inherently predisposed toward a specific linguistic variant, and are referred to as *biased agents*. This model allowed the investigation of several parameters, such as the percentage of biased people or the bias strength necessary to influence the language of a population. Contrary to the intuitive view suggesting that the biased minority would eventually adopt the language of the unbiased majority, this research suggested that the emergent shared language of the entire group is, in fact, influenced by the biases held by some individuals, even when they are the minority. Additionally, the spread of individual differences depended on the local position of individuals in the network: when biased agents strategically hold many connections or act as bridges between multiple agents, their impact on the group's language becomes more pronounced (Fagyal et al., 2010; Josserand et al., in-review). These results also resonate with the work of Navarro et al. (2018), who showed that in heterogeneous populations, languages transmitted via iterated learning (i.e., chains of multiple generations of participants where the output of one person becomes the input for the next person in the chain) can become unpredictable and often distorted by the Bayesian learners with the strongest beliefs toward a specific rule. While such agent-based models are valuable for exploring parameters relative to network structure, they may not accurately represent the dynamics of adaptation at play at the individual level. Specifically, in the two models mentioned earlier (Josserand, Allasonnière-Tang, et al., 2021; Navarro et al., 2018), communication is Bayesian (Griffiths & Kalish, 2007), which could arguably diverge from real-world communication

dynamics (Ferdinand & Zuidema, 2009) or not be fully tractable (Woensdregt et al., 2021). Thus, it is essential to complement these computational models with laboratory-controlled experiments, which allow us to observe the live formation of languages with real interacting human participants.

Laboratory-controlled experiments provide robust findings regarding the processes at play in language evolution and explore causal relationships. They often involve the laboratory-based learning of artificial languages and the observation of their evolution during transmission among participants. These approaches have been used to simulate the emergence of systematicity and compositionality in miniature languages, as well as examine the trajectory of language change over generations (S. Kirby et al., 2008, 2014; Raviv et al., 2019a; Scott-Phillips & Kirby, 2010; Tamariz & Kirby, 2016). A new paradigm entails embedding participants within micro-societies, where they collaboratively create languages from scratch as they engage in successive interactions involving both familiar and novel elements. This approach is especially valuable in understanding how individuals adapt to one another's languages within the context of language evolution. Moreover, since it enables the manipulation of group composition, this approach has also shed light on how the social environment shapes languages. Notably, research has revealed that language evolves differently within communities of varying sizes (Raviv et al., 2019b) and structures (Raviv et al., 2020). Since this micro-society communication paradigm makes it possible to artificially introduce variation within a group in a controlled manner, it serves as the ideal framework for observing the influence of individual differences on language evolution and to study how this may impact the group's language.

In the current study, we used this experimental approach to test how language evolves in heterogeneous populations of interacting participants. Our experiment involves small groups of four individuals who attempt to communicate successively in alternating pairs using an artificial language. In each group, one participant is given a biased keyboard restricting their ability to produce specific letters, thus simulating a speech variation or speech impairment that individuals may experience in their real lives. Our aim is to understand how this biased participant affects the language of the group. Will the majority wipe away the biases of the minority and use a language featuring all the available letters, or conversely, will the collective language of the group adapt to accommodate the biases of the minority? Furthermore, our study allows us to investigate how the personal characteristics of participants might promote or hinder this adaptive process. Specifically, we explore how the participants' prosociality and cognitive

flexibility may affect their tendency to accommodate to others. Prosocial behavior encompasses dimensions of empathy and perspective-taking (Caprara et al., 2005), which entail feeling others' needs in order to react adequately to them. As individuals who possess high perspective-taking abilities often mirror the actions of those they interact with (Chartrand & Bargh, 1999), we suggest that prosocial individuals would be more inclined to adapt to the biases of their interlocutor. On the other hand, being more cognitively flexible (i.e., having the ability to adapt flexibly to a constantly changing environment; Cools, 2015) is associated with a better theory-of-mind in language (Jacques & Zelazo, 2005), which prompts us to consider that cognitive flexibility could predict the extent to which participants will change their language to align to others. With this experimental approach, our study aims to shed light on the complex relationship between individual differences and language evolution, and the processes at play during linguistic adaptation.

To summarize our main results, we found that languages evolved differently in groups where a minority had a bias affecting their language. First, heterogeneous groups showed lower communicative success and overall less and slower convergence towards shared labels - a result that can be explained by more deviation from the initial labels in such groups. In addition, we observed strong partner-specific alignment, but only a partial carry-over to the group-level: participants typically adapted to the peculiarities of the biased individual during pairwise interaction, but only four out of the six groups showed a group-level adaptation of their language, i.e., by reducing the use of the biased letters in all interactions (even in those that did not include the biased participant). Notably, the degree of this population-level adaptation was negatively correlated with the individuals' learning accuracy. In the two groups that did not adapt their languages, most participants showed a very high recollection of the initial labels learnt during training. Moreover, on an individual level, learning accuracy of the initial labels significantly predicted participants' tendency to align with others, rather than their age, gender, prosociality score or cognitive flexibility. Together, these results suggest that although individuals are able to adapt their languages to fit the variations introduced by a minority, this change is only partially reflected at the group level. Nevertheless, our results strongly suggest that such pairwise variations *can* percolate to the rest of the community, and also accumulate over time - causing languages to change from their initial state in the presence of a minority.

METHOD

Our experiment is a group communication game in which four participants, in a fully connected network, interact face-to-face using a computer interface. After an initial learning phase of an artificial miniature language, participants interact in alternating dyads over multiple rounds, playing a referential game. In each communication round, one participant produces a label to describe an image to their partner, who must then identify the correct item from a set of alternatives displayed on the screen. We introduce a production (articulation-like) bias by restricting a designated participant's keyboard input, preventing them from using two specific letters. This individual is referred to as the "*biased*" participant, while the others are called "*unbiased*" participants.

Illustration 16: Panel **A**: We tested two types of groups: control homogeneous (without biased participants, on the left) and heterogeneous (with one biased participant, in gray, on the right). Panel **B**: Letter inventories for unbiased (top) and biased (bottom) participants. Panel **C**: The form-meaning mappings in the miniature language: eight alien images, each associated with a unique label. Biased letters are shown in bold.

Participants

We tested 48 participants between the ages of 18 and 50 ($M=24$, $SD=6$; 32 women), for a total of 12 groups. All participants were proficient Dutch speakers¹². The study was conducted at the Max Planck Institute for

¹² Only one participant was a German native speaker but has a C2 level in Dutch and speaks it on a daily basis for more than 10 years.

Psycholinguistics (Nijmegen, Netherlands), and participants received a compensation of 21 euros for their participation. An ethical certificate was obtained for this study (certificate number: ECSW-LT-2023-2-10-71121, Social Sciences Ethics Committee, the Netherlands).

Production Bias

Participants communicate exclusively by typing on their keyboard, with any other form of communication (e.g., speaking, pointing, gesturing) being strictly prohibited. They are explicitly instructed not to use Dutch, English, or any other known languages when typing labels, and to avoid abbreviations or any familiar symbols. Unbiased participants can type the following letters: consonants 's', 'n', 'p', 'k' and vowels 'e', 'i', 'u', 'a'. In contrast, the biased participant lacks the ability to produce the 'k' and 'a' letters, which we will refer to as the *biased letters* throughout the paper (see Illustration 16, Panel B). The biased participants were aware of their inability to produce certain letters. Importantly, the unbiased participants were not informed that one participant may have a production bias. To avoid any interfering bias based on age or gender, we ensured that any participant in the minority within their group (for example, one woman in association with three men) was not placed as the biased participant. Except for that, we randomly selected which participant would be assigned as the biased participant.

To confirm the lack of explicit awareness of our manipulation, at the end of the experiment, we collected participants' subjective feedback by inquiring about their experience. Indeed, none of the participants realized that there was one individual in the group who was systematically different. When asked why they thought communication was challenging sometimes, participants often attributed it to others having a significantly poorer memory for recalling the initial labels, or occasionally thought that they might have been exposed to different initial labels. Thus, participants were not aware of the existence of a minority in their group, but did notice potential differences between members of the groups and, subsequently, experienced difficulties in communicating with them.

Stimuli

We used a set of eight colorful alien images, adapted from Raviv & Arnon (2018) and designed by Noam Siegelman. Each alien was assigned a monosyllabic, bisyllabic, or trisyllabic nonsense label composed of a subset of letters from the

unbiased participant's inventory (see Illustration 16, Panel C), i.e., *kesip*, *esip*, *nus*, *nusa*, *aike*, *puak*, *nekuki*, *anap*. The initial language thus consisted of 8 labels, and included a total of 4 instances for each unbiased letter, and 5 instances for each biased letter.

The labels were selected such that two out of the 32 pairs of labels could only be distinguished by the use of the biased letter (*nusa/nus*, and *kesip/esip*). This design introduced an ambiguity, pushing the group to innovate to ensure successful understanding.

Illustration 17: Visual representation of the procedure. See Section Procedure for more information.

Procedure

The experiment consisted of five main parts (see Illustration 17). First, each participant was given two passive exposures to each of the eight alien images and their corresponding label, displayed together on the screen for seven seconds. Next, participants were tested on their knowledge of this initial form-meaning mapping by being presented with each image once and asked to type the corresponding label. Then, the communication game began (see Illustration 18), and participants played multiple rounds of repeated interactions in alternating pairs, switching between different communication partners in a systematic sequence (participant 1 is first paired with participant 2 in Round 1, followed by participant 3 in Round 2, and participant 4 in Round 4, continuing this pattern until Round 9) and taking turns as the producer or the guesser. Participants were informed that the unique objective of this communication phase was to maximize their communicative success, and that they were not obliged to use the initial labels.

In a given interaction, the producer was presented with an image and had to type the label they believed corresponds to it. They then showed the written label to their partner by rotating their screens, and their partners had to guess which image the producer was referring to from the set of eight possible options (the correct image plus the seven other alternatives). After the guesser selected an

image, both participants received feedback which included an indication of success or failure (i.e., whether the image was guessed correctly), as well as the correct vs. selected image. Following the feedback, participants switched roles for the next interaction (the guesser became the producer and vice versa). In a given round, each paired participant acted as a producer and a guesser for all eight images, resulting in a total of 16 interactions per round. At the end of the round, participants switched partners and interacted with another member of the group. Each participant communicates with all others. The communication process consists of nine rounds, allowing each participant to interact with each other member of the group three times. We compare two types of networks: *control* networks (where no participant is biased) to *heterogeneous* networks (with one biased participant) (see Illustration 16 Panel A). The order of stimuli presentation was randomized per round and per group. After nine communication rounds, participants were tested again on their knowledge of the language using a production completion test similar to the initial test they completed prior to interaction.

Finally, participants completed three additional tasks (see below) as well as a questionnaire about their subjective experience, and were debriefed by the experimenter. On average, the experiment lasted around 90 minutes.

Illustration 18: Explanation of the communication game experiment. Panel **A** shows the producer being presented with an image and asked to come up with a label for it. In Panel **B**, the producer types the label and rotates their computer to present the label to the guesser. The guesser must then select which image they think is the correct one out of the eight possible images. In Panel **C**, after the guesser has chosen an image, feedback is presented showing the chosen image on the left, the image presented to the producer on the right, and an indicator in the middle displaying success or failure.

Additional tasks

The study included three additional tasks. The first task is the Prosociality scale (Caprara et al., 2005), which we translated into Dutch. This questionnaire consists of 16 items that measure different aspects of prosocial behavior such as empathic concern, altruism, and volunteering using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (never) to 5 (very often). Participants' answers are then averaged to yield a total prosociality score between 1 and 5 (5 indicating high prosociality). The scale has demonstrated good reliability and validity in various studies (Caprara et al., 2012; Carlo & Randall, 2002; Luengo Kanacri et al., 2021). The full Prosociality questionnaire is provided in the Supplementary Materials.

For the second task, we adapted a version of the Dictator game as another way to measure prosociality, seeing as it provides a different (and maybe more

accurate) measure of prosociality than self-report questionnaires (Böckler et al., 2016). Participants were presented with the following fictional situation (translated here from the Dutch original):

Imagine that I give you an additional amount of 100 euros due to the excellent performance of your group during this experiment. Now, you have the choice to keep the full amount for yourself or to share it with the other participants. Since the other participants are not aware of this extra reward, the choice is entirely up to you. How much do you decide to share with the other participants?

Participants had the choice between (1) keeping the entire amount for themselves, (2) sharing the amount but keeping more for themselves, (3) equally splitting the amount between all group members, (4) sharing the amount but keeping less for themselves, or (5) giving away the entire amount). Thus, the final score ranges from 1 (not prosocial) to 5 (highly prosocial).

Third, participants had to perform a task-switching experiment adapted from Roger & Monsell's (1995) paradigm. This challenging task required participants to remember the rules of two different tasks and frequently switch between them: press Q or P for consonants vs. vowels, or press Q or P for odd vs. even numbers. The goal of this task was to quantify cognitive flexibility, which represents the capability to adapt to new situations and potentially serve as an indicator for predicting linguistic alignment. Additionally, this task also evaluated participants' working memory, a variable we measured to ensure the similarity of individuals within our control and homogeneous groups, while also exploring its potential influence on linguistic alignment. The task is presented as follows: a pair of a letter and a number (for example, G6) is presented in a quadrant of the screen (either top-left, top-right, bottom-left, bottom-right). When the set of letter/number is presented on the top of the quadrant, the participant needs to respond solely based on the letter. However, when presented at the bottom, the participant needs to respond solely based on the number. The position of the set of letters/numbers alternates between the different positions of the quadrants, shifting sequentially from top-left to top-right, then to bottom-left, and finally to bottom-right. We extracted two measures from this task: the overall inverse efficiency (reaction time divided by accuracy), which measures the global working memory, and the task-switching cost, which indicated the difficulty of switching between tasks and was normalized by the total time (see Supplementary Materials for more information).

Specific research questions

(1) First, we seek to understand how language evolves with time in heterogeneous groups. (2) Second, we explore the extent to which the language of the entire group adjusts to accommodate the idiosyncrasies of the biased participant. (3) Finally, we aim to understand if the participants adapt to their partners in pair interactions, and if yes, what factors might predict the extent of the alignment.

Measures

Before turning to the measures aiming at answering specific research questions, it is essential to assess the participants' memory of the initial labels to make sure that there are no significant differences between our control and heterogeneous groups. To do so, we measured the **learning accuracy** and the **initial production similarity** after training. Learning accuracy was a binary measure, where a value of 1 indicates correct recall by the participant, while a value of 0 indicates the presence of at least one error. Given the biased participants' inability to produce certain labels, their responses were considered "correct" (1) if they replaced the biased letter with another letter or if they omitted it. The **initial production similarity** is the normalized Levenshtein distance between the initial labels and the participants' first production, reflecting a more fine-grained accuracy score that takes into account the proportion of incorrect letters in each production. Here too, we made an adjustment for the biased participant: based on the strategy used by the biased participant to cope with the presence of biased letters, we either substituted or removed the biased letter from the initial label before computing the Levenshtein distance.

(1) We used a set of three different measures to address our first research question. First, **communicative success** indicates the success (1) or failure (0) of the interaction between two participants (as shown in Illustration 3, Panel C), aggregated by pairs. Second, **convergence** measures the similarity of the words generated for the same image in each round. It is computed using the pairwise normalized Levenshtein distance between the four labels produced for the same image at each round. Low convergence indicates that different words have been used to describe the same image, while high convergence suggests that participants used a similar label. Lastly, we examined the **production similarity** between participants' labels and the set of initial labels over time, by computing

the average Levenshtein distance between participants' productions and the initial labels at a given time.

(2) To answer the second research question, we refer to the **frequency of the biased** letters. For each round, we determine the total frequency of the biased letters ('k' and 'a') out of all the letters used in that round, which we multiplied by 100 to obtain percentages. We also computed the frequency distribution of biased letters in the initial set of labels (*kesip*, *esip*, *nus*, *nusa*, *aikē*, *puak*, *nekuki*, *anap*).

(3) To identify the degree of accommodation across participants, we created several **adaptability** measures (full details in the Supplementary Materials). For the sake of simplicity, we focus here on one adaptability score. For each round, participant, and shape, we recorded participants' most recent label production, the preceding label produced by their partner, and the label they previously produced themselves. Subsequently, we calculated the normalized Levenshtein distance between the latest label and the partner's label (d_1), as well as the distance between the latest label and the participant's own previous label (d_2). Our adaptability measure, defined as $Adapt = 2 * (1 - d_1) + d_2$, predominantly reflects whether a participant employs the same label as their partner's just before (i.e., d_1). However, this value gains even more significance if the label significantly differs from their own previously produced label (d_2). We aggregated these values of adaptability per participant.

Analysis

All analyses were conducted using mixed-effect models implemented through the `lmerTest` package (Kuznetsova et al., 2017), a package based on `lme4` package (Bates et al., 2015) in R (R Core Team, 2023). In all models, we use the group number as a random factor, and fixed effects are always considered in interaction with each other. To answer the first research question (1), data was aggregated by pair (for communicative success), by group (for convergence), and by participants (for production similarity). We built models with fixed factors for round number (coded as continuous, in reverse order so that Round 9 becomes Round 0) and group type (control/heterogeneous, dummy coded, with control as the reference level). **Model 1** predicted communicative success, **model 2** predicted convergence, and **model 3** predicted production similarity. To specifically examine how the presence of a biased participant affected the unbiased participants, we also built the exact same models with a modification,

splitting the productions of the participants in the heterogeneous group into two categories: the productions involving the biased participants and the productions involving only the unbiased participants. We compare three conditions: control, heterogeneous *with* the biased participant, and heterogeneous *without* the biased participant (dummy coded, with control as the reference level). These variations of the models will be referred to as ***model 1 bis***, ***model 2 bis***, and ***model 3 bis***.

To answer (2), we investigated whether the language of the heterogeneous groups featured less biased letters after the participants communicated. ***Model 4*** predicted the mean frequency of biased letters as a function of the group type (control/heterogeneous, dummy coded, with control as the reference level), and the moment of testing (beginning vs. end of the experiment; dummy coded, with the beginning of the experiment as the reference level; box 2 and 4 in Illustration 2 - please note that we also analyzed their evolution across rounds in the Supplementary Materials).

Regarding question (3), to predict the frequency of biased letters at the pair level, we aggregated the frequency of biased letters in two types of situations: when unbiased participants interact with the biased participant, and when they interact with another unbiased participant (this variable is called “Communicate With Biased”). ***Model 6*** predicted the mean frequency of biased letters using the group type (control/heterogeneous, dummy coded, with control as the reference level) and “Communicate With Biased” (“yes”/“no”, dummy coded, with “no” as the reference level). In this model, we also have the participant's unique ID as a random factor, since “Communicate With Biased” is a within-participants variable. Then, in order to understand which factors affect adaptability, we predicted adaptability using age, gender, working memory, cognitive flexibility, prosociality, and learning success measures (accuracy learning and initial production similarity) as fixed effects (***model 7***): all variables are centered except for gender (dummy coded, with female as the reference level). Notably, this is the only model in which we consider only the main effects of the fixed factors (i.e., without interactions).

RESULTS

We tested 6 heterogeneous groups and 6 control groups. The distribution of age, gender, and the other measures is similar between the two types of groups. On

average, participants remembered half of the initial labels (approximately 45% of correct recall). Biased participants, when they accurately recall the initial labels, either substituted the biased letters with another unbiased letter (42%) or omitted the biased letters altogether (58%).

How did language evolve in the heterogeneous groups?

Communicative success was lower in heterogenous groups compared to control groups (model 1: $\beta_{GroupTypeHet} = -32.0 \pm 9.3$, where 9.3 is the standard error, $p < 0.01$, see Figure 1A) and increased with time for both types of groups (model 1: $\beta_{Round} = -5.3 \pm 0.5$, $p < 0.0001$; Figure 9 Panel A) but this increase was faster for control groups compared to heterogenous groups (model 1: $\beta_{GroupTypeHet:Round} = 1.8 \pm 0.8$, $p < 0.05$; Figure 9A). Similarly, convergence increased with time for both groups (model 2: $\beta_{Round} = -0.04 \pm 0.005$, $p < 0.0001$; Figure 9B) and was lower for heterogeneous groups (model 2: $\beta_{GroupTypeHet} = -0.38 \pm 0.04$, $p < 0.0001$; Figure 9B). Furthermore, convergence increased faster for control groups compared to heterogeneous groups (model 2: $\beta_{GroupTypeHet:Round} = 0.03 \pm 0.007$, $p < 0.001$; Figure 9B). The greater convergence observed in the control groups could be due to their tendency to align with the initial labels, even if these labels were not immediately well remembered at first (refer to Figure 9C). In contrast, the heterogeneous groups consistently employed labels that deviated from the initial ones (significant interaction between the type of group and round in model 3: $\beta_{GroupTypeHet:Round} = -0.02 \pm 0.004$, $p < 0.0001$; Figure 9C).

One can imagine that the lower communicative success and convergence within heterogeneous groups were solely due to the outputs produced by the biased participant. However, it seems that their impact went beyond that, and that the biased participants influenced the overall performance of the entire group. In models distinguishing between productions containing or excluding the biased participant in heterogeneous groups, even unbiased participants had lower communicative success (model 1 bis: $\beta_{HeteroWithBiased} = -33 \pm 9.6$, $p < 0.01$), convergence (model 2 bis: $\beta_{HeteroWithBiased} = -0.12 \pm 0.05$, $p < 0.05$), and initial production similarity (model 3 bis: $\beta_{HeteroWithBiased} = 0.3 \pm 0.09$, $p < 0.01$) compared to control groups. This is also visible in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Panel **A**. Evolution of communicative success (% of successful interactions) from Round 1 to 9. The red line represents the average communicative success for all pairs in all control groups. In heterogeneous groups, we represent the average communicative success for pairs that did not include the biased participant (in blue) or for pairs that included the biased participant (in green). Panel **B**. Evolution of mean convergence. The y-axis shows the pairwise normalized Levenshtein distance between all words within the control group (in red), heterogeneous group with productions from all participants (in green), and heterogeneous groups excluding productions from the biased participant (in blue). This includes convergence for the testing productions before (Round = 0) and after (Round = 10) communication game. Panel **C**. Evolution of the production similarity with the initial labels with time, for control groups (in red), as well as for unbiased (in blue) and biased (in green) participants in heterogeneous groups.

Has the language of the group adapted to the specificity of the biased participant?

We analyzed the frequency of biased letters used during the first and the final testing phase. Control groups exhibited the expected pattern, maintaining a consistent frequency of biased letters (Figure 10, right panel) throughout the experiment. Among the heterogeneous groups, four out of the six groups adjusted their language in response to the presence of biased participants. Notably, the final language of these groups contained fewer biased letters (Figure 10, left panel) than their initial language. These adaptations took various forms. Unbiased participants sometimes adopted the label introduced by the biased participant, who either substituted the biased letter, removed it, or used a new label (in 31% of the occurrences where the unbiased participants did adapt). Additionally, there were instances where unbiased participants chose an alternative label that was distinct from the one used by the biased participant, yet without including any biased letters (69%). Although the decrease in the frequency of biased letters within the heterogeneous groups did not reach statistical significance, it is most likely that this is due to the lack of sufficient power given the limited number of groups and the fact that two out of six groups did not exhibit such a pattern. This interpretation is suggested when examining

only the heterogeneous groups that did show signs of adaptation, for which there was a reduction in the use of the biased letters after interacting. Indeed, if we look at a model containing only the heterogeneous groups who adapted (i.e., groups 1, 3, 4, and 5), with the moment of testing as a fixed factor to predict the frequency of biased letters, we found that this reduction is significant ($\beta_{MomentTesting} = -5.8 \pm 0.4$, $p < 0.001$).

Why did two of these groups not adapt? Notably, one of these two groups exhibited a distinct pattern: three participants, including the biased individual, retained an excellent memory for the initial labels in the very first test (approximately 80% accurate recall for these three participants). In this group, the biased participant consistently replaced the biased letter with other unbiased letters, and the group quickly converged on the initial labels with slight and consistent variations on the biased participant's side - which did not hamper the communicative success. The reasons behind the lack of adaptation in the other group are less clear. However, it is interesting to note that two out of the four participants in this group also demonstrated very high recall for the initial labels (around 80%). This situation raises intriguing questions: What factors determine who adapts and who does not? What personal attributes of group members contribute to the adaptation of the group's language?

Figure 10: The **left** panel illustrates the evolution of the mean frequency (in %, see Method for more details on this measure's calculation) of the biased letters in heterogeneous groups. In comparison, the **right** panel presents the equivalent data for control (homogenous) groups.

Specifically, we look at the mean frequency per group before (First Test) and after (Last Test) the communication game. The black dashed line shows the frequency of biased letters in the initial labels.

Who adapts and when?

While we do not observe significant adaptation at the group level, a clear pattern of adaptation emerges at the pair level. When unbiased participants communicated with the biased participant, they noticeably decreased their use of the biased letters (model 6: $\beta_{GroupTypeHet \times ComBiased} = -1.4 \pm 0.5$, $p < 0.01$; see Figure 11).

Figure 11: Mean and standard error frequency of biased letters within heterogeneous groups, when unbiased participants are interacting with other unbiased participants (left) or with the biased participant (right). The black dashed line represents the letter frequencies in the initial labels. The red bold line corresponds to the average frequency of the biased letters in control groups, accompanied by standard error ribbons.

We also aim to understand which participants were most likely to adapt and align with their partner's label using our adaptability score. This score is not specifically related to the presence or absence of biased letters, but is more generally associated with a participant's inclination to adopt their partner's productions, particularly when it contradicts their *a-priori* preference. Our results suggest that factors such as gender, age, and various metrics derived from supplementary tasks (including working memory, cognitive flexibility, and

prosociality) did not predict the participants' likelihood of adaptation. Instead, the propensity of participants to align with their partners was influenced solely by our two measures related to initial word recall—both in terms of accuracy of learning (model 7: $\beta_{AccLearning} = -0.5 \pm 0.2$, $p < 0.05$) and production similarity (model 7: $\beta_{ProdSimilarity} = -0.6 \pm 0.3$, $p < 0.05$). Thus, the stronger participants' recall of the initial labels, the less inclined they were to align.

DISCUSSION

This study investigated how language evolves in heterogeneous vs. homogeneous groups, and whether a production bias present in the minority could influence the language of the whole group. Overall, we observed differences in the language used by the control (homogeneous) and the heterogeneous groups within this experimental setting. The results suggest that heterogeneous groups exhibit a lower convergence on shared labels, notably characterized by the use of novel labels and synonymous terms for the same image. In contrast, control groups rapidly align on the initial labels they learned, despite not accurately recalling them on average. This raises the following question: does the higher linguistic variability in heterogeneous groups stem solely from the fact it takes more time for them to converge onto shared labels, or is it an inherent trait of heterogeneous populations that persists over time? Put differently, if we were to allow both heterogeneous and homogeneous groups to interact for 100 rounds, would the language of heterogeneous groups still exhibit greater variation than the control groups after communicating? Importantly, these two scenarios are not mutually exclusive. Figure 9B's trajectory seems to indicate that language has not yet stabilized even after nine rounds of communication, implying that the convergence might require more interactions in heterogeneous populations. Previous computational work (Josserand, Allasonnière-Tang, et al., 2021; Josserand et al., in-review) supports both proposals, as it shows that language takes more time to stabilize in heterogeneous compared to homogeneous populations, and that the presence of individual differences contributes to higher language variability. This notion finds further support in sociolinguistic research, which underscores that linguistic diversity is high within groups encompassing a mix of social classes or diverse ethnic backgrounds (Bright, 2017; Labov, 1986)¹³. Naturally, individual

¹³ Of course, we acknowledge that individual differences are not the sole determinant influencing emergent linguistic variation, as relatively homogenous populations sharing similar contexts can also exhibit substantial lexical diversity (Mudd et al., 2022).

differences are omnipresent, both in real-world scenarios and within our experiment: our participants showcased a wide array of differences, spanning from personality traits, attitude toward language, to various other unmeasured cognitive abilities that could potentially impact language. Nevertheless, participants in our control group were relatively homogeneous regarding their capacity to use the letters on the keyboard.

Another intriguing facet of these findings lies in the similar pattern exhibited by biased and unbiased participants. The influence of the bias in the heterogeneous groups extends beyond interactions involving the biased participants, as the interactions between the unbiased participants also exhibit lower convergence and communicative success rates. This suggests that the introduction of a biased minority exerts a broader impact on the overall convergence of the language of the whole group, including the unbiased majority. Thus, the presence of individual differences within populations may act as a catalyst for the emergence of innovative linguistic elements, thereby contributing to the broader landscape of cross-linguistic diversity. This aligns with applied research indicating a positive correlation between long-term innovation and diversity in various aspects such as gender (Nielsen et al., 2018), age (only if the age groups are heterogeneous and not polarized; Mothe & Nguyen-Thi, 2021), and cultural diversity (Scharf et al., 2014).

The question surrounding whether language accommodates the idiosyncrasies of biased participants is more challenging to answer. The results indicate varying degrees of adaptation to biased participants across the different groups. In the four groups where adaptation occurs, the language employed by the group after communication contained significantly fewer biased letters – reflecting the lingering effect of the minority on the majority language. In these groups, participants deviated from the learnt forms and adopted variants that contained less instances of the letters which the minority could not produce - hinting at a group-level language change. While this phenomenon was subtle, it aligns with theories of cultural evolution - which propose that languages gradually adjust to the biases of its speakers due to their pervasive daily usage and transmission across generations, but that these adjustments likely span multiple generations and take time to accumulate (Dediu et al., 2017; Dediu & Moisk, 2019; S. Kirby et al., 2007). Consequently, we believe that the absence of significance should not be interpreted as an absence of effect, but rather as an indicator that more groups should be tested and probably for longer periods of time. We suggest that, given more time to interact and/or larger lexicons that tax the participants'

memory more, the biased variants would eventually percolate to the rest of the community and might well affect the language as a whole.

Notably, only four out of the six groups exhibit a final language that has adapted to the biased participant. This absence of systematic adaptation is not surprising given notable real-world examples: while emergent sign languages adapted to the minority biases, conversely, many real-world languages have not adapted to the idiosyncrasies of a minority. For instance, Romance languages still often feature the “r” trill sound in their sound systems even when a small percent of the population is unable to produce this sound (Anselme, 2022). While it is evident that these differences in adaptation stem from a complex interplay of factors (Bright, 2017), this dynamic may also possess stochastic attributes. In certain cases, languages could take distinct starting paths, which would greatly impact how they develop over time (Sapir, 1921; Ventura et al., 2022). Moreover, the unique characteristics of individuals within a group might also add to the complex nature of this process. For example, people might adapt more to a prestigious minority, and less to a stigmatized minority (Bloomfield, 1933; Fagyal et al., 2010). In addition, since our goal was to examine implicit processes of language adaptation and change, our participants were not made aware of the bias of one of the members in their group. However, this is not always the case in real-life scenarios: people often consciously devise strategies to accommodate individuals with observable linguistic deficiencies, poor fluency, and speech idiosyncrasies, e.g., as is the case with child- or foreigner-directed speech. However, many idiosyncrasies that are perceived as pathological or socially “unacceptable” can carry a negative societal value that might consciously deter people from adopting them.

To understand the individual dynamics of adaptation, we zoomed in to observe what happens during interaction at the pair level. First, it is important to keep in mind that unbiased participants in the heterogeneous groups were unaware of the presence of a production bias in one of the other participants within the group. This lack of awareness thus did not predispose them towards overtly prosocial or rejecting behaviors. Nevertheless, participants in our laboratory setup demonstrated a strong propensity to adopt similar linguistic variants as their conversation partners, which supports previous observations of linguistic alignment in real-world interaction (Danescu-Niculescu-Mizil et al., 2011; Niederhoffer & Pennebaker, 2002). Interestingly, unlike some previous studies where the propensity to align was influenced by factors such as gender, age, or prosociality, our findings did not find such associations. Several reasons may contribute to this: First, our groups were relatively homogenous in terms of age

and gender demographics: 94% of the participants were between 18 and 35 years old, and 66% of them were female. Similarly, our participants showed very similar (and relatively high) prosociality scores, with 96% of participants having prosociality scores between 3 and 4.5 on the 0 to 5 prosociality scale. Thus, our sample might not have been variable enough on these dimensions to allow such associations.

However, a notable predictor of the participants' tendency to align with their partners' linguistic productions was their ability to recall the initial labels: Participants who demonstrated a strong memory retention of the initial labels showed less adaptation to their partner's language. A similar pattern was found for the two groups that did not show signs of adaptation, in which participants showed an exceptionally good memory of the initial labels. The link between better learning and reduced alignment could be potentially attributed to the participants' perception of the initial labels as representing the “ground truth” of the language. This idea aligns closely with findings from computational models, which suggest that the stronger a person's belief is in an initial language, the less likely they are to deviate from it and introduce variation (Josserand, Allassonnière-Tang, et al., 2021). These findings could be potentially related to the enforcing of linguistic policies, e.g., in situations where a language is perceived to have a “correct” or “acceptable” form, it may be likely to observe a reduced inclination for adopting new linguistic innovations. For example, the institution *Académie française* in France established strict linguistic norms, especially oriented toward the orthographic system, which may prevent people from adopting orthographic innovations (H. Walter, 2016). This phenomenon also extends to spoken language, where explicit language ideologies emerge as people propose statements regarding their own language skills, behaviors, or those of others (Pakendorf et al., 2021).

Together, this study provides an important step in understanding the weight of individual constraints on the formation of collective language characteristics, and emphasizes the importance of accounting for individual differences within a group to better understand language evolution. A compelling avenue for future investigation lies in studying potential interactions between group size and individual differences. Similarly, exploring diverse network structures where the biased participant occupies either a central or a peripheral role could shed light on how the spread of biased variants is influenced by network topology (Raviv et al., 2020). For example, having the biased participant in a central position in the network (representing an influential figure, for example), can potentially lead to them having a stronger impact on the entire community. Moreover, extending

the exploration of biases in language production to encompass biases in perception could yield valuable insights, as research suggests that individual differences in color perception may affect language evolution (Lindsey & Brown, 2002; Josserand, Meeussen, et al., 2021; see also Chapter 2 of this thesis). Finally, since our findings highlight a notable discrepancy in the language used at the pair level and at the group level, they underscore the importance of employing hierarchical Bayesian models which can account for such differences in future modeling research (Hawkins et al., 2023; Thompson et al., 2019). Finally, while the current study looked at language, we believe that the main conclusions, namely, that group-level patterns are shaped by individual differences, can be applied across other diverse fields of cultural evolution, including the evolution of tool use and cultural norms.

Conclusions

Our findings underscore that introducing a minority with different language abilities within a group influences the trajectory of language evolution. Notably, the presence of individual variations fostered the emergence of novel linguistic elements. Furthermore, individuals adapt their languages during paired interactions to accommodate variations introduced by a minority, and these adaptations are partially mirrored at the group level. In four out of the six groups, languages showed a notable reduction in the use of the letters that one of the participants was unable to produce, effectively shifting the language to the community to support the minority. The extent of this adaptation is intertwined with how strongly participants remembered the initial labels, suggesting that a stronger attachment to a conventionalized form leads to lower accommodation to the idiosyncrasies of a biased minority. Together, our results provide compelling evidence that individual differences can diffuse throughout the broader community and accumulate over time, ultimately driving changes in languages. Hence, we believe it is crucial to integrate individual differences in future work and acknowledge them as significant factors that may influence the course of language evolution.

4

INTERINDIVIDUAL VARIATION REFUSES TO GO AWAY: A BAYESIAN COMPUTER MODEL OF LANGUAGE CHANGE IN COMMUNICATIVE NETWORKS

CONTEXT

This work has been published in the journal *Frontiers in Psychology* (<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.626118>). The list of authors includes Mathilde Josserand, Marc Allasonnière-Tang, François Pellegrino, and Dan Dediu. All data, instructions for replicating the simulations, code, and Supplementary Materials are accessible on my GitHub page: <https://github.com/mathjoss/bayes-in-network>.

ABSTRACT

Treating the speech communities as homogeneous entities is not an accurate representation of reality, as it misses some of the complexities of linguistic interactions. Inter-individual variation and multiple types of biases are ubiquitous in speech communities, regardless of their size. This variation is often neglected due to the assumption that “majority rules,” and that the emerging language of the community will override any such biases by forcing the individuals to overcome their own biases, or risk having their use of language being treated as “idiosyncratic” or outright “pathological.” In this paper, we use computer

simulations of Bayesian linguistic agents embedded in communicative networks to investigate how biased individuals, representing a minority of the population, interact with the unbiased majority, how a shared language emerges, and the dynamics of these biases across time. We tested different network sizes (from very small to very large) and types (random, scale-free, and small-world), along with different strengths and types of bias (modeled through the Bayesian prior distribution of the agents and the mechanism used for generating utterances: either sampling from the posterior distribution [“sampler”] or picking the value with the maximum probability [“MAP”]). The results show that, while the biased agents, even when being in the minority, do adapt their language by going against their a priori preferences, they are far from being swamped by the majority, and instead the emergent shared language of the whole community is influenced by their bias.

INTRODUCTION

As highlighted in the presentation of the Research Topic, “[t]he question whether all languages are similarly complex is at the center of some of the most heated debates within linguistics.” This statement is based on the axiomatic assumptions that, once complexity is defined, it is both *measurable* for each language and *commensurable* between languages. Needless to say, the fact that heated debates have been flourishing for at least two decades suggests that these assumptions have led to multiple interpretations of how complexity should be defined and how it should be considered, and consequently that the complexity jigsaw puzzle has still to be solved. Several contributions to this Research Topic specifically address these aspects, e.g., Ehret et al. (2021) on the equal complexity aspect, or Ehret et al. (2021) and Joseph (2021) on measuring complexity, to name just a few. Another heated debate is about the existence of putative complexity trade-offs within each language (i.e., do phonological, morphological, and syntactic complexities interact and compensate or combine?), as primarily discussed in Easterday et al. (2021). From an epistemological standpoint, this strand of research pertains to the notion of *magnitude of complexity*, a term coined as early as the beginning of the twentieth century in linguistics (e.g., Zipf, 1965, p. 66).

Here we adopt a different perspective on linguistic complexity, namely the view that language is a *complex adaptive system*. This strand of research stemmed from the field of cybernetics after World War II and thrived in the 1970s. In his

more recent work, Jakobson adopted this perspective, stating that “[l]ike any other social modeling system tending to maintain its dynamic equilibrium, language ostensibly displays its self-regulating and self-steering properties” (Jakobson, 1973, p. 48). More recently, the fact that language exhibits properties, such as emergence, self-organization, etc., typically explaining the dynamics and structure of complex adaptive systems, was convincingly articulated by Beckner et al. (2009) in a seminal paper, and is further supported by many theoretical, simulation-based, and experimental studies (see e.g., the contributions in Mufwene et al., 2017, among others). From this perspective, the main question is not to determine whether language A is more or less complex than language B (or whether a difference between their, let’s say, phonological complexity, is compensated by a difference in syntactic complexity in the opposite direction), but to understand the mechanisms that explain the observed variation, its extension, and its evolution. As pointed by Forker (this issue), variation is probably an important aspect influencing the course of linguistic evolution, and her contribution echoes what can also be referred to as degrees of freedom in a systemic approach. In our paper, we aim at better understanding how the existence of variation among speakers within a population (or linguistic community) may shape the language (as a social convention) and its evolutionary trajectory through time (in the sense of change in a cultural evolutionary system on the glossogenetic timescale and not during human evolution at the phylogenetic timescale; Fitch, 2008). Our approach adopts a multi-agent simulation paradigm and is thus a computer modeling contribution to this Research Topic, inscribed in a productive research tradition of simulation studies using simplified languages and simplified linguistic agents acting in a simplified (socio-linguistic) environment (see below for a state of the art and references). Specifically, we focus on language change in heterogeneous populations containing a proportion of agents that are intrinsically biased toward a variant of the language. Thus, we aim to use this agent-based approach to understand whether a small proportion of individuals with such a bias can influence the structure of the language of the whole population, whether the bias of some individuals can resist to the pressure of the majority, and what effect (if any) does the structure of the network have on the rate of convergence.

Despite being so often repeated, the fact that there are about 7,000 languages being used around the world (Hammarström et al., 2018) should still evoke awe and wonder. This diversity is not restricted to the “languages,” but instead pervades all levels below and above it: from the striking geographic skew of the distribution of languages and language families, and of the number of their speakers, to intra-linguistic dialectal and sociolinguistic variation, and to the

myriad ways individuals differ in how they acquire, perceive, process, and produce language (Dediu et al., 2017; Hammarström et al., 2018). Despite centuries of inquiry, the reasons for this diversity and its patterning remain one of the greatest enigmas of the language sciences (N. Evans & Levinson, 2009). However, one of the main explanatory factors is the way changes in language, usually small, accumulate, and amplify across time in space, resulting in this astonishing diversity (Bowerman & Evans, 2014; Dediu et al., 2017; N. Evans & Levinson, 2009; Levinson & Evans, 2010). There are currently many proposals that identify various factors shaping language change, ranging from those *internal* to language (Bowerman & Evans, 2014; Campbell, 1998; Lass, 1997), to *demography* and *population movements* (Hua et al., 2019; Ostler, 2005), to environmental and ecological factors (Bentz et al., 2018; Everett et al., 2016), and even to the *biology and cognition* of the language users (Dediu et al., 2019; Wong et al., 2020). However, this enigma cannot be answered without fully embracing the complexity of language itself, “evolving” and “living” at the interface of biology, cognition, society, and culture (Levinson, 2006; Mufwene et al., 2017).

Here, we take a broad *cultural evolutionary* view of language change (Cavalli-Sforza & Feldman, 1981; Croft, 2008; Dediu et al., 2013; Richerson & Boyd, 2008) in which linguistic variation is first generated through innovation, and then it may spread (or not) through the linguistic community, due to the complex interplay between random factors (akin to drift in evolutionary biology) and various types of selective pressures (or biases). Even though predicting language change (and evolutionary change, in general) is notoriously hard (Stadler, 2016), the mechanisms underlying language change have been the object of intensive study in particular in sociolinguistics (Meyerhoff, 2015; L. Milroy & Gordon, 2008) and historical linguistics (Bowerman & Evans, 2014), but also in phonetics and phonology (Ohala, 1989; Yu, 2013). Of special interest is the so-called “*actuation problem*” (Dediu & Moisik, 2019; Weinreich et al., 1968; Yu, 2013), which can be briefly stated as “[w]hy do changes in a structural feature take place in a particular language at a given time, but not in other languages with the same feature, or in the same language at other times?” (Weinreich et al., 1968, p. 102). Multiple answers have been proposed, building upon various mechanisms. In sociolinguistics (Labov, 2010; Yu, 2013), the spread (or not) of linguistic variants is linked to their different valuations and to the frequency of interactions between interlocutors. Other explanations are based on selective forces that favor the spread of variants that are “better” functionally in some way (e.g., by optimizing articulatory effort, enhancing perception, or being cognitively easier to process; Blasi et al., 2019; Blythe &

Croft, 2012; Christiansen & Chater, 2008; Croft, 2008; Culbertson et al., 2012; Dediu et al., 2017) or through frequency-dependent processes (Pagel et al., 2019). The mechanism of neutral evolution (or drift) where randomness plays the main role (Kauhanen, 2017) has also been suggested. Far from being mutually exclusive, these explanations are probably present to various degrees in many cases of language change.

However, an essential factor that is sometimes neglected by such theories is that language users differ not only with respect to their socio-economic and political roles, but in myriad other ways (Dediu et al., 2017; Dediu & Moisik, 2019), and it has been suggested that focusing on this pool of inter-individual variation may help solve the long-standing actuation problem (Baker et al., 2011; Dediu & Moisik, 2019; Stevens & Harrington, 2014). Here, we are focusing on a specific aspect of actuation, namely on the spread of linguistic variants in a network of language users that have different capacities, constraints and preferences (which we generically term *biases*). While language users may diverge with regard to their biases, they are also embedded in a converging *communicative network* that structures their repeated linguistic interactions. Biases can be found as ubiquitous variation among normal individuals in the acquisition, perception, processing, and production of language (it is important to highlight here the *normal* dimension of variation, as opposed to the much more studied extremes of this variation usually regarded as pathological). This ranges from variation in the *anatomy of the speech organs* (such as the shape of the hard palate), producing subtle effects on the production of vowels (Dediu et al., 2019) and consonants (Dediu & Moisik, 2016, 2019), to the *learning of a second language* (Hanulíková et al., 2012; Xiang et al., 2015), to vocabulary size (Mainz et al., 2017), *speech rate* (Coupé et al., 2019), and to the *processing of pitch* in Heschl's gyrus, affecting the perception of linguistic tone even in native speakers of tone languages (Dediu & Ladd, 2007; Wong et al., 2020). For many more examples, see, among others, Stevens and Harrington (2014) and Dediu et al. (2017). As it is the case with the most complex phenotypes, this variation is due to complex interactions between genes, environment and culture (Dediu, 2015; Deriziotis & Fisher, 2013; Devanna et al., 2018), and is *pervasive, multivariate* and usually *very small*, in the sense that it doesn't significantly impede communication.

To make this more precise, an example—in some ways, extreme—might help: some languages and varieties, such as *Spanish, Italian, Scottish English*, and *Romanian*, use the alveolar trill /r/, but there is a small minority of native speakers that apparently cannot produce this sound. While this incapacity varies in degree

and is resolved, in most cases, spontaneously or through speech therapy during childhood, it does persist into adulthood in a small percentage of the population otherwise not affected by other speech and language deficits. As it happens, one of the authors is such a case, as he cannot produce the alveolar trill used in his native language, and instead systematically replaces it with a slightly retroflex approximant/ η /; other such native speakers might use other substitutions (such as the voiced uvular trill / R / or the voiced uvular fricative / \mathfrak{R} /). Importantly, this speech deficit is recognized by the native speakers and stigmatized (in fact, there is a particular mocking word for this idiosyncrasy), and is specifically targeted by teachers and speech therapists in children. Thus, using the concepts introduced above, this incapacity represents in some speakers a strong bias against the alveolar trill and, while its etiology is currently unclear and most probably diverse, it seems safe to assume that it is stable throughout the lifespan, costly to overcome for those that do, and negatively stigmatized by the speech community.

While the example above is of a strong bias present in only very few individuals, there are other types of inter-individual variation that result in (very) weak biases at the individual level that are, however, more widely shared within a group. For such cases, previous work has shown, using mathematical modeling, computer simulations, and experimental approaches, that variants induced by weak biases may be amplified by the repeated use and transmission of language under specific conditions (see Dediu et al., 2017; Janssen, 2018 for more comprehensive reviews). Early work under the Bayesian framework (Griffiths & Kalish, 2007; Kirby et al., 2007) has produced surprising results in the sense that, when considering simple transmission chains composed of one agent per generation, Bayesian samplers always converge on the prior, while maximum a posteriori (MAP) may amplify initially weak biases. Dediu (2008, 2009) shows that *ad-hoc* and Bayesian learning mechanisms behave differently in single-agent chains, homogeneous and heterogeneous two-agent chains, and complex populations, and that, in some cases, variants induced by weak biases are indeed expressed at the level of the community language. Navarro et al. (2018) show that mixing agents with different biases in the same transmission chain results in the expression of the variants induced by the stronger biases by the repeated transmission of language (“extremists win”), but in an indirect and non-transparent way. In their seminal work, Kirby et al. (2008) found that transmission chains composed of human participants also amplify individually weaker tendencies toward compositionality, findings that have been replicated, refined and contextualized since (see reviews in Tamariz & Kirby, 2015, 2016; Culbertson & Kirby, 2016). Focusing specifically on the anatomy of the vocal

tract, Dediu et al. (2019) show, using a computer model of the vocal tract capable of learning to produce vowels (using artificial neural networks and genetic algorithms), that variation in the shape of the hard palate results in very weak effects on the production of the learned vowels. These weak effects are amplified by a classic iterated learning transmission chain to the level of observed intra-dialectal variation. In the same vein, Blasi et al. (2019) show, using a combination of approaches, that variation in bite due to food consistency between agricultural and hunter-gathering populations, results in tiny differences in the effort required to produce labiodental sounds (such as “f” and “v”). These differences in effort are presumably amplified to produce robust statistical differences in the frequency of these sounds between languages.

This amplification of weak biases thus raises a crucial question relevant to language evolution, change and diversity, and, more generally, to cultural evolution: under what conditions does this amplification take place (or doesn't)? But before we proceed, we need to clarify our terminology: on the one hand, such biases have *causes* (sociolinguistic, environmental, anatomical, etc.) and any given individual may or may not be affected, i.e., the bias may be *present* or *absent* (for discrete, binary biases, such as having a frenulum of the tongue) or have a certain *numeric value* (for continuous biases, such as the degree of overjet/overbite); when zooming out at the level of a linguistic community, we are then talking about the bias being present with a certain *frequency* (for discrete biases) or have a certain *distribution* (for continuous biases). On the other hand, such a variant, when present in an individual, may or may not be expressed in the individual's linguistic behavior (e.g., not being able to articulate the alveolar trill or a lower probability of producing labiodentals); at the level of the linguistic community, a variant can be expressed with a certain frequency or have a certain distribution, and it may (or may not) be further amplified by the repeated use and transmission of language. These concepts are parallel to those from medical genetics concerning the presence of a deleterious allele in an individual's genotype (say, a mutation in one of the opsin genes on the X chromosome), its phenotypic expression (as red/green abnormal color perception), and the population frequency of such deficiencies.

With these, the simplest question concerns, for a given bias, the minimum frequency of the biased individuals in the community (i.e., the individuals expressing the bias), so that its effects are expressed and amplified in the language of the whole community. To use our “extreme” alveolar trill example, we know that about 1% of non-trilling speakers (an estimate based on the available unsystematic data) is not enough to change the Romanian language

away from the alveolar trill and toward, say, a “French-style” uvular fricative, but would 10, 25, 50% do? The complementary question is: for a given frequency, what is the minimum bias strength that would allow the variant to be expressed and amplified? And what is the time trajectory of the spread for a given strength and bias? On top of these questions, we must also not think of the speech community as a shapeless pool of speakers, each equally likely to speak to, and to learn from, any other speaker, which is completely unrealistic (Meyerhoff, 2015; L. Milroy & Gordon, 2008). Therefore, we focus here on speakers connected through communicative networks which structure the communicative exchanges, controlling thus the probability that any two speakers will interact. To the questions above concerning the bias strength and frequency, we thus add questions concerning the influence of the size of the network (the number of speakers in the community), of the structural properties of the network (random, small world, scale-free), and of the position that biased individuals have in the network (e.g., high vs. low centrality, bridging two subnetworks, etc.) on the spread of the bias.

The spread of innovation, behaviors and attitudes (among others) in social networks has received a lot of attention. Moreover, inter-individual variation seems to play an important role in these processes of network spread (Granovetter, 1978; Karsai et al., 2016). Language is not an exception, with studies ranging from “classic” sociolinguistics (L. Milroy & Gordon, 2008) to more recent network-centric (Abitbol et al., 2018; Fagyal et al., 2010; Ke et al., 2008). Language change has also been studied using real-world examples, such as the vowel chain shift in Ximu or the consonant convergence in Duoxu (Chirkova & Gong, 2014, 2019), and using experimental approaches (Raviv, 2020; Raviv et al., 2020) showing that we must consider the structure of the connectivity in linguistic communities. Social structure, and more specifically the average degree, the presence of shortcuts and the level of centrality can have an effect on linguistic categorization (Gong, Baronchelli, et al., 2012) or the degree of diffusion of a variant in a population (Gong, Shuai, et al., 2012). Using a communication game model where the probability of communication between agents is influenced by their mutual understanding, Gong et al. (2004) put forward the co-evolution of language and social structure, as well as the emergence of networks exhibiting small-world characteristics (see section 2).

Considering the speakers as individuals with different properties embedded in structured networks brings to the fore, on the one hand, the intrinsic complexity of the processes governing the amplification of variants induced by weak biases, and the contribution of individual variation to the complexity, robustness, and

diversity of language, on the other. We present here a computational framework that allows us to perform an initial exploration of these questions, and we show that, in apparent contradiction with the “common sense” view (but see Navarro et al., 2018, for similar results in simpler social settings), even relatively weak individual biases affect the shared language of the whole community in structured communicative networks. Thus, far from being “swamped” by the tyranny of the majority, individual variation affects language and may even be one of the drivers behind the emergence of linguistic diversity and complexity. As Trudgill (2011b, 2011a) points out, there are three decisive factors influencing the emergence of linguistic complexity: population size, degree of language contact, and the density of social networks—our framework naturally models the first and the third, while the second represents a natural future extension.

In section 2, we present our Bayesian agent-based model and the different parameters used in this analysis, such as the network type and size, the proportion of biased agents and the strength of the bias, the proportion of biased influencers, and the initial language of the society. In section 3, we investigate if, and how, the inclusion of biased agents in the network changes the language of the society, and the factors affecting the stabilization of the language. We close by discussing the limitations and implications of our findings, and suggest several future directions of study.

METHODS

Our simulation framework is based on previously published models (Dediu, 2008, 2009) and has three main components: the *language*, the *agents*, and the *communicative network*. The language is modeled here as being composed of one (or more) *binary features*, that are obligatorily expressed in each individual utterance produced or perceived by the agents. We may think of these abstract features as representing, for instance, the use of the alveolar trill /r/ (value 1) or of a different r-like sound (value 0), the use of pitch to make a linguistic distinction (1) or not (0), having a subject-verb word order (1) or a verb-subject order (0), making a gender distinction (1) or not (0), using center embedding (1) or not (0), or any other number of such alternatives. Thus, if we take the /r/ interpretation, a set of utterances 1,1,1 might be produced by an agent that can trill without issues, a 0,0,0 by one that cannot, and 1,0,1 by an agent that either does not make the distinction or whose propensity to trill is affected by other factors (e.g., socio-linguistic or co-articulatory). Each agent embodies three components:

language *acquisition*, the *internal representation* of language, and the *production* of utterances. The first concerns the way observed data (in the form of “heard” utterances) affect (or not) the internal representation of language that the agent has. The second is the manner in which the agent maintains the information about language. And the third, the way the agent uses its internal representation of the language to produce actual utterances.

We opted here for a *Bayesian model of language evolution* as introduced by Griffiths & Kalish (2007), and widely used in computational studies of language evolution and change (e.g. Dediu, 2008, 2009; S. Kirby et al., 2007, among others). In this approach, there is a *universe of possible languages* (discrete or continuous), $h \in U$, and an agent maintains at all times a *probability distribution* over all these possible languages. Initially, before seeing any linguistic data, the agent has a *prior distribution* over these possible languages, $p(h)$, and, following exposure to new data (in the form of observed utterances), $d = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$, this probability is updated following Bayes' rule, resulting in the *posterior distribution* $p(h|d) = \frac{p(d|h) \cdot p(h)}{p(d)}$ that reflects the new representation that the agent has of the probability of each possible language $h \in U$. In this, $p(d|h)$ is the likelihood that the observed data d was generated by language h , and $p(d)$ is a normalization factor ensuring that $p(h|d)$ is a probability bounded by 0.0 and 1.0. When it comes to producing utterances, we implemented two widely-used strategies (among, the many possible ones; Griffiths & Kalish, 2007): a language h can be sampled at random from the universe of possible languages proportional to its probability in the posterior distribution $p(h|d)$ —a so-called *sampler strategy* (or SAM), or the agent can systematically pick the language h_m that has the maximum posterior probability $\max_{h \in U} [p(h|d)]$ —a so-called *maximum a posteriori strategy* (or MAP).

In this paper, we model a single binary feature and consequently the utterances, u , collapse to a single bit of information, “0” or “1.” The observed data, d , become binary strings, and one of the simplest models of language is that of throwing a (potentially unfair) coin that returns, with probability $h \in [0, 1]$, a “1” (otherwise, with probability $1 - h$, a “0”). Thus, the universe of our languages, h , is the real number interval $U = [0, 1] \subset \mathbb{R}$, and the likelihood of observing an utterance $u \in \{0, 1\}$ is given by the Bernoulli distribution with parameter h ; for a set of utterances $d = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$, the likelihood is given by the *binomial distribution* with parameters $k = |\{u_i = 1\}_{i=1..n}|$ (the number of utterances “1”), n (the total number of utterances), and $h : p(d|h) = \text{Binomial}(k, n, h) = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!} h^k (1 - h)^{n-k}$, where $x! = 1 \cdot 2 \cdot \dots \cdot (x - 1) \cdot x$; thus, we can reduce the set of utterances

forming the data d , without any loss of information, to the number of “1” utterances (k) and the total number of utterances (n). In Bayesian inference we sometimes use the conjugate prior of a given likelihood, in this case, the Beta distribution defined by two shape parameters, α and β ¹⁴, with probability density

$$f(x, \alpha, \beta) = \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} x^{\alpha-1} (1-x)^{\beta-1} \quad , \quad \text{where } B(\alpha, \beta) \text{ normalizes the}$$

density between 0.0 and 1.0. With these, the prior distribution of language h is $f(h, \alpha_0, \beta_0)$, with parameters α_0 and β_0 defining the shape of this distribution (see below), and the posterior distribution, updated after seeing the data $d = (k, n)$, is $p(h|d) = f(h, \alpha_1, \beta_1)$, where $\alpha_1 = \alpha_0 + k$ and $\beta_1 = \beta_0 + (n - k)$; thus, the posterior distribution is also distributed Beta, with the shape parameter α “keeping track” of the “1” utterances, and β of the “0” utterances, and the Bayesian updating is reduced to simple (and very fast) arithmetic operations. When it comes to utterance production, a SAM agent chooses a value $h \in [0, 1]$ from the $B(\alpha_1, \beta_1)$ distribution [i.e., proportional to $f(h, \alpha_1, \beta_1)$], while a MAP picks the mode of the distribution, $h_M = \frac{\alpha_1-1}{\alpha_1+\beta_1-2}$; afterward, the agent uses this number between 0.0 and 1.0 as the parameter of a Bernoulli distribution (a coin throw) to extract a single “0” or “1” value with this probability—this value then is the utterance that the agent produces.

This choice (Bernoulli/Beta) does not necessarily reflect how data is used by real humans in learning a language, but it has several major advantages, most notably its simplicity, transparency, and computational efficiency making it possible to run very large simulations on a consumer-grade computer in reasonable time (Dediu, 2009). Probably the most relevant here concerns the fact that the bias can be modeled only through the shape parameters of the prior Beta distribution, α_0 and β_0 , as the likelihood function is fixed to the Binomial, and the utterance produced offers only a limited choice between SAM and MAP. However, the Beta distribution is flexible, and can be used to represent from (almost) flat (or uninformative) distributions, to extremely peaked and to “U”-shaped ones. Moreover, for unimodal cases, we can model not only the *mode* (i.e., the “preferred” value), but also the *variance* (i.e., how “strong” is this preference, operationally, how much data is needed to change the preferred value). In our simulations, we chose four different initial prior Beta distributions. The first one is almost flat, and centered around 0.5 (unbiased agents). In the three other conditions (biased agents), the agents have an intrinsic bias toward the variant “0” (the mode of their initial prior Beta distribution is 0.1), with various

¹⁴ In our simulations, the initial values of α and β are always higher than 1.

bias strength. This is visually captured by the “narrowness” of the Beta distribution, which may vary from quite flat and skewed to very narrow. See Supplementary Materials for more information for these parameters' choice, and Figure 12 for a visual representation of these distributions and of how they are updated upon seeing data. Note that here, the terms “biased agents” and “unbiased agents” do *not* refer to the mathematical properties of their Beta distributions. Instead, these terms refer only to the presence of an *intrinsic* bias, that is, a bias oriented toward the variant “0” before the agents hear any utterances (from the community convention, or from each other).

Figure 12: The evolution of some examples of Beta priors (thick solid curves) after seeing some data (utterances), to become successive Beta posterior distributions (thin curves). Blue: an agent strongly biased against the feature; red: an agent weakly biased against the feature; and black: an unbiased agent. (Top) The prior distributions before seeing any data (“at birth”), which corresponds to the case where no initial language exists in the society. (Middle) The Beta distributions updated after seeing $n = 4$ utterances all containing the value “1” (an initial language is present in the society; mildly biased toward “1”); (Bottom) An example to see the evolution of a Beta prior after seeing $n = 10$ utterances “1.” The evolution of the priors highly depends on the bias’ strength: it is very fast for weak bias, and slower for strong bias.

The *initial language* parameter corresponds to two situations (see Figure 12): on the one hand, it can model the (quite unrealistic) case where agents are born in a society without any pre-existing language or where they are not exposed to

any linguistic input ($k_0 = 0$, $n_0 = 0$), so that the agents must create their first utterances based only on their prior bias. On the other hand, it can model the more common case where agents are born in a society with a pre-existing language already biased toward the use of the feature ($k_0 = 4$, $n_0 = 4$); this is modeled by presenting all the agents with the same 4 utterances “1” in the initial iteration, so that the first utterances generated by the agents are based both on their prior bias and the linguistic input from the society. In this analysis, the variant supported by agents having a bias (both strong or weak) is always the utterance “0.” In the case of absence of pre-existing language, biased and unbiased agents both start without input. In the case of a pre-existing language, biased and unbiased agents both start with an input (exposure to four utterances of “1”): thus, the “unbiased agents” start communicating with an internal distribution of language biased toward the community convention (the variant “1”). We remind here that the terms “unbiased” and “biased” used to describe the agents refer only to the presence or absence of an *intrinsic* bias acquired by the agents before they start hearing any type of utterance. For a visualization of this dynamic (see Figure 12).

Finally, the *network* represents the socio-linguistic structure of a community, and constrains the linguistic interactions between agents. The agents are the network nodes, and if there is an edge between two nodes then those two agents will engage in linguistic interactions. Note that we consider here only static networks: there is no change, during a run, in the number of nodes and the topology of the network (i.e., the pattern of edges connecting the nodes). The only change implemented in the properties of the nodes is the update of the posterior distribution, $p(h|d)$, which is the agent's internal representation of the community's language, and does change with new data. Likewise, our model does not include directed nor weighted edges (i.e., the two connected agents can interact symmetrically, and there is no way to specify that two agents might interact “more” than others), but we do think that dynamic weighted directed networks are an important avenue to explore in the future. Here, we use three classes of network topology, namely *random*, *small-world*, and *scale-free* networks (Figure 13). The first is a highly unrealistic baseline model (Erdős & Rényi, 1959), where we specify the number of agents and the overall connectivity of the graph (in this model, always equal to 0.1¹⁵) giving the probability of adding an edge between any two nodes. However, as real-world

¹⁵ We slightly modified the Erdos-Renyi algorithm, in order to study networks without sub-graphs and/or isolated nodes (by randomly adding a link to isolated nodes). This can change the overall connectivity of the graph in very small networks (see Supplementary Materials).

networks are not generated randomly, we focus instead on small-world and scale-free networks. To generate the *small-world networks*, we use the classic “beta model” of the Watts-Strogatz algorithm (Watts & Strogatz, 1998): the algorithm first creates a ring of nodes, where each node is connected to a number N of neighbors on either side (here, $N = 4$), and then rewired with a chosen probability p ($p = 0.1$). This process leads to the creation of hubs and the emergence of short average path lengths. Small-world properties were popularized by Milgram (1967)’s “Six degrees of separation” idea, and are found in many real-world phenomena, such as social influence networks (Kitsak et al., 2010) and semantic networks (Kenett et al., 2018). Contrary to small-world and random networks, *scale-free* ones exhibit a power-law degree distribution: very few nodes have a lot of connections, while a lot have a limited number of links, and are found, for example, on the Internet (Albert et al., 1999) or in cell biology (Albert, 2005). To generate them, we used the preferential attachment algorithm (Barabási et al., 2000), which starts from a seed of nodes and gradually adds new ones; new links are created between the newly-added nodes and the pre-existing nodes following the rule that the more a node is connected, the greater its chance to receive new connections. Formally, the probability p_i that a new node is connected to node i is $p_i = \frac{k_i}{\sum_j k_j}$, where k_i is the degree of node i , and the sum is over all pre-existing nodes j .

	Random	Small-world	Scale-free
Visualization of the topology			
Degree distribution	Poisson	Exponential	Power-law
Average path length	Short	Short	Short
Clustering coefficient	Small	Large	Rather small

Figure 13: Examples of random, small-world, and scale-free networks with $N = 40$ nodes. The degree distribution is the probability distribution of the nodes’ degree (the number of connections each node has to other nodes) over the whole network. The average path length is the average number of steps along the shortest paths for all possible pairs of network nodes. The clustering coefficient corresponds to the density of neighborhood, i.e., the degree to which nodes in a graph tend to cluster together (Watts and Strogatz, 1998).

Putting everything together (Figure 14), time is discretized into *iterations*, starting with iteration 0 (the initial condition of the simulation) in increments of 1. At each new iteration, $i > 0$, all agents produce one utterance, $u \in \{0, 1\}$, using their own internal representation of language and production mechanism (as described above). These utterances are “heard” by their neighbors (the “listeners”), who update their own internal representation of the language (also as described above) using a broadcasting mode. More precisely, in a given iteration, each agent is selected in turn in a random order (random permutation) and is allowed to produce one utterance (“speak”), utterance which is “heard” by all its network neighbors. The network is *asynchronous*, which means that the language value of listeners is updated immediately after hearing the speaker's utterance (in opposition to the *synchronous* network, where the language values of all agents are updated simultaneously at the end of each iteration, after all agents have talked). The choice of using an asynchronous network was driven by its lower computational cost; but the model was also run in a synchronous mode and the results were very similar (see Supplementary Materials). A special case is represented by the initial iteration $i = 0$, where the model can either start with the agents' own prior distributions (as defined, for each agent, by its own parameters α_0 and β_0 , that may differ between agents), or we can “train” all agents on the same set of initial utterances $u_1, u_2 \dots u_l \in \{0, 1\}$ representing a pre-existing language shared by the whole community before the experiment starts. Note that not all agents in a network must share the same prior distribution (defined by α_0 and β_0) or utterance generating mechanism (SAM or MAP), and this is, in fact, one of the most important parameters we manipulate in our simulations. With time, due to how the Bayesian model was implemented, the internal distribution of agents' language becomes narrower and narrower (that is, the α and β parameters of their posterior distribution increase with time). Thus, utterances heard earlier have a larger impact on the internal representation of the language, compared with utterances encountered later. This, in turn, leads to a progressively reduced difference between the SAM and MAP strategies (see Supplementary Materials). In other terms, one could say that agents gain some confidence in their conception of the language, as they become more resistant to change with time.

	Scale-free network After 5,000 iterations	Random network After 5,000 iterations
○ Unbiased individual △ Biased individual 0 1 Internal value of the language		
Heterogeneity value	0.154	0.011

Figure 14: The evolution of the agents' internal representation of the language (node color) after 1 and 30 iterations in a scale-free network of $n = 30$ agents. In each iteration, all individuals speak and receive the utterance produced by all their neighbors. (Left) Initial state of the network before any interaction (i.e., reflecting the prior biases); (Middle) after 1 iteration; (Right) after 30 iterations.

With these, our simulation framework allows the manipulation of several parameters (see Table 3), but we limited ourselves to the conditions given in Table 4.

Table 3: Parameters defining our simulations (see also Table 2).

Parameter	Variable name	Dependencies	Comments
Network size, N	<i>size_net</i>	None	The number of nodes (i.e., agents); it is fixed for a given run
Bias location and strength, μ_0 and λ_0	<i>bias_strength</i>	None	See Figure 1
Utterance production mechanism, <i>UPM</i>	<i>learners</i>	None	
Frequency of biased agents, ν	<i>prop_biased</i>	None	The proportion of agents in the network that are biased; note that here we consider networks containing a single type of biased agents
Proportion of highest centrality agents that are biased, <i>TOP</i>	<i>influencers_biased</i>	Depends on ν	"Random" means that the biased agents are randomly placed in the network agent centrality, while "biased influencers" ensures that the top 10% highest centrality agents are biased (if $\nu \geq 10\%$, otherwise ν)
Network type, T	<i>network</i>	None	Controls the class of network topology (see Figure 2 for examples).
Initial language, k_0 and n_0	<i>init_lang</i>	None	The total number of utterances (n_0) and the number of utterances "1" (k_0) presented to all the agents in the network in the initial iteration $i = 0$ (see Figure 1)
Maximum number of iterations, I	<i>tick</i>	None	The maximum number of iterations to run
Number of independent replications per condition, R	<i>rep_id</i>	none	The number of independent runs (replications) for a given condition

Table 4: Values used in our analysis.

Parameter	Values—Main study	Values—Systematic bias effects study
Network size, N	10 ("tiny") 50 ("small") 150 ("medium"), 500 ("large") and 1,000 ("very large")	150 ("medium")
Bias location and strength, μ_0 and λ_0	$\mu_0 = 0.5, \lambda_0 = 0.9$ ("unbiased") $\mu_0 = 0.1, \lambda_0 = 0.6$ ("biased flexible") $\mu_0 = 0.1, \lambda_0 = 0.1$ ("biased rigid") $\mu_0 = 0.1, \lambda_0 = 0$ ("biased fixed")	$\mu_0 = 0.1$ (biased) $\lambda_0 = 0.01$ to 0.99, in steps of 0.01
Utterance production mechanism, UPM	SAM ("sampler") MAP ("a posteriori maximizer")	SAM ("sampler")
Frequency of biased agents, ν	0% ("fully unbiased") 10% 30% 50% 100% ("fully biased")	0–100%, in steps of 1%
Proportion of highest centrality agents that are biased, TOP	0% ("random") 10% ("biased influencers")	0% ("random") 50% ("biased influences") 100% ("biased extremely influential")
Network type, T (for random and smallworld, same parameters as before)	"Random" "Scale-free" "Small-world"	"Random" "Scale-free" "Small-world"
Initial language, k_0 and n_0	$k_0 = 0, n_0 = 0$ ("no initial language") $k_0 = 4, n_0 = 4$ ("initial language")	$k_0 = 4, n_0 = 4$ ("initial language")
Maximum number of iterations, I	5,000	500
Number of independent replications per condition, R	100	50

Due to computational costs, we performed two different types of analysis, using different sets of parameters. In both cases, all possible combinations of parameters were performed R times. While the variables in "main study" are used to understand which predictors affect the language value of agents and in which ways, the "systematic bias effect study" helps us understand to which extent the strength of the bias and the proportion of biased agents in the population affect the language value of the population after I iterations. See the text for more details.

The size of social networks depends on how social networks are defined in the literature, they can vary between a few individuals and 5,000 or more individuals (R. A. Hill & Dunbar, 2003). Small groups, such as support cliques and sympathy groups, have in general a clustering of relationships between 5 and 15 people, while modern hunter-gatherer societies are usually described as containing from 30 to 50 individuals (R. Dunbar, 1993). As reported in the ethnographic literature, there are also higher-level grouping such as the mega-bands (500 individuals) and tribes (1,500–2,000 individuals) (R. I. M. Dunbar, 1998). Here, due to the computational costs involved, we were limited to 1,000 people in a population.

In order to test our hypotheses and to further explore the simulation results, we use the following *outcomes* (dependent variables): the *language value*, l_a , the *heterogeneity* between groups, h_s , and the *stabilization time*, t_s .

Language value

The language value of an agent at a given moment varies between 0 and 1, and is the *mode* of the Beta distribution representing the internal belief of the agent concerning the distribution of the probability of utterances "1" in the language.

Biased agents typically start with a lower l_a than the unbiased agents, thus favoring the variant “0.” We also define the language value of a given group of agents (for example, a community or the whole network) as the *mean of the language values* of all the agents in the group. We decided to focus on the language value observed after 5,000 iterations, because the language value was always stabilized after this period (see Figure 24). Given that our focus here is on understanding the effect of various parameters on the emergent language and the fact that we need to aggregate over multiple agents, we also estimate various types of *variation*. First, the *inter-replication* variation is estimated by computing the standard deviation of the language values obtained among the R replications after 5,000 iterations. It captures the influence of various sources of randomness on each particular run of a given condition, and it depends on the size and the type of network, the strength of the bias, and the initial value of the language (see Supplementary Materials). It is higher for random networks compared to scale-free and small-world networks, and higher for smaller networks. Furthermore, a weak bias and the absence of an initial language both amplify this variation. However, inter-replication variation is low, confirming the relevance of the mean of the agents' language values across the different replications. Second, *inter-individual* variation across the agents in a given network is an important outcome: we found that most biased and unbiased agents have very similar behaviors within their respective groups, justifying the use of the mean language values of the biased (*langval_biased*) and the unbiased agents (*langval_control*). We also computed the mean language value of the whole population (*langval_all*): even if there may be variation between groups (the biased vs the unbiased agents) and between agents, this value is a global indicator of the average language used in the population. Third, there are *differences between the unbiased and the biased agents* (*diff*): here we used the signed difference between the mean language values of the unbiased agents and the mean language values of biased agents, as this gives very similar results to the much more computationally expensive method of computing all pairwise differences between all unbiased and biased agents.

Heterogeneity between groups

In order to study the possible differences in the language values of the agents belonging to different communities, we first detect the structural communities within the network using the Louvain community detection algorithm (Blondel et al., 2008) as implemented in NetLogo's `nw` extension package, which detects communities by maximizing modularity based on the connections agents share

with each other, and not on the agents' language values (see Figure 15). Since the network is static, we then use the detected communities to compute the language value of each community for each iteration. Our measure of heterogeneity between groups is the standard deviation of these mean language values across communities. Thus, a low number indicates that all communities have approximately the same mean language value, whereas a high number indicates that the communities have rather different language values. (Note that this value was not computed for networks containing only 10 agents).

Figure 15: Structural communities detected in a very simple scale-free network using the Louvain algorithm. On the left is the original network with all connections, and on the right the four communities detected by the algorithm (shown in different colors and with the inter-community connections removed).

Stabilization time

Intuitively, stabilization time captures how long (in terms of interaction cycles) it takes for the language of a given network to reach a stable state. Given the inhomogeneous nature of the network, we consider two measures: the moment when *the language value of the biased agents* stabilizes (*stab_biased*) and the moment when *the language value of the control agents* stabilizes (*stab_control*) (Figure 16); these measures are estimated using the language values of their respective populations. The estimation is based on the method developed in Janssen (2018, p. 79) and used a fixed-size sliding window within which we estimate the change in the language value, we multiply this number by 10,000, round it, and stop if this number is equal to zero (i.e., the slope is within ± 0.00001 of 0.0) for 50 consecutive steps. Practically speaking, the maximum number of ticks of our model is $nIterations = 5,000$, and the size of the sliding window is $w = nIterations/10$. For a given window, we estimated the change, $t(e_g)$ using the following formula, where g is the number of iterations.

Figure 16: Stabilization times for the biased and the unbiased agents. This example uses a scale-free network with 500 agents, with SAM agents, where 10% of the top influencers are strongly biased, in the presence of an initial language.

Our framework is implemented in **NetLogo 6.1.1** (see here), the experiments were run on an Intel(R) Xeon(R) W-2255, 64 Gb RAM system under Ubuntu 18.04, and the results analyzed using R 3.6.3/Rstudio 1.4 on machines running Ubuntu 18.04 and macOS 10.15 (Catalina); the full source code and results are available at Github ([mathjoss/bayes-in-network](https://github.com/mathjoss/bayes-in-network)). The runtimes were between 6 h (scale-free networks) and 3 days (random networks) for the main analysis. It is possible to study networks up to 2,000 agents, but above 1,000 agents, the computations are too slow and would require access to a computer cluster.

RESULTS

We present here a summary of the most relevant results for our discussion, with the full results, including the actual data and R code, being available in the accompanying Supplementary Materials, to which we also make explicit reference in some cases. Note that the predictors are systematically standardized (z-scored, with mean 0 and standard deviation 1) for all regression analyses (so that we can directly compare their regression slopes, β), and the p -values of all the pairwise tests are corrected for multiple testing using Bonferroni's method.

Can a Minority of Biased Agents Affect the Language of the Whole Population?

We hypothesized that the bias of a minority of agents present in a population is not swamped by the unbiased majority, but contributes to the language of the whole population. More concretely, the population containing biased agents will use more of the variant “0” compared to the population without any biased agents. As an example, Figure 17 shows the change across time in the language value of a scale-free network with 500 SAM agents, of which 10% are biased. It can be seen that the language of the network is clearly affected by the biased minority, in that even the language value of the unbiased majority is “attracted” away from its initial language toward the language value of the biased minority, resulting in an overall language, qualitatively somewhere in between the unbiased majority's and the biased minority's languages.

Figure 17: Language (vertical axis, as language values) is changing across time (horizontal axis, in ticks) in a scale-free network with 500 SAM agents of which 10% are biased. Each individual curve represents the mean language value of the biased minority (purple) and the unbiased majority (light green) for 100 independent replications. Top: The minority is strongly biased; bottom: the minority is weakly biased. (Left) The biased minority is not

overrepresented among the most influential agents in the network; (Right) the 10% most influential agents are occupied by biased agents.

But what factors, and how exactly, allow the minority's variant to be expressed in the language of the population? We used linear regression using `lm` function (R Core Team, 2020) to investigate the influence of the parameters on the language values of all the agents after 5,000 ticks, and the results (Figure 18) show that almost all variables have a statistically significant effect on the language value, but only the proportion of the population that is biased (*prop_biased*), the strength of the bias (*bias_strength*), and the initial language value (*init_lang*) have large effect sizes.

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	P-value
(Intercept)	0.42	0.00059	<2e-16
prop_biased	-0.14	0.00029	<2e-16
bias_strength	0.07	0.00029	<2e-16
size_net	0.004	0.00029	<2e-16
learnerSAM	-0.0009	0.00059	0.14
scale-free	0.01	0.00072	<2e-16
small-world	0.01	0.00072	<2e-16
influencers_biased	-0.003	0.00029	<2e-16
init_lang	0.12	0.00029	<2e-16

Figure 18: (Top) The results of the linear regression of the language values of all agents after 5,000 ticks on various parameters. Degrees of freedom (df) = 119,991, adjusted R2 = 79.4%. The variable “learner” is a factor with two levels (SAM and MAP) and treatment contrast, with the baseline level MAP included in the intercept. The same applies to the variable “network,” with “random” being the baseline level included in the intercept. (Bottom) The results of unpaired Wilcoxon tests (with adjusted significance stars, where ns: $p > 0.05$; $*p \leq 0.05$; $**p \leq 0.01$; $***p \leq 0.001$; $****p \leq 0.0001$) between the language values (vertical axis) across multiple replications vs. the parameters (horizontal axis).

A different quantification of the influence of these parameters is shown in the bottom part of Figure 18. Interestingly, we found that the effect of *influencers_biased* is negligible. However, it has a small interacting effect with network type, the bias' strength and the percentage of biased agents: the language value of the population in scale-free networks with strongly biased agents is lower when there are 10% of biased influencers (note that no interactions were entered in this regression model; however, interactions effects are available in the Supplementary Materials). A very small effect size is also observed for the network type: the language value of the population is relatively similar for scale-free, small-world and random networks.

Figure 19 shows the joint influence of the proportion of biased agents and the strength of the bias on the population's language value for the set of values in the "Systematic bias effects study" (see Table 4). We decided to further investigate the effect of these two parameters due to their large effect sizes (see Figure 18). In this study, we ran 50 independent replications for each of all the possible combinations of the bias strength (going from 0.0 = very strongly biased to 1.0 = very weakly biased, in steps of 0.01) and the proportion of biased agents in the population (going from 0 to 100% in steps of 1%). For each replication, we computed the mean language value of the population after 500 iterations, and we then averaged the 50 independent replications for each combination by taking their mean: for example, the averaged mean language value of the population for the condition $\{bias_strength=0.70 \ \& \ prop_biased=35\}$ is 0.67, but is 0.22 for the condition $\{bias_strength=0.15 \ \& \ prop_biased=80\}$. As Figure 19 shows, in general, the aggregated mean language value progressively increases with the proportion of biased agents and the strength of the bias.

Figure 19: (Top) The aggregated mean language value (color) function of bias strength (horizontal axis, systematically varying between 0.0 and 1.0 in steps of 0.01) and proportion of biased agents in the population (vertical axis, varying between 0 and 100% in steps of 1%). For each of the possible combinations of these two parameters, a colored dot indicates the aggregated mean language value of the population. (Bottom) The different language values are plotted with isolines, in contrast to the continuous scale used in the figure on the top. The isolines are the maximum values of the combination of *bias_strength* and *prop_biased* for a set of language values, and color represents the value of the language isolines. We used a network with an initial language, containing 150 SAM agents.

In order to better visualize the shape of the relationship between the bias strength and frequency (i.e., linear or not), and also to check if the proportion of biased influencers impacts the results, we also show the set of *isolines* for the mean language value of the population (see Figure 19). These isolines are defined as the maximum values of the combination of *bias_strength* and *prop_biased* for a given set of language values. Interestingly, the relationship between the strength of the bias and the proportion of biased agents is relatively linear when the proportion of biased agents is high and/or when the bias is strong, but becomes nonlinear for low frequencies of the biased agents and for weak biases. In this latter case, the effect of biased agents on the language value of the population is much stronger than expected. Moreover, this analysis helps to understand under what conditions an initial language strongly favoring “1” may change to a language favoring the variant “0”: while only in populations with a large proportion of strongly biased agents (>50%) does the language strongly favor “0” (a language value of 0.2), it is enough for only 15–20% of the

populations to have a strong bias for the language to reach a moderate preference for “0” (language value of 0.4). However, note that while these particular values critically depend on the initial language (i.e., the number of initial utterances and the distribution of “0” and “1” utterances), they do support qualitative inferences concerning the influence of biased agents in a population.

Taken together, these results clearly show that biased agents, even if in minority, can have an impact on the language of the whole population: indeed, the bias of the agents is far from being swamped by the majority! In the remaining sections we will unpack the reasons for these findings by exploring different hypotheses. First, as we could see in Figure 17, we test in which way the biased and the unbiased agents influence each other, and we suggest that the biased agents “drag down” the language value of unbiased ones. Second, we hypothesize that biased agents maintain a trace of their bias in their language, even after interacting with the unbiased agents; this thus “lowers” the mean language value of the whole population, and makes the biased agents use a different language compared to the unbiased agents, the different types of languages “cohabiting” together in the same population. Third, we explore the hypothesis that inter-individual variation within a population leads to the emergence of linguistic communities using different languages. We note that these hypotheses are not mutually exclusive, but can be all true to some extent, beyond the framework provided by the rather simple and naive modeling approach proposed here.

How Do the Biased Agents Affect the Language of the Whole Population?

Hypothesis 1: The Biased Agents Affect the Unbiased Agents (the “Language Compromise” Hypothesis)

When biased and unbiased agents are mixed together in a network, their language values, very different at first, tend to converge toward a common language value (Figure 20). Adding an initial language to the society drastically changes the language value of the population, which is not surprising since the unbiased agents, after hearing the four initial utterances of “1,” learn a high language value, while the biased agents will shift toward intermediate language values. In the following, we focus on the more realistic case where an initial language is present. Indeed, even if the case without an initial language is interesting from a theoretical perspective on the origins of linguistic systems, we

assume that, normally, the individuals are born embedded in a society with a pre-established language system.

Figure 20: The final language value of the whole population for a scale-free network with 150 SAM agents. The solid line (1) shows the initial value of the language for the unbiased agents, while the dotted lines (2) show the initial value of the language for biased agents. The horizontal axis shows the different cases considered (combinations of bias strength and proportion of biased agents in the populations), the vertical axis is the language value of the population, and the colored boxplots show the distribution of the language values among the biased (blue) and unbiased (green) agents.

We performed unpaired Wilcoxon tests comparing the language values of the unbiased agents in a population with biased agents to those in a population without biased agents, for all possible combinations of parameters, and we corrected the p -values for multiple testing using the Bonferroni method. These adjusted p -values show that, in the vast majority of the combinations (93%, 670/720), the language values of the unbiased agents in a society with biased agents are significantly different from those of a homogeneous unbiased population. Among the 50 replications with no significant differences, 33 were networks with only 10 agents, and the remaining 17 were random or small-world networks with a low proportion of weakly biased agents. In these simulations,

the biased agents are distributed randomly in the network, so that both the biased and the unbiased agents are likely to hear utterances that will change the posterior probability of their language value: each utterance “0” heard by an unbiased agent will slightly modify the distribution of its internal language value.

This hypothesis is supported: agents within a finite population tend to share quite a similar language, which means that the biased agents do affect the unbiased agents, and vice-versa. However, are the inter-individual differences always swamped by communicating within such a population? Thus, does communication necessarily force conformity among agents? We hypothesize that this is not the case, and that instead the biased agents manage to maintain a trace of their initial bias in their language, even after interacting repeatedly with the unbiased agents.

Hypothesis 2: The Biased Agents Do Maintain a Trace of the Initial Bias in Their Language, Even After Repeatedly Interacting With the Unbiased Nodes (the “Bias Resilience” Hypothesis)

To test this hypothesis, we measure the difference in the language values between the unbiased agents and the biased agents after 5,000 iterations: the higher the signed difference, the more different the languages used by the two types of agents are. A multiple regression analysis shows that only the network type (*network*) and size (*size_net*), the proportion of biased agents (*prop_biased*), and the strength of their bias (*bias_strength*) have a large effect size (Figure 21 zooms in on their effects and the Supplementary Materials). We observe that in random networks, this difference is very small, while in scale-free and small-world networks, this difference is present and depends on the proportion of biased agents and the strength of their bias.

Figure 21: Top row: The difference between the languages of the unbiased and the biased agents after 5,000 iterations, function of network type and influencers biased (panels), size (color), and bias frequency and strength (horizontal axis). We used SAM agents, there is no enrichment of biased agents among the top influencers, and agents were exposed to an initial language.

We also performed unpaired Wilcoxon tests comparing the language values of the biased and the unbiased agents in all sets of combinations, using Bonferroni multiple testing correction. The adjusted p -values are almost always significant for scale-free networks (except for 44 networks with 10 or 50 agents, often weakly biased); significant for 52% of the small-world networks, especially for big networks with strong biases; however, most random networks do not show a significant difference, with the exception of a few very small networks. Particularly in scale-free networks, the proportion of the top-influencers that are biased also affects the difference in language values between the unbiased and the biased agents (see Figure 21), especially in networks with 10% of strongly biased agents.

These results allow a more nuanced view of the first hypothesis' conclusions: while the biased agents do affect the unbiased agents and all agents do tend to reach a language compromise, the biased agents still manage to maintain a trace of their initial bias in their language, even after interacting with the unbiased agents.

Hypothesis 3: The Emergence of Linguistic Communities With Different Languages (the “Linguistic Polarization” Hypothesis)

Our results so far show that network type and size generally influence the language value of the population, suggesting that this may be due (in part) to the emergence of linguistic communities using different languages within the network (Figure 22). We estimate the existence of such linguistic communities through the heterogeneity of the language values between structural communities in the network (as detected by the Louvain community-detection algorithm). A multiple regression analysis (see Supplementary Materials for full results) shows that only network type has a big effect size on the heterogeneity between communities (Figure 23). It can be seen that the linguistic communities do not generally emerge in random networks¹⁶. On the other hand, scale-free and small-world networks tend to behave differently: even when there are only unbiased agents in the network, we can see the emergence of linguistic communities differing in their language, suggesting that network structure itself favors the emergence of linguistic communities. However, if the network contains only strongly biased agents, all agents will share the same language before and after interacting with each other, precluding the emergence of linguistic communities. The maximum heterogeneity between communities is found in scale-free networks when there is a minority of strongly biased agents.

Figure 22: An example of linguistic community emergence in scale-free (left) and random (right) networks with 50 SAM agents, 10% of which are strongly biased (triangles) while the

¹⁶ Note that the relevance of using Louvain algorithm to extract communities in random networks is debatable.

remaining 90% are unbiased (circles). Agent colors represent their language value; agents were exposed to an initial language.

Figure 23: The difference in heterogeneity between linguistic communities function of network type (columns) and size (colors), and bias strength (rows) and frequency (horizontal axis). The networks contain SAM agents, no influencers are biased, and there is an initial language.

We performed unpaired Wilcoxon tests comparing the heterogeneity of, on the one hand, the unbiased agents in a population with biased agents, to that of the unbiased agents in a population without biased agents, on the other, for all possible combinations of parameters, and we corrected the p -values for multiple testing using the Bonferroni method. These adjusted p -values show that, in scale-free networks with a strong bias, having biased agents in the network significantly affects the emergence of linguistic communities (86%, 83/96); this is also true, to a smaller extent, for small-world networks with strongly biased agents (75%, 72/96). However, in scale-free and small-world networks containing weakly biased agents, only about half of the time the comparisons are significant (45% for scale-free, and 54% for small-world); thus, the heterogeneity observed in these networks is probably mostly due to the structure of the network itself.

Thus, the hypothesis 3 is supported by our results to a certain extent: heterogeneity between linguistic communities seems to naturally emerge in heterogeneous scale-free and small-world networks but only with agents who are not too weakly biased; moreover, strongly biased agents amplify the language differences between linguistic communities in scale-free networks.

Putting the Three Hypotheses Together: Even Rare and Weak Biases Matter!

The results show that the bias, even in a minority, is not swamped by the majority: instead, it affects the language of the whole population. As the agents are interacting, the biased and the unbiased agents are influencing each other's language: consequently, the biased agents “pull” the language values of the others toward the value preferred by their bias. In random networks, all agents eventually agree on the same language value (unless the network is very small), but, due to their internal structure, both small-world and scale-free networks see the emergence of linguistic communities diverging in their languages. Moreover, in scale-free networks (and, to a smaller extent, also in small-world networks), the biased agents do retain a trace of their bias in language, and, when strongly biased, they help amplify the differences between linguistic communities. Thus, network structure is a key parameter for understanding the structural properties of the emergent languages, but does it also affect the speed with which the language reaches its stable state?

When Does the Language Stabilize?

To answer this question, we analyse the agents separately depending on their type (biased vs. unbiased) as the languages of the two types might stabilize at different times. Thus, we performed linear regressions for the biased agents, and for the unbiased agents separately (see Supplementary Materials for full results). While most of the variables have a significant effect, only the proportion of biased agents, the strength of the bias, and the size and type of network have a large effect size. As we can see in Figure 24, there is an interaction between network size and type: while stabilization time decreases with size in random networks, it is stable in small-world and scale-free networks. The stabilization time for biased and unbiased agents in all types of networks with weakly biased agents is approximately the same. However, for networks with strongly biased agents, the proportion of biased agents influences the stabilization of the language of the two types of agents differently: the lower the proportion of biased

agents, the bigger the difference in stabilization time between the biased and the unbiased agents. That is to say, when only a small proportion of the population is biased, the language of these biased agents will need a long time to stabilize, but when half of the population is biased, unbiased and biased agents will reach stability at approximately the same time. In scale-free and small-world networks, this difference is positively affected by network size, and is higher for scale-free networks.

Figure 24: Stabilization time for the biased and the unbiased agents (color), in different types of networks (columns) with two different sizes (rows), for various bias frequencies and strength (horizontal axis). The agents are SAM, there are no biased influencers, and there is an initial language.

Thus, stabilization time varies widely depending on network type and size, and the strength and frequency of the bias. In all three types of networks, the language stabilizes at roughly the same time when the networks are small, but only in random networks the language stabilizes faster as network size increases. Overall, agents in scale-free networks tend to require more time to stabilize. When the agents are strongly biased, the difference in stabilization time

between the biased and the unbiased agents is negatively influenced by the proportion of biased agents.

DISCUSSION

We introduced here an agent-based model that quantitatively investigates the dynamics of amplification and expression, to the level of the population's language, of linguistic variants influenced by individual-level biases. While our study is by far not the first to investigate the influence of communicative structure on language transmission (Gong, Baronchelli, et al., 2012; Gong et al., 2004) nor of the effects of biases on language change and evolution (S. Kirby et al., 2007; S. Kirby & Hurford, 2002), we are the first (to our knowledge) to combine the two in a non-trivial way, by allowing agents with intrinsically different biases to interact through a structured communicative network. We show that, contrary to the “intuitive view” that the biased minority ends up adopting the language of the unbiased majority, even weakly biased agents present in a small part of the population *can* affect the language of the whole population, when the communicative network of the population is structured. The reverse is also true, as biased agents are accommodating to the unbiased agents. Thus, the language value of the population reflects often mostly the initial language of the society carried by unbiased agents. The influence of the bias increases with the strength and the population frequency of the bias, but, unlike Navarro et al. (2018), we do not find here evidence for a disproportionately large influence of strongly biased agents. However, our results show that even weak and rare biases can exert a stronger influence than a priori expected, as the relationship between population language, bias strength and bias frequency is not linear. Maybe counter-intuitively, far from being “swamped” by the majority, weakly biased agents representing but a minority, can nevertheless disproportionately influence the language of the majority. With hindsight, these results may appear unsurprising given our use of a Bayesian model which, by definition, given enough data should move away from its prior and come to reflect the observed data. However, we have to point out that it is far from clear what “enough data” means, how the structured nature of the interactions affects this process, and that real languages might be far from a state of equilibrium (e.g., Cysouw, 2011)—therefore, even in this constrained context our results are arguably unexpected, showing that even weak and rare biases, implemented in a way that favors erasure by the incoming data, do survive in the emergent, community-wide behavior.

We tested here three hypotheses concerning the manner in which individual-level biases may influence the population's language. First, we investigated the way in which the biased and the unbiased agents interact and influence each other. Our findings match the prediction that the presence of biased agents has a significant effect on the language that emerges in the population, as their bias affects the language of the unbiased agents. More generally, all agents tend to converge, after interacting repeatedly, toward a compromise in their language somewhere between the initial language of the biased and the unbiased agents. Interestingly, while the network structure does not affect the final language at which the population stabilizes, it does affect the speed with which it stabilizes: this is faster in larger random networks, and generally slower in scale-free networks. This is consistent with Raviv et al. (2020)'s experimental findings, where it is suggested that stability is faster in denser networks, while sparser networks would be slower to stabilize. Differences in convergence times between different network structures was also found in the statistical physics literature that studies cultural dynamics (Baxter et al., 2008; Blythe, 2015; Castellano et al., 2009). In our simulations, the high connectivity in random networks led agents to receive many utterances from their neighbors at each iteration, while in scale-free networks, each agent heard, on average, less utterances at each iteration. However, in scale-free networks, it is important to note that the internal representation of the influencers evolves faster (i.e., become “narrower” around a specific value) than for poorly connected individuals.

The role of network structure is also highlighted by our second hypothesis: we expected that the biased agents would manage to retain a trace of their bias in their language even after interacting repeatedly with the unbiased agents. Strikingly, our findings match this expectation, but only in scale-free networks (and, to a smaller extent, also in small-world networks). In such networks, the biased agents stabilize on a slightly different language than the unbiased agents, making the two groups easily identifiable even after repeated interactions. Moreover, our results show that the presence of the bias among the top influencers in the network (agents with the highest network centrality) results in the amplification of these inter-individual differences (especially through the creation of an “elite” community with a different language), but, importantly, does not have a strong effect on the final language of the whole population (except for very small scale-free networks with 10% of strongly biased agents). Thus, communication does not necessarily enforce uniformity among the agents, but instead inter-individual variation persists even after repeated interactions in structured networks. But then, how do these types of networks match the reality

of human linguistic interactions? While a consensus has not yet been reached (Ke et al., 2008), most authors (Kaiser & Hilgetag, 2004; Xiao Fan Wang & Guanrong Chen, 2003) suggest that a realistic model should incorporate features of both scale-free and small-world networks, and that random networks are definitely out. As such, our own results can be taken to support these suggestions: indeed (as discussed in section 1), there is widespread inter-individual variation in language that persists into adulthood, but our simulated random networks lost all traces of inter-individual variation (see Heterogeneity *intra* group in the Supplementary Materials).

The third hypothesis further explores the idea that inter-individual variation may lead to the emergence of linguistic communities using different languages. Our results show, indeed, that even without any inter-individual differences in the beginning, as long as the initial bias is too strong, the structure of scale-free and small-world networks leads to the emergence of communities differing in their languages. This is broadly in line with fundamental sociolinguistic theory and data showing that multi-level structured linguistic variation within linguistic communities is the norm (Labov, 1975; Meyerhoff, 2015; L. Milroy & Gordon, 2008). Our study addresses these issues in a novel way, by explicitly modeling both inter-individual variation and structured linguistic interaction. We found that adding biased agents (and especially strongly biased agents) randomly in the scale-free and small-world networks amplify the linguistic variation between the communities, but how does such inter-individual variation influence the emergence of such communities? We suggest that randomly placing biased agents within a network may lead to the presence of several biased agents within the same structural community (i.e., a community due to the connectivity structure of the network), while some other structural communities may end up without any biased agents. Therefore, communities with many biased members will tend to differ in the use of the variant affected by the bias from the communities without any biased members. However, in reality the biases may not always be randomly distributed in the population, but instead have a patterned distribution (due to a combination of geographic, historical, and demographic factors), as found for biases rooted in human genetics (Dediu & Ladd, 2007; Wong et al., 2020) or the vocal tract (Blasi et al., 2019; Dediu et al., 2017; Dediu & Moisik, 2019), feeding precisely into this amplification and differentiation process.

Interestingly, our results also contribute to the debate concerning the differences between modeling the linguistic agents as Bayesian samplers (SAM) or maximizers (MAP). Early influential studies of simple transmission chains

(Griffiths & Kalish, 2007; S. Kirby et al., 2007) found that SAM and MAP differ fundamentally in their asymptotic behavior, in that SAM always converge to their prior distribution, while MAP's behavior is more complex (including the amplification of weak biases). However, these simple results don't generalize in more complex settings (Dediu, 2009; Ferdinand & Zuidema, 2009; Perfors & Navarro, 2014; K. Smith, 2009), and our results are in line with these findings: allowing the interactions between agents to be structured by non-random networks fundamentally alters the way language emerges in populations of SAM and MAP agents and may even erase the alleged differences between them.

Most studies of language change suggest that the replacement of one variant by another tends to follow an “S”-shaped (or sigmoid) curve (Blythe & Croft, 2012; Ke et al., 2008), where the new variant starts as very rare, increases in frequency initially slowly, then very rapidly, then slows down again, until the total replacement of the old variant. However, our simulations do not show such results because our agents have no mechanism that forces them to pick one variant over the other, their choices being instead probabilistic. Thus, it is very unlikely that one variant will completely replace the other in their languages, but, in future work, if such a behavior is deemed necessary, we could easily implement such a selection mechanism.

Despite its novelty, the work presented here suffers from several limitations that may impact its generalizability and realism. First, we use a Bayesian approach to model language acquisition and production: while this has a respectable pedigree both in the cognitive sciences in general and in studying language evolution and change in particular, it is also heavily debated to what degree the Bayesian paradigm reflects reality (e.g. Dediu, 2009; Ferdinand & Zuidema, 2009; Griffiths et al., 2008; Hahn, 2014; S. Kirby et al., 2007; Perfors, 2012). Our choice here was rather pragmatic, in the sense that our Bayesian models are very simple mathematically, computationally fast, flexible enough, and arguably realistic enough *given the aims of our study*: “[a]ll models are wrong, but some are useful” and here, a Bayesian agent usefully abstracts away from the enormous (and only partially understood) complexity of language acquisition and production but still captures the fact the linguistic behavior of one's community affects one's own representation of language, as well as the many factors affecting one's use of language. Importantly, we do believe that the main *qualitative* findings of our study do not critically depend on the use of Bayesian models, but this is, of course, an empirical question to be answered by future studies where only the agent model is changed, keeping everything else the same. Moreover, this is but a first step in a longer research programme and we

do consider a variety of models, Bayesian and not (see for some examples of such non-Bayesian models in our own work, Dediu, 2008), as appropriate, given the parameters of interest in each study. Second, we only modeled at most two discrete types of agents co-existing in a population (biased and unbiased), but the reality is much more complex and continuous; while this shortcoming can be addressed by allowing more types of agents (or a continuous distribution of agents) in a network, it greatly complexifies the experimental design and the analysis of the results. Third, the structure of our networks is rather artificial and is fixed in time; while the first issues can be addressed through the use of real-world data (e.g., sociolinguistic case studies or data derived from social media such as Facebook and Twitter), the second is more complex to implement, as it requires not only the change in network topology and connection strength, but also the removal of agents (death or emigration) and the introduction (birth or immigration) of new agents (naive or with a pre-existing language), and the move to a multi-generation paradigm. However, the fixity of our network structure might affect our results, as it is expected that the linguistic interactions themselves alter the topology and strength of the connections, creating thus complex feedback loops between the evolution of the network and of the language. Fourth, our results must be critically combined with real-world data derived from observational (Abitbol et al., 2018) and experimental studies (Raviv, 2020), in order to refine the model but also to inform future real-world experimental design, data collection and analysis.

In conclusion, our results—while preliminary—show that inter-individual variation, especially when structured by communicative networks, does affect language, and may even be one of the drivers behind the emergence of linguistic diversity and complexity. They also highlight that, when discussing the influence of biases on language change and diversity, inquiring only about the effects of bias strength and frequency in the population misses the essential role played by the fact that there is structure to human interactions, and that rarely two linguistic exchanges are mirror images of each other. Combined with other types of evidence, with the ubiquity of inter-individual variation, and the quintessentially structured nature of human interactions, this suggests that we must focus our attention on this rather neglected factor in the origins and evolution of the bewildering patterns of linguistic diversity still visible around the world.

5

HOW NETWORK STRUCTURE SHAPES LANGUAGES: SIZE AND DENSITY AS PROXIES AND NOT CAUSES

CONTEXT

This work is currently under review in Cognitive Science journal. This research was conducted during an exchange at the Artificial Intelligence lab, in Vrije Universiteit, Brussels, under the supervision of Bart de Boer. The authors are Mathilde Josserand, Marc Allasonnière-Tang, François Pellegrino, Dan Dediu, and Bart de Boer. Supplementary Materials are available in my github: https://github.com/mathjoss/NetworkStructure_ABM.

ABSTRACT

Languages show substantial variability between their speakers, but it is currently unclear how the structure of the communicative network contributes to the patterning of this variability. While previous studies have highlighted the role of network structure in language change, the specific aspects of network structure that shape language variability remain largely unknown. To address this gap, we developed a Bayesian agent-based model of how language change spreads. By isolating the relative effects of specific global network metrics and local measures of centrality across thousands of simulations, we show that both global and local characteristics of network structure play a critical role in shaping inter-

individual variation in language, while intra-individual variation is relatively unaffected. We effectively challenge the long-held belief that size and density are the main network structural factors influencing language variation, revealing that they are, in fact, proxies for the true driving forces: path length and clustering coefficient. Thus, variation is more likely to emerge in populations that are structured in small communities and where individuals are not well-connected to each other. Our study provides important insights into the theoretical mechanisms underlying language variation.

INTRODUCTION

Variation is ubiquitous not only in the natural world, but also in culture. There are intriguing patterns of variation ranging from within to between individuals (in most biological, psychological, cognitive and linguistic characteristics) and groups (most obvious in various aspects of culture). In the language domain, one can think about how two different persons would pronounce the phoneme /r/ in different ways, even if they speak the same language (Sankoff & Blondeau, 2007), or how grammatical constructions vary between English dialects (Trudgill & Chambers, 2017), or even about lexical variation (different use of ‘firefly’ and ‘lightning bug’ words for example). Why this variation exists, why it is patterned the way it is, and what processes govern its dynamics are extremely important and non-trivial scientific questions.

Language variation arises from divergences in the gradual evolution of linguistic features over time among different populations. It is customary to distinguish the emergence of an innovation (the so-called “initiation”) from the dynamics of its diffusion in the speaker community (“actuation”) (Croft, 2008; Dediu & Moisik, 2019; Solé & Vives, 2012; Stevens & Harrington, 2014; Yu, 2013). Initiation is usually seen as an individual-level process, while actuation is essentially a community-level process involving competing linguistic variants (Blythe & Croft, 2012; Fagyal et al., 2010). The selection of variants during the actuation phase can be influenced by many different factors, such as aspects of the environment (e.g., the effect of environment type on the phonemic inventories of languages; Everett et al., 2015; Maddieson & Coupé, 2015), cultural and historical factors (degree of contact with outsiders, or number of L2 speakers; Lupyan & Dale, 2010), or factors related to the structure of the network of linguistic interaction itself (Wray & Grace, 2007). Indeed, interactions between individuals in human societies are embedded in social networks with specific characteristics (Beckner

et al., 2009; M. E. J. Newman & Park, 2003), which would constrain the transmission of linguistic features (Chambers, 1995). While all human networks tend to share a few features, such as a small average path length, social network structures exhibit a great diversity across populations (M. E. J. Newman, 2003; Nichols, 1992). In turn, this diversity would influence the actuation of linguistic features, thus creating patterns of linguistic variation (Trudgill, 2011b).

It is, however, challenging to carefully disentangle the relative effects of network structure from those of the other factors involved, prompting several researchers to introduce experimental, computer modeling and observational paradigms. The rich tradition of sociolinguistic studies uses fine-grained methods that provide insight into the role of network structure (among many other factors) in the emergence and dynamics of linguistic variation (Labov, 1972, 2001, 2010; J. Milroy & Milroy, 1985; Yu, 2013). Following a different approach, Raviv et al. (2019, 2020) tackle this question with an experimental approach involving the learning and transmission of an artificial miniature language within a carefully controlled network structure. In the field of cultural evolution, Derex & Boyd (2016) show in a computer-based experiment that sparse groups of individuals are more likely to find the solution to a complex combinatorial problem compared to strongly connected groups. This experiment was later replicated in the real Agta community (Migliano et al., 2020). These laboratory experiments emphasize the role of population size and network structure on language variability. However, despite their inherent advantages, laboratory experiments are strongly constrained in terms of population size, network structure and aspects of language considered, limiting the direct extrapolation of these results to understanding the dynamics of actual linguistic communities. Artificial multi-agent models do provide ways to address some of these issues, in particular concerning the number of linguistic agents, the structure of their communicative networks, and the usually long time scale necessary for innovations to spread in large populations. Such modeling studies do confirm the importance of factors such as the ease of diffusion of a feature (Reali et al., 2014), the transitivity of the network (Lou-Magnuson & Onnis, 2018), the role of network type for linguistic categorization (Gong, Baronchelli, et al., 2012), and the role of social structure on sign language characteristics (Mudd et al., 2022).

Thus, a wide range of approaches strongly suggests that network structure likely influences language change and variation. But what exactly is meant by “network structure”? The networks used in such studies are either networks observed in the real world, or are automatically generated with specific properties (such as, for example, being fully connected, scale-free, or small-world). Any network,

whether “natural” or “artificial”, can be described using a set of measures (called *metrics*) that summarize various aspects of the network, varying between the relatively global to the quite local. As Raviv et al., (2020) observed, it is very difficult to tease apart the contribution of each network characteristic in real-world observational networks. In other words, comparing real-world populations raises the question of understanding which network structural factors are involved in the actuation of linguistic innovations, and in which manner. In contrast, multi-agent models allow a much finer degree of control over these factors. As a consequence, most agent-based modeling studies to date have investigated the separate role of various characteristics of the communicative network. However, this approach has two main limitations: first, when focusing on specific factors in isolation, it is very difficult to compare their relative influence, and to understand the interactions between them. Secondly, working with automatically generated networks has not led to a fine-grained understanding of which network metrics behind these networks actually affect the dynamics of actuation. Indeed, there are intrinsic relationships between various metrics resulting from the type of network being generated. As an example, if communities structured as scale-free networks produce more stable variation than those structured as small-world networks, is this due to their lower centrality, lower clustering coefficient, or any other metric that intrinsically differs between these two types of networks?

On the other hand, complex social and communicative networks by definition create local heterogeneities between the linguistic agents involved (be they human or artificial): different positions in the network may lead to inter-individual differences in popularity, in how agents bridge different structural communities, or in how they connect preferentially with like-minded others. For example, it has been suggested that network heterogeneity favors the stabilization of innovative linguistic features, especially if this network has tight-knit communities and popular individuals (Fagyal et al., 2010). Likewise, innovative forms seem to spread slightly faster when innovative agents have a lower clustering coefficient than conservative agents (Dekker et al., s. d.), and densely embedded social ties are more likely to drive linguistic change (Goel et al., 2016). In this context, previous work (Josserand, Allasonnière-Tang, et al., 2021) studied intrinsically different agents placed in controlled communicative networks. While inter-individual variation is widely acknowledged in sociolinguistics, phonetics and speech pathology, it is seen either as an impairment to be treated (such as the incapacity to produce the alveolar trill /r/ in the languages that canonically use it), or as noise to be controlled through large enough samples in experimental designs. In Josserand et al. (2021), agents were allowed to be different from each other in the strength of their bias towards a certain linguistic feature.

Crucially, this bias was not fixed but could be altered by exposure to data (learning) according to an agent-specific flexibility. These agents communicate through networks whose structure and size can be controlled. The results showed that the stabilized language used by a population after many rounds of interaction, as well as the temporal dynamics of the evolving language, vary depending on the type of network structure used, the type of position in the networks the biased individuals have, and the strength and flexibility of the bias. However, here too, it was hard to disentangle the contribution of the different network structure metrics and to study their relative contribution. Thus, it remains unknown what local network metrics matter for the spread of a language feature. In other terms, what characteristics should an agent possess to diffuse its language to the population? Shall this agent have many neighbors, be positioned strategically in the network, or have a high clustering coefficient?

Addressing these questions makes it essential to disentangle and bring a theoretical basis to the question of what aspects of network structure do, in fact, shape language. This has theoretical implications for understanding how languages adapt to fit their social environments and how network structure shapes language. In turn, it will help understand language differentiation and help explain the great diversity observable in the world's languages. To answer these questions, we introduce here a multi-agent model based on the one in Josserand et al. (2021). The agents use a Bayesian model of language learning in artificially generated networks where we control various metrics, and, across thousands of runs, we effectively isolated the relative influence of several global metrics (average shortest path length, clustering coefficient, global assortativity, degree distribution, and size) and of local characteristics of the agents (measures of centrality and clustering coefficients). See Figure 25 for an example. We found that these metrics have different contributions to the evolution of language in this model: while intra-individual variation is not shaped by network structure, inter-individual variation is strongly affected by the path length and the clustering coefficient.

The paper is structured as follows: in the Data and Methods, we present our Bayesian agent-based model, along with the networks used, the metrics under consideration, and the overall procedure of this analysis. In the Results, we investigate whether some of these metrics affect inter- and intra-individual variability in different types of networks and what metrics shape the language in populations where some agents are biased. We close by discussing the limitations and implications of our findings, and suggest several future directions of study.

Figure 25: Panel **A**. We first examine the differences between networks differing on a specific global metric (here, clustering coefficient, but we applied it to every metric in Table 1). Panel **B**. Next, we explore the effects of agent bias (denoted by a gray node) depending on whether the most popular, least popular, random agents (not represented here), or no agents are biased, with popularity being defined by metrics in Table 3. Panel **C**. Throughout our study, agents interact using Bayesian communication for an extended period of time. Panel **D**. Finally, we investigate the language variability within and between agents in the network. To do so, we compare language variability in networks that differ based on global metrics, using dataset 1. We also generated random, small-world, and scale-free networks (dataset 2) to explore the correlations between different metrics and their relative contributions to variability in models. Lastly, using dataset 3, we study how local variation introduced in networks shape differences in language (more specifically, spread in biased utterance, see “The Output” section) and inter- and intra-individual variability. More information about the differences between the 3 datasets will be presented in the Data and Method section.

DATA AND METHODS

Here we develop a Bayesian model of language evolution (Griffiths & Kalish, 2007) based on published work (Josserand, Allasonnière-Tang, et al., 2021), where agents exchange linguistic messages as constrained by a communicative network. Briefly, the network’s nodes represent the agents, which all have an internal representation of language, here reduced to a single feature. The agents that are connected via undirected edges in the network are called “neighbors” and can “talk” to each other. Upon “hearing” their neighbors’ utterances, an agent updates its internal representation of language to take into account the newly “heard” data using Bayes’ rule. We study how the language changes after

multiple rounds of such interactions, and, in particular, the manner in which different network structures affect these dynamics.

The language

The language in our model is a multinomial feature that can take one of k exclusive possible values. This simple representation is arguably adequate to approximate numerous aspects of human language, such as lexical choices (using one of several words or expressions to describe a given concept), allophony (different actual sounds for the same phoneme as conditioned by the phonetic environment, socio-linguistic/dialectal choices, or in free variation), or morpho-syntactic structures (different ways of organizing the sentence). Here, we call an *utterance* a token drawn from this multinomial distribution. For example, if the feature refers to the possible allophones of “r” in English, the possible utterances include the alveolar trill [r], the approximant [ɹ], and the retroflex approximant [ɻ], among others. Abstractly, we can represent the feature through the vector of its possible utterances $u = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k\}$. We fixed the number of utterances k to 10 here, but simulations ran with different values of k lead to similar conclusions.

While we also generalized our feature to a continuous one (which can represent, for example, very fine-grained measurements of vowel heights or voice-onset-time (VoT); presented in the Supplementary Materials), we decided to focus here on the case of the discrete valued feature. Indeed, using a continuous representation instead of the discrete one does not alter our conclusions, but presenting both representations lead to clutter and unnecessary complexity in the presentation of the results.

How do agents represent language?

Agents are Bayesian learners (Griffiths & Kalish, 2007). In this framework, there is a fixed “universe” of languages, U , and each possible language h from this universe ($h \in U$) has a certain probability p of being “the real one” from the agent’s “subjective” point of view. Before being exposed to any utterance, each agent has an *a priori* “belief” concerning the probabilities of each possible language, denoted $p(h)$ and known as the *a priori probability distribution* of the languages (or the *prior*). However, each time an agent “hears” an utterance, denoted as d , it updates its subjective distribution of the probabilities of the languages in light of this data using Bayes’ theorem: $p(h|d) = \frac{p(d|h)p(h)}{p(d)}$. Here,

$p(d|h)$ is the likelihood of observing data d given that the language is h , while $p(h|d)$ is the updated belief, or *posterior*, i.e. the probability of the language being h “true” after both the *prior* and the observed data d are considered. The denominator $p(d)$ acts as a normalization factor and is not of immediate concern here. While this mechanism is extremely general, we apply it here in a very particular and relatively simple setting.

More precisely, an agent’s internal representation of language is given by a vector $\mathbf{p} = (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k)$, where each component p_i represents the probability of the i^{th} utterance u_i ; as the utterances are mutually exclusive and exhaust the space of possible utterances for this features, $\sum_{i=1}^k p_i = 1$. An agent has an *a-priori* distribution that represents its initial belief in the probability of each utterance, which leads naturally to a *multinomial distribution* that represents the likelihood. More precisely, given n such utterances “heard” independently by an agent, the random variable $\mathbf{X} = (X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k)$ distributed as *Multinomial*(n, \mathbf{p}) gives the expected number of times each possible utterance u_i appears. Here, the multinomial distribution models how frequent any one of the k possible utterances should be among n “heard” independent ones, if their probabilities are given by the vector p .

To compute the posterior distribution after having seen the data, it is possible to use the very computationally expensive Markov Chain Monte Carlo technique. However, in particular cases, one may choose specific conjugate priors, which drastically simplify the application of Bayes’ theorem. The conjugate prior of a multinomial distribution is given by the *Dirichlet distribution*, which is defined by a vector of k parameters $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_k) \in \mathbb{R}^k$. These parameters α_i are related to the probability p_i of each utterance u_i , so that the vector of probabilities $\mathbf{p} = (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k)$ is distributed as $\text{Dir}(\boldsymbol{\alpha})$. The prior and posterior distributions of probabilities are modeled by Dirichlet distributions and, thus, characterized by prior (denoted here as $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$) and posterior (denoted here as $\boldsymbol{\alpha}'$) Dirichlet parameters. Using Bayes’ theorem, one can update the prior distribution $\text{Dir}(\boldsymbol{\alpha})$ into the posterior distribution $\text{Dir}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}')$ after seeing a number n of independent utterances (the data, d): it reduces to trivial arithmetic: $\alpha'_i = \alpha_i + X_i$, where, as above, X_i gives the number of times utterance u_i was “heard” in the data d . Thus, this reduces to a simple model where the parameters of the Dirichlet distribution reflect the number of “heard” utterances and the prior belief. It is important to note that, as expected for Bayesian models, both the prior beliefs and the observed data matter. Seeing enough data should be able to overwhelm even very strong a priori beliefs and the order in which the utterances in the data arrive does not matter. This generalizes the prior model studied in Josserand et al.

(2021) by allowing more than two possible utterances (i.e., from a Bayesian model with a binary feature using Binomial/Beta conjugate distributions, to a multinomial feature using Multinomial/Dirichlet conjugate distribution).

The initial language exposure

We considered two types of agent populations, differentiated by their “initial language exposure”. The agents in the first type of population are born *without* initial language exposure. Such agents are naïve regarding the language, with all possible utterances having the same probability of occurrence. This is modeled by a Dirichlet distribution with all parameters α_i being equal, $\alpha = (1, 1, \dots, 1)$. We take it to represent the situation where agents are born in a language-less community, but it may as well represent a community with a language where all possible utterances are equally frequent.

However, agents can also be born in a population *with* initial language exposure, i.e. born in a community with a pre-existing language that favors a certain utterance at the expense of the others; say, utterance 4, α_4 is 6 times more frequent than the others (for various reasons, including past internally-motivated language change, language contact, or top-down language policies). This situation is represented by a Dirichlet distribution with parameters $\alpha = \{1, 1, 1, 6, 1, \dots, 1\}$. Given how the parameters of the Dirichlet distribution reflect the number of “heard” utterances, this can be seen as modeling the fact that agents are expecting, before they hear anything, that the utterance u_4 is much more frequent than all the others. The choice of 6 is supposed to represent an initial language with a very skewed frequency of the utterances, but not too strong (however, we also investigated the effect of using 20 instead of 6 in the **Supplementary Materials**). We can interpret this initial Dirichlet distribution that an agent has as the agent’s own language *bias*.

The communication process

As described above, the agents are “born” with their initial Dirichlet distribution, which represents their bias concerning the language feature. The simulation happens in discrete timesteps (*rounds*), and in each round, the agents “speak” (i.e., produce utterances) and “hear” (i.e., receive) the utterances produced by their neighbors.

To produce utterances, an agent uses the following procedure: first, they compute the *mode* of their Dirichlet distribution, given by the vector $\mathbf{m} = (m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k)$ where $m_i = \frac{\alpha_i - 1}{\alpha_0 - k}$, with $\alpha_i > 1$ being the distribution's k parameters. Then, it uses these values m as the parameters of a multinomial distribution from which a single value is drawn $x \sim \text{Multinomial}(1, \mathbf{m})$. Finally, this value represents the utterance that is actually produced, namely u_x (see Figure 26). So, we use what is known as a sampler (or 'SAM') strategy (Griffiths & Kalish, 2007; Josserand, Allasonnière-Tang, et al., 2021) in which the agent picks any of the possible k utterances proportional to its subjective probability (as given by the agent's current Dirichlet distribution).

Conversely, upon hearing the utterances produced by its neighbors, the agent updates its current Dirichlet distribution as described above. This update consists of an addition, so that the Dirichlet hyper-parameters become $\alpha'_i = \alpha_i + X_i$, where $X = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k\}$ represents the number of times each utterance appears among those that the agent just heard.

Figure 26: Representation of the Dirichlet distribution for an agent without initial language exposure (A) and for an agent with an initial language exposure towards α_2 (B). For visualization purposes, we plotted here $k=3$ utterances instead of the $k=10$ actually used in the study. The dots represent the random draws from the Dirichlet distribution: if the random draw occurs in the **a** part, the agent will produce an utterance u_1 ; if it occurs in the **b** part, it will produce an utterance u_2 , and it will produce an utterance u_3 when drawn in the **c** region. In the condition without initial language exposure, random draws happen equally probably for all three utterances, but with initial language exposure, they occur mostly in the **b** region, resulting in many more u_2 utterances. The bar plot below each triangle is an alternative way of representing the values of the Dirichlet distribution.

The network

The agents form the nodes of a network with a static structure, fixed for the duration of a simulation, while the edges between the nodes determine the agents that can talk to each other. Given that we focus on the structure of these networks, our discussion in this section is framed in terms of nodes and edges, instead of agents and their communicative exchanges. Here, we use three classes of network topology: random, small-world, and scale-free networks. The random networks are generated using Erdős & Rényi (1959)'s algorithm, where each node has a fixed probability of connecting with other nodes in the network. The small-world networks are generated using the Watts-Strogatz algorithm (Watts & Strogatz, 1998): this algorithm starts with a ring of nodes, where each node is connected to a fixed number N of neighbors on either side, followed by a rewiring with a fixed probability p . This process leads to the generation of networks with many real-world properties (Kenett et al., 2018; Kitsak et al., 2010), such as the presence of short average path lengths (see Milgram (1967)'s "Six degrees of separation"). The scale-free networks are generated using the preferential attachment algorithm of Barabási et al. (2000), and exhibit a power-law degree distribution: most nodes have a limited number of neighbors, while few nodes have very many (Albert, 2005; Albert et al., 1999), resembling real offline and online social networks. The algorithm gradually adds new nodes to a network such that the probability p_i that the newly added node is connected to node i is $p_i = \frac{d_i}{\sum_j d_j}$ where d_i is the degree of node i , and the sum is over all pre-existing nodes j . We use these different classes of network topology to investigate the effects of specific network metrics (see Table 5).

Table 5: Table summarizing the different metrics used to describe the **global** structure of a network. The second column (“short name”) shows how these different metrics will be identified in the paper.

Name of the global network metric	Short name	Description	Mathematical description	Type of network
Average node degree	Degree	Average number of neighbors for all nodes	$D = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n k_i}{n}$ where k is the degree of a node i and n is the total number of nodes in the network	Constant for Barabasi-Albert scale-free networks with a fixed size
Network size	Size	Total number of nodes	n	All
Average shortest path length	Path length	On average, how close (defined by the number of intermediate nodes) are two random nodes	The mean of the shortest path length between all pairs of nodes: $l_G = \frac{\sum_{i,j} dist(v_i, v_j)}{n(n-1)}$, where $dist$ is the shortest path length between two nodes	All, as soon as there are no isolated components
Global assortativity coefficient	Assortativity	Preference for a network's nodes to attach to others that are similar (here, in terms of nodes's degree)	The mean of the local assortativity based on the node degree, where local assortativity is defined as $\rho = \frac{j(j+1)(\overline{m_j} - \mu_j)}{2M\sigma_d^2}$, where M is the number of edges in the network, j is the excess degree of a particular node and $\overline{m_j}$ is the average excess degree of its neighbors. (The excess degree distribution j is defined as $j(k) = \frac{(k+1)P(k+1)}{D}$). Thus, assortativity can vary between -1 (highly disassortative) to 1 (highly assortative).	All
Average clustering coefficient	Clustering	Measure of the degree to which nodes in a network tend to cluster together	The average local clustering coefficient of all nodes, where the local clustering is defined as: $c_i = \frac{\lambda_G(v)}{\tau_G(v)}$, where $\lambda_G(v)$ is the number of triangles on $v \in V(G)$, $V(G)$ being the set of all nodes in the undirected graph G , and $\tau_G(v)$ is the number of triangles on $v \in G$. The clustering coefficient varies between 0 (the friends of my friends are never connected) and 1 (the friends of my friends are all connected)	Constant in scale-free networks
Degree distribution: the shape of the power law distribution	Degree distribution	Shape of the degree distribution for power-law distributions: how strongly hubs gather all connections	A power-law distribution is defined as $P(k) \sim k^{-\alpha}$ where α is the exponent of the distribution. The larger the exponent, the rarer the large values are. The exponent is found by applying “log” to the degree distribution and looking at the slope of the obtained new graph. Exponents in scale-free networks obtained with Barabasi-Albert algorithm usually present some random fluctuations and vary between 2 and 3.	Only networks exhibiting a power-law distribution

In this study, we aim to isolate the effect of the different metrics in order to understand how they may influence language variability. Please note that we focus on these metrics because they capture essential properties of communicative networks that have been claimed, or may arguably contribute to language dynamics within networks. Moreover, some of these metrics are very

hard to disentangle and, therefore, their effects might be confounded in most previous studies. To overcome those difficulties, we generated hundreds of thousands of networks, and then selected two sets of networks, each containing 100 networks: for a given metric, we selected the two sets of networks guaranteeing that the averages for the other metrics in the two sets were similar except for the metric under consideration (see Table 6). We used scale-free networks to analyze the independent effects of the network size, the path length, the assortativity, and the degree distribution; small-world networks for the clustering coefficient; and random networks for the average degree and path length (see the **Supplementary Materials**).

Table 6: Table showing the absolute differences between the two sets of networks. Each column refers to the two sets of networks varying only in the shown metric, the rows showing the absolute difference between the two sets in the appropriate metric given by the names. For example, the second row shows the differences between the two sets of networks differing by design in path length: these two sets contain 100 networks each, have the same size, clustering coefficient, average degree, and almost the same degree distribution and assortativity, but (as intended) markedly different path length. The networks in the first four columns are scale-free networks, while networks for comparing clustering coefficient (5th row) are small-world networks, and the networks used to study differences in degree (6th row) are random networks. These numbers should be interpreted with caution, as the strength of a difference of “1” or “0.01” may vary depending on the metric being analyzed.

Metric value ¹	Difference between the two sets varying in the network metric (in bold) ²					
	Size	Path length ³	Degree distribution	Assortativity	Clustering	Node degree
Size	50	0	0	0	0	0
Path length	0.01	1.61	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Degree distribution	0.00	0.01	0.49	0.01	--	--
Assortativity	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.32	0.01	0.01
Clustering	0	0	0	0	0.26	0.01
Degree	0.02	0	0	0	0	0.60

These metrics reflect the *global* network structure, but there is *local* heterogeneity between nodes, which is captured by node-level metrics. In the second part of this paper, we investigate the influence of local network heterogeneity on language change. To do so, 20% of the agents are *biased* (i.e., their initial Dirichlet distribution gives preference to utterance u_7 , which was

arbitrarily chosen) and occupy nodes in the network based on their local metrics: for example, we bias the 20% agents with the highest or lowest node degree. This way, we aim to observe what happens in a group where a minority shows a preference for using a particular utterance over other options. These *biased* agents contrast with the *unbiased* agents who have no preference for any utterance. Here too, we study two types of networks with and without initial language exposure. With this, we compare the effects of different local network metrics (see Table 7), and we also compare these with a set of networks with the 20% of biased agents placed in random nodes, as well as with homogeneous networks (i.e., where all nodes contain unbiased agents).

Table 7: Table showing the different metrics used to describe the **local** structure of the network. See Table 5 for notation definitions.

Name of the local network metric	Description	Mathematical description
Node degree	Number of neighbors of a given node	Number of neighbors of a given node, here denoted as k_i
Clustering coefficient	How well-connected are the neighbors of a given node (shows whether the node belongs to a clique)	See Table 1 for the mathematical description of local clustering coefficient
Betweenness centrality	Proportion of shortest paths between members of the network that passes through a given node	The betweenness centrality of a node v can be defined as: $g(v) = \sum_{i \neq v \neq j} \frac{\sigma_{ij}(v)}{\sigma_{ij}}$, where σ_{ij} is the total number of shortest paths from node i to node j and $\sigma_{ij}(v)$ is the number of those paths that pass through v (but not where v is an endpoint)
Eigenvector centrality	The amount of influence a node has on a network: nodes that are connected to many other nodes that are themselves well-connected (and so on) get a higher Eigenvector centrality score	Given $A = (a_{v,t})$ the adjacency matrix of an undirected graph G , the relative centrality of a node i is given by: $x_v = \frac{1}{\lambda} \sum_{j \in M(v)} x_j = \frac{1}{\lambda} \sum_{t \in V(G)} a_{v,t} x_t$ where $M(v)$ is a set of the neighbors of v and λ is constant. In this implementation, the eigenvector centrality is normalized such that the highest eigenvector centrality a node can have is 1. This implementation is designed to agree with Gephi's implementation out to at least 3 decimal places.
Closeness centrality	The normalized average length of the shortest path between the node and all other nodes in the graph	The normalized closeness centrality is defined here as $C(v) = \frac{n-1}{\sum_{ij} dist(v_i, v_j)}$

Measurements

Previous studies (see Figure 13 in Josserand et al., 2021) have shown that in a type of Bayesian model of language change similar to the ones implemented here but where the linguistic feature was binary, language stabilized before 1000

rounds in all network types (see our **Supplementary Materials** for visualization). Here, we introduced a conservative margin and analyzed the inter- and intra-individual variability after 3000 rounds (when all agents had produced 3000 utterances) in order to make sure that language would have stabilized. First, we define *inter-individual variability* by how different the agents are regarding their internal language representation. For example, if agents tend to use different utterances (some preferentially u_4 while some others preferentially u_3), the inter-individual variability will be high. We estimate inter-individual variation using the Kullback-Leibler divergence, which is a measure of the statistical distance between two probability distributions (as coded in the *entropy* package in R; Hausser & Strimmer, 2021). To do so, we computed for all possible pairs of agents the pairwise Kullback-Leibler divergence between their Dirichlet distributions, and then averaged the resulting pairwise Kullback-Leibler divergences to obtain an average measure of the inter-individual variation in the network.

Secondly, *intra-individual variability* captures how consistent an agent is in its own language productions. For example, if an agent uses equally likely two utterances (u_2 and u_8 half of the time each, for example), its intra-individual variability will be high. On the contrary, an agent that always uses the same utterance has a low intra-individual variation. We estimate intra-individual variation as the entropy of an agent's Dirichlet distribution (as coded in the *entropy* package, using Jeffreys prior¹⁷; Hausser & Strimmer, 2021), which is bounded between 0 and $\log_2(k)$, where here $k=10$. The *average* of this intra-individual variation across all agents captures their propensity to consistently use the same utterance (a high average indicates that agents switch between different utterances, while a low average suggests that agents tend to use the same utterance consistently), while its *standard deviation* across all agents captures to what degree there are differences between the agents regarding their intra-individual variation (a high standard deviation suggests that while some agents always use the same utterance, others show a high variability, and a low standard deviation suggests that all agents tend to be equally consistent or not in their language production). See Figure 27 for a visualization of the entire process.

¹⁷ This ensures that the resulting entropy value is robust and not overly influenced by the specific parameterization of the probability distribution. We also selected other priors, but conclusions were the same.

Figure 27: A schematic representation of the multi-agent model. (A) Agents are “born” embedded in a network with a fixed structure and with given characteristics. Each agent has an internal language representation given by the parameters of the Dirichlet distribution (see gray bar plot in Figure 24). For visualization purposes, we decided to represent $k=3$ utterances here instead of the $k=10$ utterances used in the paper. (B) **Step 1.** Each agent randomly extracts a number from its Dirichlet distribution: here, the probability of picking any of the three utterances is the same. **Step 2.** Each agent produces the chosen utterance (here, u_1 for the agent on the left and u_3 for the one on the right). **Step 3.** Each agent hears the utterance(s) of its neighbor(s) and updates its own Dirichlet distribution accordingly. (C) After each individual talks 3000 times, we measure the inter- and intra-individual variation among the agents in the final network.

Third, we measure the *spread of the biased utterance* in the configuration consisting of a heterogeneous population. In this context, this value represents the degree of importance of the biased utterance (u_7) in the population. To compute it, we normalize the parameters of the Dirichlet distribution for each agent, and then we average the value of the parameter α_7 for all agents. If the biased utterance u_7 is regularly used by the agents, the *spread of the biased utterance* will be high. On the contrary, if biased agents did not spread their preference for the biased utterance to the population, then the *spread of the biased utterance* will be low.

The procedure

We conducted three types of simulations. In the first (which we will call *dataset 1*), we systematically compared two sets of networks differing in exactly one metric, as described above. To assess whether a difference is meaningful or not, we used Cohen's d , a statistical metric that measures the difference between two groups. This metric is computed by dividing the difference between the means of the two groups by the pooled standard deviation of the groups. In the *dataset 2*, we ran a series of simulations with random, scale-free, and small-world networks using a wide range of parameters. We first look at how the metrics co-vary over a wide range of values. We then model how these metrics influence the final variability in the communicative network using linear regression models. In the third (*dataset 3*), we looked at the spread of the biased utterance, as well as inter- and intra-variation in various networks where 20% of the agents are biased toward a biased utterance.

RESULTS

Dataset 1

To produce sets of networks that vary only in one metric, we needed to use multiple types of networks. We used scale-free networks to investigate the influence of assortativity, degree distribution, path length, and size. Small-world networks were used to examine the impact of the clustering coefficient, while random networks were used to investigate the effect of the average node degree. The inter- and intra-individual variation (mean and standard-deviation) values for each network type and metric are presented in Figure 28.

Figure 28: Measure of inter-individual variation (left column), mean of intra-individual variation (column in the middle), and standard deviation of intra-individual variation (right column). Each row shows the results for one metric: for example, the first row shows the results for 100 networks that have a low assortativity on average (in blue), and 100 networks with a high assortativity (in yellow) (see Table 2), in networks with an initial or emergent language. Each row shows the results for a specific metric (from up to down, assortativity, degree distribution, path length, size, clustering, node degree). Depending on the network type used to study the metric of interest, the x scale may vary. The x scale of inter-individual variation shows the mean pairwise Kullback-Leibler divergence, while the two other columns show respectively the mean and the standard deviation of the entropy for all agents, computed using the final Dirichlet distribution for each agent.

Clustering coefficient. Both networks without (Cohen’s $d = 4.2$) and with (Cohen’s $d = 4.2$) initial language exposure exhibit a strong influence of clustering coefficient on inter-individual variability, as shown in Figure 28. Networks without a clique structure tend to display lower levels of inter-individual variation. Similar to most other metrics, clustering coefficient has no effect on the mean amount of intra-individual variability. However, higher clustering coefficients lead to more differences among individuals in terms of intra-individual variation (with some agents consistently using the same utterance and

others switching between several different utterances), which is observed in networks with and without an initial language exposure (Cohen's $d = 2.0$ and Cohen's $d = 2.2$, respectively).

Path length. The path length strongly affects inter-individual variability, in both networks without (Cohen's $d = 1.5$) and with (Cohen's $d = 1.5$) initial language exposure. Thus, networks where agents are easily reachable by others are likely to show low levels of inter-individual variation. Path length does not affect the mean amount of intra-individual variability, but it does slightly positively affect the standard deviation of intra-individual variation in networks with an initial language exposure only (Cohen's $d = 0.7$).

Size. The network size also influences language variability, but its effect quickly disappears with higher initial language exposure. Big networks show higher inter-individual variation in networks without (size: Cohen's $d = 0.9$) and with initial language exposure (size: Cohen's $d = 0.5$). However, an additional analysis suggests that the stronger the initial language, the less the network size will play a role in shaping inter-individual variation. More specifically, Cohen's d drops to 0.3 when the initial language exposure is strong (see Supplementary Materials). Thus, the size of the population only affects inter-individual variation in languages with weak or absent language initial exposure. As for intra-individual variation, size does not appear to have any impact on the amount and standard-deviation of intra-individual variation observed.

Average node degree. The average node degree has a discernible but moderate impact on the degree of language variation among individuals, compared to other metrics. In networks without (Cohen's $d = -0.7$) and with an initial language exposure (Cohen's $d = -0.7$), networks with a low average node degree typically exhibit high inter-individual variation. However, the average node degree does not affect any type of intra-individual variation.

Assortativity and degree distribution. Finally, both assortativity and degree distribution have no observable effect on inter-individual nor intra-individual variation. Networks where individuals are preferentially connected to similar individuals, and networks with very skewed degree distributions, do not show specific patterns of variation.

Initial language exposure. The initial language exposure affects inter- and intra-individual variation: networks without initial language exposure exhibit greater inter- and intra- individual variation (both mean and standard-deviation).

Notably, the amount of intra-individual variability is solely affected by the initial language exposure.

Dataset 2

Here, we also use simulations obtained using automatically generated random, small-world, and scale-free networks (all generated networks were kept without any specific selection criteria). We analyzed the Pearson’s correlations between the metrics (see Figure 29). The clustering coefficient, the node degree, and the path length are highly correlated with each other. Thus, the more neighbors a given agent has on average, the more likely the friends of this agent will be connected to each other, and the lower the average path length will be in the network. Network size, assortativity and degree distribution also correlate to the other metrics. Bigger networks have lower clustering coefficient, higher path length (except for random networks) and assortativity. These results reflect the necessity of the sampling procedure used above to study the effect of the different metrics separately.

Figure 29: Correlation matrix with the different metrics in scale-free (left), small-world (middle), and random (right) networks.

Using this same set of simulations, we applied several linear models to predict the variability in different network types using our metrics as predictors (see Figure 30). The different metrics were z-scored, so that their effect sizes can be compared. Encouragingly, these results concur with the previous findings comparing sets of networks. Indeed, the models show that the path length is the best predictor for inter-individual variation, followed by the clustering coefficient. For scale-free networks (in which the clustering coefficient does not vary), the initial language exposure is the strongest predictor of inter-individual variation. The effect sizes of the other metrics are very small, corroborating the idea that

network size, average degree, assortativity, and degree distribution are not important for understanding inter-individual variability. In all network types, the initial language exposure language type is the only strong predictor for the mean intra-individual variation. As for the standard deviation of intra-individual variation, they are influenced by path length, clustering coefficient, and initial language exposure. The adjusted R^2 in these models indicate that the different network metrics explain on average 75% of the inter-individual variation, 96% of the mean intra-individual variation, and 74% of the standard deviation of the intra-individual variation. Interactions also exist in several metrics including path length, size, clustering coefficient, and initial language exposure (see Supplementary Materials for more details).

Figure 30: Results of the nine regression models, for the three types of networks (random, scale-free, and random) and the three dependent variables (inter-individual variation, mean and standard deviation of intra-individual variation). All predictors were z-scored, which allows the comparison of their effect size. The estimate and the std error are plotted for each predictor (but the standard errors are usually too small to see). Note that the results for the scale-free models are slightly different since the clustering coefficient is not included in this model.

Dataset 3

Network structure leads to local heterogeneity between agents. We biased 20% of the agents with the lowest (*non-popular agents*) or highest (*popular agents*) value of different metrics, namely the clustering coefficient, the betweenness centrality, the closeness centrality, the eigenvector centrality, and the node degree. We compared these networks to networks where 20% of the agents were biased randomly with respect to the considered metric, and to networks where none of the agents were biased at all. We remind the reader that while unbiased agents have no preference for any utterance (in the situation without initial language exposure) or a preference for utterance u_4 (in the situation with

initial language exposure), the biased agents carried a preference for using the utterance u_7 (which we call here the biased utterance). First, we found that the *spread of the biased utterance* is higher in networks where popular individuals are biased (namely, networks where biased individuals have high values in the different metrics), regardless of the metrics chosen. In scale-free networks (see Figure 31) and small-world networks with low rewiring probability (see **Supplementary Materials**), the average node degree and the betweenness centrality are the metrics that favor the most the spread of the biased utterance. However, all metrics are equally influential in random networks or other types of small-world networks (see **Supplementary Materials**). On the contrary, the eigenvector centrality and closeness centrality are the most important metrics to predict the amount of inter-individual variation. Networks where agents have very low or very high eigenvector or closeness centrality show high amounts of inter-individual variation (in scale-free and small-world networks). However, it is harder to see the effect of biasing popular agents on intra-individual variation (both mean and standard deviation), as the effect varies a lot depending on the type of network chosen. Nevertheless, we speculate that the biased agents with higher centrality measures lead to higher mean intra-individual variability since agents with higher centrality measures have more neighbors, resulting in more agents being confronted to conflicting utterances.

Figure 31: Results of the spread of the biased utterance, inter- and intra-individual variation in several scale-free networks containing 150 agents, with 20% of the agents biased, in a population with an initial language exposure (results were similar with a population without an initial language exposure; see **Supplementary Materials**). The first row shows the results for networks without any biased agents, the second row shows the results for networks where the 20% of agents were chosen randomly, the third row shows the results for networks where 20% of the agents with the highest eigenvector centrality (in blue) and lowest eigenvector centrality (in green) were biased. The other rows show the same type of results for the other metrics, namely closeness centrality, degree, and betweenness centrality. The dashed line indicates the median value for the set of networks in which random agents were biased.

DISCUSSION

Understanding patterns of variability within a language provides important insights into the great diversity observable in the world's languages. While many studies highlight the role of network structure on language change, no differentiation was made between different network characteristics in real world-populations or agent-based models, making it impossible to disentangle their relative contributions. In this study, we applied several methods using a Bayesian agent-based model of language change to understand how specific characteristics of a network shape language.

We found that network structure affects the inter-individual language variability. But contrary to what was suggested in the literature (Dale & Lupyan, 2012; Raviv et al., 2020; Trudgill, 2011a; Wray & Grace, 2007), the size and the density of a social network do not seem to be the important factors to consider. Instead, path length and the clustering coefficient are the parameters that influence language variability. The confusion between size and density on the one hand, and clustering and path length on the other hand, can be easily understood given that these factors are highly correlated: bigger and well-connected populations tend to have shorter path lengths and higher clustering coefficients. But while the size and the density of a population can accurately predict patterns of variation, theoretically, these measures are only proxies for what really shapes language variability, namely path length and clustering coefficient. Hampering the transmission of information and promoting the existence of distinct communities within a population will favor the emergence of variation in a language. Also, a population growing in size will not necessarily witness more variation, as long as the transmission of information is effective; this is in particular the case in populations with hubs, which facilitate the circulation of information.

The type of language, a factor extrinsic to the network structure, also plays an important role in shaping inter-individual variability. Thus, individuals born in a society with strong pressure to use a specific language are less likely to use different types of utterances. In turn, this would explain why emerging sign language in small remote villages (such as Al Sayyid Bedouin Sign Language sign language in Israel; Jaraisy & Stamp, 2022) usually exhibit more variation than official deaf community sign languages taught at schools, even though these official languages are characterized by sparser and larger populations of signers (Meir et al., 2012; Mudd et al., 2020). The predictions of our model are also consistent with the experimental findings of (Raviv et al., 2019b), as our

model shows an effect of size and number of neighbors in small communities without any pre-existing language. However, we suggest that their results cannot be generalized to the dynamics of most real-world populations, as the effect of size and node degree fade away when populations already possess a specific language. We suggest that the pressure for conformity (and more specifically, for using the dominant variant in the population) is the main factor underlying the differences between an established language and an emerging language. Importantly, the strong role of the type of language suggests that non-structural factors do play a very important role to shape language variability, and that network structure cannot alone account for all the diversity present in real-world networks. For example, other extrinsic factors such as the role of a shared context (Mudd et al., 2022) and the openness to strangers (Dale & Lupyan, 2012) were not taken into account here, but they might have additional contributions to the effect of network structure.

On the contrary, intra-individual variability is not shaped by the network structure, but only by the type of language of the society in which an individual is born. An individual born in a society with low pressure to use a specific form of language will use different types of utterances to refer to the same concept. These findings relate to the study of very recent emergent sign languages, such as Kata-Kolok, where high intra-individual variation was observed (Lutzenberger et al., 2021). However, differences between individuals regarding their level of intra-individual variation are affected by the network structure. Here too, high path length and high clustering coefficient increase the probability that the population possesses both individuals very confident in their language beliefs and individuals with low confidence in which language form to use. We suggest that both high path length and high clustering coefficients are related to the presence of structural communities (cliques), which then lead to linguistic communities. Individuals bridging these communities are then more likely to possess high intra-individual variation, changing their language according to whom they are speaking to, while individuals inside communities use the language spoken by their group unconditionally.

Our results also suggest that the local heterogeneity implied by network structure influences the language spoken by the group, which is consistent with previous work (Josserand, Allasonnière-Tang, et al., 2021). Agents transmit language in a different way depending on their position in the network. Most popular agents play an important role when spreading an alternative language form, especially if these agents are bridging communities (betweenness centrality) or have many neighbors. However, the agents who increase the amount of inter-individual

variation in a network are characterized by their degree of influence (eigenvector centrality) or how close they are to other agents in the network (closeness centrality). However, here too, the presence of popular biased individuals does not seem to affect intra-individual variation patterns.

Together, these results suggest that differences at both the global and local level of network structure (especially for path length and clustering coefficient) influence language inter-individual variability, and also highlight the weak role of network structure on intra-individual variation. However, one potential limitation of our study is that the degree of contrast between the sets of networks generated based on a single metric may not have been strong enough to capture the full extent of the metric's influence. For instance, the magnitude of the difference between the high and low node degree networks may have been insufficient to fully explain the impact of node degree on language variability. Also, our "flat" Bayesian model contrasts with human abilities to differentiate and track various language varieties. This highlights the potential for elaborating more complex simulations (such as hierarchical Bayesian models) in future research, and meanwhile, our conclusions should be extrapolated with caution to real-world language networks. Additionally, the model only accounted for static networks, whereas real-world networks are dynamic and evolve through interactions. While interactions are the driving force behind network structure, further research could explore the mechanisms of preferential attachment to gain a deeper understanding of their impact on language variability.

DISCUSSION

DISCUSSION

Why are there over 8,000 languages spoken on Earth today? Within the field of language evolution, many explanations have been proposed for this longstanding inquiry. Among these explanations, differences in human anatomy and physiology across different populations were put forward as shaping languages' sound systems (Dediu & Moisik, 2019; Dediu et al., 2017). In this work, we examined whether group-level differences in eye physiology, due to exposure to UV radiation, might play a role in shaping color lexicons. Because our findings uncovered substantial individual differences *within* a given group, we also studied how languages evolve in groups where each person has unique language abilities, and what are the mechanisms under which inter-individual variation can influence the course of language evolution.

To explore the influence of inter-group and inter-individual variation on language evolution, this doctoral thesis used various methods, such as data analysis, natural experiments, experiments involving language creation in controlled lab settings, and agent-based models. This work was achieved in collaboration with many researchers: Dan Dediu contributed to all Chapters, François Pellegrino to all Chapters except Chapter 1; Emma Meeussen and Asifa Majid to Chapter 1, Serge Caparos to the Introduction, Chapter 2, and Discussion, Limor Raviv to Chapter 3, Marc Allasonnière-Tang to Chapters 4 and 5, and Bart de Boer to Chapter 5. Their contributions considerably helped improve this research and broaden my research perspective. Also, I was lucky to have the support of not just one, nor two, but three dedicated supervisors, each with distinct expertise in my subject. This is not an acknowledgment section, but just an acknowledgment

of the collaborative nature of my work. In this chapter, I will use "I" to discuss personal thoughts and ideas, while "we" will be employed to denote collective research efforts.

This chapter summarizes the main findings from the previous chapters and puts them back in the context of my personal scientific journey during the Ph.D. I first turn to the conclusions of part 1 and discuss the obtained results. Then, I shift to the conclusions of part 2, exploring what our dual methodology teaches us regarding our research question, both collectively and individually. Finally, I present a general conclusion, acknowledge certain limitations, and propose potential paths for future research.

DIFFERENCES IN COLOR PERCEPTION MAY SHAPE COLOR LEXICONS

Many languages do not have a specific term to talk about the blue color, instead encompassing it under other color terms. To explain this variation, many possible variables (including cultural or environmental variables) have been proposed during more than a century of research. Among these factors, it has been suggested that changes in eye physiology, due to UV-light incidence, can lead to faults in blue color perception which causes the color lexicon to adapt (*lens brunescence hypothesis*; Lindsey & Brown, 2002).

I was first confronted with this hypothesis at the beginning of my Master 2 internship at the Laboratoire Dynamique du Langage, three and a half years ago. The goal was to investigate the lens brunescence hypothesis using up-to-date statistical methods, with the hypothesis that UV incidence *does* affect the presence of a word for blue. While I was initially convinced by this hypothesis, my enthusiasm faded as I explored the criticisms that arose following the publication of Lindsey & Brown's (2002) (see Introduction; Hardy et al., 2005; Regier & Kay, 2004). This caused a shift in my perspective: while the initial objective was to explore the negative effect of UV incidence, my aim turned towards illustrating that by factoring in more variables, particularly cultural ones, the impact of UV incidence would become less pronounced, which would provide a line of argument *against* the lens brunescence hypothesis.

Thus, we performed a data analysis involving 142 populations and numerous cultural and environmental variables. We found that the presence of a specific

DISCUSSION

term for 'blue' was determined by several cultural and environmental factors that interact. On the one hand, we found an important role of the population size which brings forward cultural complexity as one of the main contributors to the presence of a specific term for 'blue'. This comes as unsurprising since much research had already linked color technology and color lexicons, suggesting that the presence of dyeing techniques and colored manufactured artifacts would affect the communicative need people would have to refer to new colors, thus leading to the addition of new color terms (Berlin & Kay, 1969; Ember, 1978; Gibson et al., 2017; Zaslavsky et al., 2020).

On the other hand, we also found that populations who live near lakes would also be more likely to possess a term for 'blue'. We were careful not to over-interpret this result, especially given that no effect of distance to oceans and rivers is to be noted. There are two possibilities: either distance to lakes acts as a proxy for another unmeasured variable, or there is something specific about lakes' color that increases the need people have to refer to blue color. If the latter, then the presence of the effect of distance to lakes would align with the idea that culture *alone* does not dictate the evolution of color lexicons. This is supported by the example of the Maniq hunter-gatherer population, a non-industrialized group that surprisingly possesses a high number of color terms, thus suggesting that the presence of color technology is not an obligatory condition for the emergence of new color terms (Wnuk et al., 2022). Also, Twomey et al. (2021) showed that cross-cultural differences in communicative needs, which shape the partitioning of color terms, are partly explained by differences in the local biogeography of linguistic communities.

More importantly, UV incidence remained a significant factor, even when being mixed with other cultural and environmental factors. I was genuinely surprised by this outcome, as I had not expected it to maintain its significance given the presence of other, I believed, stronger cultural factors. Of course, the presence of a correlation between UV incidence and the presence of a term for 'blue' does *not* necessarily imply that UV incidence has a direct causal effect on color lexicons. Although a causal pathway involving the lens brunescence hypothesis is particularly plausible given the experimental evidence provided by Lindsey and Brown (2002) and Walter (2011), I do not exclude the possibility that UV incidence could affect the presence of a specific term for 'blue' based on other causal pathways. As an example, one can postulate that UV incidence could partially impact the food production system, thus affecting economic development; however, I believe that our climate variables would reflect this sort

DISCUSSION

of causal assumption. It is also plausible that the proxies we used for the very hard-to-measure cultural complexity may lead to some biases in our data.

Additionally, this effect could potentially stem from random factors resulting from the fact that the 142 populations we selected may not fully capture the diversity of real-world languages and over-represent Indo-European languages. My main supervisor, Dan Dediu, learned about new datasets containing information about color lexicons. Because we were both curious to double-check our findings and see if they remained consistent with a larger set of data, I collected additional populations and improved the precision of UV-B incidence indicators. Then, D. Dediu collected a few additional data, replicated the analysis, and also used new methods, such as latent variable Structural Equation Models and phylogenetic methods. This replication study involves 823 languages (see Illustration 6 in the Introduction; Dediu, 2023). Encouragingly, the negative linear effect of UV-B incidence on the presence of a word for 'blue' remained present and strong with this new dataset. However, the effect of distance to lakes becomes less pronounced, though it can still be detected as a discernible trend. Contrary to Josserand et al. (2021), the effect of cultural complexity seems better captured by subsistence mode than by population size. Notably, subsistence mode plays a crucial role in explaining the color naming pattern in populations where UV exposure is relatively low. This supports the idea that higher UV-B levels impose a negative pressure on the presence of a term for 'blue', while conversely, lower UV-B levels do not impose a pressure towards or against 'blue', allowing other factors (such as cultural ones) to operate.

The lens brunescence hypothesis has sparked extensive discussion, not only as a response to Lindsey and Brown's 2002 paper (Hardy et al., 2005; Regier & Kay, 2004; S. Walter, 2011), but also following our paper (Josserand et al., 2023; Josserand, Meeussen, et al., 2021; see Follow-up: comment on the paper) with the critiques of Hardy et al.'s (2023). To me, the whole argument could be boiled down to a single question: Are cultural influences the only force shaping color vocabularies, or could eye physiology also play a role? I personally found value in each of the criticisms presented by Hardy et al. (2023), especially since they were built on earlier solid research. I also want to acknowledge the respectful and thorough process shown by researchers on the opposing side who engaged in a comprehensive discussion with us on this matter. However, these critics also made me realize that one of the main conclusions of our initial paper (color vocabularies result from a complex interplay of various cultural and environmental factors) had been lost and oversimplified to this bold claim that "color vocabularies *are* shaped by UV incidence". Also, I wished that Hardy et

DISCUSSION

al. (2023) could have provided *new* data or arguments that could substantiate their criticisms. Essentially, the debate around the lens brunescence hypothesis can be likened to a prolonged tennis match, where numerous researchers over the years have volleyed arguments in favor of one side or the other. To truly settle the question of the hypothesis' validity, it becomes imperative to add, again, replications or new data into the pool of experiments.

Providing additional (or contradictory) evidence for the lens brunescence hypothesis became the idea for a second piece of work. A main criticism of the lens brunescence hypothesis involves chromatic adaptation, a process ensuring that the perceived color of objects remains relatively consistent under varying lighting conditions, and which could also potentially compensate for changes caused by aging eyes. In other words, this criticism is essentially captured by this question: Is the effect of lens brunescence on color perception strong enough to remain uncompensated in color categorization? While many studies have investigated age-related changes in color perception (Beirne et al., 2008; Cooper et al., 1991; D. W. Kline & Scialfa, 1996; Kinneer & Sahraie, 2002; Knoblauch et al., 1987; V. C. Smith et al., 1985; Verriest, 1963; Wijk et al., 1999), fewer have explored variations in color perception across diverse populations (Davies et al., 1998; Nacer et al., 2001), and to my knowledge, none linked these variations in color perception with patterns of color naming. Thus, while the lens brunescence hypothesis posits that populations residing in high UV incidence areas experience worse color perception, this connection remains insufficiently explored.

To address this issue and get around the inherent limitations of our statistical studies, we decided to capitalize on a fieldwork opportunity in Namibia, which provided excellent conditions for a natural experiment. The two fieldworks that we did initially stemmed from an idea put forth by one of my former internship supervisors, Giorgio Vallortigara. His objective was to conduct tests within a non-"WEIRD" population – one with limited exposure to formal mathematics – to gain deeper insights into the acquired and inherited roots of mental number line (i.e., this tendency that human and non-human animals have to mentally organize numerosities along a left-to-right spatial continuum). He reached out to Serge Caparos, a specialist in cross-cultural cognitive psychology with extensive experience working with the Himba community for over a decade, who later became one of my Ph.D. supervisors. S. Caparos not only welcomed me to participate in conducting the mental number line experiment (the details of which I will not cover here, but a preprint is accessible [here](#); see Eccher et al., in-

DISCUSSION

review), but also granted me the opportunity to undertake additional color perception tasks relevant to my doctoral research.

Luckily, the Himba population proved to be an ideal group for investigating the lens brunescence hypothesis. Indeed, their exposure to UV incidence is very high and compounded by their predominantly outdoor lifestyle. Moreover, historically, the Himba people had fewer color terms in their vocabulary compared to the French people. However, due to recent exposure to English-language schooling, a portion of the Himba population has acquired new color terms, including a specific term to distinguish between blue and green colors (Mylonas et al., 2022). The primary objective of this experiment was to compare color perception between French and Himba participants while carefully controlling for confounding variables, ensuring the robustness of the results under consideration. We found that the color perception of young Himba participants and young French participants is very similar. However, as participants age, the decline in color discrimination becomes more pronounced among Himba participants compared to their French counterparts. Although we anticipated a more significant decrease in the perception of blue colors, we discovered that this decline applies to both blue and red colors. We hypothesize that this age-related decline in the Himba population could be attributed to higher UV exposure. Nevertheless, we do not rule out the possibility that other factors may be at play, such as differences in the statistics of the color environment or other environmental and genetic factors.

Since I started the project on color in 2019, a significant body of recent research has been published in an effort to finally answer the long-standing question of "why color lexicons are the way they are" (notably, with the work of Zaslavsky). This recent research suggests that while differences in communicative need drive populations to adopt new color terms, there is a common perceptual structure shared among all humans that results in strong similarities between languages. I personally find this new framework very elegant and well substantiated. The study we conducted with the Himba people, I hope, adds an interesting nuance to this hypothesis. In this study, we do not seek to challenge the previous claims but only suggest that perceptual structure could also drive differences in color lexicons. Indeed, since all populations do not necessarily perceive colors in the exact same way, there may be group-level differences in the perceptual space that could potentially influence color vocabularies. Of course, we acknowledge the need to gather more data from various populations and explore in greater details the biological processes underlying these differences.

DISCUSSION

These two fieldworks brought the most significant scientific surprise of my Ph.D. In our first fieldwork, we employed two widely recognized tasks for assessing color perception, as well as several other tasks aiming at measuring general cognitive ability (i.e., a broad underlying factor that impacts overall performance across a range of tasks, encompassing processing speed, working memory, and problem-solving ability; Demetriou et al., 2002; Rypma et al., 2006; the tasks include, in our case, a numerical ability task and an adaptation of the WAIS matrices task)¹⁸ used in the project for other research questions. Although I did not initially intend to correlate the performance at the color perception tasks and the non-verbal intelligence tasks, as such tests did not respond to any prior hypothesis, I nevertheless eventually performed such tests for (exploratory) control purposes. Surprisingly, the analyses produced remarkably strong correlations between general cognitive ability and performance at the perceptual tasks. This unexpected finding made me wonder to what extent the perceptual tests we employ are affected by the confounding factor of general cognitive ability. While this might not be a significant concern within a population where access to education is widespread, addressing this question becomes crucial when examining cross-cultural differences, as countries can differ massively in terms of school exposure. Thus, an effect showing a difference in perception might reflect a difference in exposure to schooling. Consequently, education might be a crucial factor impacting participants' performance in a specific task, and further investigation is essential to ascertain whether a particular task is suitable for cross-cultural application. This experience has underscored the importance of applying caution and skepticism when approaching seemingly "well-established" and "validated" experiments.

We made substantial efforts to address the issue of a correlation between cognitive ability and performance at color perceptual tasks. However, one may wonder how many cross-cultural studies and conclusions are somewhat polluted by a lack of control of this parameter. For example, several studies highlight that color perception abilities are lower in teenagers compared to young adults, reaching an optimum around 20 years of age (the curve of color perception performance across ages would follow a U-shape; Bosten, 2022; Kinnear & Sahraie, 2002). However, because our results and previous findings (Cranwell et al., 2015, who refer to the non-verbal intelligence with the Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence task; Wechsler, 1999) strongly suggest an

¹⁸ General cognitive ability is largely influenced by schooling (Peng & Kievit, 2020); thus, this measure was only used in the Himba group only.

DISCUSSION

association between non-verbal intelligence and performance at several color perception tests, I am now inclined towards the view that teenagers might perceive colors as effectively as young adults do, and their comparatively lower performance may in fact stem from differences in general cognitive ability. Naturally, one could wonder whether sensory discrimination is linked to intelligence: I will not engage in this debate here, but arguments can be presented to support both sides (R. B. Evans & Deary, 1994; Jensen, 2006; Melnick et al., 2013; Sheppard & Vernon, 2008).

This provides me the opportunity to reiterate that our intent *never* was to contrast high-level cognition across French and Himba populations. The sole purpose of measuring general cognitive ability was to examine inter-individual variations *within* the Himba group itself, to assess whether these measures correlated with performance at color perception tasks. Also, it is important to highlight that the differences in color perception are *very* subtle and concern only the discrimination of very similar red and blue colors (even though it is plausible to imagine that such decreases in color discrimination could potentially extend to other colors like yellow or green). Furthermore, it is worth noting that the incidence of genetic red-green color perception abnormalities among Himba people was notably low (approximately 1% of the males). In this respect, at the group level, Himba individuals are comparatively better color perceivers than their French counterparts, among whom this rate approaches 8% of the males. Moreover, a hypothesis suggests that these two broad categories of atypical color perception may interact with each other (Brown & Lindsey, 2004; Josserand, Meeussen, et al., 2021). This hypothesis states that if someone already experiences lens brunescence, having in addition a red-green abnormal color perception could severely impair their ability to perceive color, which could potentially impact their survival. Thus, there might exist a stronger selective pressure against the genetic alleles responsible for red-green color abnormalities in populations exposed to high levels of UV-B radiation. In the second part of Chapter 1, we investigated this hypothesis and initially found a negative correlation between UV exposure and the prevalence of red-green color deficiency in males. However, the findings from Chapter 2, indicating similar color perception among young French and young Himba participants, prompt a reevaluation of this hypothesis. While the initial evolutionary perspective suggested an impact on offspring-raising abilities, most non-industrialized human cultures generate offspring before the age of 25 (Allal et al., 2004; K. Hill & Hurtado, 1996), at which point the effects of lens brunescence are less pronounced. Furthermore, there is no scientific evidence that achromatopsia, which is the total inability to distinguish colours, could lead to an

evolutionary disadvantage. Thus, at a personal level, my belief in this hypothesis is quite low.

The U-shape pattern of color perception between different age groups also brings up intriguing questions about *who* drives language change. In fact, both the lens brunescence hypothesis and the outcomes of our natural experimental study indicate that young adults have similar color perception abilities regardless of whether they reside in areas with high or low UV incidence. This could suggest that languages primarily adapt to older adults, which also relates to the study of Blasi et al. (2019). While humans generally start out with overbite and overjet bite configuration (the typical “agriculturalist” bite configuration; see Illustration 5 in the Introduction), chewing hard food gave rise to an edge-to-edge bite after adolescence (the typical “hunter-gatherer” bite configuration). The persistence of overbite and overjet configurations into adulthood was closely associated with the increased prevalence of softer diets, which became more common as agriculture and food processing advanced. Blasi et al. (2019) showed that the edge-to-edge bite configuration makes the production of labiodentals sounds slightly more challenging, which may explain why hunter-gatherers often lack labiodentals in their sound systems. As it is particularly older people in hunter-gatherer groups that are affected by teeth erosion - thus imposing a negative pressure on using labiodentals - this study also suggests that language may primarily adapt to older adults.

A BIASED MINORITY CAN INFLUENCE THE LANGUAGE OF A GROUP

A notable proportion of the Himba population showed a decrease in color perception. However, precisely quantifying this percentage proves challenging, given the gradual nature of this age-related process. Additionally, even within the same population and within the same age group, large individual differences in color perception remain. These findings give rise to important questions: Is there a distinct threshold beyond which language fails to adapt to the biases of a part of the population, or does this process occur incrementally? What proportion of biased participants is necessary to impact the group's language, how strong must their bias be, where should they be strategically positioned within the network, and how long should they interact? The study of the influence of color perception on color lexicons prompted these questions and set the stage for the second part of this Ph.D. dissertation. Similarly to Motamedi et al. (2022),

DISCUSSION

this second part aimed to address these questions through the use of two types of approaches: agent-based modeling and laboratory experiments.

Before introducing the results, I will give a brief reminder in terminology (see Illustration 19 below). We will refer to *agents* in the modeling study, *participants* in the experimental study, and *individuals* when combining outputs from both types of methods. In both the modeling and the experimental work, individual differences were present *before* communication. In the modeling study, this is represented as the prior belief of biased agents toward a specific language form. In the experimental study, this is denoted by the incapacity of one biased participant to use some letters on the keyboard. This first layer of inter-individual variation is what we mean when we talk about “the effect of *individual differences* on language”. In this context, “*heterogenous* population” refers to populations combining both biased and unbiased individuals. We aimed to study whether these individual differences affect *language*. When referring to language, we are alluding to various attributes, such as its *value*, but also its *variability*. Indeed, in both types of study, the language adopted by the entire population can exhibit varying degrees of variation, regardless of whether individual differences were introduced or not. Thus, individuals might employ different language forms for the same concept, or on the contrary, they might unanimously adopt the same language form. This second layer of variation is referred to in statements like “introducing heterogeneity affects *variation in language*”.

Illustration 19: Visual representation of the terminology. Green individuals are unbiased, while blue individuals are biased.

What have these methods, *together*, taught us about language evolution?

The key message from this part is the following: weakly biased individuals, even when present in a small minority of the population, *can* influence the language

DISCUSSION

of the entire community, rather than being overshadowed by the majority. This finding is supported by the results of the modeling and, to a lesser degree, the laboratory experiment. This conclusion might seem counterintuitive, as we commonly assume that the majority prevails, and a minority of individuals with distinctive speech traits may be perceived as “outliers” and disregarded. However, this conclusion is *not* as straightforward as saying: “The language of the entire population will conform and adopt the biases of the minority.” Instead, the language of the whole population adapts to the minority *only to a certain extent*, related to the number of biased agents and the strength of their bias. For example, in the laboratory experiment, biased letters were not entirely removed from the final vocabulary; rather, they were just less frequently present on average. This is consistent with the finding of Jameson & Komarova (2009a, 2009b), who showed that introducing agents with genetically abnormal red-green color perception affects the location of the boundaries of color categories, but does not systematically affect the number of color terms.

Additionally, heterogeneous populations witness more variability in the final language than their homogenous counterparts. This is particularly the case if the biased individuals have a higher eigenvector centrality (how well-connected and important an individual is based on the importance of their neighbors) or closeness centrality (how easily an individual can reach others). Our experimental approach added an interesting twist to this finding: even unbiased participants present high levels of language variation when interacting with other unbiased participants. This could be interpreted as if the introduction of heterogeneity injects an element of confusion throughout the entire group, prompting the emergence of new labels. Thus, we propose that the presence of individual differences plays a pivotal role in the emergence of linguistic innovations, contributing to cross-linguistic diversity.

These results also highlight the role of the belief in an initial “established” language, which affects both language value and variability. In the modeling work, this initial language is represented as a preference at birth to favor one language variant over another. In the experimental work, this manifests as the initial labels that participants can recall to varying degrees. In both cases, individuals can start communicating with a preconceived notion about how language is. We found that the stronger the belief in an initial language, the less the language of the group adapts to the biases of the minority, and the lower the inter- and intra-individual variability in the final language. What may this initial “established” language refer to in the real world? In the previous chapters, we suggest that the existence of linguistic policies might create such a bias. Indeed,

these linguistic regulations often aim to establish an objective standard for language structure and may dictate rules for language construction or writing. While national institutions like l'Académie Française provide good illustrations of this, explicit language ideologies also exist in spoken languages (Pakendorf et al., 2021). Nevertheless, we must approach these comparisons with caution.

What has the *experimental* approach taught us about our question?

Before further discussing the experimental findings, I would like to make a small parenthesis to briefly contextualize this Chapter within my Ph.D. journey. Originally, this experimental part was intended to be conducted during a year-long research exchange at the Center for Language Evolution in Edinburgh. Regrettably, this exchange was canceled due to the COVID crisis (compounded by Brexit-related factors). It is worth noting that almost two out of my three years of Ph.D. were impacted by the COVID pandemic, which led to many missed opportunities, and also an emphasis on the modeling work. It was not until the beginning of my final year, after having the chance to meet with Limor Raviv, that the possibility of carrying out this experimental part emerged. I must also mention that during the 3-month exchange at the Max Planck Institute, my goal was to test eight groups in each condition. Surprisingly, assembling groups of four participants in the lab turned out to be considerably more challenging than initially anticipated. Although Limor Raviv has dedicated a substantial portion of her Ph.D. dissertation (Raviv, 2020) to discussing how challenging it is to organize these group experiments, I could only comprehend the extent of these challenges when being directly engaged in the process.

In addition to the results discussed earlier, the experimental approach has also allowed us to explore the individual dynamics of adaptation. We discovered that even if a participant's internal language is not originally tailored to align with that of the biased participant (for instance, if this participant believes the correct word for a shape is 'kesip'), this participant still tends to modify their language when engaging in face-to-face communication with the biased participant (and use a word like 'esip', that does not contain any biased letters, exclusively when speaking with this biased participant). This relates to previous theories about linguistic alignment. There is considerable evidence indicating that individuals tend to unconsciously adjust their language during face-to-face communication on a various range of linguistic characteristics (Branigan et al., 2000; Brennan & Clark, 1996; Chartrand & Bargh, 1999; Giles et al., 1991; Pardo, 2006).

DISCUSSION

Our results revealed that some participants do indeed align more with their conversation partners than others. However, this tendency is not predicted by any of the factors we considered, including prosociality, gender, age, working memory, and cognitive flexibility. There are several explanations for this pattern. Firstly, it is plausible that this outcome is genuinely accurate, and these factors indeed do *not* impact the propensity for linguistic alignment. For example, it is conceivable (and hopeful) that in today's world, especially in the Netherlands, gender differences have become minimal. Alternatively, it is possible that the variables and tests we chose are not appropriate, and using different measures (such as other prosociality indicators) might have led to the emergence of an effect. Notably, we lacked measures of prestige, which could have been a useful indicator of participants' adaptability. Finally, another possibility is that our participants were too homogeneous in their personal characteristics, thus not capturing enough variation. For instance, our sample had few men, few older participants, and most participants shared similar prosociality scores. However, we should remember that this experiment was not initially designed to investigate social biases in linguistic alignment; its primary aim was to observe how language adapts to a minority. Delving deeper into the impact of gender and age biases in pair interactions is actually the central focus of Lewis Cheung's Ph.D. at the Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics (Nijmegen, the Netherlands). Consequently, it is likely that new insights into this question will emerge shortly after my own Ph.D. concludes.

What has the *modeling* work taught us about our question?

The modeling work allowed us to span a wide range of values for the bias strength and the proportion of biased individuals. Our results suggest that the relationship between bias strength and the percentage of biased agents is not linear, which results in an over-representation of the biased agents in the language of the population. This resonates with the work of Navarro et al. (2018), who propose a disproportionate impact of the biased agents, namely the ones with the strongest *a-priori* beliefs. Furthermore, as we explored different levels of bias strength, we found that all agents (both biased and unbiased) tend to adapt, and eventually converge toward a middle ground in their language¹⁹. However, an intriguing nuance emerges from this conclusion. In scale-free networks (and to a lesser extent, small-world networks), the biased agents still

¹⁹ Of course, this occurs if biased agents do not have a bias that totally restrains them from completely producing a language variant.

DISCUSSION

retain a trace of their bias in their language even after repeated interactions with unbiased agents. This means that while some network structures can “erase” the differences that some agents had at birth, others preserve these individual differences.

Additionally, modeling work enabled us to explore language evolution at the scale of a whole population, encompassing the relationship between structural communities (who is connected to whom) and linguistic communities (who shares a similar language with whom; see Illustration 20). Our work suggests that linguistic communities are more likely to emerge in networks containing structural communities, such as scale-free networks. Also, we found that introducing biased agents within a group fosters the emergence of linguistic communities. We believe that this phenomenon is due to the presence of (by chance) several biased agents within the same structural community, while other structural communities may lack biased agents. Thus, structural communities housing multiple biased individuals may amplify the bias of these agents. In reality, biases may not be uniformly dispersed within a population; they rather follow a structured distribution linked to factors such as human genetics (Dediu and Ladd, 2007; Wong et al., 2020), feeding precisely into this amplification process.

Illustration 20: An illustration of the difference between structural and linguistic communities. Dots represent individuals, and the color represents their internal language value (for example, blue can be ‘soda’, green can be ‘pop’, and turquoise can refer to people using both ‘pop’ and ‘soda’). Panel **A** shows two structural communities and two linguistic communities. Panel **B** shows two structural communities but no linguistic communities. Panel **C** shows no structural communities but two linguistic communities. Panel **D** shows no structural communities and no linguistic communities.

Originally, I did not intend to conduct two modeling studies. However, a few unexpected results emerged from our initial modeling study. Particularly, we found that the influence of the “top influencers” (those agents with higher centrality) on the overall language of the population was *not* very pronounced,

DISCUSSION

except in specific network types. This unexpected finding, along with the unexplained differences between our network structures, motivated us to undertake a second modeling study. This second study focused on the internal metrics of the global network structure rather than just exploring predefined network types, such as random, small-world, or scale-free. To start, we investigated what specific metrics in network structure contribute to the presence of language variation. In this first part, we did not introduce any individual differences, and populations are homogeneous. Subsequently, we introduced individual differences (similarly to the first modeling study), but this time, we explored various local metrics for defining centrality, in order to shed light on where biased individuals should be positioned within a network to effectively affect language.

We found that network structure has an effect on inter, but not intra-individual language variability. While previous literature has highlighted population size and density as key network structure factors that influence language, our findings suggest that these measures serve as proxies for the “real” drivers of language variability, namely path length and clustering coefficient. Networks where there are on average many intermediary people between two individuals (high path length) are likely to witness high language variability. While larger networks usually have longer path lengths, our findings show that as a population grows, it does not necessarily lead to more language variation, as long as information spreads efficiently. On the other hand, the clustering coefficient measures how often the friends of a specific person within a group are also friends with each other. Assuming the same mean amount of connection per individual, networks with high clustering coefficients often consist of several smaller structural communities, which lead to higher language variation.

GENERAL CONCLUSION

The conclusions of this work align with the research directions pursued by my main supervisor, suggesting that languages adapt in response to anatomical or physiological changes acquired by speakers in different populations. Our study contributes to this body of literature by demonstrating that external pressures can influence not only sound systems, but also semantics. Thus, differences in UV incidence may lead to differences in the perceptual color space, which then may cause differences in color lexicons. While variations in color perception exhibit distinct patterns among different groups, we also identified substantial

DISCUSSION

individual differences within a single population, which prompted our interest in understanding how language adapts to these individual variations. Our findings propose that languages adapt, at least to some degree, to the idiosyncrasies of their speakers, even when their biases are only present in the minority within the population. They also suggest that network structure may affect the extent to which a language will adapt to the bias of its speakers. More generally, our results suggest that language evolution stems from intricate processes influenced by a myriad of interacting variables, and that variation in languages can only be understood in the context of their cultural, biological, and physical environments.

Moreover, I hope that this Ph.D. thesis can serve as an illustrative example of employing multiple methods to explore the evolution of language. The use of various methods enabled us to explore the limits of our hypotheses and determine whether their results remained consistent across different approaches. For instance, the natural experiment in the first part allowed us to recognize that the influence of UV incidence might affect all colors, and could also be related to other age-related physiological effects than the lens brunescence. Similarly, the combination of experimental work and modeling provided a dual perspective on the same research questions, for which the conclusions, fortunately, did converge. Combining these methods also helped overcome certain limitations that each approach might have individually. Indeed, we have to emphasize that each of our studies combines multiple limitations, inherent to the type of method used (see the “Methods” section in the Introduction) or to the analysis performed. For example, in our data analysis, we simplified populations and languages into geographic dots, while populations usually inhabit (possibly) large areas. Furthermore, our measures of cultural complexity might not fully capture the nuances of exposure to advanced dyeing techniques and colored artifacts. Also, the conclusions drawn from natural experiments are influenced by various confounded factors between the two populations, making it challenging to disentangle the exact source of the observed differences in color perception. Technical differences in experimental setups between the two populations also impact these findings. In the laboratory experiment, our conclusions are based on a limited number of groups containing a limited number of participants. The modeling work also has its own limitations, with some researchers questioning how accurately Bayesian models (or agent-based models more generally) reflect real-world processes. Also, the models we used rely on theoretical assumptions and have a static connectivity (i.e., the connections between agents are fixed and do not change with time). Thus, it is

DISCUSSION

important to exercise caution when applying our findings to real-world language networks.

There are avenues of exploration that will be pursued in the near future. Zaslavsky et al. (2018) built a model for the evolution of color terms, showing that all languages tend to optimize the trade-off between the complexity and accuracy of the lexicon. While a shared perceptual structure between all humans would explain why languages categorize colors similarly, variations in communication needs would account for the wide range of color terms used, thus “pushing” populations along the optimal trade-off (Zaslavsky et al., 2022). So far, this model assumes that we all share a universal perceptual system. However, Chapter 2 revealed inter-group and inter-individual differences in color perception, and also helped gain insights into the approximate extent of these differences, quantifying them in terms of units within the CIELAB color space. Consequently, a promising avenue for future investigation involves using the model of color terms’ evolution (Zaslavsky et al., 2018) and distorting the perceptual space into two distinct conditions – one for the French population and another for the Himba – to study how such distortions influence patterns of color naming. While the exact details remains to be discussed, a model akin to the one employed by Chaabouni et al. (2021) might offer valuable insights, and serve as a meaningful extension of the work already done in part 1. Another quite straightforward improvement to the existing research planned for the near future involves the inclusion of additional groups in the experiment of Chapter 3.

Naturally, there are several other potential paths for future exploration. First, it would be interesting to perform color perception tests with other populations, as well as using other color stimuli, and investigate in more detail the biological effects of UV incidence on color perception. In the laboratory experiment, an avenue for exploration involves examining how network structure and the presence of a biased individual interact. This can be achieved by strategically placing the biased person in either a central or peripheral position within the network, which would allow us to better understand how a minority’s bias might propagate in various types of network structures. Also, the results from the laboratory experiment suggest that building hierarchical models (such as the one of Hawkins et al., 2023) would be relevant to studying language evolution within heterogeneous populations.

Additionally, there is a project that I had hoped to undertake during my Ph.D. research but was constrained by both time and financial limitations. This project would have been an ideal link between the first and second parts of my research.

DISCUSSION

It involves a combination of a natural experiment and a laboratory experiment, centered around the population residing on Pingelap Island (see Illustration 21).

Illustration 21: Pingelap island, in the Federate States of Micronesia. Photograph by PJF Military Collection / Alamy Stock Photo, from National Geographic.

In the late 18th century, a catastrophic typhoon struck Pingelap Island, leading to a famine that drastically diminished the population (Morton et al., 1971). The island's chief at the time possessed a rare genetic trait called *achromatopsia*, a condition characterized by total color blindness, and thus could only see the world in terms of shades of grey. As the population suddenly decreased, the genetic mutation responsible for achromatopsia became more prevalent due to the limited genetic diversity among the survivors (Morton et al., 1972). As a result, a significant portion of Pingelap's inhabitants inherited this condition, leading to an unusually high prevalence of this type of color blindness (between 5 and 10% of the population; Hussels & Morton, 1972). This situation presents a fascinating opportunity for investigating the interplay between color perception and color naming, along with the impact of a minority on the language of the majority. I would particularly like to document the color vocabulary of individuals with both typical and atypical color perception. Additionally, studying interactions between those with typical and atypical color perception could provide valuable insights into language evolution and adaptation. While Hussels & Morton (1972) suggest that achromatopsia interferes with activities in bright sunlight (such as fishing and picking breadfruit), work in the taro pit and at home is much less impaired. Also, it has even been proposed that achromatopsia, while preventing to see any colors, might enhance sensitivity to variations in light and shade, potentially leading to more effective fishing during dawn (De Wilde, 2017), but this suggestion has not been scientifically investigated yet (to my knowledge).

DISCUSSION

Thus, delving into this aspect could have formed an intriguing supplementary hypothesis.

Therefore, it appears that after the completion of this Ph.D., I still do not have ready-made answers for the existence of over 8,000 languages spoken on Earth today. Instead, this work has left me with more than 8,000 questions! For instance, an important hypothesis of this Ph.D. dissertation – the lens brunescence hypothesis – remains, I believe, subject to debate. Nonetheless, the research presented in this dissertation provided additional supporting arguments that, I hope, encourage its consideration as a plausible hypothesis. Moreover, digging into individual differences is a work that likely extends beyond a lifetime, given the multitude of facets within this complex issue, and I feel as if I have only dipped my toe into an ocean of questions. However, I am hopeful that this Ph.D. had “*apporter sa pierre à l’édifice*”, in other words, has added a small contribution to the field of language evolution, by shedding light on how physiological variations impact languages and how inter-individual differences play a role in shaping language evolution.

References

- Abitbol, J. L., Karsai, M., Magué, J.-P., Chevrot, J.-P., & Fleury, E. (2018). Socioeconomic Dependencies of Linguistic Patterns in Twitter: A Multivariate Analysis. *Proceedings of the 2018 World Wide Web Conference on World Wide Web*, 1125-1134. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3178876.3186011>
- Acerbi, A., Mesoudi, A., & Smolla, M. (2020). *Individual-based models of cultural evolution. A step-by-step guide using R*. [Preprint]. Open Science Framework. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/32v6a>
- Adam, A. (1969). A further query on color blindness and natural selection. *Social Biology*, 16(3), 197-202. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19485565.1969.9987819>
- Albert, R. (2005). Scale-free networks in cell biology. *Journal of Cell Science*, 118(21), 4947. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jcs.02714>
- Albert, R., Jeong, H., & Barabási, A.-L. (1999). Diameter of the World-Wide Web. *Nature*, 401(6749), 130–131. <https://doi.org/10.1038/43601>
- Allal, N., Sear, R., Prentice, A. M., & Mace, R. (2004). An evolutionary model of stature, age at first birth and reproductive success in Gambian women. *Proceedings. Biological Sciences*, 271(1538), 465-470. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2003.2623>
- Allen, J. S., Miller, J. L., & DeSteno, D. (2003). Individual talker differences in voice-onset-time. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 113(1), 544-552. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.1528172>
- Anselme, R. (2022). *La représentation du trill en typologie : De l'acoustique à l'inventaire phonémique* [PhD Thesis]. Université Lumière - Lyon II.
- Anselme, R., Pellegrino, F., & Dediu, D. (2023). What's in the r? A review of the usage of the r symbol in the Illustrations of the IPA. *Journal of the International Phonetic Association*, 1-30. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0025100322000238>
- Baddeley, A., Rubak, E., & Turner, R. (2016). *Spatial point patterns : Methodology and applications with R*. CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Baker, A., Archangeli, D., & Mielke, J. (2011). Variability in American English s-retraction suggests a solution to the actuation problem. *Language Variation and Change*, 23(3), 3. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0954394511000135>

REFERENCES

- Bamshad, M. J., Wooding, S., Watkins, W. S., Ostler, C. T., Batzer, M. A., & Jorde, L. B. (2003). Human Population Genetic Structure and Inference of Group Membership. *American Journal of Human Genetics*, *72*, 578–589.
- Barabási, A.-L., Albert, R., & Jeong, H. (2000). Scale-free characteristics of random networks: The topology of the world-wide web. *Physica A: Statistical Mechanics and Its Applications*, *281*(1), 1. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4371\(00\)00018-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4371(00)00018-2)
- Barbur, J. L., & Rodriguez-Carmona, M. (2015). Color vision changes in normal aging. In A. J. Elliot, A. Franklin, & M. D. Fairchild (Éds.), *Handbook of Color Psychology* (p. 180-196). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107337930.009>
- Bates, D., Mächler, M., Bolker, B., & Walker, S. (2015). Fitting Linear Mixed-Effects Models Using lme4. *Journal of Statistical Software*, *67*(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v067.i01>
- Baxter, G. J., Blythe, R. A., & McKane, A. J. (2008). Fixation and Consensus Times on a Network: A Unified Approach. *Physical Review Letters*, *101*(25), 258701. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.101.258701>
- Beckner, C., Ellis, N. C., Blythe, R., Holland, J., Bybee, J., Ke, J., Christiansen, M. H., Larsen-Freeman, D., Croft, W., & Schoenemann, T. (2009). Language is a complex adaptive system: Position paper. *Language Learning*, *59*(Suppl 1), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9922.2009.00533.x>
- Beirne, R. O., McIlreavy, L., & Zlatkova, M. B. (2008). The effect of age-related lens yellowing on Farnsworth-Munsell 100 hue error score. *Ophthalmic and Physiological Optics*, *28*(5), 448-456. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-1313.2008.00593.x>
- Bentz, C., Dediu, D., Verkerk, A., & Jäger, G. (2018). The evolution of language families is shaped by the environment beyond neutral drift. *Nature Human Behaviour*, *2*(11), 11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-018-0457-6>
- Berlin, B., & Kay, P. (1969). *Basic Color Terms, Their Universality and Evolution*. California University Press.
- Bickel, B., Nichols, J., Zakharko, T., Witzlack-Makarevich, A., Hildebrandt, K., Rießler, M., Bierkandt, L., Zúñiga, F., & Lowe, J. B. (2017). *The AUTOTYP typological databases (Version 0.1.0)*. <https://github.com/autotyp/autotyp-data/tree/0.1.0>
- Bilous, F. R., & Krauss, R. M. (1988). Dominance and accommodation in the conversational behaviours of same- and mixed-gender dyads. *Language & Communication*, *8*(3), 183-194. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0271-5309\(88\)90016-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0271-5309(88)90016-X)
- Bimler, D. L., Kirkland, J., & Jameson, K. A. (2004). Quantifying variations in personal color spaces: Are there sex differences in color vision? *Color*

REFERENCES

- Research & Application*, 29(2), 128-134.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/col.10232>
- Birch, J. (2012). Worldwide prevalence of red-green color deficiency. *Journal of the Optical Society of America. A, Optics, Image Science, and Vision*, 29(3), 313-320. <https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSAA.29.000313>
- Blasi, D. E., Moran, S., Moisik, S. R., Widmer, P., Dediu, D., & Bickel, B. (2019). Human sound systems are shaped by post-Neolithic changes in bite configuration. *Science*, 363(6432). <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aav3218>
- Blondel, V. D., Guillaume, J.-L., Lambiotte, R., & Lefebvre, E. (2008). Fast unfolding of communities in large networks. *Journal of Statistical Mechanics: Theory and Experiment*, 2008(10), P10008. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-5468/2008/10/P10008>
- Bloomfield, L. (1933). *Language* (Holt, New York).
- Blythe, R. A. (2015). Colloquium : Hierarchy of scales in language dynamics. *The European Physical Journal B*, 88(11), 11. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjb/e2015-60347-3>
- Blythe, R. A., & Croft, W. (2012). S-curves and the mechanisms of propagation in language change. *Language*, 88(2), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1353/lan.2012.0027>
- Boas, F. (1940). *Race, Language, and Culture*. University of Chicago Press.
- Böckler, A., Tusche, A., & Singer, T. (2016). The Structure of Human Prosociality : Differentiating Altruistically Motivated, Norm Motivated, Strategically Motivated, and Self-Reported Prosocial Behavior. *Social Psychological and Personality Science*, 7(6), 530-541. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1948550616639650>
- Borel, P., de Edelenyi, F. S., Vincent-Baudry, S., Malezet-Desmoulin, C., Margotat, A., Lyan, B., Gorrard, J.-M., Meunier, N., Drouault-Holowacz, S., & Bieuvelet, S. (2011). Genetic variants in BCMO1 and CD36 are associated with plasma lutein concentrations and macular pigment optical density in humans. *Annals of Medicine*, 43(1), 47-59. <https://doi.org/10.3109/07853890.2010.531757>
- Bornstein, M. H. (1973). Color vision and color naming : A psychophysiological hypothesis of cultural difference. *Psychological Bulletin*, 80(4), 257–285.
- Bortfeld, H., & Brennan, S. E. (1997). Use and acquisition of idiomatic expressions in referring by native and non-native speakers. *Discourse Processes*, 23(2), 119-147. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01638537709544986>
- Bosten, J. M. (2022). Do You See What I See? Diversity in Human Color Perception. *Annual Review of Vision Science*, 8, 101-133. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-vision-093020-112820>
- Bowern, C., & Evans, B. (2014). *The Routledge Handbook of Historical Linguistics*. Routledge.

REFERENCES

- Branigan, H. P., Pickering, M. J., & Cleland, A. A. (2000). Syntactic co-ordination in dialogue. *Cognition*, 75(2), B13-B25. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-0277\(99\)00081-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-0277(99)00081-5)
- Branigan, H. P., Pickering, M. J., Pearson, J., & McLean, J. F. (2010). Linguistic alignment between people and computers. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 42(9), 2355-2368. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pragma.2009.12.012>
- Brennan, S. E., & Clark, H. H. (1996). Conceptual pacts and lexical choice in conversation. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory, and Cognition*, 22(6), 1482-1493. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0278-7393.22.6.1482>
- Bright, W. (2017). Social Factors in Language Change. In F. Coulmas (Éd.), *The Handbook of Sociolinguistics* (p. 81-91). Blackwell Publishing Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781405166256.ch5>
- Brown, A. M., & Lindsey, D. T. (2004). Color and language: Worldwide distribution of Daltonism and distinct words for "blue". *Visual Neuroscience*, 21(3), 409-412. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0952523804213098>
- Bürkner, P.-C. (2018). Advanced Bayesian Multilevel Modeling with the R Package brms. *The R Journal*, 10(1), 395. <https://doi.org/10.32614/RJ-2018-017>
- Butcher, A. (2006). Australian aboriginal languages: Consonant-Salient Phonologies and the « Place-of-Articulation Imperative ». In J. Harrington & M. Tabain (Éds.), *Speech Production: Models, Phonetic Processes, and Techniques* (p. 187-210). Psychology Press: NY.
- Butcher, A. R. (2018). The special nature of Australian phonologies: Why auditory constraints on human language sound systems are not universal. *Proceedings of Meetings on Acoustics*, 35(1), 060004. <https://doi.org/10.1121/2.0001004>
- Byrd, D. (1992). Preliminary results on speaker-dependent variation in the TIMIT database. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 92(1), 593-596. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.404271>
- Campbell, L. (1998). *Historical Linguistics: An Introduction*. MIT Press.
- Caprara, G. V., Alessandri, G., & Eisenberg, N. (2012). Prosociality: The contribution of traits, values, and self-efficacy beliefs. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 102(6), 1289-1303. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0025626>
- Caprara, G. V., Steca, P., Zelli, A., & Capanna, C. (2005). A new scale for measuring adults' prosocialness. *European Journal of psychological assessment*, 21(2), 77-89.
- Carlo, G., & Randall, B. A. (2002). The Development of a Measure of Prosocial Behaviors for Late Adolescents. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 31(1), 31-44. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1014033032440>

REFERENCES

- Castellano, C., Fortunato, S., & Loreto, V. (2009). Statistical physics of social dynamics. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 81(2), 591-646. <https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.81.591>
- Cavalli-Sforza, L. L., & Feldman, M. W. (1981). *Cultural Transmission and Evolution : A quantitative approach*. Princeton University Press.
- Chaabouni, R., Kharitonov, E., Dupoux, E., & Baroni, M. (2021). Communicating artificial neural networks develop efficient color-naming systems. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(12), e2016569118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2016569118>
- Chambers, J. K. (1995). *Sociolinguistic Theory: Linguistic Variation and Its Social Significance*. Blackwell Publishers.
- Chartrand, T. L., & Bargh, J. A. (1999). The chameleon effect : The perception–behavior link and social interaction. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 76(6), 893-910. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.76.6.893>
- Chirkova, K., & Gong, T. (2014). Simulating vowel chain shift in Xumi. *Lingua*, 152, 65-80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lingua.2014.09.009>
- Chirkova, K., & Gong, T. (2019). Modeling change in contact settings : A case study of phonological convergence. *Language Dynamics and Change*, 9(1), 1-32. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22105832-00802006>
- Christiansen, M. H., & Chater, N. (2008). Language as shaped by the brain. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 31(5), 489-509. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X08004998>
- Clark, H. H. (1996). *Using Language*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511620539>
- Conklin, H. C. (1973). Color Categorization. *American Anthropologist*, 75(4), 931–942. <https://doi.org/10.1525/aa.1973.75.4.02a00010>
- Conway, B. R., Ratnasingam, S., Jara-Ettinger, J., Futrell, R., & Gibson, E. (2020). Communication efficiency of color naming across languages provides a new framework for the evolution of color terms. *Cognition*, 195, 104086. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2019.104086>
- Cools, R. (2015). Neuropsychopharmacology of Cognitive Flexibility. In A. W. Toga (Ed.), *Brain Mapping* (p. 349-353). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-397025-1.00253-0>
- Cooper, B. A., Ward, M., Gowland, C. A., & McIntosh, J. M. (1991). The use of the Lanthony New Color Test in determining the effects of aging on color vision. *Journal of Gerontology*, 46(6), P320-324. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronj/46.6.p320>
- Cortez, P. (2010). Data Mining with Neural Networks and Support Vector Machines Using the R/rminer Tool. In *Advances in data mining : Applications and theoretical aspects : 10th industrial conferences, ICDM 2010, Berlin, Germany, July 12-14, 2010 : Proceedings: Vol. Springer* (p. 572-583). Perner.

REFERENCES

- Coupé, C., Oh, Y., Dediu, D., & Pellegrino, F. (2019). Different languages, similar encoding efficiency: Comparable information rates across the human communicative niche. *Science Advances*, 5(9), eaaw2594. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aaw2594>
- Cranwell, M. B., Pearce, B., Loveridge, C., & Hurlbert, A. C. (2015). Performance on the Farnsworth-Munsell 100-Hue Test Is Significantly Related to Nonverbal IQ. *Investigative Ophthalmology & Visual Science*, 56(5), 3171-3178. <https://doi.org/10.1167/iovs.14-16094>
- Croft, W. (2008). Evolutionary Linguistics. *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 37, 219-234.
- Culbertson, J. (2012). Typological Universals as Reflections of Biased Learning: Evidence from Artificial Language Learning. *Language and Linguistics Compass*, 6(5), 5. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lnc3.338>
- Culbertson, J., & Kirby, S. (2016). Simplicity and Specificity in Language: Domain-General Biases Have Domain-Specific Effects. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.01964>
- Culbertson, J., Smolensky, P., & Legendre, G. (2012). Learning biases predict a word order universal. *Cognition*, 122(3), 306-329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2011.10.017>
- Cysouw, M. (2011). Understanding transition probabilities. *Linguistic Typology*, 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.1515/lity.2011.028>
- Cysouw, M., Dediu, D., & Moran, S. (2012). Comment on "Phonemic Diversity Supports a Serial Founder Effect Model of Language Expansion from Africa". *Science*, 335(6069), 657. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1208841>
- D. W. Kline, & Scialfa, C. T. (1996). Visual and auditory aging. In *Handbook of the psychology of aging* (4 Academic Press Inc., p. 181-203). Birren J.D., Schaie W. (Eds.).
- Dale, R., & Lupyan, G. (2012). Understanding the origins of morphological diversity: The linguistic niche hypothesis. *Advances in Complex Systems*, 15(03n04), 03n04. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0219525911500172>
- Danescu-Niculescu-Mizil, C., Gamon, M., & Dumais, S. (2011). Mark my words!: Linguistic style accommodation in social media. *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on World Wide Web - WWW '11*, 745. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1963405.1963509>
- Davey, P. G., Lievens, C., & Ammono-Monney, S. (2020). Differences in macular pigment optical density across four ethnicities: A comparative study. *Therapeutic Advances in Ophthalmology*, 12, 2515841420924167. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2515841420924167>
- Davidoff, J., Davies, I., & Roberson, D. (1999). Colour categories in a stone-age tribe. *Nature*, 398(6724), 203-204. <https://doi.org/10.1038/18335>

REFERENCES

- Davies, I. R. L., Laws, G., Corbett, G. G., & Jerrett, D. J. (1998). Cross-cultural differences in colour vision : Acquired 'colour-blindness' in Africa. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 25(6), 1153-1162. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869\(98\)00150-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869(98)00150-0)
- De Busser, R. (2015). *The influence of social, cultural, and natural factors on language structure : An overview* (p. 1-28). <https://doi.org/10.1075/clsc.6.01bus>
- De Soete, G. (1984). Ultrametric tree representations of incomplete dissimilarity data. *Journal of Classification*, 1(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01890124>
- De Vos, C. (2011). A signers' village in Bali, Indonesia. *Minpaku Anthropology Newsletter*, 33, 4-5.
- De Wilde, S. (2017). *The island of the colorblind*. KEHRER.
- Deakin, J., Aitken, M., Robbins, T., & Sahakian, B. J. (2004). Risk taking during decision-making in normal volunteers changes with age. *Journal of the International Neuropsychological Society: JINS*, 10(4), 590-598. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1355617704104104>
- Dediu, D. (2008). The role of genetic biases in shaping the correlations between languages and genes. *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, 254(2), 400-407. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtbi.2008.05.028>
- Dediu, D. (2009). Genetic biasing through cultural transmission : Do simple Bayesian models of language evolution generalise? *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, 259(3), 552-561. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtbi.2009.04.004>
- Dediu, D. (2015). *An Introduction to Genetics for Language Scientists : Current Concepts, Methods, and Findings*. Cambridge University Press.
- Dediu, D. (2023). Ultraviolet light affects the color vocabulary : Evidence from 834 languages. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1143283>
- Dediu, D., Cysouw, M., Levinson, S.C., Baronchelli, A., Christiansen, M.H., Croft, W., Evans, N., Garrod, S., Gray, R., Kandler, A., & Lieven, E. (2013). Cultural evolution of language. In Richerson, P.J. & Christiansen, M.H. (Éds.), *Cultural evolution : Society, technology, language, and religion* (Vol. 12, p. 303–332). MIT Press.
- Dediu, D., Janssen, R., & Moisik, S. R. (2017). Language is not isolated from its wider environment : Vocal tract influences on the evolution of speech and language. *Language & Communication*, 54, 9-20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.langcom.2016.10.002>
- Dediu, D., Janssen, R., & Moisik, S. R. (2019). Weak biases emerging from vocal tract anatomy shape the repeated transmission of vowels. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 3, 1107–1115. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-019-0663-x>

REFERENCES

- Dediu, D., & Ladd, D. R. (2007). Linguistic tone is related to the population frequency of the adaptive haplogroups of two brain size genes, ASPM and Microcephalin. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *104*(26), 10944-10949. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0610848104>
- Dediu, D., & Moisik, S. R. (2016). Anatomical Biasing Of Click Learning And Production : An MRI And 3d Palate Imaging Study. In S. G. Roberts, C. Cuskley, L. McCrohon, L. Barceló-Coblijn, O. Fehér, & T. Verhoef (Éds.), *The Evolution of Language : Proceedings of the 11th International Conference (EVOLANGX11)*. Online at <http://evolang.org/neworleans/papers/57.html>.
- Dediu, D., & Moisik, S. R. (2019). Pushes and pulls from below : Anatomical variation, articulation and sound change. *Glossa: A Journal of General Linguistics*, *4*(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.5334/gjgl.646>
- Deeb, S. S. (2005). The molecular basis of variation in human color vision. *Clin Genet*, *67*(5), 5. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1399-0004.2004.00343.x>
- Dekker, P., Gipper, S., & De Boer, B. (s. d.). Mechanisms of change in person markers : Conversational priming versus frequency. *Unpublished manuscript under review*.
- Del Tredici, M., & Fernández, R. (2018). The Road to Success : Assessing the Fate of Linguistic Innovations in Online Communities. *arXiv:1806.05838 [cs]*. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1806.05838>
- Delahunt, P. B., Webster, M. A., Ma, L., & Werner, J. S. (2004). Long-term renormalization of chromatic mechanisms following cataract surgery. *Visual Neuroscience*, *21*(3), 301-307. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0952523804213025>
- Delattre, P., & Freeman, D. C. (1968). A Dialect Study of American R's by X-ray Motion Picture. *Linguistics*, *6*(44), 44. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ling.1968.6.44.29>
- Demetriou, A., Christou, C., Spanoudis, G., & Platsidou, M. (2002). The development of mental processing : Efficiency, working memory, and thinking. *Monographs of the Society for Research in Child Development*, *67*(1), i-viii, 1-155; discussion 156.
- Derex, M., & Boyd, R. (2016). Partial connectivity increases cultural accumulation within groups. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *113*(11), 11. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1518798113>
- Deriziotis, P., & Fisher, S. E. (2013). Neurogenomics of speech and language disorders : The road ahead. *Genome biology*, *14*(4), 204. <https://doi.org/10.1186/gb-2013-14-4-204>
- Devanna, P., Dediu, D., & Vernes, S. C. (2018). The Genetics of Language : From complex genes to complex communication. In S.-A. Rueschemeyer & M. G. Gaskell (Éds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Psycholinguistics* (p. 864-898). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198786825.013.37>

REFERENCES

- Dietz, L., Bickel, S., & Scheffer, T. (2007). Unsupervised Prediction of Citation Influences. *Ghahramani, Zoubin: ICML 2007: proceedings of the Twenty-Fourth International Conference on Machine Learning, ACM*, 233-240 (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1145/1273496.1273526>
- Dinardo, J. (2010). Natural Experiments and Quasi-Natural Experiments. In S. N. Durlauf & L. E. Blume (Éds.), *Microeconometrics* (p. 139-153). Palgrave Macmillan UK. https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230280816_18
- Dunbar, R. (1993). Coevolution of neocortical size, group size and language in humans. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences - BEHAV BRAIN SCI*, 16. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X00032325>
- Dunbar, R. I. M. (1998). The social brain hypothesis. *Evolutionary Anthropology: Issues, News, and Reviews*, 6(5), 178-190. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1520-6505\(1998\)6:5<178::AID-EVAN5>3.0.CO;2-8](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1520-6505(1998)6:5<178::AID-EVAN5>3.0.CO;2-8)
- Duncan, G., Wormstone, I. M., & Davies, P. D. (1997). The aging human lens : Structure, growth, and physiological behaviour. *British Journal of Ophthalmology*, 81(10), 818-823. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjo.81.10.818>
- Dunning, T. (2012). *Natural Experiments in the Social Sciences: A Design-Based Approach*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139084444>
- Easterday, S., Stave, M., Allasonnière-Tang, M., & Seifart, F. (2021). Syllable Complexity and Morphological Synthesis : A Well-Motivated Positive Complexity Correlation Across Subdomains. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 638659. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.638659>
- Eccher, E., Josserand, M., Caparos, S., Boissin, E., Buiatti, M., Piazza, M., & Vallortigara, G. (in-review). *A universal left-to-right bias in number-space mapping across ages and cultures*. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/w2st6>
- Eckert, P. (2000). *Linguistic Variation as a Social Practice.: Vol. Hoboken, NJ: (Blackwell Publishers Inc.)*.
- Ehret, K., Blumenthal-Dramé, A., Bentz, C., & Berdicevskis, A. (2021). Meaning and Measures : Interpreting and Evaluating Complexity Metrics. *Frontiers in Communication*, 6, 640510. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomm.2021.640510>
- Eisenstein, J. (2019). Measuring and Modeling Language Change. *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North*, 9-14. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/N19-5003>
- Eisenstein, J., O'Connor, B., Smith, N. A., & Xing, E. P. (2014). Diffusion of Lexical Change in Social Media. *PLOS ONE*, 9(11), e113114. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0113114>
- Ember, M. (1978). Size of color lexicon : Interaction of cultural and biological factors. *American Anthropologist*, 80(2), 2.
- Erdős, P., & Rényi, A. (1959). On Random Graphs I. *Publicationes Mathematicae (Debrecen)*, 6, 290-297.

REFERENCES

- Evans, N., & Levinson, S. C. (2009). The myth of language universals: Language diversity and its importance for cognitive science. *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 32(5), 5. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X0999094X>
- Evans, R. B., & Deary, I. J. (1994). Sensory discrimination and intelligence: Postmortem or resurrection? *The American Journal of Psychology*, 107(1), 95-115.
- Everett, C. (2013). Evidence for Direct Geographic Influences on Linguistic Sounds: The Case of Ejectives. *PLoS ONE*, 8(6), 6. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0065275>
- Everett, C., Blasi, D. E., & Roberts, S. G. (2015). Climate, vocal folds, and tonal languages: Connecting the physiological and geographic dots. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 201417413. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1417413112>
- Everett, C., Blasi, D. E., & Roberts, S. G. (2016). Language evolution and climate: The case of desiccation and tone. *Journal of Language Evolution*, 1(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jole/lzv004>
- Fagiolo, G., Moneta, A., & Windrum, P. (2007). A Critical Guide to Empirical Validation of Agent-Based Models in Economics: Methodologies, Procedures, and Open Problems. *Computational Economics*, 30(3), 195-226. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10614-007-9104-4>
- Fagyal, Z., Swarup, S., Escobar, A. M., Gasser, L., & Lakkaraju, K. (2010). Centers and peripheries: Network roles in language change. *Lingua*, 120(8), 2061-2079. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lingua.2010.02.001>
- Farnsworth, D. (1957). *The Farnsworth-Munsell 100-Hue Test for the examination of color discrimination*. (Revised 1957. Maryland: Munsell Color Company, Inc.).
- Fehér, O., Ritt, N., & Smith, K. (2019). Asymmetric accommodation during interaction leads to the regularisation of linguistic variants. *Journal of Memory and Language*, 109, 104036. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jml.2019.104036>
- Fehér, O., Wonnacott, E., & Smith, K. (2016). Structural priming in artificial languages and the regularisation of unpredictable variation. *Journal of Memory and Language*, 91, 158-180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jml.2016.06.002>
- Ferdinand, V., & Zuidema, W. (2009). Thomas' theorem meets Bayes' rule: A model of the iterated learning of language. *Proceedings of the 31st Annual Conference of the Cognitive Science Society*, 1786-1791. <http://csjarchive.cogsci.rpi.edu/Proceedings/2009/papers/376/paper376.pdf>
- Fillmore, C. J., Kempler, D., & Wang, W. S.-Y. (2014). *Individual Differences in Language Ability and Language Behavior*. Academic Press.

REFERENCES

- Fitch, W. T. (2008). Glossogeny and phylogeny: Cultural evolution meets genetic evolution. *Trends in Genetics*, 24(8), 373–374. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tig.2008.05.003>
- Fletcher. (1980). *The City University Colour Vision Test (2nd ed.)* (London: Keeler).
- Foulkes, P., & Docherty, G. (2006). The social life of phonetics and phonology. *Journal of Phonetics*, 34(4), 4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wocn.2005.08.002>
- Fox, M. (2008). *Talking Hands: What Sign Language Reveals About the Mind* (Reprint édition). Simon & Schuster.
- Frank, M. C., Everett, D. L., Fedorenko, E., & Gibson, E. (2008). Number as a cognitive technology: Evidence from Pirahã language and cognition. *Cognition*, 108(3), 819–824. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2008.04.007>
- Frank, S., & Smith, K. (2018). *A model of linguistic accommodation leading to language simplification* [Preprint]. PsyArXiv. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/4ynwu>
- Gao, S., & Regier, T. (2022). Culture, communicative need, and the efficiency of semantic categories. *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society*, 44(44). <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/11t7n64g>
- Geiger, L. (1923). *Contributions to the History of the Development of the Human Race*. Theclassics Us. <https://books.google.fr/books?id=rPE3ngEACAAJ>
- Gerow, A., Hu, Y., Boyd-Graber, J., Blei, D. M., & Evans, J. A. (2018). Measuring discursive influence across scholarship. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(13), 3308–3313. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1719792115>
- Gerrish, S. M., & Blei, D. M. (2010). A language-based approach to measuring scholarly impact. *Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on International Conference on Machine Learning*, 375–382.
- Gibson, E., Futrell, R., Jara-Ettinger, J., Mahowald, K., Bergen, L., Ratnasingam, S., Gibson, M., Piantadosi, S. T., & Conway, B. R. (2017). Color naming across languages reflects color use. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(40), 10785–10790. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1619666114>
- Gibson, E., Futrell, R., Piantadosi, S. P., Dautriche, I., Mahowald, K., Bergen, L., & Levy, R. (2019). How Efficiency Shapes Human Language. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 23(5), 389–407. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2019.02.003>
- Gilbert, A. L., Regier, T., Kay, P., & Ivry, R. B. (2006). Whorf hypothesis is supported in the right visual field but not the left. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 103(2), 489–494. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0509868103>

REFERENCES

- Giles, H., Coupland, N., & Coupland, J. (1991). Accommodation theory: Communication, context, and consequence. In *Contexts of accommodation: Developments in applied sociolinguistics* (p. 1-68). Editions de la Maison des Sciences de l'Homme. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511663673.001>
- Gladstone, W. E. (1858). *Studies on Homer and the Homeric Age: Prolegomena. Achaeis or, The Ethnology of the Greek races*. Oxford University Press.
- Gnisci, A. (2005). Sequential strategies of accommodation: A new method in courtroom. *The British Journal of Social Psychology*, 44(Pt 4), 621-643. <https://doi.org/10.1348/014466604X16363>
- Goel, R., Soni, S., Goyal, N., Paparrizos, J., Wallach, H., Diaz, F., & Eisenstein, J. (2016). The Social Dynamics of Language Change in Online Networks. *arXiv:1609.02075 [physics]*. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1609.02075>
- Gold, J. I., & Watanabe, T. (2010). Perceptual learning. *Current biology: CB*, 20(2), 10.1016/j.cub.2009.10.066. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2009.10.066>
- Gong, T., Baronchelli, A., Puglisi, A., & Loreto, V. (2012). Exploring the roles of complex networks in linguistic categorization. *Artificial Life*, 18(1), 107-121. https://doi.org/10.1162/artl_a_00051
- Gong, T., Ke, J., Minett, J. W., & Wang, W. S.-W. (2004). A Computational Framework to Simulate the Co-evolution of Language and Social Structure. *Artificial Life - ALIFE*.
- Gong, T., & Shuai, L. (2013). Computer simulation as a scientific approach in evolutionary linguistics. *Language Sciences*, 40, 12-23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.langsci.2013.04.002>
- Gong, T., Shuai, L., Tamariz, M., & Jäger, G. (2012). Studying Language Change Using Price Equation and Pólya-urn Dynamics. *PLOS ONE*, 7(3), e33171. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0033171>
- Granovetter, M. (1978). Threshold Models of Collective Behavior. *American Journal of Sociology*, 83(6), 6. <https://doi.org/10.1086/226707>
- Grégoire, J., Noel, M., & Van Nieuwenhoven, C. (2001). *Tedi-math, a test for diagnostic assessment of mathematical Disabilities*.
- Griffiths, T. L., & Kalish, M. L. (2007). Language Evolution by Iterated Learning With Bayesian Agents. *Cognitive Science*, 31(3), 441-480. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15326900701326576>
- Griffiths, T. L., Kemp, C., & Tenenbaum, J. B. (2008). Bayesian models of cognition. In *The Cambridge handbook of computational psychology* (p. 59–100). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511816772.006>
- Guo, J., Gabry, J., Goodrich, B., Weber, S., Lee, D., Sakrejda, K., Martin, M., University, T. of C., Sklyar (R/cxxfunplus.R), O., Team (R/pairs.R, T. R. C., R/dynGet.R), Oehlschlaegel-Akiyoshi (R/pairs.R), J., Maddock

REFERENCES

- (gamma.hpp), J., Bristow (gamma.hpp), P., Agrawal (gamma.hpp), N., Kormanyos (gamma.hpp), C., & Steve, B. (2020). *rstan : R Interface to Stan* (2.21.2). <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rstan>
- Hahn, U. (2014). The Bayesian boom : Good thing or bad? *Frontiers in Psychology*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2014.00765>
- Hammarström, H., Bank, S., Forkel, R., & Haspelmath, M. (2018). *Glottolog 3.2*. Max Planck Institute for the Science of Human History. <http://glottolog.org>
- Hammarström, H., Forkel, R., Haspelmath, M., & Bank, S. (2023). *glottolog/glottolog : Glottolog database 4.7* (v4.8). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8131084>
- Hammond, B. R. (2012). The Visual Effects of Intraocular Colored Filters. *Scientifica*, 2012, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.6064/2012/424965>
- Hammond, B. R., & Caruso-Avery, M. (2000). Macular pigment optical density in a Southwestern sample. *Investigative Ophthalmology & Visual Science*, 41(6), 1492-1497.
- Hanulíková, A., Dediu, D., Fang, Z., Bašňáková, J., & Huettig, F. (2012). Individual Differences in the Acquisition of a Complex L2 Phonology : A Training Study. *Language Learning*, 62, 79-109. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9922.2012.00707.x>
- Hardy, J. L., Frederick, C. M., Kay, P., & Werner, J. S. (2005). Color Naming, Lens Aging, and Grue : What the Optics of the Aging Eye Can Teach Us About Color Language. *Psychological Science*, 16(4), 321-327. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0956-7976.2005.01534.x>
- Hardy, J. L., Werner, J. S., Regier, T., Kay, P., & Frederick, C. M. (2023). Sunlight exposure cannot explain “grue” languages. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-28280-1>
- Hausser, J., & Strimmer, K. (2021). *entropy : Estimation of Entropy, Mutual Information and Related Quantities*. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=entropy>
- Hawkins, R. D., Franke, M., Frank, M. C., Goldberg, A. E., Smith, K., Griffiths, T. L., & Goodman, N. D. (2023). From partners to populations : A hierarchical Bayesian account of coordination and convention. *Psychological Review*, 130(4), 977-1016. <https://doi.org/10.1037/rev0000348>
- Hays, D. G., Margolis, E., Naroll, R., & Perkins, D. R. (1972). Color Term Salience. *American Anthropologist*, 74(5), 1107-1121. <https://doi.org/10.1525/aa.1972.74.5.02a00050>
- Heider, E. R. (1972). Probabilities, Sampling, and Ethnographic Method : The Case of Dani Colour Names. *Man*, 7(3), 448. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2800917>

REFERENCES

- Heider, E. R., & Olivier, D. C. (1972). The structure of the color space in naming and memory for two languages. *Cognitive Psychology*, 3(2), 337-354. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0285\(72\)90011-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0285(72)90011-4)
- Henrich, J. (2004). Demography and Cultural Evolution : How Adaptive Cultural Processes can Produce Maladaptive Losses: The Tasmanian Case. *American Antiquity*, 69(2), 2. <https://doi.org/10.2307/4128416>
- Henrich, J., Heine, S. J., & Norenzayan, A. (2010). The weirdest people in the world? *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 33(2-3), 2-3. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X0999152X>
- Hering, E. (1964). *Outlines of a theory of the light sense*. Harvard University Press.
- Hightower, K. R. (1995). The role of the lens epithelium in development of UV cataract. *Current Eye Research*, 14(1), 71-78. <https://doi.org/10.3109/02713689508999916>
- Hill, K., & Hurtado, A. M. (1996). *Ache Life History: The Ecology and Demography of a Foraging People* (1^{re} éd.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351329248>
- Hill, R. A., & Dunbar, R. I. M. (2003). Social network size in humans. *Human Nature (Hawthorne, N.Y.)*, 14(1), 53-72. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12110-003-1016-y>
- Hockett, C. F. (1985). Distinguished Lecture : F. *American Anthropologist*, 87(2), 2. JSTOR.
- Holsinger, K. E., & Weir, B. S. (2009). Genetics in geographically structured populations : Defining, estimating and interpreting F(ST). *Nature Reviews.Genetics*, 10(9), 9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrg2611>
- Honkola, T., Ruokolainen, K., Syrjänen, K. J. J., Leino, U.-P., Tammi, I., Wahlberg, N., & Vesakoski, O. (2018). Evolution within a language : Environmental differences contribute to divergence of dialect groups. *BMC Evolutionary Biology*, 18(1), 132. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12862-018-1238-6>
- Hood, S. M., Mollon, J. D., Purves, L., & Jordan, G. (2006). Color discrimination in carriers of color deficiency. *Vision Research*, 46(18), 2894-2900. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.visres.2006.02.028>
- Hothorn, T., Hornik, K., & Zeileis, A. (2006). Unbiased Recursive Partitioning : A Conditional Inference Framework. *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics*, 15(3), 651-674. <https://doi.org/10.1198/106186006X133933>
- Hothorn, T., & Zeileis, A. (2015). partykit: A Modular Toolkit for Recursive Partytioning in R. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 16, 3905-3909.
- Hua, X., Greenhill, S. J., Cardillo, M., Schneemann, H., & Bromham, L. (2019). The ecological drivers of variation in global language diversity. *Nature Communications*, 10(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-09842-2>

REFERENCES

- Hussels, I. E., & Morton, N. E. (1972). Pingelap and Mokil Atolls : Achromatopsia. *American Journal of Human Genetics*, 24(3), 304-309.
- Jacques, S., & Zelazo, P. D. (2005). Language and the Development of Cognitive Flexibility : Implications for Theory of Mind. In J. W. Astington & J. A. Baird (Éds.), *Why Language Matters for Theory of Mind* (p. 144-162). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195159912.003.0008>
- Jaint, N., Verma, P., Mittal, S., Mittal, S., Singh, A. K., & Munjal, S. (2010). Gender based alteration in color perception. *Indian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology*, 54(4), 366-370.
- Jakobson, R. (1973). *Main trends in the Science of Language* (Harper&Row: New-York, Vol. 4). Routledge. https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S0047404500006230/type/journal_article
- Jameson, K. A., & Komarova, N. L. (2009a). Evolutionary models of color categorization. I. Population categorization systems based on normal and dichromat observers. *J Opt Soc Am A Opt Image Sci Vis*, 26(6), 6.
- Jameson, K. A., & Komarova, N. L. (2009b). Evolutionary models of color categorization. II. Realistic observer models and population heterogeneity. *J Opt Soc Am A Opt Image Sci Vis*, 26(6), 6.
- Jameson, K., & D'Andrade, R. G. (1997). It's not really red, green, yellow, blue : An inquiry into perceptual color space. In C. L. Hardin & L. Maffi (Éds.), *Color Categories in Thought and Language* (1^{re} éd., p. 295-319). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511519819.014>
- Janssen, R. (2018). *Let the agents do the talking : On the influence of vocal tract anatomy on speech during ontogeny and glossogeny* [PhD Thesis]. Radboud University/Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics.
- Jaraisy, M., & Stamp, R. (2022). The Vulnerability of Emerging Sign Languages : (E)merging Sign Languages? *Languages*, 7(1), 49. <https://doi.org/10.3390/languages7010049>
- Javitt, J. C., & Taylor, H. R. (1995). Cataract and latitude. *Documenta Ophthalmologica*, 88(3-4), 307-325. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01203684>
- Jensen, A. R. (2006). *Clocking the mind : Mental chronometer individual differences* (p. xi, 272). Elsevier.
- Johnson, K., Ladefoged, P., & Lindau, M. (1993). Individual differences in vowel production. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 94(2 Pt 1), 701-714. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.406887>
- Jones, E., Gallois, C., Callan, V., & Barker, M. (1999). Strategies of Accommodation : Development of a Coding System for Conversational Interaction. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology*, 18(2), 123-151. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0261927X99018002001>

REFERENCES

- Jones, S., Cotterill, R., Dedney, N., Muir, K., & Joinson, A. (2014). Finding Zelig in Text: A Measure for Normalising Linguistic Accommodation. In *COLING 2014*.
- Joseph, J. E. (2021). Why Does Language Complexity Resist Measurement? *Frontiers in Communication*, 6, 624855. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomm.2021.624855>
- Josserand, M., Allasonnière-Tang, M., Pellegrino, F., & Dediu, D. (2021). Interindividual Variation Refuses to Go Away: A Bayesian Computer Model of Language Change in Communicative Networks. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 626118. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.626118>
- Josserand, M., Allasonnière-Tang, M., Pellegrino, F., Dediu, D., & de Boer, B. (in-review). How network structure shapes languages: Size and density as proxies and not causes. *Cognitive Science*.
- Josserand, M., Meeussen, E., Dediu, D., & Majid, A. (2023). Reply to: Sunlight exposure cannot explain. *Scientific Reports*, 13(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-28281-0>
- Josserand, M., Meeussen, E., Majid, A., & Dediu, D. (2021). Environment and culture shape both the colour lexicon and the genetics of colour perception. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-98550-3>
- Juricevic, I., & Webster, M. A. (2009). Variations in normal color vision. V. Simulations of adaptation to natural color environments. *Visual Neuroscience*, 26(1), 133-145. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0952523808080942>
- Kaimbo Wa Kaimbo, D., Spileers, W., & Missotten, L. (1994). [The Farnsworth-Munsell 100 Hue test in the Bantu population. Preliminary results]. *Journal Francais D'ophtalmologie*, 17(11), 664-667.
- Kaiser, M., & Hilgetag, C. C. (2004). Spatial growth of real-world networks. *Physical Review E*, 69(3), 036103. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.69.036103>
- Kapnola, E. E. (2016). *Individual differences in speech perception: Sources, functions, and consequences of phoneme categorization gradiency* [Doctor of Philosophy, University of Iowa]. <https://doi.org/10.17077/etd.feubmitk>
- Karsai, M., Iñiguez, G., Kikas, R., Kaski, K., & Kertész, J. (2016). Local cascades induced global contagion: How heterogeneous thresholds, exogenous effects, and unconcerned behaviour govern online adoption spreading. *Scientific Reports*, 6, 27178. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep27178>
- Kauhanen, H. (2017). Neutral change 1. *Journal of Linguistics*, 53(2), 327–358. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022226716000141>
- Kay, P. (2009). *The world color survey*. CSLI Publications.

REFERENCES

- Kay, P., & Kempton, W. (1984). What Is the Sapir-Whorf Hypothesis? *American Anthropologist*, 86(1), 65-79. <https://doi.org/10.1525/aa.1984.86.1.02a00050>
- Kay, P., & McDaniell, C. K. (1978). The Linguistic Significance of the Meanings of Basic Color Terms. *Language*, 54(3), 610. <https://doi.org/10.2307/412789>
- Ke, J.-Y., Gong, T., & Wang, W. (2008). Language change in social networks. *Communications in Computational Physics (Cicp)*, v.3, 935-949 (2008), 3.
- Kemp, C., & Regier, T. (2012). Kinship Categories Across Languages Reflect General Communicative Principles. *Science*, 336(6084), 1049-1054. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1218811>
- Kemp, C., Xu, Y., & Regier, T. (2018). Semantic Typology and Efficient Communication. *Annual Review of Linguistics*, 4(1), 109-128. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-linguistics-011817-045406>
- Kenett, Y. N., Levy, O., Kenett, D. Y., Stanley, H. E., Faust, M., & Havlin, S. (2018). Flexibility of thought in high creative individuals represented by percolation analysis. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(5), 5. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1717362115>
- Kerzel, D., & Schönhammer, J. (2013). Salient stimuli capture attention and action. *Attention, Perception, & Psychophysics*, 75(8), 1633-1643. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13414-013-0512-3>
- Kinnear, P. R., & Sahraie, A. (2002). New Farnsworth-Munsell 100 hue test norms of normal observers for each year of age 5-22 and for age decades 30-70. *British Journal of Ophthalmology*, 86(12), 1408-1411. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjo.86.12.1408>
- Kirby, K., Gray, R., Greenhill, S., Jordan, F., Gomes-Ng, S., Bibiko, H.-J., Blasi, D., Botero, C., Bowern, C., Ember, C., Leehr, D., Low, B., Mccarter, J., Divale, W., & Gavin, M. (2016). D-PLACE: A Global Database of Cultural, Linguistic and Environmental Diversity. *PLoS ONE*, 11(7), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0158391>
- Kirby, S., Cornish, H., & Smith, K. (2008). Cumulative cultural evolution in the laboratory: An experimental approach to the origins of structure in human language. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 105(31), 10681-10686. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0707835105>
- Kirby, S., Dowman, M., & Griffiths, T. L. (2007). Innateness and culture in the evolution of language. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104(12), 5241-5245. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0608222104>
- Kirby, S., Griffiths, T., & Smith, K. (2014). Iterated learning and the evolution of language. *Current Opinion in Neurobiology*, 28, 108-114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conb.2014.07.014>

REFERENCES

- Kirby, S., & Hurford, J. R. (2002). The Emergence of Linguistic Structure : An Overview of the Iterated Learning Model. In A. Cangelosi & D. Parisi (Éds.), *Simulating the Evolution of Language* (p. 121-147). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4471-0663-0_6
- Kirchner, R. (1998). *An Effort-Based Approach to Consonant Lenition* [PhD Thesis, UCLA]. <http://roa.rutgers.edu/files/276-0898/roa-276-kirchner-2.pdf>
- Kitsak, M., Gallos, L. K., Havlin, S., Liljeros, F., Muchnik, L., Stanley, H. E., & Makse, H. A. (2010). Identification of influential spreaders in complex networks. *Nature Physics*, 6(11), 11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nphys1746>
- Knoblauch, K., Saunders, F., Kusuda, M., Hynes, R., Podgor, M., Higgins, K. E., & de Monasterio, F. M. (1987). Age and illuminance effects in the Farnsworth-Munsell 100-hue test. *Applied Optics*, 26(8), 1441. <https://doi.org/10.1364/AO.26.001441>
- Knoblauch, K., Vital-Durand, F., & Barbur, J. L. (2001). Variation of chromatic sensitivity across the life span. *Vision Research*, 41(1), 23-36. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0042-6989\(00\)00205-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0042-6989(00)00205-4)
- Kong, E. J., & Edwards, J. (2016). Individual differences in categorical perception of speech : Cue weighting and executive function. *Journal of Phonetics*, 59, 40-57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwocn.2016.08.006>
- Kooti, F., Yang, H., Meeyoung, K., Kaist, C., Gummadi, K. P., & Mason, W. (2012). The Emergence of Conventions in Online Social Networks. *ICWSM 2012 - Proceedings of the 6th International AAAI Conference on Weblogs and Social Media*.
- Kraft, J. M., & Werner, J. S. (1999). Aging and the saturation of colors 2 Scaling of color appearance. *Journal of the Optical Society of America A*, 16(2), 231. <https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSAA.16.000231>
- Krupnik, I., & Müller-Wille, L. (2010). Franz Boas and Inuktitut Terminology for Ice and Snow : From the Emergence of the Field to the "Great Eskimo Vocabulary Hoax". In *SIKU: Knowing Our Ice : Documenting Inuit Sea Ice Knowledge and Use* (p. 377-400). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-8587-0_16
- Kuznetsova, A., Brockhoff, P. B., & Christensen, R. H. B. (2017). lmerTest Package : Tests in Linear Mixed Effects Models. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 82(13), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v082.i13>
- Labov, W. (1966). *The Social Stratification of English in New York City* (2^e éd.). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511618208>
- Labov, W. (1972). *Sociolinguic Patterns* (Blackwell).
- Labov, W. (1975). Sociolinguistic Patterns. *Language*, 51(4), 1008. <https://doi.org/10.2307/412715>
- Labov, W. (1979). Locating the Frontier Between Social and Psychological Factors in Linguistic Variation. In *Individual Differences in Language*

REFERENCES

- Ability and Language Behavior* (p. 327-340). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-255950-1.50025-1>
- Labov, W. (1986). The social origins of sound change. In *Dialect and Language Variation* (p. 524-541). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-051130-3.50044-6>
- Labov, W. (1994). *Principles of Linguistic Change: Vol. 1: Internal Factors* (Oxford, UK: Blackwell).
- Labov, W. (2001). *Principles of linguistic change Vol. 2: Social Factors*. Blackwell.
- Labov, W. (2010). *Principles of Linguistic Change: Cognitive and Cultural Factors*. Wiley-Blackwell. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444327496>
- Ladd, D. R., Roberts, S. G., & Dediu, D. (2015). Correlational Studies in Typological and Historical Linguistics. *Annual Review of Linguistics*, 1(1), 221-241. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-linguist-030514-124819>
- Laeng, B., Brennen, T., Elden, Å., Gaare Paulsen, H., Banerjee, A., & Lipton, R. (2007). Latitude-of-birth and season-of-birth effects on human color vision in the Arctic. *Vision Research*, 47(12), 1595-1607. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.visres.2007.03.011>
- Lapointe, F. J., & Kirsch, J. a. W. (1995). Estimating Phylogenies from Lacunose Distance Matrices, with Special Reference to DNA Hybridization Data. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 12(2), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.molbev.a040209>
- Lass, R. (1997). *Historical linguistics and language change*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Lev-Ari, S., & Peperkamp, S. (2013). Low inhibitory skill leads to non-native perception and production in bilinguals' native language. *Journal of Phonetics*, 41(5), 320-331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wocn.2013.06.002>
- Lev-Ari, S., & Peperkamp, S. (2014). The influence of inhibitory skill on phonological representations in production and perception☆. *Journal of Phonetics*, 47, 36-46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wocn.2014.09.001>
- Levinson, S. C. (2000). Yéli Dnye and the Theory of Basic Color Terms. *Journal of Linguistic Anthropology*, 10(1), 3-55.
- Levinson, S. C. (2006). On the Human 'Interaction Engine'. In S. C. Levinson & N. Enfield (Éds.), *Roots of Human Sociality: Culture, Cognition and Interaction*. Berg Publishers.
- Levinson, S. C., & Evans, N. (2010). Time for a sea-change in linguistics: Response to comments on « The myth of language universals ». *Lingua*, 120, 2733-2758. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lingua.2010.08.001>
- Lewontin, R. C. (1972). The apportionment of human diversity. In T. Dobzhansky, M. K. Hecht, & W. C. Steere (Éds.), *Evolutionary biology* (Vol. 6, p. 381-398). Springer, New York. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-1-4684-9063-3_14

REFERENCES

- Liaw, A., & Wiener, M. (2001). Classification and Regression by RandomForest. *Forest*, 23.
- Lindsey, D. T., & Brown, A. M. (2002). Color naming and the phototoxic effects of sunlight on the eye. *Psychological science*, 13(6), 506–512.
- Lindsey, D. T., & Brown, A. M. (2006). Universality of color names. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 103(44), 16608-16613. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0607708103>
- Lindsey, D. T., & Brown, A. M. (2009). World Color Survey color naming reveals universal motifs and their within-language diversity. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 106(47), 19785-19790. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0910981106>
- Lindsey, D. T., & Brown, A. M. (2021). Lexical Color Categories. *Annual Review of Vision Science*, 7, 605-631. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-vision-093019-112420>
- List, J.-M., Forkel, R., Greenhill, S. J., Rzymiski, C., Englisch, J., & Gray, R. D. (2022). Lexibank, a public repository of standardized wordlists with computed phonological and lexical features. *Scientific Data*, 9(1), 316. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01432-0>
- Loreto, V., Mukherjee, A., & Tria, F. (2012). On the origin of the hierarchy of color names. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109(18), 6819-6824. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1113347109>
- Lou-Magnuson, M., & Onnis, L. (2018). Social Network Limits Language Complexity. *Cognitive Science*, 42(8), 2790-2817. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cogs.12683>
- Luengo Kanacri, B. P., Eisenberg, N., Tramontano, C., Zuffiano, A., Caprara, M. G., Regner, E., Zhu, L., Pastorelli, C., & Caprara, G. V. (2021). Measuring Prosocial Behaviors: Psychometric Properties and Cross-National Validation of the Prosociality Scale in Five Countries. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.693174>
- Lupyan, G., & Dale, R. (2010). Language Structure Is Partly Determined by Social Structure. *PLoS ONE*, 5(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0008559>
- Lutzenberger, H., de Vos, C., Crasborn, O., & Fikkert, P. (2021). Formal variation in the Kata Kolok lexicon. *Glossa: a journal of general linguistics*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.16995/glossa.5880>
- MacKeigan, T., & Muth, S. Q. (2006). A grammatical network of Tzotzil-Mayan colour terms. In C. P. Biggam & C. Kay (Éds.), *Progress in Colour Studies* (p. 25-36). John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://doi.org/10.1075/z.pics1.06mac>
- Maddieson, I., & Coupé, C. (2015). Human spoken language diversity and the acoustic adaptation hypothesis. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 138(3), 1838–1838. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.4933848>

REFERENCES

- Mainz, N., Shao, Z., Brysbaert, M., & Meyer, A. S. (2017). Vocabulary Knowledge Predicts Lexical Processing: Evidence from a Group of Participants with Diverse Educational Backgrounds. *Frontiers in Psychology, 8*, 1164. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01164>
- Majid, A., & Kruspe, N. (2018). Hunter-Gatherer Olfaction Is Special. *Current Biology, 28*(3), 409-413.e2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2017.12.014>
- Malt, B. C., & Majid, A. (2013). How thought is mapped into words : How thought is mapped into words. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Cognitive Science, 4*(6), 583-597. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcs.1251>
- McElreath, R. (2020). *Statistical rethinking : A Bayesian course with examples in R and Stan*. CRC Press/Taylor & Francis Group.
- Meir, I., Israel, A., Sandler, W., Padden, C. A., & Aronoff, M. (2012). The influence of community on language structure : Evidence from two young sign languages. *Linguistic Variation, 12*(2), 247-291. <https://doi.org/10.1075/lv.12.2.04mei>
- Melnick, M. D., Harrison, B. R., Park, S., Bennetto, L., & Tadin, D. (2013). A strong interactive link between sensory discriminations and intelligence. *Current biology : CB, 23*(11), 1013-1017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2013.04.053>
- Meyerhoff, M. (2015). *Introducing Sociolinguistics*. London: Routledge. doi: 10.4324/9780203874196
- Meyers, K. J., Johnson, E. J., Bernstein, P. S., Iyengar, S. K., Engelman, C. D., Karki, C. K., Liu, Z., Igo, R. P., Truitt, B., Klein, M. L., Snodderly, D. M., Blodi, B. A., Gehrs, K. M., Sarto, G. E., Wallace, R. B., Robinson, J., LeBlanc, E. S., Hageman, G., Tinker, L., & Mares, J. A. (2013). Genetic Determinants of Macular Pigments in Women of the Carotenoids in Age-Related Eye Disease Study. *Investigative Ophthalmology & Visual Science, 54*(3), 2333. <https://doi.org/10.1167/iovs.12-10867>
- Mielke, J., Baker, A., & Archangeli, D. (2016). Individual-level contact limits phonological complexity : Evidence from bunched and retroflex /ɹ/. *Language, 92*(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1353/lan.2016.0019>
- Migliano, A. B., Battiston, F., Viguier, S., Page, A. E., Dyble, M., Schlaepfer, R., Smith, D., Astete, L., Ngales, M., Gomez-Gardenes, J., Latora, V., & Vinicius, L. (2020). Hunter-gatherer multilevel sociality accelerates cumulative cultural evolution. *Science Advances, 6*(9), eaax5913. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aax5913>
- Migliano, A. B., Page, A. E., Gómez-Gardeñes, J., Salali, G. D., Viguier, S., Dyble, M., Thompson, J., Chaudhary, N., Smith, D., Strods, J., Mace, R., Thomas, M. G., Latora, V., & Vinicius, L. (2017). Characterization of hunter-gatherer networks and implications for cumulative culture. *Nature Human Behaviour, 1*(2), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-016-0043>
- Milgram, S. (1967). The small-world problem. *Psychology Today, 1*(1), 1. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1037/e400002009-005>

REFERENCES

- Milroy, J., & Milroy, L. (1978). *Belfast: Change and Variation in an urban vernacular: Vol. Trudgill, P. (ed.), Sociolinguistic patterns in British English*. London: Arnold.
- Milroy, J., & Milroy, L. (1985). Linguistic change, social network and speaker innovation. *Journal of Linguistics*, 21(2), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022226700010306>
- Milroy, L. (1987). *Language and Social Networks*. Wiley. <http://books.google.fr/books?id=rFliAAAAMAAJ>
- Milroy, L., & Gordon, M. (2008). *Sociolinguistics: Method and Interpretation*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Milroy, L., & Milroy, J. (1992). Social Network and Social Class: Toward an Integrated Sociolinguistic Model. *Language in Society*, 21(1), 1-26.
- Mirjalili, F., Luo, M. R., Cui, G., & Morovic, J. (2019). Color-difference formula for evaluating color pairs with no separation: ΔE_{NS} . *Journal of the Optical Society of America A*, 36(5), 789. <https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSAA.36.000789>
- Moisik, S. R., & Dediu, D. (2017). Anatomical biasing and clicks: Evidence from biomechanical modeling. *Journal of Language Evolution*, 2(1), 1. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1093/jole/lzx004>
- Moreland, J. D., & Dain, S. L. (1995). Macular pigment contributes to variance in 100 hue tests. In B. Drum, A. J. Adams, C. R. Cavonius, S. J. Dain, G. Haegerstrom-Portnoy, K. Kitahara, K. Knoblauch, A. Kurtenbach, B. B. Lee, J. Mollon, J. D. Moreland, J. Pokorny, L. T. Sharpe, H. A. Sperling, W. H. Swanson, & E. Zrenner (Éds.), *Colour Vision Deficiencies XII: Proceedings of the twelfth Symposium of the International Research Group on Colour Vision Deficiencies, held in Tübingen, Germany July 18–22, 1993* (p. 517–522). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-0507-1_62
- Morgan, L. H. (1877). *Ancient society: Or researches in the lines of human progress from savagery through barbarism to civilization* (Reprint der Ausgabe Chicago ca.1877). Andesite Press.
- Morton, N. E., Harris, D. E., Yee, S., & Lew, R. (1971). Pingelap and Mokil Atolls: Migration. *American Journal of Human Genetics*, 23(4), 339-349.
- Morton, N. E., Lew, R., Hussels, I. E., & Little, G. F. (1972). Pingelap and Mokil Atolls: Historical genetics. *American Journal of Human Genetics*, 24(3), 277-289.
- Motamedi, Y., Schouwstra, M., Smith, K., Culbertson, J., & Kirby, S. (2019). Evolving artificial sign languages in the lab: From improvised gesture to systematic sign. *Cognition*, 192, 103964. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2019.05.001>
- Motamedi, Y., Wolters, L., Naegeli, D., Kirby, S., & Schouwstra, M. (2022). From improvisation to learning: How naturalness and systematicity shape

REFERENCES

- language evolution. *Cognition*, 228, 105206.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2022.105206>
- Mothe, C., & Nguyen-Thi, T. U. (2021). Does age diversity boost technological innovation? Exploring the moderating role of HR practices. *European Management Journal*, 39(6), 829-843.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2021.01.013>
- Mudd, K. (2022). *How social structure affects the persistence and features of shared sign languages*. Artificial Intelligence Lab, VUB University.
- Mudd, K., de Vos, C., & de Boer, B. (2020). The effect of cultural transmission on shared sign language persistence. *Palgrave Communications*, 6(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-020-0479-3>
- Mudd, K., de Vos, C., & de Boer, B. (2022). Shared Context Facilitates Lexical Variation in Sign Language Emergence. *Languages*, 7(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.3390/languages7010031>
- Mufwene, S., Pellegrino, F., & Coupé, C. (Éds.). (2017). *Complexity in Language : Developmental and Evolutionary perspectives*. Cambridge University Press.
- Murman, D. L. (2015). The Impact of Age on Cognition. *Seminars in Hearing*, 36(3), 111-121. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0035-1555115>
- Mwinga, M., Kavezuva, C., Shifdi, A., & Simasiku, P. (2022). *Opuwo economic profil*. First Capital Namibia. <https://firstcapitalnam.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/Opuwo-Economy-Profile-Report.pdf>
- Mylonas, D., Caparos, S., & Davidoff, J. (2022). Augmenting a colour lexicon. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 9(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-022-01045-3>
- Nacer, A., Mosa'ad, A., & Al-Abdulmunem. (2001). *Color vision testing in an area with high levels of ambient illumination*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12009-001-0007-Z>
- Napoli, D. J., Sanders, N., & Wright, R. (2014). On the linguistic effects of articulatory ease, with a focus on sign languages. *Language*, 90(2), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1353/lan.2014.0026>
- Naroll, R. (1970). What Have We Learned from Cross-Cultural Surveys? *American Anthropologist*, 72(6), 1227-1288. <https://doi.org/10.1525/aa.1970.72.6.02a00030>
- Natale, M. (1975). Convergence of mean vocal intensity in dyadic communication as a function of social desirability. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 32(5), 790-804. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.32.5.790>
- Navarro, D. J., Perfors, A., Kary, A., Brown, S. D., & Donkin, C. (2018). When Extremists Win: Cultural Transmission Via Iterated Learning When Populations Are Heterogeneous. *Cognitive Science*, 42(7), 7. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cogs.12667>

REFERENCES

- Nettle, D. (2012). Social scale and structural complexity in human languages. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 367(1597), 1597. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2011.0216>
- Newman, M. E. J. (2003). The Structure and Function of Complex Networks. *SIAM Review*, 45(2), 167-256. <https://doi.org/10.1137/S003614450342480>
- Newman, M. E. J., & Park, J. (2003). Why social networks are different from other types of networks. *Physical Review E*, 68(3), 036122. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.68.036122>
- Newman, R. (1997). Individual differences and the link between speech perception and speech production. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 102(5_Supplement), 3114-3114. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.420560>
- Newman, R. S., Clouse, S. A., & Burnham, J. L. (2001). The perceptual consequences of within-talker variability in fricative production. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 109(3), 3. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.1348009>
- Nichols, J. (1992). *Linguistic Diversity in Space and Time* (The University of Chicago Press).
- Niederhoffer, K. G., & Pennebaker, J. W. (2002). Linguistic Style Matching in Social Interaction. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology*, 21(4), 337-360. <https://doi.org/10.1177/026192702237953>
- Nielsen, M. W., Bloch, C. W., & Schiebinger, L. (2018). Making gender diversity work for scientific discovery and innovation. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 2(10), 10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-018-0433-1>
- Noble, B., & Fernandez, R. (2015). Centre Stage : How Social Network Position Shapes Linguistic Coordination. *Proceedings of the 6th Workshop on Cognitive Modeling and Computational Linguistics*, 29-38. <https://doi.org/10.3115/v1/W15-1104>
- Nölle, J., Fusaroli, R., Mills, G. J., & Tylén, K. (2020). Language as shaped by the environment : Linguistic construal in a collaborative spatial task. *Palgrave Communications*, 6(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-020-0404-9>
- Ohala, J. J. (1989). Sound change is drawn from a pool of synchronic variation. In L. E. Breivik & E. H. Jahr (Éds.), *Language change : Contributions to the study of its causes* (p. 173–198). Mouton de Gruyter.
- Olkkonen, M., Witzel, C., Hansen, T., & Gegenfurtner, K. R. (2010). Categorical color constancy for real surfaces. *Journal of Vision*, 10(9), 16. <https://doi.org/10.1167/10.9.16>
- Ostler, N. (2005). *Empires of the word : A Language History of the World*. Harper Collins Publishers: London.
- Pagel, M., Beaumont, M., Meade, A., Verkerk, A., & Calude, A. (2019). Dominant words rise to the top by positive frequency-dependent selection.

REFERENCES

- Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 116(15), 15.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1816994116>
- Pakendorf, B., Dobrushina, N., & Khanina, O. (2021). A typology of small-scale multilingualism. *International Journal of Bilingualism*, 25(4), 835-859.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/13670069211023137>
- Paramei, G. V. (2005). Singing the Russian Blues : An Argument for Culturally Basic Color Terms. *Cross-Cultural Research*, 39(1), 10-38.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1069397104267888>
- Paramei, G. V., & Oakley, B. (2014). Variation of color discrimination across the life span. *JOSA A*, 31(4), A375-A384.
<https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSAA.31.00A375>
- Pardo, J. S. (2006). On phonetic convergence during conversational interaction. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 119(4), 2382-2393.
<https://doi.org/10.1121/1.2178720>
- Peng, P., & Kievit, R. A. (2020). The Development of Academic Achievement and Cognitive Abilities : A Bidirectional Perspective. *Child Development Perspectives*, 14(1), 15-20. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdep.12352>
- Perfors, A. (2012). Bayesian models of cognition : What's built in after all? *Philosophy Compass*, 7(2), 127–138.
- Perfors, A., & Navarro, D. J. (2014). Language evolution can be shaped by the structure of the world. *Cognitive Science*, 38(4), 4.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/cogs.12102>
- Peterson, G. E., & Barney, H. L. (1952). Control Methods Used in a Study of the Vowels. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 24(2), 175-184. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.1906875>
- Pickford, R. W. (1947). Sex differences in colour vision. *Nature*, 159(4044), 606.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/159606b0>
- Pokorny, J., Smith, V. C., & Lutze, M. (1987). Aging of the human lens. *Applied Optics*, 26(8), 1437. <https://doi.org/10.1364/AO.26.001437>
- Postmus, T. (2023). *A Review on Linguistic Style Matching*. University of Twente.
https://essay.utwente.nl/94402/7/Postmus_BA_EEMCS.pdf
- Powell, A., Shennan, S., & Thomas, M. G. (2009). Late Pleistocene Demography and the Appearance of Modern Human Behavior. *Science*, 324(5932), 1298–1301. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1170165>
- R Core Team. (2020). *R: a language and environment for statistical computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>
- R Core Team. (2021). *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing (2021). <https://www.R-project.org/>
- R Core Team. (2023). *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>

REFERENCES

- Rajeevan, H. (2003). ALFRED: The ALlele FREquency Database. Update. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 31(1), 270–271. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkg043>
- Rajeevan, H., Soundararajan, U., Kidd, J. R., Pakstis, A. J., & Kidd, K. K. (2012). ALFRED: An allele frequency resource for research and teaching. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 40(D1), D1010–D1015. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkr924>
- Ratliff, F. (1976). On the Psychophysiological Bases of Universal Color Terms. *Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society*, 120(5), 311–330.
- Raviv, L. (2020). *Language and society: How social pressures shape grammatical structure* [PhD Thesis]. Radboud University/Mac Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics.
- Raviv, L., & Arnon, I. (2018). Systematicity, but not compositionality: Examining the emergence of linguistic structure in children and adults using iterated learning. *Cognition*, 181, 160–173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2018.08.011>
- Raviv, L., Meyer, A., & Lev-Ari, S. (2019a). Compositional structure can emerge without generational transmission. *Cognition*, 182, 151–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2018.09.010>
- Raviv, L., Meyer, A., & Lev-Ari, S. (2019b). Larger communities create more systematic languages. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 286(1907), 20191262. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2019.1262>
- Raviv, L., Meyer, A., & Lev-Ari, S. (2020). The Role of Social Network Structure in the Emergence of Linguistic Structure. *Cognitive Science*, 44(8), e12876. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cogs.12876>
- Real, F., Chater, N., & Christiansen, M. H. (2014). The paradox of linguistic complexity and community size. In *The Evolution of Language* (p. 270–277). WORLD SCIENTIFIC. https://doi.org/10.1142/9789814603638_0035
- Regier, T., Carstensen, A., & Kemp, C. (2016). Languages Support Efficient Communication about the Environment: Words for Snow Revisited. *PLOS ONE*, 11(4), e0151138. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0151138>
- Regier, T., & Kay, P. (2004). Color Naming and Sunlight: Commentary on Lindsey and Brown (2002). *Psychological Science*, 15(4), 289–290. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0956-7976.2004.00670.x>
- Regier, T., & Kay, P. (2009). Language, thought, and color: Whorf was half right. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 13(10), 439–446. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2009.07.001>
- Regier, T., Kay, P., & Khetarpal, N. (2007). Color naming reflects optimal partitions of color space. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104(4), 1436–1441. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0610341104>

REFERENCES

- Regier, T., Kemp, C., & Kay, P. (2015). Word Meanings across Languages Support Efficient Communication. In *The Handbook of Language Emergence* (p. 237-263). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118346136.ch11>
- Remington, L. A. (2012). *Clinical anatomy and physiology of the visual system*. Elsevier/Butterworth-Heinemann. <http://site.ebrary.com/id/10500645>
- Richerson, P. J., & Boyd, R. (2008). *Not By Genes Alone: How Culture Transformed Human Evolution*. University of Chicago Press.
- Richerson, P. J., & Christiansen, M. (Éds.). (2013). *Cultural evolution : Society, technology, language, and religion* (Vol. 12). MIT Press.
- Rivers, W. H. R. (1901). *Primitive color vision*. [//catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/000374904](http://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/000374904)
- Roberson, D., Davidoff, J., Davies, I. R. L., & Shapiro, L. R. (2004). The Development of Color Categories in Two Languages : A Longitudinal Study. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 133(4), 554-571. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-3445.133.4.554>
- Roberts, S., & Winters, J. (2012). Social Structure and Language Structure : The New Nomothetic Approach. *Psychol Lang Commun*, 16. <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10057-012-0008-6>
- Robinson, A. (2007). *Story Of Writing* (Second Edition: Alphabets Hieroglyphs And Pictograms). <https://www.amazon.ca/-/fr/Andrew-Robinson/dp/B00OL3LM9U>
- Rodríguez-Carmona, M., Sharpe, L. T., Harlow, J. A., & Barbur, J. L. (2008). Sex-related differences in chromatic sensitivity. *Visual Neuroscience*, 25(3), 433-440. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S095252380808019X>
- Rogers, R. D., & Monsell, S. (1995). Costs of a predictable switch between simple cognitive tasks. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 124(2), 207-231. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0096-3445.124.2.207>
- Rooy, R. V., & Raf Van. (2020). *Language or Dialect?: The History of a Conceptual Pair*. Oxford University Press.
- Rosseel, Y. (2012). lavaan : An R Package for Structural Equation Modeling. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 48(2), 2.
- Rypma, B., Berger, J. S., Prabhakaran, V., Martin Bly, B., Kimberg, D. Y., Biswal, B. B., & D'Esposito, M. (2006). Neural correlates of cognitive efficiency. *NeuroImage*, 33(3), 969-979. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2006.05.065>
- Rzyski, C., Tresoldi, T., Greenhill, S. J., Wu, M.-S., Schweikhard, N. E., Koptjevskaja-Tamm, M., Gast, V., Bodt, T. A., Hantgan, A., Kaiping, G. A., Chang, S., Lai, Y., Morozova, N., Arjava, H., Hübler, N., Koile, E., Pepper, S., Proos, M., Van Epps, B., ... List, J.-M. (2020). The Database of Cross-Linguistic Colexifications, reproducible analysis of cross-linguistic polysemies. *Scientific Data*, 7(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-019-0341-x>

REFERENCES

- Sandler, W., Meir, I., Padden, C., & Aronoff, M. (2005). The emergence of grammar : Systematic structure in a new language. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 102(7), 2661-2665. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0405448102>
- Sankoff, G., & Blondeau, H. (2007). Language Change across the Lifespan : /R/ in Montreal French. *Language*, 83(3), 560–588.
- Sapir, E. (1921). *Language : An Introduction to the Study of Speech* (New York: Harcourt, Brace&World Inc.,).
- Scharf, S., Foster, J., & Behdinan, K. (2014). Optimizing Linguistic Diversity in Highly Multicultural Engineering Design Teams. *2014 ASEE Annual Conference & Exposition Proceedings*, 24.959.1-24.959.11. <https://doi.org/10.18260/1-2--22892>
- Schefrin, B. E., Werner, J. S., Plach, M., Utlaut, N., & Switkes, E. (1992). Sites of age-related sensitivity loss in a short-wave cone pathway. *Journal of the Optical Society of America. A, Optics and Image Science*, 9(3), 355-363. <https://doi.org/10.1364/josaa.9.000355>
- Scott-Phillips, T. C., & Kirby, S. (2010). Language evolution in the laboratory. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 14(9), 411-417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2010.06.006>
- Sebregts, K. (2014). *The sociophonetics and phonology of Dutch r*. LOT, Netherlands Graduate School of Linguistics.
- Sheppard, L. D., & Vernon, P. A. (2008). Intelligence and speed of information-processing : A review of 50 years of research. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 44(3), 535-551. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2007.09.015>
- Shiels, A., & Hejtmancik, J. F. (2015). Molecular Genetics of Cataract. *Progress in molecular biology and translational science*, 134, 203-218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.pmbts.2015.05.004>
- Shinomori, K., Panorgias, A., & Werner, J. S. (2016). Discrimination thresholds of normal and anomalous trichromats : Model of senescent changes in ocular media density on the Cambridge Colour Test. *Journal of the Optical Society of America. A, Optics, image science, and vision*, 33(3), A65-A76.
- Siuda-Krzywicka, K., Witzel, C., Chabani, E., Taga, M., Coste, C., Cools, N., Ferrieux, S., Cohen, L., Seidel Malkinson, T., & Bartolomeo, P. (2019). Color Categorization Independent of Color Naming. *Cell Reports*, 28(10), 2471-2479.e5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2019.08.003>
- Skagerlund, K., Forsblad, M., Tinghög, G., & Västfjäll, D. (2022). Decision-making competence and cognitive abilities : Which abilities matter? *Journal of Behavioral Decision Making*, 35(1), e2242. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bdm.2242>
- Smith, K. (2009). Iterated learning in populations of Bayesian agents. *Proceedings of the 31st Annual Conference of the Cognitive Science*

REFERENCES

- Society*, 697–702.
<http://141.14.165.6/CogSci09/papers/123/paper123.pdf>
- Smith, V. C., Pokorny, J., & Pass, A. S. (1985). Color-Axis Determination on the Farnsworth-Munsell 100-Hue Test. *American Journal of Ophthalmology*, 100(1), 176-182. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9394\(14\)75002-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0002-9394(14)75002-0)
- Solé, M.-J., & Vives, D. R. i. (2012). *The Initiation of Sound Change : Perception, Production, and Social Factors*. John Benjamins Publishing.
- Spencer, H. (1898). *The Principles of Sociology: Vol. New York: D. Appleton and Company* (New York: D. Appleton and Company).
- Spielman, S. E. (2017). Point Pattern Analysis. In *International Encyclopedia of Geography* (p. 1-9). American Cancer Society. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118786352.wbieg0849>
- Stadler, K. (2016). *Direction and directedness in language change : An evolutionary model of selection by trend-amplification*.
- Stark, A. E. (2020). On Random and Systematic Variation in the Prevalence of Defective Color Vision. *Twin Research and Human Genetics*, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1017/thg.2020.74>
- Stevens, M., & Harrington, J. (2014). The individual and the actuation of sound change. *Loquens*, 1(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.3989/loquens.2014.003>
- Steward, J. H. (1955). *Theory of Culture Change : The Methodology of Multilinear Evolution: Vol. Urbana, IL: University of Illinois Press*.
- Stone, M., Szafir, D. A., & Setlur, V. (2014). An Engineering Model for Color Difference as a Function of Size. *Color and Imaging Conference*, 6.
- Szafir, D. A., Stone, M., & Gleicher, M. (2014). Adapting Color Difference for Design. *Color and Imaging Conference*, 22(1), 228-233. <https://doi.org/10.2352/CIC.2014.22.1.art00040>
- Tamariz, M., & Kirby, S. (2015). Culture : Copying, Compression, and Conventionality. *Cognitive Science*, 39(1), 171–183. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cogs.12144>
- Tamariz, M., & Kirby, S. (2016). The cultural evolution of language. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 8, 37–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2015.09.003>
- Thompson, B., Raviv, L., & Kirby, S. (2019, juin 18). Complexity can be maintained in small populations: A model of lexical variability in emerging sign. *Talk presented at the Interaction and the Evolution of Linguistic Complexity Workshop*. Talk presented at the Interaction and the Evolution of Linguistic Complexity Workshop., Edinburg, UK.
- Tiede, M. K., Boyce, S. E., Holland, C. K., & Choe, K. A. (2004). A new taxonomy of American English /r/ using MRI and ultrasound. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 115(5), 5. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.4784878>

REFERENCES

- Tregillus, K. E. M., Werner, J. S., & Webster, M. A. (2016). Adjusting to a sudden “aging” of the lens. *Journal of the Optical Society of America A*, 33(3), A129. <https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSAA.33.00A129>
- Trudgill, P. (2011a). Social structure and phoneme inventories. *Linguistic Typology*, 15(2), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1515/lity.2011.010>
- Trudgill, P. (2011b). *Sociolinguistic Typology : Social Determinants of Linguistic Complexity*. OUP Oxford.
- Trudgill, P., & Chambers, J. K. (2017). *Dialects of English : Studies in Grammatical Variation*. Routledge.
- Turchin, P., Brennan, R., Currie, T., Feeney, K., Francois, P., Hoyer, D., Manning, J., Marciniak, A., Mullins, D., Palmisano, A., Peregrine, P., Turner, E. A. L., & Whitehouse, H. (2015). Seshat : The Global History Databank. *Cliodynamics*, 6(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.21237/C7clio6127917>
- Twomey, C. R., Roberts, G., Brainard, D. H., & Plotkin, J. B. (2021). What we talk about when we talk about colors. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(39), e2109237118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2109237118>
- Urban, M. (2012). *Analyzability and semantic associations in referring expressions : A study in comparative lexicology* [Leiden University]. <https://hdl.handle.net/1887/19940>
- Urban, M. (2023). Foggy connections, cloudy frontiers : On the (non-)adaptation of lexical structures. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1115832>
- van Baaren, R. B., Holland, R. W., Steenaert, B., & van Knippenberg, A. (2003). Mimicry for money : Behavioral consequences of imitation. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 39(4), 393-398. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1031\(03\)00014-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1031(03)00014-3)
- Ventura, R., Plotkin, J. B., & Roberts, G. (2022). Drift as a Driver of Language Change : An Artificial Language Experiment. *Cognitive Science*, 46(9), e13197. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cogs.13197>
- Verriest, G. (1963). Further Studies on Acquired Deficiency of Color Discrimination. *Journal of the Optical Society of America*, 53(1), 185. <https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSA.53.000185>
- von Helmholtz, H. (1924). *Treatise on Physiological Optics*. Optical Society of America.
- Walter, H. (2016). La norme linguistique dans le dictionnaire de l'académie française: *La linguistique*, Vol. 52(1), 55-68. <https://doi.org/10.3917/ling.521.0055>
- Walter, S. (2011). Perceiving “grue” : Filter simulations of aged lenses support the Lens-Brunescence hypothesis and reveal individual categorization types. In C. P. Biggam, C. Hough, C. Kay, & D. R. Simmons (Eds.), *New*

REFERENCES

- Directions in Colour Studies* (p. 329-342). John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://doi.org/10.1075/z.167.37wal>
- Watts, D. J., & Strogatz, S. H. (1998). Collective dynamics of 'small-world' networks. *Nature*, 393(6684), 440–442. <https://doi.org/10.1038/30918>
- Weale, R. A. (1988). Age and the transmittance of the human crystalline lens. *The Journal of Physiology*, 395(1), 577-587. <https://doi.org/10.1113/jphysiol.1988.sp016935>
- Webster, M. A., Miyahara, E., Malkoc, G., & Raker, V. E. (2000). Variations in normal color vision. II. Unique hues. *Journal of the Optical Society of America. A, Optics, Image Science, and Vision*, 17(9), 1545-1555. <https://doi.org/10.1364/josaa.17.001545>
- Webster, M. A., Mizokami, Y., & Webster, S. M. (2007). Seasonal variations in the color statistics of natural images. *Network: Computation in Neural Systems*, 18(3), 213-233. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09548980701654405>
- Webster, M. A., Webster, S. M., Bharadwaj, S., Verma, R., Jaikumar, J., Madan, G., & Vaithilingham, E. (2002). Variations in normal color vision. III. Unique hues in Indian and United States observers. *Journal of the Optical Society of America. A, Optics, Image Science, and Vision*, 19(10), 1951-1962. <https://doi.org/10.1364/josaa.19.001951>
- Wechsler, D. (1999). *Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence*. American Psychological Association. <https://doi.org/10.1037/t15170-000>
- Wechsler, D. (2008). *Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale—Fourth Edition*. American Psychological Association. <https://doi.org/10.1037/t15169-000>
- Weinreich, U., Labov, W., & Herzog, M. I. (1968). *Empirical Foundations for a Theory of Language Change*. University of Texas Press. http://mnytud.arts.unideb.hu/tananyag/szoclingv_alap/wlh.pdf
- Werner, J. S., Peterzell, D. H., & Scheetz, A. J. (1990). Light, vision, and aging. *Optometry and Vision Science: Official Publication of the American Academy of Optometry*, 67(3), 214-229. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00006324-199003000-00013>
- Werner, J. S., Scheffrin, B. E., & Bradley, A. (2010). Optics and vision of the aging eye. In *Handbook of optics* (Vol. 3, p. 20:30).
- West, S. K., Duncan, D. D., Muñoz, B., Rubin, G. S., Fried, L. P., Bandeen-Roche, K., & Schein, O. D. (1998). Sunlight exposure and risk of lens opacities in a population-based study: The Salisbury Eye Evaluation project. *JAMA*, 280(8), 714-718. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.280.8.714>
- Whorf, B. L. (1940). *Science and linguistics*. Technology Review.
- Wichmann, S., Müller, A., & Velupillai, V. (2010). Homelands of the world's language families: A quantitative approach. *Diachronica*, 27(2), 247–276. <https://doi.org/10.1075/dia.27.2.05wic>

REFERENCES

- Wierzbicka, A. (1990). The meaning of color terms : Semantics, culture, and cognition. *Cognitive Linguistics*, 1(1), 99-150. <https://doi.org/10.1515/cogl.1990.1.1.99>
- Wijk, H., Berg, S., Sivik, L., & Steen, B. (1999). Color discrimination, color naming and color preferences in 80-year olds. *Aging Clinical and Experimental Research*, 11(3), 176-185. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03399660>
- Willemys, M., Gallois, C., Callan, V. J., & Pittam, J. (1997). Accent accommodation in the job interview : Impact of interviewer accent and gender. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology*, 16(1), 3-22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0261927X970161001>
- Witzel, C. (2019). Misconceptions About Colour Categories. *Review of Philosophy and Psychology*, 10(3), 499-540. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13164-018-0404-5>
- Wnuk, E., Verkerk, A., Levinson, S. C., & Majid, A. (2022). Color technology is not necessary for rich and efficient color language. *Cognition*, 229, 105223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2022.105223>
- Woensdregt, M. S., Spike, M., de Haan, R., Wareham, T., van Rooij, I., & Blokpoel, M. (2021). Why is scaling up models of language evolution hard? *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society*, 43(43). <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/021734q4>
- Wong, P. C. M., Kang, X., Wong, K. H. Y., So, H.-C., Choy, K. W., & Geng, X. (2020). ASPM-lexical tone association in speakers of a tone language : Direct evidence for the genetic-biasing hypothesis of language evolution. *Science Advances*, 6(22), eaba5090. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aba5090>
- Woo, G. C., & Lee, M.-H. (2002). Are ethnic differences in the F-M 100 scores related to macular pigmentation? *Clinical & Experimental Optometry*, 85(6), 372-377.
- Wray, A., & Grace, G. W. (2007). The consequences of talking to strangers : Evolutionary corollaries of socio-cultural influences on linguistic form. *Lingua*, 117(3), 3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lingua.2005.05.005>
- Xiang, H., van Leeuwen, T. M., Dediu, D., Roberts, L., Norris, D. G., & Hagoort, P. (2015). L2-proficiency-dependent laterality shift in structural connectivity of brain language pathways. *Brain Connectivity*, 5(6), 6. <https://doi.org/10.1089/brain.2013.0199>
- Xiao Fan Wang, & Guanrong Chen. (2003). Complex networks : Small-world, scale-free and beyond. *IEEE Circuits and Systems Magazine*, 3(1), 6-20. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCAS.2003.1228503>
- Yendrikhovskij, S. N. (2001). A computational model of colour categorization. *Color Research & Application*, 26(S1), S235-S238. [https://doi.org/10.1002/1520-6378\(2001\)26:1+<::AID-COL50>3.0.CO;2-O](https://doi.org/10.1002/1520-6378(2001)26:1+<::AID-COL50>3.0.CO;2-O)

REFERENCES

- Young, R. W. (1991). *Age-related cataract*. Oxford University Press.
- Young, R. W. (1994). The Family of Sunlight-Related Eye Diseases: *Optometry and Vision Science*, 71(2), 125-144. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00006324-199402000-00013>
- Yu, A. C. L. (2013). *Origins of Sound Change : Approaches to Phonologization*. Oxford University Press.
- Yu, A. C. L., & Zellou, G. (2019). Individual Differences in Language Processing : Phonology. *Annual Review of Linguistics*, 5(1), 131-150. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-linguistics-011516-033815>
- Zaslavsky, N., Garvin, K., Kemp, C., Tishby, N., & Regier, T. (2022). The evolution of color naming reflects pressure for efficiency : Evidence from the recent past. *Journal of Language Evolution*, 7(2), 184-199. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jole/lzac001>
- Zaslavsky, N., Kemp, C., Regier, T., & Tishby, N. (2018). Efficient compression in color naming and its evolution. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(31), 7937-7942. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1800521115>
- Zaslavsky, N., Kemp, C., Tishby, N., & Regier, T. (2019). Color Naming Reflects Both Perceptual Structure and Communicative Need. *Topics in Cognitive Science*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tops.12395>
- Zaslavsky, N., Kemp, C., Tishby, N., & Regier, T. (2020). Communicative need in colour naming. *Cognitive Neuropsychology*, 37(5-6), 312-324. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02643294.2019.1604502>
- Zellou, G. (2017). Individual differences in the production of nasal coarticulation and perceptual compensation. *Journal of Phonetics*, 61, 13-29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wocn.2016.12.002>
- Zhou, X., Espy-Wilson, C. Y., Boyce, S., Tiede, M., Holland, C., & Choe, A. (2008). A magnetic resonance imaging-based articulatory and acoustic study of "retroflex" and "bunched" American English /r/. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 123(6), 6. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.2902168>
- Zipf, G. K. (1965). *The Psycho-Biology Of Language* (Cambridge: The MIT Press; Houghton Mifflin Co). Originally Printed by Houghton Mifflin Co (1935): 20-48.